

PREPSOIL DELIVERABLE

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Preface

This report reports on the findings from two studies conducted within the Horizon Europe financed project *PREPSOIL*. The first, and the largest, study is a quantitative online study conducted in seven EU countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Sweden) about soil health awareness among professionals that are seen as key actors for supporting change towards more soil health friendly practices within agricultural, forest and urban land uses. According to our knowledge, that study is unique to its kind. The same set of questions was distributed (albeit in native languages) to professionals with the mandate to either support soil management change (such as advisors or consultants) or other key actors who have the power to influence the soil health discourse in respective land use and country. In order to put relevant questions to the identified key persons in each land use type, somewhat different questions was formulated in the three different surveys (agriculture, forest and urban).

Our aim was to gather at least 25 answers for each land use in each country. This proved to be difficult – especially when it came to the forest survey. In Denmark and Netherlands, the forest sector is very small due to natural geographical reasons, which made it difficult to reach the set aim. Germany and France, on the other hand, had difficulties reaching out to the respondents and/or to make them answer the survey. Also for the urban survey, it was difficult for Germany and France to reach out to their targeted respondents and collect the wished-for number of answers. Although we did not fully reached our goal, we believe that the surveys reveal some interesting data that is useful for future planning of supporting the Mission Soil – both at country level and EU level. As the contexts (such as climate, natural geographical preconditions and policy) differ between the participating countries, we decided to report on the findings in two different ways. Chapter 4 presents the data on an aggregated and more overarching level, highlighting similarities and differences between country results. After that, in Chapter 5, we present the results in more depth in country-wise reports for those surveys that reached the minimum requirement for the number of answered surveys. That means that each country report consists of 1-3 sub-chapters, depending on the response rate for the three surveys.

The second study, which had a qualitative approach, proved to be more difficult to conduct in a similar way in all countries. The ambition was that each participating country should conduct two focus group interviews: one with a group of farmers that are interested in farm management practices that supports soil health (such as regenerative farming, conservation agriculture, agroforestry, etc.) and that together constitute an informal learning network in soil health issues, and one with advisors that are working with soil/plant issues to see how/if they integrate soil health aspects in their advices. The purpose with the study was to explore the strengths and weaknesses of the two different kinds of learning systems that these two groups are a part of: the farmers with their informal and experience-based learning system, and advisors with their more formal learning system grounded in research but with the dilemma that soil health studies are still rather few. Moreover, the study aimed to explore the potentials for increasing the co-learning between these two groups when it comes to soil health issues in order to contribute to increased knowledge development within AKIS.

There are several reasons for why it was difficult to conduct the qualitative study in the same way in all countries. As soil health has become an increasingly popular topic the past few years, we have noticed a stakeholder fatigue to participate in soil health related studies. The reluctance to contribute to yet another study, hindered some of the countries to conduct the study as it was planned. Instead, they either reused material from already conducted workshops within PREPSOIL WP2 (as for

Germany), or conducted the study in an alternative way by co-arranging a workshop for advisors that was relevant for several on-going EU projects and by making an online questionnaire targeted to farmers (as for Poland). To arrange meetings with agricultural actors during springtime was also a challenge, which made Denmark and Netherlands to conduct parts of their data collection as individual telephone interviews instead. The differences in data collection methods influence the data obtained. As a consequence, it was difficult to draw generalized cross-country conclusions based on the material.

Based on our experience in conducting these studies, we would like to emphasize the importance to allow different approaches in different countries in EU funded projects with many participants. As context differs between countries, it is of crucial importance to work with an issue in the most suitable way and be able to build on already existing networks. Especially when we are making studies that are involving humans. It is also important to keep in mind that different countries have very different prerequisites to get in contact with experts and authority representatives, as websites often do not reveal names of their workers. Having that said, we would like to invite you to an interesting reading about how different key actors in society view the soil health concept and how learning about soil health could be strengthened.

The authors through Jenny Höckert, SLU Sweden

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Chapter 1. Executive summary

According to EU Mission Soil, it is estimated that between 60 and 70% of EU soils are unhealthy. Through various efforts, the Mission aims to lead the transition to towards healthy soils by 2030. In order to reach that ambitious goal, soils need to be managed differently than today. This puts people and their soil management practices at the core of the Mission. In order to change soil management practices it is of crucial importance that people are aware of, have relevant knowledge and the ability to change management practices in a more sustainable direction. That means that it is not only soil managers (in all kinds of land uses) that might need to rethink their soil management strategies and find other ways of managing the soil that supports soil health. Also other key stakeholders – such as advisors, consultants and key actors that have the power to influence the soil health discourse regionally and nationally – are important as change agents or enablers of change.

In this report we present and discuss findings from two different studies conducted within the Horizon Europe financed project *PREPSOIL*. The first study is a quantitative online study conducted in seven EU countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Sweden) about soil health awareness among professionals that are seen as key actors for supporting change towards more soil health friendly practices within agricultural, forest and urban land uses. The survey results showed that there were rather large differences both between countries and land use types to what extent they agreed with the problem description regarding soil health as put forward in Mission Soil. In general, Spain was the country that agreed the most with the problem description, while Sweden and Poland were the countries that agreed the least. When comparing land use types, the urban respondents were the ones who agreed the most, while the forest respondents agreed the least. In all countries and in all land use types a majority of all respondents, except the Swedish forest respondents, found soil health a relevant concept. Despite that, it was only in agriculture that the concept was considered to be used to any larger extent – although not in Spain or Germany. Obviously, soil health was regarded as a concept with a potential that is yet to be realized.

The surveys pinpointed lack of awareness/knowledge and lack of governance as two hindrances for improved soil health, both across land use types and countries. At EU level, the importance of improving soil health is clearly formulated in Mission Soil. However, there seems to be a gap between the EU level and the national/regional level. As long as soil health is not considered an urgent question also at national/regional level and not integrated in relevant policies and steering documents, it will consequently not be considered as an important aspect to take into account when it comes to soil management practices in the different land uses. The lack of national/regional clarity on how to integrate the Mission Soil ambition in different land uses in different countries/regions, most likely also affect the willingness and possibilities to participate in competence development measures in soil health relevant topics. In all surveys, except the Spanish agricultural and forestry surveys, more than 25% of the respondents did not know if there were relevant competence development measures on soil health for them. However, more than 30% of the Spanish respondents answered that there were no relevant competence development measures for them. In all three surveys, “the soil health concept in general”, “how to assess soil health” and “management strategies to improve soil health” were topics that were ranked high as prioritized topics to learn more about. The preferred format for such competence development measures, were often a combination of digital events and field visits – thus a combination of learning in both theory and practice.

The second study had a qualitative approach and was only conducted in agriculture. The ambition was to explore possibilities for improved co-learning on soil health between pioneer farmers interested in improving soil health through agricultural strategies such as conservation agriculture, regenerative

agriculture or agroforestry who tend to exchange experience-based knowledge with each other in informal networks due to the perceived lack of competence among agricultural advisors on the one hand, and agricultural advisors interested in soil issues on the other hand. Unfortunately, it proved to be difficult to perform the study in a similar way in all countries, which made it difficult to draw conclusions beyond those at country level. However, the participants from all countries could see benefits if the farmers' experience-based knowledge and the advisors' research based knowledge could be better integrated via co-learning spaces such as demonstration farms and co-learning sessions at conferences – preferable also together with researchers. The participating farmers further emphasized the need for trustworthy and unbiased knowledge in relation to soil health that is applicable to region relevant challenges.

We can thus see that the creation of structures for e.g. "lighthouse" activities for demonstrations and as spaces for co-learning could be a promising effort to build awareness and share good examples among different AKIS actors. Of course, such structures would be beneficial also for other land uses.

Chapter 2. Introduction

PREPSOIL (Preparing for the ‘Soil Deal for Europe’ Mission) is a CSA project financed by Horizon Europe and being the first funded project in the EU Mission Soil. This report is part of PREPSOIL WP6 “Promoting soil education, awareness and engagement of Communities of Practice, more specifically Task 6.3 Enhancing vocational, professional and life-long learning in soil management”.

The main goal of Mission Soil, is to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030 ([EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe](#)). In order to reach the ambitious goals set by the mission, people who manage soils will need to *do* things differently (European Commission, 2020; European Commission, 2023). Hence, new practices needs to be developed. In this process, advisors, consultants and other influential key actors will be important mediators of change (e.g. Leeuwis and van den Ban (2004); modernAKIS (2023)). But, in order for these key actors to be able to inspire and motivate landowners and land managers (in agricultural, forest and urban soil contexts) to make changes in prevailing soil management practices, it is of utmost importance that they: *i*) are aware of the EU Mission Soil and *ii*) have enough knowledge regarding soil management practices that supports a positive development of the soil health.

Hence, order to be able to support these key actors in an appropriate way (be it either on EU or national level), PREPSOIL Task 6.3 was designed to learn more about the abovementioned issues. This was done through a combination of a quantitative and a qualitative study. The quantitative study was conducted as three online surveys (one per land use type: agriculture, forest and urban) that was sent to identified key actors in the participating countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Sweden). The quantitative study is described in Chapters 2.1 and 3.1 and the results are presented in Chapters 4 and 5. Chapter 4 presents the results as a cross-country analysis, where similarities and differences between country results are highlighted and discussed on a more overarching level. Chapter 5, in turn, presents country-wise results, where each country’s results are discussed on a deeper level and in relation to the mean values of all survey answers.

To complement the quantitative study, a qualitative study was also performed – albeit only within the agricultural sector. The reason for this was threefold: 1) the soil health concept is hitherto mostly used within the agricultural sector, 2) the PREPSOIL consortium mainly consisted of partners with an expertise in agriculture, and 3) within the agricultural knowledge and innovation system (AKIS), there is an ongoing discussion whether advisory services are “fit for purpose” to support sustainable soil management (Ingram and Mills, 2018). In their paper, Ingram and Mills (*ibid*) concluded that there is need for building capacity in advisory services for sustainable soil management and they give several suggestions on how this could be done. As Mission Soil was launched after the study by Ingram and Mills (2018), PREPSOIL Task 6.3 wanted to better understand how the soil health concept is now used among farmers and advisors that are interested in soil (health) issues, but who are part of two different kinds of learning systems. We also wanted to explore what obstacles to soil health learning they see and meet, as this is crucial not only for farmers and advisors who would like to actively work with improving soil health on farm level, but also for the Living Labs that are funded as a part of Mission Soil ([Living labs of Mission Soil | Mission Soil Platform](#)). The qualitative study is described in Chapters 2.2 and 3.2 and the results are presented in Chapter 6.

2.1. Rationale and objectives of the quantitative study

In agriculture, advisors are often seen as important mediators for change towards a more sustainable agriculture at farm level (e.g. Leeuwis and van den Ban (2004); modernAKIS (2023)). Based on that, the

rationale of this task was to assess the awareness and understanding of the soil health concept among advisors/consultants within agriculture and forestry, as well as other important and influential actors/key persons who have power and mandate to influence soil management practice at field/forest level and/or the discourse on soil health within each soil use type (the respondents are further described in Chapter 3.1.3) As the mission of PREPSOIL was to include urban soil health as well, soil health awareness was also assessed among people working with soil related issues at municipal/regional level with for instance environmental issues, park management and urban planning.

How mediators for change, as well as other influential actors, perceive the soil health concept and contribute to the discourse on soil health will affect recommendations given. Moreover, it will also affect what aspects of soil health that will be considered important in a certain region/country. Hence, knowing more about these key actors' perceptions of soil health and their perceived needs for competence development is crucial in order to be able to support them in their transformative supporting endeavours.

The aim of this sub-task was three-fold:

- i. to assess the awareness and understanding of soil health among actors working as advisors/consultants within agriculture and forestry + actors with the power of influencing urban soil management at municipality/regional level + actors with the potential of influencing the discourse on soil health regarding agricultural/forestry/urban soils,
- ii. to explore the key actors' soil knowledge and how they obtain new knowledge, and
- iii. to explore how the notion of soil health was manifested in practice in their professional work.

2.2. Rationale and objective of the qualitative study

In many parts of the world, including Europe, there are farmers who are practicing (or interested in developing) soil management practices that differs from what is seen as “normal” in conventional and organic agriculture, with an increased focus on soil health and sustainability. Conservation Agriculture, Regenerative Agriculture and Agroecology are some approaches to sustainable soil management that are gaining traction in farming, policy and food industry. But when it comes to the possibility to receive agricultural advisory services with a focus on supporting these agricultural approaches and improving soil health, however, there are large differences depending on where you live. In the US, for example, The Soil Health Division is part of the Natural Resources Conservation Service at U.S. Department of Agriculture (<https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/conservation-basics/natural-resource-concerns/soils/soil-health>) which means that soil health issues is integrated as a part of the national advisory service system. In Sweden, however, soil health was not mentioned in the large public financed agricultural advisory programme “Focus on Nutrients” until 2023 ([Ny rådgivning med hållbarhetsfokus - Greppa](#)), but they still lack an expert to contact in issues related to soil health. Ingram and Mills (2018) even ask if advisory services are “fit for purpose” to support sustainable soil management in their assessment of advice in Europe.

The lack of advisory support related to soil health and sustainable soil management means that this group of farmers are largely left to their own learning journey (Höckert and Lundström, 2024). This opinion is even shared by actors within the advisory system (ibid). To compensate for the weak national advisory support in soil health related issues, farmers engaged in for instance Regenerative Agriculture and Conservation Agriculture develop their own “learning systems” or “community of practices” (Wenger, 1998) with peers for sharing ideas and experiences (Höckert and Lundström, 2024). These

informal learning systems are hence rich in experiences and local, situated knowledge. These kind of learning systems thus differ from the formalised learning system with advisors giving research-based advices. Even though there is an increased interest in soil health related issues both among public and private agricultural advisory organisations/programmes/initiatives, there is still limited research built on field trials and/or on-farm research related to soil health that advisors could base their advices on (e.g. Basch et al, 2015).

Obviously, learning systems based on experiences and learning systems based in research have different strengths and weaknesses. In this sub-task we wanted to explore possible strategies for co-learning between these two different kinds of learning systems by conducting two focus group interviews in each country – one with farmers engaged in soil health issues and one with soil-interested advisors.

The objective of this sub-task was hence two-fold:

- i. to explore and analyse strengths and weaknesses among two different kinds of learning systems (Communities of Practices) within soil health – one grass-root, self-organised farmer initiative and one public/private extension (programme), and
- ii. to identify possible improvements through co-learning between these two learning systems.

Chapter 3. Methodology

As this report include data and lessons learnt from two different kinds of studies, this chapter is divided in two parts. The first part describes the methodology for the quantitative study (described in Chapter 2.1) and the second part the methodology for the qualitative study (described in Chapter .2).

3.1. The quantitative internet-based survey on soil health awareness

This study was performed in in three land use types (agricultural, forest and urban) in seven countries (Denmark, France, Germany, The Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Sweden).

3.1.1. Development of the survey

The survey was developed during April-August 2023. As the main purpose of the survey was to assess the awareness and understanding of soil health among the identified key actors in each country, the EU Commission report “Caring for soil is caring for life” (European Commission, 2020), where Mission Soil is described, was an important document when forulating the survey questions. As the PREPSOIL T6.3 members were mostly involved in soil health issues related to agricultural soils, interviews with researchers at SLU involved in urban and forest soils issues were held to ensure a proper understanding of the challenges that these land uses are faced by. The survey was also informed by two other surveys/reports done in related topics within EJP Soil, namely D5.3 “*Foresight study for soil science professional needs*” (Veenstra et al, 2023a; see also Veenstra et al, 2024) and D7.10 “*Concept for the implementation of sustainable practices*” (Matson et al, under review). Before finalising the first version of the survey, we awaited the proposal of the Soil Health Law, in order to be able to include relevant aspects in the survey.

In order to be able to easily distribute the survey in native languages as well as compile and analyse survey data, an online survey using Netigate (Netigate AB, Sweden; [Home page – Netigate](#)) as the survey tool was chosen as the method for data collection. Hence, in phase one, three parent surveys (one for each land use type) was developed in Netigate. The survey comprised six parts with different themes (Figure 1):

1. General background questions (Q1-10),
2. Questions related to soil health (Q10-15),
3. Assessment of soil challenges (Q16-17),
4. Soil challenges that the workplace deals with (Q18-19)
5. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health (Q19-20)
6. Questions related to competence development.

Figure 1. Illustration of survey themes.

In September 2023, the first versions were test-runned by professionals from within and outside academia that could have been potential respondents. Moreover, task leaders in Prepsoil WP2

commented the surveys, to make sure that lessons learnt from their “soil-need workshops” were included in the surveys (see PREPSOIL report Delivery 2.1 “Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types” for further reading: <https://zenodo.org/records/12743276>). Lastly, the country representatives engaged in the task reviewed the surveys to ensure that country specific challenges were included in the surveys. After the review process, final versions of the surveys were developed.

The surveys contained four types of questions: radio buttons (where one answer option was allowed), checkboxes (where several answer options can be chosen), matrices (where one respond to several questions using the same answer options) and text boxes (open-ended questions). The matrices questions used a 7-graded Likert scale. The Likert scale questions did not offer, “I don’t know” as an answer option, except for Q22, and all questions except the open-ended questions were compulsory to answer.

The final survey versions were translated in Netigate by the task participants to native languages (Danish, French, German, Dutch, Polish, Spanish and Swedish) during October-December 2023 with the instruction to stay as close as possible to the formulations used in the English parent surveys. This was very important as the native surveys did not exist as own surveys, but only as mirrors to the parent surveys. Hence, all answers fed into the parent surveys. The final parent surveys in English are found in Appendix 1: Agricultural survey, Appendix 2: Forest survey and Appendix 3: Urban survey.

In the end of December 2023, all native surveys except the French were launched. The French surveys were launched in February 2024. The surveys were open until the end of April 2024.

3.1.2. Selection of study regions

In order to ensure representative and comparable answers, each participating country selected three regions where they conducted the surveys. Together, the regions should constitute a representative sample for the country as a whole and cover different soil types (if they are unevenly distributed within the country). The regions could for instance represent north/middle/south or agricultural vs forest dominated areas, depending on what would be most suitable in each country. Furthermore, within each region, three municipalities were chosen for the survey study. The municipalities chosen should represent three different kinds of municipalities with a variation of landscapes and/or soil challenges. In each region, there were representation from a metropolitan municipality, a rural municipality and a mixed municipality (somewhere in between the first two). The main reason for selecting three municipalities in each study region was to find relevant stakeholders for the urban survey, as they tend to work on municipality level. For the agricultural and forest surveys, however, the regions are probably the most relevant geographical level, as the respondents we wanted to approach tend to work on regional or cross-regional level (depending on region/country size).

In Chapter 5, each country presents their study regions as part of the country-wise reports (except France, who chose not to write a country report).

3.1.3. The respondents

Based on the objective formulation (see Chapter 2.1), each participating country was responsible for identifying and distributing the survey to the selected key respondents. Each country was encouraged to find respondents representing private actors, public actors, NGOs and other influential actors/networks working in the selected municipalities/regions as well as on national level. To reach

similar respondent groups in the participating countries, Swedish key stakeholders were shared as inspiration for the other participating countries (Table 1).

Agricultural key stakeholders	Forestry key stakeholders	Urban key stakeholders
Private crop advisors	Swedish Forest Agency	Municipalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unit of urban planning • Unit of park management/municipal ecologists • The environmental office
Advisors working with public funded extension within the advisory programme “Focus on Nutrients”	Skogssällskapet [The Forest Society; <i>a public service foundation whose main objectives are to ensure sustainable forest and land management</i>]	The County Administrative Boards
Board of Agriculture	Forest owners associations	The Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions
Swedish Environmental Protection Agency	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency
The County Administrative Boards: Unit of Nature and rural areas	The County Administrative Boards	Boverket – the Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning
The Federation of Swedish Farmers	The Federation of Swedish Farmers	Private consultants in landscape architecture, environmental issues, geotechnics and urban planning
NGO: Swedish Society for Nature Conservation	NGO: Swedish Society for Nature Conservation, WWF, Greenpeace	SLU Think tank Movium [<i>on urban development</i>]
Agricultural Cooperatives	SkogForsk [Forestry Research Institute of Sweden]	
KRAV – a label for organic food	Researchers at SLU	
Researchers at SLU	Forest media	
Agricultural media		

Table 1. Key stakeholders for the three surveys (agriculture, forest and urban) from a Swedish perspective. The compilation was used as inspiration for the other participating countries in order to find relevant respondent groups in their respective countries.

In order to obtain approximately the same number of answers per country and thus make the data easier to compare between countries, a goal was set to achieve at least 25 responses per survey and country. Even before the data collection phase started, it was decided that Denmark and The Netherlands would be exempted from this target for the forest survey, as the forest sector in these countries is very small. Unfortunately, the target was not achieved by all countries. Table 2 presents the number of started and completed surveys for respective country at the closing of surveys the 30th April 2024. In the cross-country analysis (Chapter 4) the green and yellow marked countries in Table 2 are presented by an own bar in the graphs, while the red marked countries are included in the bar representing the total number of answers. Tables 3, 4 and 5 presents the geographical distribution of answers from the completed surveys (agriculture, forest, urban) in the participating countries. As can be noted, all countries did not have an even distribution of answers among the selected study regions. Hence, at country level, perspectives on soil challenges might be missing – especially when the total number of answers are few. The respondents are more thoroughly described in Chapter 4 (the cross-country analysis), but especially in the country-wise reports (Chapters 5.1-5.6).

	Agricultural survey Completed (started)	Forest survey Completed (started)	Urban survey Completed (started)
Denmark	28 (54)	8 (31)	21 (60)
France	15 (36)	2 (19)	6 (28)
Germany	30 (56)	0 (14)	3 (14)
Netherlands	30 (58)	5 (28)	31 (52)
Poland	44 (88)	42 (84)	26 (63)
Spain	35 (87)	38 (60)	18 (48)
Sweden	32 (60)	52 (87)	38 (77)
TOTAL	214 (439)	147 (323)	163 (342)

Table 2. Number of completed and started surveys per survey and country. The green marked boxes indicate that the target of achieving at least 25 responses was reached, the orange marked boxes that the target was almost reached and the red marked that the target was not reached.

AGRICULTURAL SURVEY	DK Denmark	F France	DE Germany	NL Netherlands	PL Poland	SP Spain	SE Sweden	Total
Region 1	3	3	1	6	6	2	2	23
<i>Urban municipality</i>	2	-	13	-	2	7	1	25
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	1	6	-	4	5	-	16
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	6	-	-	1	-	7
Region 2	12	1	4	6	8	7	2	40
<i>Urban municipality</i>	-	-	3	1	6	2	1	13
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	1	3	-	2	1	-	7
<i>Rural municipality</i>	1	4	3	3	2	-	-	13
Region 3	-	3	-	3	11	1	12	30
<i>Urban municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	4	1	2	7
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	-	3	-	1	1	1	6
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	2	1	2	1	1	1	8
National level	7	1	4	12	1	5	16	46
Other	4	1	2	7	3	10	2	29
Total number of respondents (completed surveys)	28	15	30	30	44	35	32	214

Table 3. Geographical distribution of completed agricultural surveys in participating countries.

FOREST SURVEY	DK Denmark	F France	DE Germany	NL Netherlands	PL Poland	SP Spain	SE Sweden	Total
Region 1	2	-	-	-	3	-	8	13
<i>Urban municipality</i>	2	-	-	-	1	-	3	6
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	2	-	-	-	1	1	3	7
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
Region 2	1	2	-	1	9	-	7	20
<i>Urban municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	2	-	2	4
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	-	-	1	7	-	1	9
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Region 3	1	-	-	2	2	9	13	27
<i>Urban municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	-	5	1	6
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	-	-	-	1	3	3	7
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	-	1	-	4	2	7
National level	2	-	-	-	7	16	20	45
Other	1	-	-	-	15	11	5	32
Total number of respondents (completed surveys)	8	2	-	5	42	38	52	147

Table 4. Geographical distribution of completed forest surveys in participating countries.

URBAN SURVEY	DK Denmark	F France	DE Germany	NL Netherlands	PL Poland	SP Spain	SE Sweden	Total
Region 1	2	-	-	3	3	1	1	10
<i>Urban municipality</i>	3	-	-	9	4	2	5	23
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	-	-	4	-	1	3	8
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Region 2	5	2	-	2	3	-	2	14
<i>Urban municipality</i>	1	1	-	3	6	-	5	16
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	1	-	1	7	-	4	13
<i>Rural municipality</i>	-	-	2	-	-	-	5	7
Region 3	5	-	-	2	2	6	4	19
<i>Urban municipality</i>	4	-	-	1	3	6	3	17
<i>Mixed municipality</i>	-	1	-	1	-	6	2	10
<i>Rural municipality</i>	1	-	-	-	-	6	2	9
National level	2	1	-	7	-	-	3	13
Other	3	-	-	1	3	9	1	17
Total number of respondents (completed surveys)	21	6	3	31	26	18	38	143

Table 5. Geographical distribution of completed urban surveys in participating countries

3.1.4. Data analysis

The survey responses were downloaded from Netigate as excel files, power-points and pdf:s and distributed to the participating counties. As it was noted that many respondents had only answered the first questions, only the completed surveys were included in the analysis. The Netigate reports included graphs, distribution of answers, mean values as well as texts in native languages from the open-ended questions. The open-ended questions were analysed by thematic coding done by each country. A protocol for the report writing was developed to streamline the country-wise reports, which are presented in Chapters 5.1-5.6. Before that chapter, however, a selected number of questions are presented in a cross-country analysis to provide an overview of the data and to highlight similarities and differences in results between the participating countries (Chapter 4).

3.1.5. Ethical considerations

In each country, the surveys were distributed to people who were considered as being key informants in relation to the survey objectives, without taking any consideration to either gender or age. Each country was responsible for collecting email addresses to the potential respondents. In many cases, the surveys were sent to anonymous info-mails to municipalities, country administrations and authorities. These e-mail lists have been shared within each country team, but not between countries. As soon as Task 6.3 have fulfilled its commitments, the email lists will be deleted. In the surveys, no questions regarding gender or age was put, as it was not considered relevant data for the study. As no sensitive or personal data was collected in the surveys, it is not possible to connect a specific response to a specific respondent.

3.2. The qualitative study on potentials for improved co-learning on soil health in agriculture

3.2.1. Performance of the study

As described in Chapter 2.2, the qualitative study did only involve stakeholders in agriculture. The study was conducted in Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Sweden – albeit with different methods.

The initial idea was that each country should perform two focus groups interviews – one with a grass-root, self-organised farmer initiative who are interested in soil health issues and who are sharing knowledge and experience within the group and one with public/private advisors engaged in soil issues. Based on the objective formulation (see Chapter 2.2), and discussions held at internal task meetings, each country selected participants who were compatible with this. The participants are described in each country report in Chapter 6. Survey protocols as well as a report protocol was developed to ensure that each country collected and reported comparable data. The survey protocols are found in Appendix 4 (interview guide for farmers) and Appendix 5 (interview guide for advisors). As Germany had been involved in PREPSOIL WP2 and conducted workshops with the same stakeholder group, it was decided that relevant data from those workshops could be reused in this task to avoid stakeholder fatigue. In Netherlands, it was impossible to find a common date for a focus group interview. Hence, the data collection was obtained by individual telephone interviews instead. In Poland, a workshop with advisors serving three related projects were held (NBSOIL, PREPSOIL and Nutricheck). Table 6 describes how data to the qualitative study was obtained in each country.

Workshops, interviews and focus group interviews were held in native languages. The individual interviews/focus group interviews were guided by the developed protocol. The interviews were recorded to facilitate transcription. Based on the transcriptions, country-wise reports were written in English guided by the report protocol.

	Farmers	Advisors
Denmark	Digital focus group interview + telephone interviews	Digital focus group interview
Germany	Reused data from workshop PREPSOIL WP2	Reused data from workshop PREPSOIL WP2
Netherlands	Individual in-person/telephone interviews	Individual in-person interviews
Poland	Online survey	Workshop with advisors (coordinated by PREPSOIL, NBSOIL and Nutricheck)
Spain	Digital focus group interview	Digital focus group interview
Sweden	Digital focus group interview	Digital focus group interview

Table 6. Methods used for data collection in respective country.

3.2.2. Ethical considerations

In Chapter 6, each country describes the farmer and advisor group engaged and interviewed in this sub-task. All participants participated on free will. As soon as Task 6.3 have fulfilled its commitments, the recordings from the interviews will be deleted. The recordings have only been available within each country team and not shared between countries. During the interviews, no sensitive data about the participants was collected. From the transcripts, which are in local languages, it is not possible to either identify which participants have participated in the interview, nor to identify individual statements related to a specific person. In the analysis, the focus was to explore similarities and differences in narratives in relation to the topics discussed between the two focus groups (farmers versus advisors) – not to identify any regional differences between the participants.

Chapter 4. Soil health awareness among key stakeholders in agricultural, forest and urban land uses: A cross-country analysis

In the following chapter, Chapter 5, survey results are thoroughly presented in country-wise reports. Before going into details, this chapter presents the survey results on an aggregated and more overarching level where both similarities and differences between country results are highlighted. The chapter is divided in three sub-chapters, one for each survey. The figures are labelled according to the question number in the survey (see Appendix 1, 2 and 3). The prefix CC is to clarify that the figures belongs to the cross-country analysis chapter.

4.1. The agricultural survey

As the agricultural survey had a good enough response rates for all countries (see Table 2, page 16), the graphs presenting the data will show one bar per country. In addition to that, a bar representing a mean value of the total is also presented in the figures.

4.1.1. Description of respondents

The respondents in each country were chosen because they were either working as consultants/advisors or considered to be an actor with the potential of influencing the soil health discourse in agriculture. Figure CC-Q7A shows that a majority of the respondents had studied soil sciences during their education, except for the Dutch respondents. A majority of the respondents had also received some kind of training in soil health issues, although the share varied between 55% for the Polish respondents and 88% for the Swedish respondents (Figure CC-Q8A). Regarding the question to what extent the respondents considered themselves to work with soil issues, it differed between countries (Figure CC-Q3A). In The Netherlands, 47% of the respondents claimed they were working with soil issues “to a very large extent”, followed by the Polish and Spanish respondents (45% each). In France, this share is only 13%. Of course, the difference may be because the French respondents did not actually work with soil issues to the same extent. However, it can also depend on differences in how you view your own work. The traditional focus of agricultural advisors has been on above-ground issues connected to the crop and yield, and not so much on the soil. Although many of the Dutch respondents had not studied soil science in their education (63%), the Netherlands was the country next after Sweden who rated their soil knowledge high (5-7 on the 7-graded scale) in relation to their needs (Figure CC-Q9A). Among the Spanish respondents, there were 28% who rated their knowledge as a 1 or a 2 (where 1=deficient).

Figure CC-Q3A. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent".

Figure CC-Q7A. "Have you studied soil science?"

Figure CC-Q8A. "Have you received training on soil health related issues?"

Figure CC-Q9A. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?"

4.1.2. The respondents and the soil health concept

In Q11, the respondents were presented to the EU Commission statement regarding unhealthy soils in Europe and the problems that are causing this unhealthiness. In the question, the respondents should rate to what extent they agreed with this problem formulation. As seen in Figure CC-Q11A, there were large differences to what extent the different countries agreed with the problem formulation. Germany and Spain both rated this question high, followed by France (more than 80% of their respondents rated this question a 5-7). This can be compared to Sweden, where less than 40% of the respondents gave the same rating. Most likely, the Spanish, German and French respondents have more own experiences with soil issues that can be related to poor soil health. Agreeing on a problem description or not have implications for the willingness to work on an issue. As long as a person do not agree with a problem formulation, the incentives for working with that issue will probably not be very high. This can of course also be related to the extent to which soil problems linked to poor soil health are considered to really be a real problem in the specific region/country or not. It can also be linked to lack of knowledge about the soil health concept in general.

In Q12, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil. The first perspective was *soil fertility*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain plant growth. In the soil fertility concept the focus is mainly on the ecosystem service "provision of food, fibre and fuel". The other perspective was *soil health*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services in terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services. Also in this question, the rating varied between the countries (Figure CC-Q12A). While almost 60% of the Swedish and German respondents voted in favour for the soil fertility concept or gave a neutral response (1-4), about 60% of the Danish, Dutch, German, France and Spanish respondents voted in favour for the soil health concept (5-7). Obviously, there were different views on soils among the approximate same group of respondents, despite most respondents have studied soil science at university level during their education.

Figure CC-Q13aA presents the results to the question whether soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture or not. As seen, also in this question the answers varied widely. While approximately 90% of the French and Spanish respondents "strongly agreed" to its relevance, only 31% of the Swedish respondents voted the same. When comparing Figure CC-Q13aA and Figure CC-Q13bA, it can be concluded that there were discrepancies between the perceived relevance and to what extent the concept is already being used. Although Sweden had the smallest proportion of respondents who "strongly agreed" that soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture, they had the largest share (25%)

of respondents who “strongly agreed” that soil health is already used by the agricultural sector. In Netherlands and Germany, this share was only 3%.

Many respondents gave a positive vote regarding the questions about how knowledgeable they are about the soil health concept in general (Figure CC-Q14aA) and how agricultural management affects soil health (Figure CC-Q14bA). However, only a rather small proportion of the respondents gave the highest scoring in these two questions. Obviously, there are potentials for competence development in these issues – especially if the respondents are considered to be important mediators for change at farm level.

In Q15a, the respondents were asked to what extent an adoption of the soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil. Once again, there were a great variation between the countries (Figure CC-Q15aA). In Denmark and Germany, approximately 10% of the respondents voted “not at all” and in Sweden 60% of the respondents voted 1-4 (where 1 being “not at all” and 4 a neutral response). In Spain, however, 71% of the respondents agreed to “a very high extent” that an adoption of the soil health concept would imply a mindshift, and in total, almost all Spanish respondents gave a positive vote on the question. The Spanish respondents were also the ones that agreed the most with the statement that an adoption of the soil health concept would change how their workplace would deal with soil issues (51% voted “a very high extent”). This can be compared to Sweden, where 66% of the respondents voted negatively (1-3), followed by Netherlands (57%) and Germany (53%).

Figure CC-Q11A. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?”

Figure CC-Q12A. "The following perspective of soil aligns with my own view"

Figure CC-Q13a. "Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture"

Figure CC-Q13b. "The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept"

Figure CC-Q14aA. "How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?"

Figure CC-Q14bA. "How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?"

Figure CC-Q15aA. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?"

Figure CC-Q15bA. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?"

4.1.3. Soil challenges in the different countries

As expected, the challenges perceived as a soil problem varied a lot between the countries, which can also be seen in Table CC-Q16A. When comparing total means, "To decrease desertification" got the lowest number (2.97). However, as one could expect, Sweden ranked this challenge very low (mean 1.13), while it was perceived as a more severe problem in Spain (mean 5.37). The challenge that got the highest total mean was "To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage" (5.22). For this challenge, the variation was also less between the countries, where Germany had the lowest mean (4.60) and The Netherlands highest (5.50). The challenge with highest individual mean was Denmark who had a mean of 5.89 for "To manage peatlands", followed by Spain for "To increase soil organic matter" (5.66). It is notable that the German respondents did not score any challenge particularly high, while the Spanish means exceeded 4 for all challenges. However, the standard deviation for the Spanish means are always the highest between the countries, indicating that there are different opinions either between different respondents or between different regions.

By looking at the range of voting for the different soil challenges among the participating countries, it becomes obvious that it is very important to let each individual country decide what aspects of an issue that is relevant to work with. The differences in standard deviations (both within and between countries) also tells us that regional adjustments are needed in order to put the effort on right challenges.

	SE	DK	NL	DE	PL	FR	SP	Total
To increase soil organic matter	4.16 (1.39)	5.18 (1.60)	5.13 (1.20)	4.03 (1.54)	5.30 (1.46)	4.73 (1.57)	5.63 (1.82)	4.93 (1.62)
To increase soil biodiversity	4.31 (1.42)	4.82 (1.54)	4.67 (1.42)	3.27 (1.69)	5.14 (1.42)	5.27 (1.06)	5.66 (2.00)	4.74 (1.72)
To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage	5.13 (1.29)	5.43 (1.42)	5.50 (1.20)	4.60 (1.67)	5.14 (1.46)	5.40 (1.62)	5.49 (2.03)	5.22 (1.58)
To improve soil fertility	4.63 (1.19)	4.61 (1.61)	5.10 (1.27)	4.60 (1.72)	5.34 (1.41)	5.47 (1.26)	5.17 (2.12)	4.98 (1.60)
To improve nutrient cycling	4.25 (1.25)	5.25 (1.82)	5.07 (1.31)	4.23 (1.78)	5.14 (1.42)	5.00 (1.51)	5.03 (2.16)	4.86 (1.69)
To decrease soil compaction	5.16 (1.03)	5.00 (1.46)	5.43 (1.09)	3.83 (1.61)	4.57 (1.67)	5.40 (0.97)	5.34 (2.04)	4.92 (1.60)
To decrease soil erosion	3.31 (1.31)	4.00 (1.58)	3.34 (1.61)	4.10 (1.47)	4.91 (1.52)	5.07 (1.65)	5.63 (2.03)	4.33 (1.82)
To decrease salinization	1.84 (1.15)	2.21 (1.29)	3.30 (1.79)	2.90 (1.47)	4.18 (1.91)	3.40 (2.09)	4.49 (2.30)	3.27 (1.99)
To decrease desertification	1.13 (0.41)	1.46 (0.78)	2.03 (1.66)	3.00 (1.69)	3.84 (1.93)	3.40 (1.99)	5.37 (2.23)	2.97 (2.19)
To avoid soil sealing	4.41 (1.50)	3.18 (1.65)	3.07 (1.59)	3.83 (1.65)	4.27 (1.53)	4.80 (1.76)	5.06 (2.08)	4.08 (1.82)
To manage peatlands	3.88 (1.87)	5.89 (1.50)	4.70 (1.90)	3.80 (2.02)	3.95 (1.86)	2.87 (1.63)	4.17 (2.27)	4.24 (2.05)

Table CC-Q16A. "To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?" The respondents were presented with a matrix where they rated each challenge individually on a 1-7 Likert scale (1=Not at all; 7=To a very large extent). The question did not involve prioritizing the challenges listed. The table presents mean values and standard deviation in brackets. Green marked boxes indicate that the mean ≤ 3 and red boxes that the mean ≥ 5 . The challenge with the highest mean for each country and the total is marked with bold numbers.

4.1.4. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

In an open-ended question (Q19), the respondents had the possibility to share ideas about what they perceived as hindrances to improved soil health in their region/country. Table CC-Q19A summarizes the themes mentioned in each country report. As can be seen, three themes occur in all countries: *lack of knowledge/awareness, economic aspects and lack of political governance*.

In the following question, the respondents were invited to suggest measures to deal with the perceived hindrances/shortcomings. As the measures were very different in detail level, and also connected to the national context, these will not be listed here. A common question for all countries, that is also relevant on EU level, is of course how the Common Agricultural Policy could be developed to better support agricultural management practices that supports a positive development of soil health.

	Denmark	Germany	Netherlands	Poland	Spain	Sweden
Hindrances for improved soil health in agriculture	Lack of relevant information/ education Economic conflicts Continued intensification and expansion of agriculture Lack of political will to support/ implement systemic changes	Lack of education and training on soil health Lack of public and political awareness and support Economic interests and counter-productive subsidies Practical implementation challenges	Knowledge (poor/insufficient information on how to improve soil health) Attitude (lack of land manager motivation to make soil-health-related changes) Markets (lack of consumer involvement in supporting soil health) Policies (current legal framework not suited to ensure soil health)	Social aspects: lack of knowledge and awareness of farmers Economic aspects: Low prices on agricultural products & high costs on inputs Legal aspects: weak protection of land & lack of stable policies	Lack of education & knowledge about proper soil management Economic challenges and ineffective agricultural policies Current unsustainable agricultural practices & impact of climate change	Lack of knowledge (of methods that improve soil health & importance of micro life) Poor economy/ Profitability Political governance/ today's regulations

Table CC-Q19A. Perceived hindrances for improved soil health as mentioned by the agricultural respondents (open-ended question).

4.1.5. Competence development

As for many other questions, also the ones concerning relevant topics for competence development and preferred formats for competence development measures differed a lot between the countries. In Figure CC-Q21A and Figure CC-Q23A the answer options with the highest total mean values are presented. Regarding the need for competence development, “Soil management strategies to improve soil health” (52%) and “How to assess soil health” (50%), received a total average of over 50% of the votes. This is a bit contradicting to the results presented in Figure CC-Q14aA and Figure CC-Q14bA, where a majority of the respondents claimed to have good knowledge about the soil health concept as well as how agricultural management affects soil health. The preferred format for competence development measures were field visits (total mean 57%), followed by via good examples (47%) and live webinars (43%). We can thus see that the creation of structures for e.g. “lighthouse” activities for demonstration and showcase of soil health practices could be a promising effort to build awareness and share good examples.

The survey did not provide any answers as to how many competence development activities are *de facto* available, but it can be stated that if there are any, they are not well known among the respondents. Figure CC-Q22A shows that on average 28% of the respondents did not know whether there were adequate competence development measures available for them or not. As with the other questions, the answers varied widely. In France, 20 % of the respondent claimed that there were adequate measures available “to a very large extent”, while in Spain 31% of the respondent voted “not at all”. If these respondents are to be able to function as knowledge bridges to farmers and landowners and be able to raise soil health issues within the sector and function as mediators for change, competence development measures need to be improved for this target group.

Figure CC-Q21A. "Which soil related topics would you like to learn more about?" The full list of suggested topics can be found in Appendix 1, question 21.

Table CC-Q22A. "Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?"

Table CC-Q23A. "I would like to learn more about agricultural soil health through". The full list of suggested methods can be found in Appendix 1, question 23.

4.2. The forest survey

For the forest survey, only three of the seven participating countries reached a response rate that enabled individual presentation of answers (see Table 2, page 16). In the figures below, these countries (Sweden, Poland and Spain) are presented by an own bar in the graphs. In the bar representing the total mean value, however, answers also from Denmark, Netherlands and France are included. Germany lacked respondents for this survey. Since both Germany and France are two countries with large forest areas, more data would have been desirable to understand how the soil health concept is understood and used in forestry sector. We therefore ask readers to keep this in mind when reading following chapters and recommend that further studies are conducted with forestry stakeholders to understand their needs.

4.2.1. Description of respondents

The respondents in each country were chosen because they were either working as consultants/advisors or considered to be an actor with the potential of influencing the soil health discourse in forestry. Similar to the agricultural respondents, figure CC-Q7F shows that a majority of the respondents had studied soil sciences during their education. The mean for the forest respondents was even slightly higher than for the agricultural respondents (79% vs 74%). However, unlike the agricultural respondents, a majority of the forest respondents had not received any training in soil health issues (Figure CC-Q8F). Regarding the question to what extent the respondents considered themselves to work with soil issues, the answers were rather similar between the countries. Compared to the total mean bar, however, one can see that both the Polish and Spanish respondents considered themselves working with soil to somewhat less extent, while the Swedish respondents graded 5-7 to a bit higher extent. The Polish respondents were also the ones who answered “not at all” to the largest extent (14%). When looking at Figure CC-Q9F, one can see that there are rather large differences regarding how the respondents rated their soil knowledge in relation to their needs. While approximately 66% of the Swedish respondents rated their knowledge as a 5-7, only 13% of the Spanish respondents did the same. As much as 26% of the Spanish respondents even rated their soil knowledge as deficient. Obviously, there seems to be some kind of gap between the soil sciences taught during education versus the perceived soil knowledge needed at work.

Figure CC-Q3F. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent.”

Figure CC-Q7F. "Have you studied soil science?"

Figure CC-Q8F. "Have you received training on soil health related issues?"

Figure CC-Q9F. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?"

4.2.2. The respondents and the soil health concept

In Q11, the respondents were presented to the EU Commission statement regarding unhealthy soils in Europe and the problems that are causing this unhealthiness. In the question, the respondents should rate to what extent they agreed with this problem formulation. As seen in Figure CC-Q11F, there were large differences to what extent the different countries agreed with the problem formulation. In Spain, almost 60% of the respondents rated this question high (5-7, where 7=strongly agree), compared to 30% of the Swedish respondents. Compared with the agriculture survey, the share of respondents who

voted “strongly disagree” was higher (10% for forest survey vs 2% for agricultural survey). Among the Polish respondents, 21% strongly disagreed with the statement.

In Q12, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil. The first perspective was *soil fertility*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain production. In the soil fertility concept the focus is mainly on the ecosystem service “provision of food, fibre and fuel”/production of forest raw material. The second perspective was *soil health*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services in terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services. Also in this question, the voting varied between countries (Figure CC-Q12F). In Sweden, approximately 40% of the respondents voted in favour of the “soil fertility” perspective and a similar share for the “soil health” perspective. In Spain, though, almost 70% of the respondents voted in favour of the “soil health” perspective. Obviously, there were different views on soils among the approximate same group of respondents, despite most respondents had studied soil science at university level during their education.

Figure CC-Q13aF presents the results to the question whether soil health was perceived as a relevant concept in forestry or not. As seen, also in this question the answers varied between the presented countries. In Poland and Spain, almost 80% of the respondents found the soil health concept relevant for forest soils, while only 40% of the Swedish respondents agreed. When comparing Figure CC-Q13aF and Figure CC-Q13bF, it can be concluded that also in the forest sector, there were discrepancies between the perceived relevance and to what extent the concept was already being used. In Sweden, 40% of the respondent “strongly disagreed” that the concept is already used, while in Poland that share was only 10%. Poland was also the country with the largest share of votes in the positive half of the scale, and 17% of their votes was on the answer option “strongly agree”.

In line with the above-mentioned results showing that only 30% of the forest respondents had received training in soil health issues (Figure CC-Q8F), Figure CC-Q14aF indicates rather low levels regarding how knowledgeable the respondents perceived themselves regarding the soil health concept in general. Despite these rather low levels, the respondents felt more confident about their knowledge on how forest management affects soil health (CC-Q14bF). In all countries, however, 20-40% of the respondents rated themselves at the lower half of the scale (1-3; total mean 28%).

In Q15a, the respondents were asked to what extent an adoption of the soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil. Once again, there was a great variation between the countries (Figure CC-Q15aF). In Sweden and Poland, approximately 40% of the respondents voted 5-7 (where 7 is “to a very large extent”). In Spain, that share was 73%. In line with that, the Spanish respondents were also the ones who believed that an adoption of the soil health concept would change how their workplace would deal with soil issues to the largest extent. While 16% of the Spanish respondents believed that it would affect the working practice to “a very large extent”, that share was only 5 % in Poland and 2% in Sweden.

The attitude to the soil health concept in relation to forest soils was obviously somewhat ambiguous. Although a majority of respondents thought that soil health was a relevant concept in relation to forest soils (mean 65%), a minority of respondents believed that an adoption of the concept would change the way their workplace would work with soil issues (mean 31%).

Figure CC-Q11F. "To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?"

Figure CC-Q12F. "The following perspective of soil aligns with my own view"

Figure CC-Q13aF. "Soil health is a relevant concept in forestry"

Figure CC-Q13bF. "The forest sector already uses soil health as a concept"

Figure CC-Q14aF. "How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?"

Figure CC-Q14bF. "How knowledgeable are you about how forest management affects soil health?"

Figure CC-Q15aF. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry imply a mindshift concerning soil?"

Figure CC-Q15bF. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?"

4.2.3. Soil challenges in the different countries

Compared with the agricultural survey, the forest survey got much less differences between the countries when it came to grading different challenges in relation to forest soils. Most challenges resulted in means ranging from 3-5, meaning rather neutral ranking. In general, the Swedish respondents gave the lowest voting and the Spanish the highest for the proposed problems. The challenge with the highest country mean, however, was Poland who had a mean of 5.02 for the challenge “To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage”. This was also the challenge which got the highest mean value for Spain (4.92) as well as for the total (4.56). Other challenges that were ranked a bit higher on individual basis was “To decrease soil erosion” (Spain; mean 4.89) and “To decrease desertification” (Spain; mean 4.84). The total mean that got the lowest ranking was “To decrease desertification” – although ranging from 1.40 for Sweden to 4.84 for Spain.

In this survey and looking only at the mean values, the challenges considered as the most severe versus the least severe challenges to deal with are thus shared between the forest and the agricultural respondents. As the standard deviation differ between the proposed challenges, it is reasonable to believe that there are regional differences regarding how large a problem a challenge is perceived.

	Sweden	Poland	Spain	Total
To increase soil organic matter	2.75 (1.44)	4.24 (1.76)	4.37 (1.55)	3.74 (1.77)
To increase soil biodiversity	4.56 (1.34)	4.43 (1.66)	4.45 (1.35)	4.54 (1.49)
To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage	3.85 (1.35)	5.02 (1.74)	4.92 (1.72)	4.56 (1.67)
To improve soil fertility	3.62 (1.32)	4.31 (1.63)	4.63 (1.46)	4.10 (1.52)
To improve nutrient cycling	3.50 (1.31)	4.43 (1.68)	4.58 (1.55)	4.16 (1.59)
To decrease soil compaction	4.13 (1.53)	4.12 (1.53)	4.53 (1.71)	4.27 (1.61)
To decrease soil erosion	3.90 (1.51)	4.62 (1.54)	4.89 (1.90)	4.30 (1.71)
To decrease salinization	2.06 (1.28)	3.90 (1.74)	4.05 (1.49)	3.16 (1.74)
To decrease desertification	1.40 (0.99)	4.10 (1.99)	4.84 (1.87)	3.10 (2.19)
To avoid soil sealing	2.60 (1.58)	3.76 (1.57)	4.39 (1.83)	3.46 (1.80)
To manage peatlands	4.15 (1.60)	4.69 (2.18)	3.97 (1.83)	4.33 (1.92)

Table CC-Q16F. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in forest soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?” The respondents were presented with a matrix where they rated each challenge individually on a 1-7 Likert scale (1=Not at all; 7=To a very large extent). The question did not involve prioritizing the challenges listed. The table presents mean values and standard deviation in brackets. Green marked boxes indicate that the mean ≤ 3 and red boxes that the mean ≥ 5 . The challenge with the highest mean for each country and the total is marked with bold numbers.

4.2.4. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

In an open-ended question (Q19), the respondents had the possibility to share ideas about what they perceived as hindrances to improved soil health in their region/country. Table CC-Q19F summarizes the themes mentioned in each country report. Two themes were mentioned in all three countries: *lack of knowledge and the prevailing culture in forestry*.

	Poland	Spain	Sweden
Hindrances for improved soil health in forestry	Legal aspects: e.g. lack of forest water management programs Cultural aspects: current silvicultural principles & state of knowledge of foresters Environmental aspects: overexploitation of forests & soil pollution	Lack of knowledge and awareness Traditional forest management methods Lack of resources, political support Forest fires, desertification and effects of climate change	Economy (efficient forestry & gentle machines are expensive) Lack of knowledge & awareness Culture: business-as-usual

Table CC-Q19F. Perceived hindrances for improved soil health as mentioned by the forest respondents (open-ended question).

Also in this survey, the question on perceived hindrances were followed by a question where the respondent were invited to suggest measures to deal with the hindrances/shortcomings. As with the agricultural survey, the measures were anchored in national contexts and will thus not be discussed here. Moreover, the EU lacks a common forest policy, which means forest issues are guided by national policies.

4.2.5. Competence development

Just like many other questions, also the ones concerning relevant topics for competence development and preferred formats for competence development measures differed a lot between the countries. In Figure CC-Q21F and Figure CC-Q23F the answer options with the highest total mean values are presented. Concerning prioritised topics for competence development, three topics received almost the same share, namely “The soil health concept in general” (50%) and “Soil biodiversity” and “Forest management strategies to improve soil health” (49% each). When looking at preferred formats for competence development measures, they varied more between the countries. While the Spanish and Swedish respondents were very positive to digital courses (68% and 62%), the Polish respondents were rather negative to that format (indicated as a preferred format only by 7%). Instead, they preferred field visits (55%) and forestry magazines (31%).

As for the agricultural survey, the forest survey did not provide any data on how much competence development measures that was *de facto* available for this stakeholder group. However, and similar to the agricultural survey, a large proportion of the respondents did not know if there were adequate measures available for them or not (total mean 34%). Moreover, 39% of the Spanish respondents answered “not at all” (total mean 13%). Among the Spanish respondents, none was giving a positive answer to the question. Obviously, this is a question to focus on during the coming years.

Figure CC-Q21F. "Which forest soil related topics would you like to learn more about?" The full list of suggested topics can be found in Appendix 2, question 21.

Table CC-Q22F. "Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?"

Table CC-Q23F. "I would like to learn more about forest soil health through" The full list of suggested methods can be found in Appendix 2, question 23.

4.3. The urban survey

In the urban survey, five of the seven participating countries reached a response rate that enabled individual presentation of answers (see Table 2, page 16). In the figures below, these countries (Sweden, Denmark, Poland, Netherlands and Spain) are presented by an own bar in the graphs. In the bar representing the total mean value, however, answers from also Germany and France are included.

4.3.1. Description of respondents

The respondents in each country were chosen as they were regarded either as an actor with the power of influencing urban soil management at municipality/regional level or as an actor with the potential of influencing the urban soil discourse. Unlike the agricultural and forest respondents, only 45% of the urban respondents had studied soil science during their education – ranging from 32% in The Netherlands to 57% in Denmark (Figure CC-Q7U). This can be compared with the total mean of 74% for the agricultural respondents and 78% for the forest respondents. The proportion of the urban respondents who had received some kind of training in soil health issues was about the same as for the forest respondents (approximately 30%), although ranging from 18% in Sweden to 52% in Denmark. Regarding the question to what extent the respondents considered themselves to work with soil issues, more than 70% of the respondents rated 5-7 (where 7 being “to a very large extent”) except for the Polish respondents were 54% voted the same (Figure CC-Q3U). Just like the Spanish forest respondents, the Spanish urban respondents was the largest group who considered themselves having “deficient” soil knowledge in relation to their needs (22%). Among the Polish respondents, 12% perceived themselves having deficient soil knowledge. Just like the other surveys, few respondents claimed to have “excellent” knowledge in relation to their needs. In The Netherlands, however, 94% of the respondents gave a rating of 5-7, which was the country with the highest score by far. This compares with Spain, where only 17% of the respondents rated the same.

Figure CC-Q3U. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent"

Figure CC-Q7U. "Have you studied soil science?"

Figure CC-Q8U. "Have you received training on soil health related issues?"

Figure CC-Q9U. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?"

4.3.2. The respondents and the soil health concept

In Q11, the respondents were presented to the EU Commission statement regarding unhealthy soils in Europe and the problems that are causing this unhealthiness. In the question, the respondents should rate to what extent they agreed with this problem formulation. As seen in Figure CC-Q11U, there were differences to what extent the different countries agreed with the problem formulation also among the urban respondents. Overall, however, the urban respondents agreed with the problem formulation to a higher extent than the agricultural and forest respondents did. The percentage of urban respondents who voted 5-7 on the Likert scale was 77% (total mean), compared to 67% for the forest and agricultural respondents (Figures CC-Q11A, F and U). Among the countries, the Spanish respondents were once again the ones voted "strongly agree" to the highest extent (72%), compared

with 23% for the Dutch respondents. However, when adding the votes for 5-7, the Dutch respondents were the ones who agreed with the problem formulation to the greatest extent (87%), compared with 56% for the Polish respondents.

In Q12, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil. The first perspective was called *“Targeted soil use”*, defined as *“focus on one or a few specific functions at a time”* (i.e. as foundation for buildings/infrastructure, as medium for water purification or as growing medium for trees and plants). The second perspective was called *“Focus on a wide range of soil ecosystem services simultaneously”*, followed by the sentence *“Soil health is the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems”*. Also in this question, the ranking varied between the countries. In Sweden and Denmark, a majority of the respondents voted in favour for the *“targeted soil use”*-half of the scale (1-3; both 39%), although a neutral response was their most common answer (CC-Q12U). In Poland and Spain, the most common answer was *“focus on a broad range of ecosystem services”* (Poland 42% and Spain 50%). One possible explanation to the differences in perspectives may be related to how closely and/or integrated one works across responsibility boundaries with other stakeholders representing a different soil focus compared to the own. Another explanation could be that in countries that are suffering from hot weather and droughts more often (like for instance Spain compared to Sweden and Denmark), the respondents have been trained/forced into a more holistic view on soil to solve the challenges they are faced by. However, as this survey did not provide any answers on that issue, this is purely speculations.

The question whether soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils showed unanimous answers – in all countries, a majority of the respondents answered affirmatively to that question (Figure CC-Q13aU). In Spain, no respondents disagreed. Again, the Spanish and Polish respondents were among those who agreed the most. However, although soil health was perceived as a relevant concept for urban soils, the urban sector does not use it yet (CC-Q13bU). That view was shared by all countries. Nevertheless, if soil health would be an adopted concept, all respondents except the Danish claimed that it would imply a mindshift concerning soil (Figure CC-15aU). In Denmark, approximately the same proportion of respondents believed that it would imply a mindshift as those who did not, while in Spain all respondents claimed it would. A majority of the respondents from all countries, except those from Denmark, did also believe that an adoption of the soil health concept would change how their workplace would deal with soil issues. In Spain, as much as 67% of the respondents claimed that it would change their practice *“to a very large extent”*, which was by far the highest share among the countries (in Sweden, Denmark and Poland that share was about 5%). Obviously, the respondents saw a great potential with introducing the soil health concept to the urban sector, and a majority did believe that it would affect how they would deal with soil issues as well. A limiting factor can be assumed to be insufficient knowledge and awareness about the concept. Figure CC-Q14aU indicates rather low ratings regarding the respondents’ perceived knowledgeability about the soil health concept for all countries except for The Netherlands. In Poland, Spain and Denmark, 23-33% of the respondents voted that they were *“not at all”* knowledgeable about the concept. As for the forest respondents, however, a larger proportion of the urban respondents felt more confident regarding their knowledge about how soil management affects soil health. Nevertheless, between 20-55% of the respondents rated their knowledge in the lower half of the scale (1-3, where 1 is *“not at all”*).

Figure CC-Q11U. "To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?"

Figure CC-Q12U. "The following perspective of soil aligns with my own view"

Figure CC-Q13aU. "Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils"

Figure CC-Q13bU. "The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept"

Figure CC-Q14aU. "How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?"

Figure CC-Q14bU. "How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?"

Figure CC-Q15aU. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils imply a mindshift concerning soil?"

Figure CC-Q15bU. "To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?"

4.3.3. Soil challenges in the different countries

Just like the agricultural survey, the challenges perceived as a problem for urban soils varied between the countries (Table CC-Q16U). However, two of the challenges were perceived as problematic for most of the countries. “To avoid or remediate contamination of soils/soil pollution” got the highest total mean (5.57). That was also the challenge with the highest individual mean for Sweden, Poland and Netherlands. Moreover, “To improve water retention” was a challenge that got rather high mean for all countries. The challenge with highest individual mean was Spain having a mean of 6.22 for “Desealing artificial surfaces” followed by “To avoid soil sealing” (also Spain; mean 6.11). When comparing all three surveys, those two challenges were the ones that got the highest mean.

When comparing total means, “To decrease soil erosion” got the lowest ranking (3.97) – although ranging from 2.32 in The Netherlands to 5.44 in Spain. It is worth noting that in Spain all suggested challenges got a mean that was above 5. It is also a bit surprising that Netherlands, which is the most densely populated country, does not judge soil sealing or desealing to be a problem. Just like the other two surveys, there are challenges with high standard deviation, meaning that there are large differences in scoring – either between different professions or between regions. When prioritising which issues to work on in a country, it is thus important to let regions decide where to focus efforts so that resources are used wisely.

	Sweden	Denmark	Poland	Netherlands	Spain	Total
To increase organic matter	4.03 (1.40)	2.62 (1.29)	4.81 (1.66)	3.45 (1.64)	5.17 (1.17)	3.99 (1.70)
To improve water retention	4.89 (1.1)	5.38 (1.43)	5.12 (1.65)	5.48 (1.36)	5.56 (2.06)	5.23 (1.49)
To improve soil fertility	4.13 (1.24)	3.29 (1.45)	4.88 (1.37)	3.32 (1.53)	5.56 (1.89)	4.19 (1.68)
To increase soil biodiversity	5.13 (1.42)	4.33 (1.78)	5.00 (1.30)	3.97 (1.91)	5.11 (2.16)	4.67 (1.76)
To decrease soil erosion	3.84 (1.60)	4.24 (1.60)	4.77 (1.34)	2.32 (1.25)	5.44 (1.83)	3.97 (1.80)
To decrease soil compaction	4.34 (1.46)	3.71 (1.48)	4.54 (1.52)	3.84 (1.87)	5.67 (1.56)	4.33 (1.67)
To avoid soil sealing	5.39 (1.01)	3.14 (1.25)	4.69 (1.66)	3.87 (1.68)	6.11 (1.29)	4.70 (1.74)
Desealing artificial surfaces	4.79 (1.42)	3.71 (1.20)	4.65 (1.44)	2.10 (1.40)	6.22 (1.27)	4.20 (1.91)
Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation	5.29 (1.19)	4.95 (1.50)	4.92 (1.44)	5.48 (1.13)	5.44 (2.01)	5.19 (1.44)
To avoid or remediate contamination of soils/soil pollution	5.47 (1.31)	5.81 (1.37)	5.15 (1.59)	5.81 (1.33)	5.72 (1.48)	5.57 (1.45)
Recycling/Reuse of soils	4.74 (1.43)	5.90 (1.31)	4.38 (1.69)	4.84 (1.69)	5.67 (1.20)	4.98 (1.60)

Table CC-Q16U. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?” The respondents were presented with a matrix where they rated each challenge individually on a 1-7 Likert scale (1=Not at all; 7=To a very large extent). The question did not involve prioritizing the challenges listed. The table presents mean values and standard deviation in brackets. Green marked boxes indicate that the mean ≤ 3 and red boxes that the mean ≥ 5 . The challenge with the highest mean for each country and the total is marked with bold numbers.

4.3.4. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

In an open-ended question (Q19), the respondents had the possibility to share ideas about what they perceived as hindrances to improved urban soil health in their region/country. Table CC-Q19U

summarizes the themes mentioned in country reports. Just like the other two surveys, there are common themes between countries – as well as recurring themes between the surveys. As can be seen, all countries mentioned *lack of knowledge/awareness* and *lack of political governance* as two hindrances.

	Denmark	Netherlands	Poland	Spain	Sweden
Hindrances for improved urban soil health	Economic & regulations hindrances: minimal legal requirements + regulation insufficiently comprehensive Lack of general understanding of soil health concept + importance of soil functions in urban settings	Urban area is limited Limited knowledge/awareness of urban soils Urban soil health not prioritized in policies and decisions	Legal aspects: lack of legal regulations & investment pressure Educational and administrative aspects: lack of awareness & lack of land use plans Environmental aspects: soil sealing, disturbed water retention, improper management	Lack of political interest and social awareness Lack of knowledge among technicians and professionals working with soil Absence of sustainable drainage systems Poor urban planning Prioritization of economic criteria over environmental ones	High pressure on land Conflict of interests: need to build more and improve economy The political governance: there are no governing documents that regulates how ecosystem services are to be safeguarded Lack of knowledge/awareness

Table CC-Q19U. Perceived hindrances for improved soil health as mentioned by the urban respondents (open-ended question)

In the following question, the respondents were invited to suggest measures to the perceived hindrances. In all countries, the need for competence development in soil health issues and a clearer governance were mentioned.

4.3.5. Competence development

As for many other questions, also the ones concerning relevant topics for competence development and preferred formats for competence development measures differed a lot between the countries. In Figure CC-Q21U and Figure CC-Q23U the answer options with the highest total mean values are presented. Among the suggested topics, two topics got votes from over 50% of the respondents, namely “The soil health concept in general” (59%) and “How to assess soil health (for specific land use functions)” (54%). When looking at preferred formats for competence development measures, live webinars got the highest ranking (53%), followed by via good examples (47%) (Figure CC-Q23F). In the figure, it becomes clear that certain measures were more appreciated by respondents from some countries than from others. For example, digital courses were preferred by 74% of the Swedish respondents, but only by 12% of the Polish respondents.

Just like the other two surveys, the urban survey did not provide any data on how much competence development measures that are *de facto* available for this stakeholder group. However, and similar to the other surveys, a large proportion of the respondents did not know if there were adequate measures available for them or not (total mean 36%). Moreover, 39% of the Spanish respondents answered “not at all” (total mean 10%). Among the participating countries, The Netherlands and Poland had the largest share of participants who gave a positive answer to the question (approximately 40% voted 5-7). In Spain, that proportion was only 6%. Obviously, this is a question to focus on during the coming years also for the urban sector.

Figure CC-Q21U. “Which urban soil related topics would you like to learn more about?” The full list of suggested topics can be found in Appendix 3, question 21.

Table CC-Q22U. “Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?”

Table CC-Q23U. “I would like to learn more about urban soil health through” The full list of suggested methods can be found in Appendix 3, question 23.

Chapter 5. Soil health awareness among key stakeholders in agricultural, forest and urban land uses: Country reports

This chapter also reports the findings from the quantitative surveys, but on a more detailed country level. The first sub-chapter presents and discusses the results from Denmark (5.1), followed by Germany (5.2), The Netherlands (5.3), Poland (5.4) Spain (5.5) and lastly Sweden (5.6). France decided to not write a chapter to present and discuss their data. However, their answers are included in the total means, and in Chapter 4.1 their results from the agricultural survey are presented.

All country reports follow the same structure. In the first part, the study regions are presented and the national soil (health) and environmental discourse is described. In the second part, the respondents are presented. The third part presents the results from the quantitative survey. Depending on the number of answered surveys each country had per survey, this part consists of 1-3 sections (agriculture/forest/urban). In the fourth part, the survey data are discussed, followed by policy recommendations in the fifth part. Each country report ends with a number of key messages.

5.1. Country report: Denmark

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5.1.1. Introduction to study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study regions

Denmark is a relatively small country in Northern Europe, with an area of just under 43,000 km² [1]. The surface in Denmark consists primarily of morainic post-glacial landscapes in the east, with glaciofluvial plains in the west of the Jutland peninsula and uplifted Holocene marine sediments in the north [2]. The gentle, low-lying terrain that characterizes the Danish landscape combined with a temperate coastal climate, gives good conditions for agriculture, which is the dominant land-use type covering approximately 59.5% of the total land area. Forests, in turn, cover 13.4% of the country's surface, while heaths and all other types of terrestrial nature account for just under 9%. Finally, urban areas cover 7.6% of the total surface, with roads and other infrastructure accounting for a further 5.6% [1].

Denmark is officially divided into five political Regions: North Jutland (Region Nordjylland), Middle Jutland (Region Midtjylland), Southern Denmark (Region Syddanmark), Zealand (Region Sjælland) and the Capital Region (Region Hovedstaden). Given the small size of the political Regions, however, in this assessment we consider three larger study regions corresponding approximately to the country's main landscape components, namely, East Denmark, Mid and South Jutland, and North Jutland (Figure DK-1).

East Denmark, similarly to region A7 in the PREPSOIL Soil Needs Assessment, covers the islands of Zealand (which contains the Capital Region) and Funen, as well as most of the smaller islands in the Danish Archipelago. This study region is characterized by loamy moraine soils, and a drier and warmer climate relative to the rest of the country [3]. Of the approximately 13,000 km² covered by this study region, 59% is in agricultural land-use, which is dominated by arable agriculture in terms of both total area usage and number of specialized farms, with only a little over a quarter of the agricultural area in the region dedicated to livestock [4, 5]. Although less than a third of the country by area, East Denmark is home to 54% of the Danish population and contains several of the largest urban centers in the country, including the Greater Copenhagen area and Odense, respectively the largest and third largest cities in Denmark. Finally, 29% of all forests in Denmark are located in East Denmark, corresponding to 12.5% of the region's land area [6]. This includes Gribskov, the fourth largest contiguous forest in the country (56km²). Although the general trend in Denmark is an increase in forest land-use at a rate of 35 km² per year [7], the forest area in East Denmark has shrunken by 7 km² between 2011 and 2021, according to national statistics [6].

Mid and South Jutland covers an area of approximately 21,800 km² in the continental portion of Denmark reaching from the German border in the south to the area around the Mariager inlet and the Limfjord sound in the north. The landscape in Mid and South Jutland includes most of the sandy glaciofluvial soils in Denmark, particularly on the western half of the peninsula. As with Denmark as a whole, agriculture is the principal land-use type in Mid and South Jutland, accounting for 62% of the region's surface. In terms of area, agricultural soil is used predominantly for keeping livestock, mostly cattle and other grazing livestock, although the region has a slightly higher number of individual farms dedicated to field crops [4, 5]. Mid and South Jutland is home to six of the ten largest urban centers in the country outside of Greater Copenhagen, including Aarhus, Denmark's second most populous city. These urban centers are home to 613,386 inhabitants as of 2023, or just under 30% of the study

region's population [8, 9]. Forest in Mid and South Jutland covers just over 3100 km², corresponding to 14.4% of the study region's area and 54.6% of all the forests in the country. Furthermore, Mid and South Jutland contains the municipality of Silkeborg, which has both the greatest total and relative forested areas in all of Denmark, at 246 km² and 28.9% respectively [6]. This includes two of the tree largest forests in Denmark, namely Silkeborgskovene (224km²) and Klosterheden (64 km²).

North Jutland, the area north of the Limfjord, contains only a moderate portion of Denmark's total soil organic carbon stocks, with 9% (50.3 Tg) of the country's total SOC stocks in under 20% of the surface area [10]. However, North Jutland contains the two largest raised bogs in Denmark, including Lille Vildmose, the largest remaining active raised bog in the Northern European Plain (Belgium, Denmark, the Netherlands, northern Germany and northern Poland) [11]. Like in the rest of Jutland, the principal land-use type in North Jutland is agriculture, with most of the area dedicated to grazing and other livestock, and roughly equal numbers of individual cropping and livestock farms [4, 5]. North Jutland contains Rold Skov the second largest forest in Denmark (80 km²), although overall forests cover just under 12% of the region's surface area. Finally, Denmark's fourth largest urban center by population, the city of Aalborg, is found in North Jutland, home to 120,000 inhabitants and by far the largest urban center in the region.

Figure DK-1. Study regions and map of soils of Denmark. Surface geology map elaborated by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) (version 2, 2011).

National soil health and environmental discourse

The principal environmental concern in agricultural land use in Denmark since the 1980's has been reducing nutrient emissions from agriculture and avoiding the negative effects from nutrient pollution in freshwater and coastal environments [3]. Thus, a significant portion of the soil and environment-related discussion at a national level currently centers on the government's fertilizer and agrochemical application restrictions for farmers. The resulting plans and regulations, although relatively strict and initially successful [3], are seen by environmental groups as too lax, allowing for the pollution of aquatic ecosystems and ground water resources with nutrients and pesticides from agriculture (e.g., The Local 2024 [12]).

Only recently, other soil issues such as greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration in soil, as well as improving the quality/health of soils have begun to be widely discussed. However, present policy goals for greenhouse gas emission reductions are ambitious, e.g., cutting national emissions by 70% by 2030, and particular focus falls on the agricultural sector. This is for instance reflected in the climate goals set out by the Danish government in a 2021 political agreement for the green transition of the agricultural sector [13] and more recently, the Danish Green Tripartite Agreement, to be

implemented gradually starting in 2025 . For instance, the political agreement states the goal of establishing 100,000 ha of permanent set-aside, including 88,500 ha of low-laying peaty soils. Furthermore, there is an increasing political interest in Denmark regarding climate change adaptation of the agricultural sector, which naturally includes protecting agricultural soils from current and future negative effects brought by rising temperatures and increasingly intense and unpredictable weather patterns [14].

On a more localized level, the dominant soil-related issues in Danish agricultural soils are soil compaction (most prevalent in the loamy soils of eastern Denmark), soil erosion (wind-related in the west and tillage and water-related in the east) and loss of soil organic carbon due in part to the widespread use of mineral fertilizers over animal manures in arable land, particularly in eastern Denmark [15]. Additionally, nearly half of all agricultural land in Denmark is artificially drained to avoid water waterlogging [16]. These drainage systems can be affected by compaction, damaged or undersized drainage pipes [17], and by climate change, which in Denmark leads to wetter winters, and increased risk of extreme rainfall events[18]. These changes contribute to rising issues with flooded and waterlogged fields, which have garnered attention in both national and agricultural media in recent years (e.g., tvmidtvest 2018[19], Politikken 2020[20], Ingeniøren 2024[21])

Denmark has experienced net afforestation since the 1950's, and this trend is expected to continue throughout the 21st century, consisting primarily of agricultural land turned over to either forestry or forest natural areas. The effects of this change on soil health, however, are highly dependent on the level of management newly afforested areas receive. State forests, although a small fraction of the total forests in Denmark have all been fully converted to nature-based forest management, and are expected to carry out significant carbon sequestration, especially in the soil, over the next 100 years [22]. The principal environmental and soil-related issues discussed in Denmark in relation to forests, forest management and forestry are related to the overwhelming share of forest area in Denmark dedicated to forestry. This has led to a decrease in biodiversity in the living tree stock, as well as a widespread reduction in the age of standing tress, as well as removal of dead tree biomass [7]. Additionally, there are concerns regarding soil compaction in managed forest soil due to the use of heavy machinery. Finally, although seldom nowadays in Denmark, practices such as clear-cutting and drainage and ditching of wet forest soils in the past have likely led to a loss of soil organic matter in both mineral and peaty forest soils [22, 23]. In turn, all these factors are known to result in a loss of plant, animal and microbial biodiversity in forest soils[24].

In Danish urban and settled areas, the most notable soil-related issues which have recently received national media attention involve soil pollution. A few notable examples include the use of contaminated soil in the construction of the Lynetteholmen islet, a major harbor expansion project in Copenhagen[25], a large landslide from a contaminated soil landfill near Randers[26], as well as suspicions of PFAS contamination in thousands of private grounds[27] and confirmed soil and groundwater PFAS contamination around a military airfield[28].

Outside the issues of soil pollution, urban soil in Denmark may face challenges related to development planning and soil cover, despite a general perception that Danish urban centers are green. Atwell [29] found that provincial towns in Denmark suffer from a predominance of non-functional lawn which have little tree or shrub cover and thus provide minimal biodiversity and human welfare benefits, even when they appear as widespread green areas on paper. In recent years there have been multiple initiatives from ministries (e.g. "Together for a WILDER Denmark"[30]), the Danish broadcasting corporation (e.g. DR [31]), companies (e.g. Arla [32]), private organizations (e.g. "Wild on purpose" [33]) aimed at increasing biodiversity in urban areas.

5.1.2. The respondents

A total of 256 people were identified as relevant stakeholders and contacted as potential survey respondents. The main criterion for selection was a professional involvement in activities which affected or relied to some extent on soil functions in each of the three land-use types considered (agricultural, forestry/nature and urban). This included agricultural and forestry advisors, municipal civil servants involved with city planning, as well as employees in architectural and engineering consultancies and construction firms. A secondary criterion involved trying to keep a balanced proportion between potential respondents whose professional activities fell predominantly within a single study region. Finally, a number of researchers whose academic areas of interest involved agricultural soils, forest and natural environments and urban environments at a broader geographical scale were also contacted. Of these, 145 people initiated the survey and 57 completed it (Table DK-1). Due to a low completion rate for the forest-related survey, this category is omitted from the rest of the analysis.

	Number of candidates		
	approached	initiating the survey	completing the survey
Agricultural survey	81	54	28
Forest survey	82	31	8
Urban survey	93	60	21
In total	256	145	57

Table DK-1. Number of people approached for the survey, initiating and completing the survey.

The geographical distribution of the work of respondents that answered the second question in the survey is fairly even for urban land use, although the national level is slightly underrepresented. On the other hand, the distribution of the agricultural respondents is highly skewed towards the national level and Mid and South Jutland while North Jutland is underrepresented with only one respondent. This is also true for the number of people approached for the survey where fewer candidates from North Jutland were approached (Table DK-2).

Danish respondents	East Denmark	Mid- and south Jutland	North Jutland	In total
Total (agriculture/urban)				
Municipality characterized with a large proportion of forest and nature areas	Hillerød 0	Lemvig 0	Mariagerfjord 0	0
Municipality characterized with a large proportion of urban areas	Copenhagen 5 (2/3)	Esbjerg 1 (0/1)	Aalborg 4 (0/4)	10
Municipality characterized with a large proportion of agricultural areas	Ringsted 0	Ringkøbing-skjern 1 (1/0)	Brønderslev 1 (0/1)	2
Regional	5 (3/2)	17 (12/5)	5 (0/5)	27
National	9 (7/2)			9
Other	7 (4/3)			7

Table DK-2. Distribution of respondents on municipality, regional or national level

The distribution of the Danish respondents that answered the second question in relation to whether they work at municipality, regional or national level, was very skewed towards the regional level. This is especially true for Mid- and South Jutland, with 17 of the respondents working at regional level as opposed to only two working at municipality level. The Danish urban respondents tend to be more

evenly distributed with nine respondents working at municipality level and 12 working at regional level, and only 2 at national level. No respondents worked at municipality level with forest/nature.

Some of the stakeholders we contacted reported difficulties in answering the survey questions due to unfamiliarity with some of the terms used. The absence of an 'I don't know' option may have led to respondents with limited knowledge or those not directly working with soil to not complete the survey.

5.1.3. Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the Danish survey data. The chapter consists of two sections – one for the agricultural survey and one for the urban survey. The forestry survey is omitted due to lack of respondents. In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the surveys (see Appendix 1 and 3). The prefix DK indicates that the figures belong to the Danish chapter and the suffix A or U indicates which survey they belong to (Agriculture or Urban).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

Of the 28 Danish respondents who completed the agriculture survey, seven worked at national level, 15 at regional level with 12 in the region of Mid and South Jutland, 3 in East Denmark and none in North Jutland (Q1) (Table DK-1). This means that the study regions East Denmark and North Jutland are underrepresented in the answers. The lack of respondents from North Jutland can be compensated to a certain degree by the respondents from Mid and South Jutland, as the two regions have similar proportions of agricultural land, as well as similar distributions among different agricultural activities. However, the lack of respondents from North Jutland means that important perspectives regarding agriculture on peaty and organic soils might be underrepresented. Only three respondents reported working at municipality level.

When asked to indicate one or more areas in which they were professionally involved with soil health (Q2), 43% of Danish respondents selected “research”, while 35% selected policy work and only 29% selected advisory work. Interestingly, the share of respondents who indicated working in advisory work is well below the total frequency among respondents across countries, which was 50%. Similarly, the percentage of respondents who indicated a background in nature conservation was lower than the share across all participating countries (11% in Dk vs 22 % in total).

In terms of the extent to which soil issues form part of their work (Q3), about 36% of Danish respondents selected the highest option “to a very large extent”, which is nearly the same rate as across all countries. However, a larger portion of the Danish respondents judged their work involvement in soil health as low (cat. 1-3), compared to respondents across countries (29% in Dk vs. 21% in total).

Although most types of employment for respondents (Q4) did not differ much between Danish and overall respondents, a considerably higher share of Danish respondents (43%) indicated that they are employed by an academic institution (e.g., university), compared to overall respondents (24%). In turn, there were no Danish respondents employed by a national authority (0%) compared to 15% across the other countries. Likewise, a considerable share of respondents (46%) hold an academic (i.e., PhD/doctoral) degree, while only about 32% hold master’s/engineering degree (Q5). This is quite different from the distribution among respondents across countries, where non-academic long secondary educations are the most common.

Most of the respondents were educated within the agricultural sciences (61%) and natural sciences/engineering (18%) (Q6), and most have studied soil sciences (82%) (Q7) and received further training on soil health related issues (75%) (Q8). This corresponds well with the respondents rating of their own needs in relation to knowledge concerning soil (Q10), where 25% rated themselves as “excellent”. This is higher than across all countries (15%), although the share of Danish respondents that rated their knowledge in the second highest score was smaller than that of all countries combined. The average score for Denmark was 5.18, while the average score across countries was 4.87. In general, the respondents were experienced within the field of soil related issues (Q10), with 75% having more than 5 years of working experience within this field.

Figure DK-Q2A. “In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to...”

Figure DK-Q3A. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent” Mean for Denmark 5.11 and for the total 5.21.

Figure DK-Q4A. "I am employed by..."

Figure DK-Q6A. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure DK-Q9A. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?" Mean value for Denmark 5.18 and for the total 4.87.

The respondents and the soil health concept

Regarding the question of sharing the EU Commissions view on unhealthy soil (Q11) there is close correspondence between the Danish results and the overall results, both having an average score of 5.21 on a scale of 1-7. Likewise, the majority of respondents (61% in Dk and 55% in total, pooled for cat. 5-7) agree more with the definition of soil health as the ability to sustain a broad range of ecosystem services, while a minor fraction (14% in DK and 17% in total, pooled for cat. 1-3) agree more with the perspective that soil health is the ability to sustain plant growth (Q12). The average score is 4.93 for Denmark and 4.84 for the total.

The Danish respondents also agree that *soil health* is a relevant concept in agriculture (Q13a), with an average a little higher than average for the total group of respondents (6.21 in Dk vs. 6.07 across countries). More than half of the Danish respondents (57%, cat. 5-7) agree that the agricultural sector already uses *soil health* as a concept (Q13b) while this proportion is only 45% of the total number of respondents across countries. The average score is 4.75 in Dk vs 4.25 in total. This corresponds well with the answers to “how knowledgeable you are regarding the soil health concept in general” (Q14a). Close to half of the respondents (46%) assess that they are very knowledgeable (cat. 6 and 7 on a scale of 7) while this is only true for 30% of respondents across countries. A similar picture appears in the question “how knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health” (Q14b). In this case 64% of the Danish respondents assess themselves as very knowledgeable (kat. 6 and 7, on a scale of 7), while 42% of the total respondents assess themselves as such.

Possibly, because many of Danish respondents already consider the soil health concept as integrated into the agricultural sector, fewer of the Danish respondents believe that an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture would imply a paradigm shift in the field (Q15a). Hence, 39% of the respondents fall into the categories 1-3 (where 1 is no paradigm shift) compared to 16 % of the total respondents, and only 7% of the Danish respondents think that it requires a large shift in paradigm. The corresponding figure for the total group of respondents is 26%.

There is a similar pattern in regard to the Danish responses to “to what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues” (Q15b). The average for the Danish respondents is 3.36, while the average for the total group of respondents is 4.05. There is a tendency for higher scores in categories 1 and 2 when addressing mindshift in workplaces (18% for cat. 1 and 11% for cat. 2) compared to mindshifts in agriculture in general (11% in cat. 1 and 4% in cat. 2), indicating that the soil health concept is perceived better integrated in the workplaces (research institutes, administrative offices, and advisory companies, see Description of respondents) than in the general agricultural practice.

Figure DK-Q11A. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)”? Mean value for Denmark 5.21 and for the total 5.21.

Figure DK-Q13aA. “To what extent do you agree on following: Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture” Mean value for Denmark 6.21 and for the total 6.07.

Figure DK-Q13bA. “To what extent do you agree on following: The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept” Mean value for Denmark 4.75 and for the total 4.25.

Figure DK-Q14aA. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?”. Mean value for Denmark 5.43 and for the total 4.76.

Figure DK-Q14bA. “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?”. Mean value for Denmark 5.57 and for the total 5.03.

Figure DK-Q15aA. To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?. Mean value for Denmark 4.18 and for the total 5.12.

Figure DK-Q15bA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues? Mean value for Denmark 3.36 and for the total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the region and soil challenges that the respondents work with

The Danish respondents rate the following agricultural soil challenges (Q16) higher than the total across country-average: increasing soil organic matter, increasing soil biodiversity, improving water retention/infiltration/drainage, improve nutrient cycling, decrease soil compaction and managing peatlands. However, of all these challenges, only "managing peatlands" was ranked considerably higher than the overall average across countries. This stands out with a Danish average score of 5.89

compared to the total average score of 4.24, particularly given the expected underrepresentation of this issue due to a low response rate from North Jutland. This corresponds well with the issues presented in 1.2 National soil health and environmental discourse. In the Atlantic European environmental zone, which covers most of Denmark, agriculture has been less susceptible to drought compared to most other European countries and hence the Danish respondents score considerably lower than the overall respondents to the soil challenges “decrease salinization” and “decrease desertification”, with averages of 1.46 vs 2.97 for desertification, and 2.21 vs. 3.27 for salinization. When asked about other soil-related challenges (Q17), Danish respondents mentioned few additional issues, but brought up the issue of nutrient pollution from agriculture, which remains a highly relevant problem in the country. The average ratings for the degree at which workplaces deal with different soil challenges (Q18) among Danish respondents followed a nearly identical pattern.

Figure DK-Q16A. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure DK-Q18A. “To what extent do your workplace deal with the following challenges in agricultural soils?”.

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

The hindrances for improved soil health (Q19) identified by Danish participants centered around four main topics: lack of relevant information/education, continued intensification and expansion of Danish

agriculture, economic conflicts and lack of political will to support/implement systemic changes. Some interesting examples are the conflict between selling crop biomass for biogas production vs. preserving it in the soil to protect organic carbon content, lack of political will to make room for emerging practices in regulation and a lack of general understanding/agreement on the concept of soil health.

When asked to propose measures to address these hindrances (Q20), respondents suggested a broad range of action areas, although a majority did not suggest concrete actions.

The most common action area, suggested by 6 out of 18 Danish participants, was a need for changes in Danish and European policies (e.g., the Common Agricultural Policy). Here, the common theme was that more or more strict regulations are not needed. Instead, respondents expressed a need for policies promoting practices and systems that protect and improve soil health (opposite to dictating actions and punishing pollution), but which also preserve and increase the farmer's freedom of practice within the overall systems.

The second most common action area, proposed by four participants, was the need for a more practice-oriented approach by regulators and researchers, where the economic, material and social perspectives are included. Here, respondents highlighted the need to consider practical aspects of agriculture, such as income losses or trade-offs associated with sustainable practices in research and regulations, as well as the applicability of soil health initiatives in concrete local communities. One participant here called for the direct involvement of researchers and regulators in concrete practical settings, meaning direct involvement in debates, communication of knowledge and co-development of concrete solutions.

Other measures proposed by Danish respondents included promoting a holistic focus in farming and agronomy educations (2 respondents), promoting a market and product chain for plant-based food and green biorefined products, particularly to increase human consumption of plant-based foods (2 respondents) and, finally, taxing, conversion and set-aside of agricultural lands in key strategic environments, such as soil carbon-rich areas (2 participants).

Competence development

When asked to select at least one soil-related topic they wished to know more about (Q21), over half Danish respondents pointed out climate change adaptation (53%), assessment/monitoring of soil health (57%) and soil management strategies for soil health (e.g., sustainable or regenerative practices) (57%), all at a higher rate than among respondents across countries. This suggests that Danish respondents are particularly interested in the process of identifying and solving soil health issues in the future. Interestingly, fewer respondents indicated a desire to know more about the concept of soil health in general compared to all respondents across countries (36% vs. 43 %, respectively), suggesting that they themselves feel sufficiently informed on the general topic. Danish responses to this question corresponded otherwise with the general pattern across all participant countries.

As with respondents across all participating countries, a large share of Danish respondents did not know whether there existed soil health-related competence development opportunities which were relevant for them (Q22). However, when asked which avenues for further learning on soil health they were interested in (Q23), Danish respondents chose physical courses, webinars, podcasts and reports (publications) at considerable higher rates than respondents overall across countries.

Finally, two additional comments regarding soil health in agriculture (Q24) were received, where respondents asked for support for advisors in communicating with farmers regarding important soil health topics, as well as highlighting the importance of returning organic matter to the soil.

The urban survey

Description of the respondents

Of the 21 Danish respondents who completed the urban survey, two worked at national level, 12 at regional level, with two in East Denmark and five in both Mid and South Jutland and in North Jutland (Table DK-1). Finally, nine respondents worked at municipality level. This suggests that the survey achieved a relatively equal representation of the different regions. However, the overall response rate for urban land-use was low, and it is obvious from Q2 (working background), that the Danish respondents differ the overall respondents across countries.

When asked to point out one or more soil issues that they deal with professionally (Q2), most Danish respondents selected environmental issues (67%), recycling/reuse of soils (57%), while notable fractions selected urban planning (33%) and exercise of authority (19%). Considerably more respondents indicated that they work with recycling/reuse of soils in Denmark than in all countries combined (57% in Dk vs 27% in total) while respondents across countries are better represented in the categories “maintenance” (18% in total vs 5% in Dk), “urban planning” (50% in total vs 33% in Dk), “policy work” (23% in total vs 10% in Dk) and “research” (16% in total vs 0% in Dk). Consequently, the professional background of respondents from Dk is not fully aligned with the background of the other participating countries.

Overall, an absolute majority (57%) of Danish respondents in the urban category reported to work with soil related issues to a very large extent (Q3), which surpasses the rate reported across participating countries (42%). However, this is largely compensated for by fewer Danish respondents choosing the second and third highest ranks.

Danish respondents also differed from the respondents overall in terms of the sector in which they were employed (Q4). Here, a large share of respondents indicated that they worked in private companies (52% vs 15% in total), and fewer for regional authorities (38% in Dk vs 57% in total). This is quite different from the distribution across countries, which is dominated by public sector employees.

Danish respondents of the urban survey, unlike in the agricultural survey, had a very similar educational background to that of the participants across countries (Q5). Here, over 76% of respondents have completed a long secondary education (masters/engineer degree), while only 5% have a PhD/doctoral degree, and approximately 19% have completed a short secondary education or less.

In terms of their specific educational topic (Q6), the majority of urban land-use respondents in Denmark reported an educated within the environmental (43%) and natural sciences/engineering (29%), and approximately 24% reported the topic of their education as “other”. Furthermore, a majority of Danish urban respondents reported having studied soil sciences (57%, Q7) and about half (52%) reported receiving training on soil health related issues (Q8). This corresponds well with Danish urban respondents rating of their knowledge of soil issues relative to their professional needs (Q9), where 57% rated themselves as either “excellent” or “next to excellent”. This is considerable higher than across countries (34% for the two highest ranks pooled), where fewer respondents reported receiving education (45% in total, Q7) and training (33%, Q8) in soil issues. However, there is also a noticeable share of Danish urban respondents who assess their own knowledge as close to deficient (cat. 3: 19%, Q9).

Finally, Danish respondents have generally a long professional experience with soil related issues (Q10), with over half (57%) having more than 10 years of working experience within this field. This is similar to the results reported across all participating countries.

Figure DK-Q2U. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to..."

Figure DK-Q3U. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent" Mean for Denmark 5.62 and for the total 5.51.

Figure DK-Q4U. "I am employed by..."

Figure DK-Q6U. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Figure DK-Q9U. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value for Denmark 5.19 and for the total 4.62.

The respondents and the soil health concept

When asked to what extent they agreed with the statement made by the EU, that a majority of soil in Europe are in poor health (Q11), nearly half of Danish respondents (48%) expressed that they strongly agreed. An equal share (48%) expressed neutral points of view (ranks 4 and 5 out of 7). While there were no disagreements (cat. 1-3). This reflects largely the same pattern as that of respondents across countries. However, when asked about their agreement with either the targeted soil use or the ecosystem services perspectives for soil (Q12), urban respondents in Denmark primarily answered neutrally between the two (38% of respondents, cat. 4), and fully in favor of the targeted soil use perspective (24%, cat. 1), with only 14% responding in full agreement with the ecosystem services perspective (cat. 7), and few to no responses in partial agreement either way. This is quite different from the responses across all participating countries, which were more evenly split over the spectrum between the two perspectives, although with a visible skew towards the ecosystem services perspective.

The opinion of Danish respondents reflected a range of agreement on the relevance of the soil health concept for urban soils (Q13a), where 38% of respondents strongly agreed, and nearly all other respondents were evenly distributed across neutral to partially agreeing, with only one respondent partially disagreeing. In turn, Danish respondents mostly disagreed with the statement that the urban sector already implements the concept of soil health (Q13b), with 33% disagreeing strongly and most of the remainder answering either neutrally (24%) or in partial disagreement (29%). These responses mostly match the responses across countries, except for Q13b, where there were more neutral responses, at the cost of partial disagreements, among Danish respondents than overall across countries.

Danish urban respondents generally judged their own knowledge regarding soil health (Q14a) quite low, with two thirds of respondents choosing either the lowest rank (“not knowledgeable at all”) or the second lowest rank (33% each). This differs quite markedly from respondents across countries, whose judgement of their own knowledge regarding soil health was more evenly distributed across the response range, with a slight skew towards partially positive judgements. When asked specifically about their knowledge of the effects of management on soil health (Q14b), the responses in Denmark were considerably more positive, with 33% expressing a partially positive judgement and 67% of respondents choosing neutral to positive judgements. However, 23% of respondents still chose the second to lowest rank for their knowledge about management effects on soil health. In general, these responses resemble those of respondents across countries, except for the relatively high share that judged their knowledge as partially poor (cat. 2).

The opinions of Danish respondents were largely neutral with a slight skew towards partially negative regarding the extent to which implementing the concept of soil health in urban soil would imply a paradigm shift (Q15a). This is quite different from the general opinions expressed across countries, which were mostly partially and fully positive. Similarly, 61% of Danish respondents expressed a neutral stance and partial agreement (rank 5 of 7) when asked whether implementing the concept of soil health would lead to a change in how their workplace dealt with soil issues (Q15b), with 33% expressing complete or partial disagreement. These responses were largely similar to responses across participating countries.

Figure DK-Q11U. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to urban soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?” Mean value for Denmark 5.81 and for the total 5.60.

Figure DK-Q13aU. “To what extent do you agree on following: Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils”. Mean value for Denmark 5.62 and for the total 5.72.

Figure DK-Q13bU. “To what extent do you agree on following: The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept”. Mean value for Denmark 2.90 and for the total 2.50.

Figure DK-Q14aU. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value for Denmark 2.52 and for the total 3.71.

Figure DK-Q14bU. “How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?”. Mean value for Denmark 4.14 and for the total 4.00.

Figure DK-Q15aU. To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils imply a mindshift concerning soil? Mean value for Denmark 4.10 and for the total 5.24.

Figure DK-Q15bU. To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues? Mean value for Denmark 3.76 and for the total 4.59.

Soil challenges in the region & soil challenges that the respondents work with

Danish respondents answered rather differently to respondents across countries regarding relevant challenges in urban soils (Q16), where only “improving water retention”, “climate change adaptation” and “reducing and mitigating soil pollution” received similar average scores in Denmark as in the surveyed countries overall. In contrast, Danish respondents gave considerably lower scores to “decrease soil compaction” (mean Dk score 3.71 vs 4.33 in total), “avoid soil sealing” (mean Dk score 3.71 vs 4.20 in total), “improve soil fertility” (mean Dk score 4.29 vs 4.19 in total) and “increase soil organic matter” (mean Dk score 2.62 vs 3.99 in total), compared to respondents across countries.

Regarding soil challenges already dealt with in their workplace (Q18), Danish respondents gave considerably higher scores to “improve water retention/infiltration/drainage” (mean Dk score 5.05 vs 4.36 in total), “climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation” (mean Dk score 5.33 vs 4.70 in total), avoid or remediate contamination of soils/soil pollution” (mean Dk score 6.38 vs 5.20 in total), “recycling/reusing of soils” (mean Dk score 6.29 vs 4.57 in total) and “promote awareness of sustainable soil management” (mean Dk score 5.76 vs 4.31 in total) relative to respondents across countries.

Figure DK-Q16U. "To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?"

Figure DK-Q18U. "To what extent do your workplace deal with the following challenges in urban soils?"

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Danish respondents identified three hindrances for improved soil health in urban areas (Q19): economy, regulation, and awareness. The economic hindrance was expressed as a limiting factor where contractors and stakeholders adhere to the minimum legal requirements in terms of soil management in order to minimize expenses. In turn, the regulation hindrance was expressed in terms of it being insufficiently comprehensive, as well as too heavy and bureaucratic even when opportunities for better soil management exist. These two hindrances were primarily expressed together. Lack of awareness was expressed, firstly, as a lack of general understanding of the concept of soil health for urban land-use and, secondly, as a lack of public awareness of the importance of soil functions in urban settings.

The majority of the measures proposed by respondents (Q20) pertained regulations with a similar focus. Six out of 9 Danish respondents highlighted a need for changes in regulations governing urban soils to make them more effective, although most did not specify further. Concrete proposals here included harmonizing regulations at a national level, introducing maximum case processing times for

regulators, and adopting the precautionary principle in the use of chemicals in construction, shifting the burden of ensuring safety from public authorities to the chemical industry proving.

A single respondent proposed raising awareness of the climate and environmental relevance of good health in urban soils.

Competence development

When asked to select one or more soil-related topics they wished to learn more about (Q21), 62% of Danish urban respondents chose “recycling/reuse of soils”, 57% chose soil “pollution/remediation of soils” and 57% chose “soil management strategies to improve soil health”. Additionally, 42% of Danish respondents indicated an interest in learning more about the topic “the soil health concept in general” and 38% indicated interest in “how to assess soil health (for specific land use functions)”. These responses correspond broadly with responses across countries, although the interest among Danish respondents in recycling of soil and soil pollution was considerably higher than that of respondents overall, of whom only 42 % and 36%, respectively, picked these categories.

Similarly to respondents across countries, Danish urban respondents predominantly expressed not knowing whether competence development opportunities relevant for them exist (Q22). Specifically, 48% selected the option “I don’t know”, while 23% answered neutrally and partially positive (cat. 4 and 5). Finally Danish respondents expressed a desire to learn more about soil health in urban soils (Q23) from primarily formal channels, with 57% selecting webinars, 48% selecting physical courses, 48% digital courses, and 33% choosing reports. This is somewhat different to the responses across countries, where informal/personal channels such as “via good examples” and “field visits”, received considerably more attention.

5.1.4. Discussion

Denmark is a relatively small and homogeneous country. Despite recognizable environmental differences, such as the dominant landscape and soil types and a climatic gradient from east to west, the land-use distribution is dominated by agriculture throughout the country. Within agriculture, the documented soil challenges vary to a certain degree among the study regions, with more focus on the challenges of intensive arable agriculture in East Denmark, cattle farming in Middle and South Jutland, and the management of peaty soils in Northern Jutland. However, agricultural soils in all study regions experience all the documented challenges to a certain degree. The urban land-use soil issues identified here are also fairly homogeneous across Denmark, where low biodiversity from sealed soils and non-functional green areas (i.e. bare lawns) are evenly distributed throughout the country, and cases of soil pollution are punctual and not reserved to any particular region.

Respondents to the agriculture and urban surveys in Denmark were dominated by regional and national level actors, with very few selecting a particular municipality as their professional area of influence. This is likely related to the small size and relative homogeneity of the Danish landscape and soil-related activities, which makes it unlikely that a stakeholder’s involvement in soil issues would be limited to a small political boundary such as a municipality. Additionally, it is likely that few municipal government employees, whose work area would naturally fall within municipal boundaries, completed the survey in Denmark.

Stakeholders that completed the survey related to agricultural soils in Denmark generally considered themselves well-informed about soil health issues, already working with and having many years of experience in soil health issues and having received training specifically regarding soil health. Although

these responses were not very different from those the survey respondents overall, the Danish case did show a noticeable overrepresentation of academics involved in research institutions and universities. This is likely to color their overall responses, as the topic of soil health is already quite broadly embraced in the academic environment. Fortunately, this bias is not present among respondents of the survey related to urban soils. Here, respondent's background was largely the same in Denmark as overall across countries, with a majority of highly educated, non-academic professionals. On the other hand, a very large share of Danish respondents in the urban survey indicated that they work in the private sector, which likely introduces a bias of its own. Regardless, respondents in both the agricultural and urban surveys rated their own knowledge about soils as high, reflecting awareness and interest on the topic. Finally, it is important to recognize that the overall discussion of soil health and soil-related issues awareness in Denmark suffers the low response rate from stakeholders involved in forest land-use. Even though not a dominant land-use type as agriculture, forest areas and forestry remain important in the country, perhaps even more so due to their relative scarcity.

In spite of the concept of soil health being relatively new, the concept of soil health seems to be widely accepted in Denmark in the agricultural sector, as reflected by the broad agreement of respondents with the ecosystem services perspective on soil health, as well as a majority judging their own knowledge of the concept positively. On the other hand, the concept did not appear to be as widely supported among respondents of the urban survey in Denmark, as most respondents were either noncommittal about the different perspectives on soil or preferred the targeted soil use perspective over an ecosystem services view. This sets Danish urban survey respondents apart from respondents across countries, and suggests that the concept of soil health in urban settings is not very well-understood among urban stakeholders in Denmark. Nevertheless, there appears to be a general recognition of the need for a concept of soil health in some form, as Danish urban survey respondents largely agreed that soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils.

The geographical and environmental conditions in Denmark are reflected in the respondents' priorities regarding soil health challenges. There was a strong focus among the agricultural survey respondents around the issues previously documented across the country (e.g., nutrient cycling, water infiltration, increasing soil organic matter, etc.) and very little importance was given to the issues of salinization and desertification. Interestingly, even though the region of North Jutland was underrepresented among agricultural survey respondents, managing peatlands was the highest ranked soil challenge in Denmark. This suggests that the potential for carbon sequestration/mitigation of emissions from improving the management of organic and peaty soils in Denmark is widely known and acknowledged. Interestingly, the topic of increasing organic carbon content in soils was given very low priority among Danish urban survey respondents, also compared to respondents across countries. Otherwise, the priorities indicated for urban soils in Denmark relate quite well to already documented challenges, with strong focus for soil pollution and recycling/reusing of soils, some importance given to increasing biodiversity. Interestingly, high importance was also given to climate change adaptation and improving water retention, infiltration and drainage in urban soils, with suggests and awareness of flooding as a relevant challenge in urban areas.

Respondents to both agricultural and urban surveys identified a lack of awareness and/or education on the concept and importance of soil health as a major hindrance to improving soil health in their respective environments in Denmark. Here, however, agricultural respondents focused more on increasing awareness and education of key actors, including policy makers, regarding concrete management systems and actions beneficial to soil health. Urban respondents, on the other hand, focused on increasing awareness of the importance of soils more generally. Besides this, both groups

identified the economic aspect, in which caring for soil health is perceived to come with implicit economic trade-offs, as a hindrance for adopting soil health-minded management. Finally, both groups expressed that more comprehensive, aggressive and straightforward regulations and incentives aimed at protecting and improving soil health are necessary on behalf of Danish authorities. Here, it is relevant to point out that there were no respondents to either survey in Denmark who were involved in national-level government or regulatory agencies, so their perspective is not included.

5.1.5. Implications for policy

From a policy perspective, agricultural and urban soils appear to be at different stages of the process towards better soil health. Stakeholders in agricultural soils, on the one hand, appear to be widely aware and involved in the topic of soil health and mostly require space and incentives within the existing regulatory frameworks in Denmark and in the EU overall. Wider room for soil health-minded management initiatives within the relatively strict agricultural regulation in Denmark was mentioned specifically by survey respondents, as were incentive-based schemes for improving soil health. A change in this direction, of course, would need to be balanced with a stronger focus in research and monitoring of emerging practices in order to ensure good intentions translate into actual soil health and environmental benefits.

On the other hand, stakeholders in urban settings appear to require greater outreach, information and education regarding both the concept and the importance of soil health. Once the ecosystem services perspective of soils and soil health is more widely acknowledged, the survey results suggest that a stronger regulatory focus is needed regarding soil pollution and the use/reuse of potentially polluted soils, as well as ensuring urban soils are resilient to a changing climate in Denmark. Additionally, we would argue that the issues of soil sealing and de-sealing artificial surfaces (as well as ensuring that existing green areas are actually capable of functioning as such), need to be given more importance, as they are relevant for a wide range of soil-related ecosystem services and are currently not widely perceived as important.

5.1.6. Key messages

1. There is a clear need for Danish agricultural practitioners to engage directly with authorities and researchers in concrete soil health-related discussion, research and implementation initiatives. This represents an opportunity to capitalize on the existing awareness and engagement regarding soil health by making use of the Living Labs concept.
2. The existing awareness of soil health could support a shift in agricultural policy from pollution avoidance to promoting sustainable practices which protect and promote soil health, so long as issues like nutrient pollution and greenhouse gas emissions are included as key elements of soil health in the Danish agricultural context. This presents the potential double benefit of addressing societal and global concerns such as marine eutrophication and climate change, while supporting farmers in the adoption of sustainable practices they, or their communities of practice, are interested in.
3. There is a need for increasing awareness of the importance of soils, the concept of soil health and an ecosystem services paradigm among Danish urban soil users, managers and regulators. Outreach and direct involvement of soil health advocates in discussions with all relevant urban stakeholders in Denmark is necessary.

4. Low engagement of forest-related stakeholders in this survey reflects low awareness of the concept of soil health in forest soils in Denmark. Outreach and soil health advocacy are necessary here.

5.2. Country report: Germany

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5.2.1. Introduction to the study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study region

The study focus area is the state of Brandenburg, which is in north-eastern Germany and covers 29.640 km². It is an excellent case study to represent modern agriculture in Europe, because it is an agricultural state characterized by intensive use; approximately 45% of its area is dedicated to intensive agricultural land use. Compared to other German states, Brandenburg shows a relatively high share of organic agriculture (12% of the agricultural area), and this share is continuously increasing (Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz (MLUK), 2019).

Brandenburg is representative for very large-scale high technology and industrialized agriculture. Farm sizes are among the largest in Europe (242 ha). With a mean daily high temperature of 14°C, Brandenburg is one of Germany's warmest regions. Out of the 5412 farms, 818 are currently operating as organic farms. Around a third of all agriculturally used land is arable, another third is used to produce forage for animals and another third is used by farms who combine livestock rearing with arable farming. Currently 38000 people are employed in the agricultural sector (3% of total employees in Brandenburg). The area suffers from low precipitation, and it is expected that climate change aggravates the situation so that farming may be economically non-viable in the future (Kipping 2020; Ihinegbu & Ogunwumi 2021). The low share of employees in the agricultural sectors does not correctly reflect its relevance for the economy, as agriculture plays an important role in managing ecosystem services and in the maintenance of cultural landscapes and rural development. And the overall economic output is estimated at 3.8 billion Euro annually. An additional 11500 people are employed in the upstream and downstream sector such as the food and fodder production (Landesregierung Brandenburg, 2023 a & b).

Figure DE-1. Soil fertility in Brandenburg, Germany.

Issue	High tech agriculture in combination with poor soils. Low precipitation aggravated climate change, increasing risk of drought and yield failures
Dominant land use	High Tech Agriculture
Secondary land use	Forestry; metropolitan region Berlin is spreading into Brandenburg
Climatic Zone	Continental
Soil WRB classification	Luvisols
Soil texture	Dominantly loamy sand, sandy loam; 4% organic soils
Dominant topsoil	Loamy sand and sandy loam
Soil threat	SOC decline, compaction, biodiversity decline, soil erosion (water, wind, tillage); decreasing water retention capacities
Socioeconomic driver	Digitalization, new marketing options
Problem statement of socioeconomic driver	How to exploit the use of digitalization and new marketing options for soil improving management; large (international) holdings buying up the land
Problem statement of biophysical driver	Climate change leading to drought risk
Pressure/Current state vs desired state	Profit driven high tech agriculture- > ecosystem service supporting high tech agriculture.
Governance Regime /Policy Strategy	Large farms, CAP important, new private governance regimes (e.g. carbon farming) popping up, absence of advisory services
Opportunities of socioeconomic driver	Short supply chain (vicinity to Berlin metropolitan area), high tech solutions for ecosystem service supporting agriculture, science-practice cooperation in living lab context
Opportunities of biophysical driver	Young pleistocene landscape with high landscape diversity; attractive landscape for recreation of the Berlin metropolitan region

Table DE-1. General information about the selected region.

National soil health and environmental discourse in agriculture

In Germany, farming in the case study area is hampered by the area's poor soil quality, which is of young Pleistocene origin and primarily made up of sand and loam. The agricultural area has a large proportion of low-quality soils; about two-thirds are sandy or sandy-loamy soils. This situation, combined with less than average rainfall (less than 579 average 1991-2020), makes agricultural output difficult. Agricultural sector is under constant pressure in Berlin's suburbs due to requests for rededication as residential land, increasing interest in regional food production. Gutzler et al. (2015) predicted increased cropland use for renewable energy generation based on the significant rise in maize output for biogas fermentation following the enactment of the Act on Granting Priority to Renewable Energy Sources in 2000.

This is one of the reasons why Brandenburg farmers either produce in the organic niche, benefiting from the high prices offered in Berlin for regional, organic food, or use advanced technology, like heavy-duty machinery and intense fertilizer and pesticide use (Gutzler et al., 2015). Additionally, 8% of Brandenburg is set aside as a conservation area, which has a significant impact on bird biodiversity. The PV area usage in Brandenburg has risen to 2300 hectare to the latest available data in 2017, which will lead to conflicts of interest with agricultural production and food production. The current German soil law “Bodenschutzgesetz” is being revised, as it focused primarily on limiting toxins and regulated

the amount. The new law is expected to move into a more prescriptive direction of management options.

5.2.2. The respondents

From the onset of this task, the partner responsible to organise the survey has conveyed to the task leader that the previous soil needs assessment workshop region will be used for this task. Therefore, the study in Germany was focused on the agriculture sector and on the Brandenburg. The survey was sent to the participants of the Soil needs assessment workshop, existing networks and newsletters of the ongoing projects at ZALF (Benchmarks, Natioons, Solo, Soilwise, EJP Soil, Bonares) and various stakeholder networks involved in the agriculture advisory in Brandenburg. However, due to less participation, we sent the personal invitations to the participant groups based on the suggestions from the task leader. Since the participation was still low, the study region was expanded across Germany and questionnaire links were sent to more than 150 participants cross Germany to increase the chances of completing the survey. The details of the participants contacted were mentioned in the Table DE-2. The participants were mostly from the policy and implementation circles and lacks the perspectives of the people directly engaged in the advisory services.

The survey was sent to people found by putting key words on Google. For the agricultural survey, people were contacted who were on official lists of regional states (for the state of Brandenburg) for agricultural advisors. Those, who seemingly were working with crops, on soils were contacted, while those working on animal husbandry exclusively were rather not contacted. Several of those agricultural advisors were further also involved in additional activities, like working for an organic label, some association, having an agriculture related business or being a practicing farmer. Further people were found through the key words “agriculture soils Germany” or “soils organization”. The websites of major environmental and agricultural and environmental institutes, NGOs and chambers were checked for people working on soils or agriculture and environmental protection.

For the forest survey, a similar approach was taken, but searching for the keyword “forest soils Germany”, “foresters”, “sustainable forest”, “forest association”. On the websites which were found, also further links and partnering websites were offered. Also, Forest Associations, organizations regarding forests, research institutes for forestry and forest soils and NGOs working on forests were searched for and contacted. For the urban survey stakeholders were found by entering key words like “urban planning soil”, “urban soils”, etc.

	Agricultural Survey	Forest Survey	Urban Survey
Local / Municipality level	Farmers, Municipal Administration Environment	Local Initiative for Soil health	
Regional level	Advisors (organic and conventional) Nature conservation associations Agricultural chambers Provincial agricultural chambers Researchers / Research Projects Nature parks Organic labels' regional associations Start-ups in agricultural innovation	Researchers on forest soils	Provincial Ministry for Environment and Agriculture
National level	Researchers Advisors Farmers associations WWF Landscape preservation societies Federal Control Association Federal Agriculture Agency Organic labels' producer associations	Young Foresters Network Network of Forestry Organizations WWF Forest Owners Association Forest Protection Association Association of Family Businesses of Land and Forestry Workers Association Agroforestry	Institute for soils Regional development network
Total number of distributed surveys	107	16	30
Started surveys	56	14	14
Completed surveys	30	0	3

Table DE-2. Details of the contacted persons for the survey in Germany

5.2.3. Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the German survey data. The chapter consists of one section – the agricultural survey. The forestry survey and the urban survey are omitted due to lack of respondents. In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the survey (see Appendix 1). The prefix DE indicates that the figures belongs to the German chapter and the suffix A indicates which survey they belong to (Agriculture).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

The survey questions from Q1-Q10 describes the survey respondents in Germany. The survey respondents in Germany are mainly from the urban areas with 43% respondents coming from the Brandenburg region. The high number of participants from the Brandenburg region indicates the strong network of the research partners in that region. The survey respondents' perspectives will also

align with the workshop participants as the workshop was focused on the Brandenburg region. The high number (60%) of the participants represent the counselling and advisory group of soil issues that gives us the valid inputs to our assessment of the advisory services in Germany. The remaining participants represent the several aspects, majorly the policy (36%), research (23%), of the advisory services related to agriculture (refer Figure DE-Q2A 1 for additional information).

In relation to the work about the soils among the participants work is very high (4.83, refer Figure DE-Q3A 1) but still lesser than the total of 5.21 from all the countries. This high average among the participants is not surprising given that the survey participants working on the soils in general. At the same time, it is very interesting that the participants from the private agencies represent about 60% of the total participants in Germany (refer Figure DE-Q4A 1). Since the agricultural advisory services in Brandenburg is privatised, which was represented in the participants as well. The organisation of the advisory service strongly differs across the states in Germany. While it is privatised in Brandenburg, e.g. in Niedersachsen and Hessen and Nordrhein Westfalen it is public and very strong. The national level policy actors are second largest representatives (20%), which might result in national level policy relevant aspects in the agricultural advisory systems in Germany. The participants are highly educated with masters (70%), PhD (13%) and only 16% are with bachelor's degree. The popular theme of the education is agriculture (63%) followed by natural sciences (10%) and others (17%) (Figure DE-Q6A 1). Almost all the participants studied soil sciences in their education (87%), which is again not surprising given their educational background in agriculture. However, only 56% participants received training on the soil health related issues. This is not clear if this was during their education or during their professional work experience. Despite of this, the participants rated very high (average 4.67) their knowledge concerning soils (Figure DE-Q9A 1). Their work experience is also very high on the soil related issues as 44% participants worked more than 10 years, and 30 % participants worked between 5 and 10 years.

Figure DE-Q2A 1: "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to"

Figure DE-Q3A 1: "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent" Mean value: Germany 4.83; Total 5.21.

Figure DE-Q4A 1: "I am employed by"

Figure DE-Q6A 1: "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure DE-Q9A 1: “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Germany 4.67; Total 4.87.

The respondents and the soil health concept

The survey further collected the opinions of the participants on the soil health problem formulations from the EU Commission, which claims that more than 70% of the soils in Europe are affected due to soil erosion, soil compaction, reduced content of organic matter, soil pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing. The question to what extent the participants agreed with that problem formulation in relation to agricultural soils in their region/country gave rise to a large and relatively even distribution along the 7-point Likert scale. The participants in Germany are very knowledgeable about the reasons behind poor quality of soil health in Germany. This is shown with a mean acceptance of 5.90 to the EU Commission reports on the unhealthy soils, which is higher than the total mean of 5.21 (refer Figure DE-Q11A 1). Only few participants responded with lower side of the scale (3 and 4). No participant disagreed with the statements that shows that high level of knowledge on the soil health issues in Germany.

This trend of high knowledge among the Germany survey respondents on the soil health concepts continued in the following questions. The questions 12 presented two perspectives on soil: 1) Soil fertility is defined as the ability of soil to sustain plant growth. The focus is mainly on the soil ecosystem service: provision of food, fibre and fuel. 2) Soil health is defined as the ability of the soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services. Germany respondent’ mean (5.23) higher than the total participants’ mean (4.84). However, majority of the Germany participants are bit unsure and choose the scale 4 which is kind of balancing on both views. Overall, majority of the respondents choose the soil health perspective to support the broad range ecosystem services from the agriculture soils in Germany (refer to Figure DE-Q12A 1).

The following questions then asked the application of soil health concepts in the agriculture sector in Germany. The soil health concept uses in agriculture sector considered high in Germany. The mean value is 5.63, very close to the total participants mean 6.07 (refer Figure DE-Q13aA 1). However, the soil health concept use in agriculture sector is not well represented with mean value of 3.70, which is less than the total participants mean of 4.25 (refer Figure DE-Q13bA 2). In contrast, the knowledge about the soil health concepts (Germany 4.53; Total 4.76) and agricultural management affects soil health (Germany 4.87; Total 5.03) is higher side in Germany and very close to total participants (refer to Figure DE-Q14aA 1 and Figure DE-Q14bA 2). This indicates that the knowledge and soil health concepts may not directly result in their use in the sector. The Germany respondents perceive that the adoption of soil concept would imply mind shift at personal level (Germany 4.87; Total 5.12), but less favourable in changes at the workplace (Germany 3.57; Total 4.05). This indicates that need for changes

in the institutional level to adopt the soil health concepts to improve the agriculture sector in Germany (Refer to Figure DE-Q15aA 1 and Figure DE-Q15bA 2).

Figure DE-Q11A 1. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)” Mean value: Germany 5.90; Total 5.21.

Figure DE-Q12A 1: “The following perspective of soil aligns with my own view” Mean value: Germany 5.23; Total 4.84.

Figure DE-Q13aA 1: “Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture” Mean value: Germany 5.63; Total 6.07.

Figure DE-Q13bA 2: “The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept”, Mean value: Germany 3.70; Total 4.25.

Figure DE-Q14aA 1: “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Germany 4.53; Total 4.76

Figure DE-Q14bA 2: “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?” Mean value: Germany 4.87; Total 5.03.

Figure DE-Q15aA 1: “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Germany 4.87; Total 5.12.

Figure DE-Q15bA 2: “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Germany 3.57; Total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the region & soil challenges that the respondents work with

The respondents’ perceived that main challenges related to soil health in Germany are “to improve the water retention/infiltration/drainage” (mean 4.60), and “to improve soil fertility” (mean 4.60), followed by “to improve the nutrient cycling” (mean 4.23), and “to decrease the soil erosion” (mean 4.10), and “to increase the soil organic matter” (mean 4.03). Two challenges are equally perceived with 3.83 mean are “to decrease the soil compaction” and “to avoid soil sealing” which have similar implications in the agriculture management. The challenge related "to improve soil fertility" is equally rated the highest by both Germany and the total respondents. Challenges related to water retention/infiltration and nutrient cycling are rated highly by both groups, though slightly higher for the total group. Germany participants rated the importance of increasing soil biodiversity, decreasing soil erosion, and decreasing salinization significantly lower than the total group. The importance of managing peatlands is rated equally by Germany and total participants. The least considered challenges related to soil health in Germany are salinization (mean 2.90) and desertification (mean 3.00) and to increase the soil biodiversity (mean 3.27). Refer to Figure DE-Q16A 1 for additional information. The participants further perceived that their workplaces (Figure DE-Q18A 2) are dealing with the relevant soil health concepts. There is a general alignment between Germany and the total respondent group on many soil management challenges, with some notable differences in the emphasis on specific issues like salinization, desertification, and soil sealing. The focus of the organisations in Germany was even spread into promoting awareness of sustainable soil management and importance of soil health. Promoting awareness of sustainable soil management and improving soil fertility are universally high priorities, indicating a strong focus on long-term soil health and productivity.

Figure DE-Q16A 1: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure DE-Q18A 2: “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in agricultural soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

The participants mentioned several challenges currently faced in Germany. Soil health in agriculture faces numerous obstacles categorized into economic and financial constraints, knowledge and training deficiencies, public and political awareness and support, and practical implementation challenges. Refer to for a short summary Table DE-Q19A 1.

Economic and Financial Constraints: Economic interests and counterproductive subsidies hinder sustainable practices, while high costs and lack of financial support make it difficult for farmers to transition to sustainable methods. Economic pressures, such as high lease prices and competition for land, further exacerbate the issue, often prioritizing short-term profitability over long-term soil health.

Knowledge and Training Deficiencies: There is a significant lack of education and training on soil health, with insufficient practical training programs and advisory services. This knowledge gap extends to decision-makers and managers, resulting in a lack of comprehensive soil health management strategies. Additionally, the slow transfer of research findings to practical applications hinders

progress. This clearly indicates a better science to policy interfaces and knowledge transfer mechanisms with clear feedback mechanisms.

Public and Political Awareness and Support: The lack of awareness and appreciation for soil health among the public and policymakers leads to inadequate support and misguided regulations. Bureaucratic hurdles and the strong influence of profit-oriented lobby groups further impede sustainable soil management practices.

Practical Implementation Challenges: Practical issues such as changing groundwater levels, monocultures, large machinery, and intensive farming practices contribute to soil degradation. The lack of effective implementation support and advisory services also poses significant barriers to adopting sustainable practices.

To address the challenges and obstacles in improving soil health in agriculture, the following measures are suggested by the participants in Germany. By implementing these comprehensive measures, it is possible to address economic constraints, enhance knowledge and training, raise public and political awareness, and support practical implementation, ultimately leading to significant improvements in soil health in agriculture. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated effort to provide financial incentives, enhance education and training, raise public and political awareness, and support practical implementation of sustainable soil health practices. A long list of these measures was listed in the Table DE-Q19A 2

Economic and Financial Constraints	<p>Economic interests, non-consideration of external costs, counterproductive subsidies</p> <p>Lack of financial support for conversion into soil health improving practices</p> <p>Economic pressure and competition for land</p> <p>High lease prices</p> <p>High production costs</p> <p>Conventional agriculture's focus on short-term profitability</p> <p>Need subsidies and monetary support for farmers who want to try regenerative agriculture</p> <p>Lack of aid based on appropriate criteria</p> <p>Ownership of land as a means of production preventing investment in soil fertility</p> <p>Low livestock numbers</p> <p>High leasehold shares on farms leading to lack of commitment and care</p> <p>Displacement of small local farms</p>
Knowledge and Training Deficiencies	<p>Lack of thematisation in training (trainees, lateral entrants, part-time farmers, master craftsmen)</p> <p>Lack of practical, low-threshold further training programs and advice</p> <p>Lack of regional best-practice and businesses models</p> <p>Lack of expertise among decision-makers, managers, and land users</p> <p>Knowledge transfer from research to practice is lacking</p> <p>Deficits or slow implementation on topics of humus build-up, compaction, soil biodiversity</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about local conditions</p> <p>Knowledge requirements and costs burdening farms</p> <p>Lack of sound advice to the farmers</p> <p>Too little time, information, interest, and room for manoeuvre in implementation</p>
Public and Political Awareness and Support	<p>Lack of public and political awareness of the importance of soil health</p> <p>Misguided advice in the past and lack of reappraisal</p> <p>Excessive bureaucracy preventing professional decisions</p> <p>Lack of appreciation (and pricing) of the environmental services provided by soils</p> <p>Hostility to science in day-to-day work of the authorities</p> <p>Unrealistic, dictatorial, and unscientific EU directives and German nature conservation laws</p> <p>Strong influence of lobby groups and private profit-oriented companies</p> <p>Soil predominantly perceived as an ever-present resource</p> <p>Lack of understanding of soil as an organism</p> <p>Partly a lack of awareness because high yields are still possible with fertilizers and pesticides</p>
Practical Implementation Challenges	<p>Changing groundwater levels, degraded peatlands, intensive use</p> <p>Crops with too little root growth</p> <p>Large machinery compensating for labor shortage</p> <p>Diverse crop rotations fitting in with direct marketing</p> <p>Intensive silage maize cultivation with loss of humus</p> <p>No crop rotation leading to monocultures</p> <p>Erosion by water or wind, drought</p> <p>Crop rotations too tight without catch crops, machinery too large, tillage too intensive</p> <p>Established concepts still working</p> <p>Implementation problems in practice (lack of support, advice on funding applications, administrative processing)</p>

Table DE-Q19A 1: Summary of hindrances related to soil health.

Economic and Financial Measures	<p>Subsidies in the Right Place: Redirect agricultural subsidies to support soil health-promoting practices and away from practices that degrade soil health.</p> <p>Reduction of Harmful Subsidies: Eliminate subsidies that incentivize harmful agricultural practices and promote site-adapted cultivation methods.</p> <p>Financial Incentives for Conversion: Provide financial support for farmers transitioning to sustainable practices, covering potential losses during the conversion period.</p> <p>Promote Sales Markets: Develop markets for diverse crops to encourage crop rotation and reduce dependency on monocultures.</p> <p>Public Funding for Land Economy: Increase public funding for agricultural businesses based on scientific research, counseling, and training.</p>
Knowledge and Training Measures	<p>Expand Training Curricula: Integrate soil protection and climate impact adaptation topics into agricultural education programs at all levels.</p> <p>Expand Advisory and Support Services: Enhance practical training and advisory services to provide farmers with actionable knowledge on soil health.</p> <p>Low-Threshold Education Programs: Develop easily accessible soil education programs through channels frequently used by farmers, emphasizing long-term profitability.</p> <p>Practice-Oriented Research: Increase research focused on practical applications such as erosion prevention, deep-rooted crop varieties, and soil microorganism monitoring.</p> <p>Mandatory Agronomy Education: Require formal agronomy education for farm operators to ensure comprehensive knowledge of soil health management.</p>
Public and Political Awareness Measures	<p>Recognize Soil-Conserving Measures: Promote and acknowledge the benefits of soil-conserving practices in policies and society, including biodiversity benefits of no-till systems.</p> <p>Transparent Data Collection: Implement science-based, transparent data collection to inform and shape soil health policies.</p> <p>Public Awareness Campaigns: Launch campaigns to raise public and political awareness about the importance of soil health and its impact on ecosystem services and food security.</p> <p>Honest Acknowledgment of Status Quo: Transparently communicate the current state of soil health and prioritize challenges based on scientific evidence.</p>
Practical Implementation Measures	<p>Reduce Silage Maize Cultivation: Minimize the cultivation of silage maize to prevent humus loss and promote more sustainable crop rotations.</p> <p>Better Distribution of Organic Fertilizers: Ensure effective distribution of organic fertilizers across farms and regions to enhance soil fertility.</p> <p>Enhanced Soil Monitoring: Strengthen monitoring of soil health, particularly focusing on soil microorganisms and other indicators of soil quality.</p> <p>Long-Term Land Leasing: Establish a land pool or agency to organize long-term land leases, providing farmers with planning security and controlling land conditions.</p> <p>Promote Soil Sampling: Encourage regular soil sampling and analysis to optimize soil management practices.</p>
Implementation and Evaluation Strategy	<p>Formulate and Prioritize Challenges: Develop a clear understanding and prioritization of soil health challenges based on scientific evidence.</p> <p>List and Evaluate Options for Action: Identify and assess options for addressing soil health challenges, considering priority, feasibility, expected results, and resource requirements.</p> <p>Evaluate Willingness to Implement: Assess the readiness and capacity for implementation of soil health measures among stakeholders.</p> <p>Continuous Progress Evaluation: Monitor and evaluate progress regularly, making necessary adjustments to ensure effectiveness.</p> <p>Clear Communication of Decisions: Transparently communicate decisions regarding implementation, including reasons for any rejections based on economic or practical considerations.</p>

Table DE-Q19A 2: List of measures suggested by participants to improve the soil health in Germany.

Competence development

The respondents mentioned several themes for the competence and trainings that could enhance the advisory services on soil health in agriculture in Germany. The survey reveals a strong interest among

respondents from Germany, in understanding the broader concepts (54%) of soil health and management (60%), the impact of climate change (60%) and biodiversity (50%). There is also notable interest in practical thematic aspects such as soil assessment, biology, and nutrient cycling. Conversely, topics like soil erosion, salinization, and pollution gathered less interest, suggesting that these areas might need more awareness-raising initiatives even among the advisors. There is considerable interest on learning about how to assess the soil health in Germany (50%) which was higher than the total participants' interest (45%). When it comes to improve their competence on the soil related concepts in their advisory services, only 33% of the participants mentioned that they are not aware of the competence improvement measures available for them. Remaining participants of 50% are aware of these competence measures. The participants wished to learn about the soil health improvement in agriculture soils through lessons from good examples (66%), field visits (56%), in-persons trainings (53%), digital courses (40%), and webinars (43%).

5.2.4. Discussion

The survey respondents in Germany are mainly from the urban areas, highly educated on soil, works at national level counselling and advisory, policy and research that gives the valid inputs to the assessment of the advisory services in Germany. The agricultural advisory services in Brandenburg State in Germany is privatised, high participation of private actors in the survey is justified. The respondents have been working on soil issues for very long time and received trainings on soil health, and as a result rated high in their knowledge. The participants are very knowledgeable about the reasons behind poor quality of soil health in Germany. This trend of high knowledge on the soil health concepts continued and majority of the respondents choose the soil health perspective to support the broad range ecosystem services from the agriculture soils in Germany. The soil health concept uses in agriculture sector considered high in Germany but may not result in using the knowledge in sector to improve the soil health. Furthermore, respondents perceive that the adoption of soil health concept would imply mind shift at personal level but less favourable in changes at the workplace. This indicates that need for changes in the institutional level to adopt the soil health concepts to improve the agriculture sector in Germany.

5.2.5. Implications for policy

The main challenges identified in Germany are to improve the water retention, and to improve soil fertility. There is a general alignment on many soil management challenges, with some notable differences in the emphasis on specific issues like salinization, desertification, and soil sealing. Soil health in agriculture faces numerous obstacles categorized into economic and financial constraints, knowledge and training deficiencies, public and political awareness and support, and practical implementation challenges.

The focus of the organisations in Germany was even spread into promoting awareness of sustainable soil management and importance of soil health. Promoting awareness of sustainable soil management and improving soil fertility are universally high priorities, indicating a strong focus on long-term soil health and productivity. Several themes for the competence and trainings that could enhance the soil health in agriculture are identified with notable interest in practical aspects such as soil assessment, biology, and nutrient cycling. Conversely, topics like soil erosion and pollution garner less interest, suggesting that these areas might need more awareness-raising initiatives. Other topics such as salinization are not relevant in the region because of biophysical conditions. There is considerable interest on learning about how to assess the soil health. The preferred methods to learn about the soil

health improvement are through lessons from good examples, field visits, in-person trainings, digital courses, and webinars.

5.2.6. Key messages

1. Addressing the soil related challenges requires a coordinated effort to provide financial incentives, enhance education and training, raise public and political awareness, and support practical implementation of sustainable soil health practices.
2. The scientific knowledge generated about the local soil health concepts are not translated into actions that is visible through the degraded nature of agriculture soils.
3. The disparity in interest levels for the various topics of interest among the participants indicates the need for targeted educational programs focusing on high-interest topics while also emphasizing the importance of less popular but critical soil health issues.
4. A clear demand for open and accessible advisory services, competence development models on sustainable soil management practices and their environmental impact is emerging.
5. Institutional level changes are required to create a better advisory system.

5.3. Country report: The Netherlands

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5.3.1. Introduction to the study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study regions

The total land area of the Netherlands is 4.2 million ha, of which approximately 2.2 million ha is under agricultural use, 0.5 million ha is forest/nature and 0.4 million ha is built-up areas (data source: CBS, see Table NL-1). For this study, we focused on three regions of the country: North-Holland, Gelderland and Friesland. North-Holland located in the northwestern part of the Netherlands, on the North Sea, and includes an inhabited Wadden-island Texel. Northeast of North-Holland is Friesland, a province in the northern part of the Netherlands, which also includes several inhabited Wadden-islands. Gelderland is inland, in the central-east part of the Netherlands, and is the province with the largest land area (Figure NL-1).

Figure NL-1. The three Netherlands study regions. Map from Wikipedia (Author: Alphathon; Accessed: June, 2024; Link: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Map_provinces_Netherlands-en.svg#filelinks; red circles added for this report)

As indicated by the national statistics, over half of the land area in the Netherlands is used for agriculture, while very little is used for forestry. Within each region, 3 municipalities were targeted that spanned an urban to rural gradient. As forests play a relatively minor role nationally, the focus was on regions that differed with respect to urban and agricultural area. In North-Holland, municipalities chosen were Amsterdam, Zaanstad and Bergen. In Gelderland, the municipalities were Arnhem, Nijmegen, Apeldoorn and Ede. In Friesland, the study focused on Leeuwarden, Súdwest-Fryslân and Ooststellingwerf. Table NL-1 shows basic land-use statistics of the different regions and municipalities.

Region <i>Municipalities</i>	Total area (ha)	Total agricultural area (ha)	Total forest area (ha)	Built up and developed land (ha)
North-Holland	409 193	156 707 (38%)	12 840 (3%)	46 322 (11%)
<i>Amsterdam</i>		12%	1%	38%
<i>Zaanstad</i>		43%	1%	28%
<i>Bergen</i>		35%	14%	6%
Friesland	574 877	257 222 (45%)	11 344 (2%)	18 423 (3%)
<i>Leeuwarden</i>		60%	2%	14%
<i>Súdwest-Fryslân</i>		47%	0%	3%
<i>Ooststellingwerf</i>		72%	11%	3%
Gelderland	513 630	296 745 (58%)	93 465 (18%)	48 750 (9%)
<i>Arnhem/Nijmegen</i>		15%	16%	40%
<i>Apeldoorn</i>		24%	48%	11%
<i>Ede</i>		34%	34%	8%

Table NL-1: Land use statistics from the Netherlands study regions and municipalities. Data shown are from 2017 statistics of the CBS (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek; accessed June ,2024):

<https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/70262ned/table?dl=2C288>

National soil health and environmental discourse

As reflected by the >50% of land area dedicated to agriculture, the agricultural sector in the Netherlands is an important national source of income. Agricultural exports in 2023 were valued at over 120 billion euros (source: CBS; <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/news/2024/10/dutch-agricultural-exports-worth-nearly-124-billion-euros-in-2023>). Forms of intensive agriculture in the Netherlands have created problems, however, with efforts to control the manure surplus causing considerable controversy.

The Netherlands is also the 5th most densely populated country in Europe, with the first 4 all being microstates. Of the regions within this study, North-Holland has a population density of over 1100 inhabitants per square kilometer, followed by Gelderland (430) and then Friesland (197; source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1404371/netherlands-population-density-by-province/>).

Therefore, in addition to expectations put on agricultural soils, also urban areas in the Netherlands are under considerable pressure.

5.3.2. The respondents

While respondents were sought from the agricultural, urban and forest sectors, forestry is less of a key sector in the Netherlands than it is in neighbouring countries. Therefore, the response level for forestry was low, and the forest survey will not be a focus of this report.

Although respondents were welcomed from any region of the country, the selection of directly-contacted survey respondents focused on three municipalities within each region. Focusing on only three municipalities allowed for the required number of contacts to remain at a manageable number. The three municipalities also spanned an urban to rural gradient, in order to gather data from actors facing different types and intensities of soil-related issues. However, respondents were encouraged to both forward the survey to other colleagues (including those outside the target regions), and to identify themselves as national rather than regional if they felt that was more appropriate. Ultimately, 50% of the agricultural survey respondents specifically identified with one of the target regions, with 40% active at the national level and 23% active in other regions (note: it was possible to choose more than one answer). In the urban survey, over 50% of respondents were active in North-Holland,

followed by 20% in Gelderland and 6% in Friesland; 23% of the urban respondents were active at the national level.

In reaching out to potential respondents, we focused on groups that worked in areas where they could influence how soil management occurs within the Netherlands. This included those working directly for municipalities, as well as stakeholders within research, education, communication and consultancy, among others. Contact was made via email in order to invite survey participation; email addresses were found through websites or from within existing networks. Potential respondents were emailed once and invited to participate in one of the surveys (agriculture, forest or urban). Some respondents were asked specifically to participate in the survey known to be most relevant to them, while others were invited to choose the survey they considered most relevant. As the survey was anonymous, it was unknown who had/had not chosen to participate, so all potential respondents were sent one reminder email, 1-2 weeks following the initial request.

The average response rate in comparison to the number of invitation emails was approximately 50%. Of those who started the survey, the average completion rate was also 50%. Ultimately, there were a total of 30 completed surveys for the agricultural sector and 31 completed surveys for the urban sector.

5.3.3 Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the Dutch survey data. The chapter consists of two sections – one for the agricultural survey and one for the urban survey. The forestry survey is omitted due to lack of respondents. In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the surveys (see Appendix 1 and 3). The prefix NL indicates that the figures belong to the Dutch chapter and the suffix A or U indicate which survey they belong to (Agriculture or Urban).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

Figures NL-Q2 to Q10A present the agricultural respondents. Note that in Figure Q2, respondents were allowed to choose more than one response. As such, there were three 'top' categories of soil-related professions, each identified by 46-50% of respondents: policy, counselling/advisory and research. Other professions identified by over 20% of respondents included communication and nature conservation, followed by education and environmental issues, each with 20%. Most of the Netherlands respondents had a Masters or PhD degree (73%), but a surprising 43% did not major in Agriculture, Forestry, Environmental/Natural Science or Horticulture, which was in stark contrast to the average of all countries in this study, which showed less than 20% of respondents from other disciplines than those mentioned above.

Figure NL-Q2A. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to..."

Figure NL-Q3A. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Netherlands 5.77; Total 5.21.

Figure NL-Q4A. "I am employed by"

Figure NL-Q6A. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Figure NL-Q9A. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Netherlands 5.37; Total 4.87.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the background questions the respondents were presented by the soil health problem formulation from the EU Commission, stating that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. The responses peaked around 5 on a 7 point scale, indicating that NL respondents were not strongly in agreement (in fact, strong agreement in NL was strikingly lower than across all countries), but tended more toward agreement than disagreement (Figure NL-Q11A).

Next, respondents were asked how they viewed soil – predominantly in terms of soil fertility (i.e. production of crops) or as a source of multiple ecosystem services (i.e. soil health). Approximately 37% of respondents identified with the soil health definition, but 27% of respondents chose 4 on the 7-point scale – halfway between the two definitions – possibly indicating that these respondents felt that there was a need for both definitions (Figure NL-Q12A).

As with most respondents across all countries, the NL participants strongly agreed that soil health was a relevant concept in agriculture (Figure NL-Q13aA), but also consistent with the total averages, they were not confident that it was already being used within the industry, with a national average of 4.3 for that question (NL-Q13bA). They were more confident in their own skill levels, with a national average of 5.3 when asked about their knowledge of the soil health concept and an average of 5.1

when asked if they considered themselves knowledgeable about how management is affecting soil health (NL-Q14aA and Q14bA). The NL respondents felt that an adoption of the soil health concept would somewhat imply a mindshift concerning soil (mean 4,93; Figure NL-Q15aA), but were much less certain that it would change how their own workplace would deal with soil issues (mean 3,63; Figure NL-Q15bA).

Figure NL-Q11A. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your country?” Mean value: Netherlands 4.87; Total 5.21.

Figure NL-Q12A. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Netherlands 5.37; Total 4.84.

Figure NL-Q13aA. “Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture.” Mean value: Netherlands 6.27; Total 6.07.

Figure NL-Q13bA. “The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: 4.30; Total 4.25.

Figure NL-Q14aA. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Netherlands 5.30; Total 4.76.

Figure NL-Q14bA. “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?” Mean value: Netherlands 5.10; Total: 5.03.

Figure NL-Q15aA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Netherlands 4.93; Total 5.12.

Figure NL-Q15bA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Netherlands 3.63; Total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Among the soil challenges listed in Q16A, the main challenges considered to be problems in the Netherlands were soil compaction and water regulation. Other topics that ranked high (>5) were organic matter, soil fertility and nutrient cycling. Desertification was considered the least problematic.

The following question, which specifically asked which of those issues was dealt with the most, highlighted that a lot of effort is spent on awareness of soil health and sustainable soil management. Additionally, while the four topics from Q16A were again identified, biodiversity was also ranked highly – possibly indicating that although it receives a lot of attention, it is perceived as less of a problem than other issues.

Figure NL-Q16A. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure NL-Q18A. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in agricultural soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Stakeholders’ perceptions of hindrances and measures for soil health were explored through two open questions in the survey. When asked about perceived hindrances, stakeholders identified four general categories: attitude, knowledge, markets and policies. Table Q19A shows those four categories, with some key quotes from the survey (note: phrasing may have changed during translation from Dutch and some quotes have been condensed). The other frequent hindrance to soil health that was mentioned by respondents was environmental limitations, such as climate and soil type, which constrain the potential of a land manager to make changes to soil management.

<p>Attitude (lack of land manager motivation to make soil-health-related changes)</p> <p><i>“Short-term thinking, especially on rented land and how to deal with it.”</i></p> <p><i>“Attitude: we have healthy and well-functioning soil, see high yields”</i></p> <p><i>“The bond with the soil that people used to experience, where you take care of soil and nature is no longer there.”</i></p>
<p>Knowledge (poor/insufficient information on how to improve soil health)</p> <p><i>“Available knowledge does not land/too little/not in the right way on the farm.”</i></p> <p><i>“Understanding the consequences of one's own actions would give a grower a lot to improve. Now, mostly only area data available.”</i></p> <p><i>“Too little practical knowledge about the effects of measures.”</i></p>
<p>Markets (lack of consumer involvement in supporting soil health)</p> <p><i>“The market not paying or asking to operate in a way that takes soil health into account. The market is the most determinant of how a user manages land.”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of earning models for soil ecosystem services other than primary production.”</i></p> <p><i>“Revenue model, soil measures often cost more money than they generate, at least in the short term.”</i></p>
<p>Policies (current legal framework not suited to ensuring soil health)</p> <p><i>“Policies that are not congruent or consistent with soil health....often well-intentioned rules, subsidies, etc. have effects that the creators of such a rule or subsidy did not foresee.”</i></p> <p><i>“Have to work within the framework of existing policy.”</i></p> <p><i>“Just further legal clamping down on soil health, too few opportunities to measure at plot level.”</i></p>

Table NL-Q19A. Four categories of responses from soil stakeholders regarding hindrances to improving soil health, including quotes from respondents within each category.

When asked to suggest measures to deal with perceived hindrances, there were many specific recommendations, such as collaboration between livestock/agriculture, avoidance of plant protection products, and stimulation of organic fertilizer use. With respect to the four general categories identified in Q19A, there were no suggested measures for how to change the intrinsic motivation of individual land managers (attitude), but there were several comments calling for inclusive discussions on a larger scale. Within the knowledge category, there were numerous comments around both knowledge development and dissemination; an interesting sub-theme here was the call for having the freedom/opportunity for testing and experimentation – something that should ideally be addressed through soil health living labs. Table Q20A shows the four categories from Q19A, with related quotes from the survey (note: phrasing may have changed during translation from Dutch and some quotes have been condensed).

<p>Attitude (motivation to make soil-health-related changes through inclusivity)</p> <p><i>“Tackled together with farming partners.”</i></p> <p><i>“Not a few researchers and policymakers sitting in an ivory tower trying to figure out how to do it.”</i></p> <p><i>“Communication.”</i></p>
<p>Knowledge (collect/disseminate information on how to improve soil health)</p> <p><i>“Creating space (financial, legal, ...) to do/test things.” “Increase room for experimentation that will allow demonstrating over time that certain things do/don't work.”</i></p> <p><i>“Research successful regenerative agriculture in other countries and translate that to Dutch agriculture. Include results in teaching programmes at agricultural schools, provide free excursions or workshops to existing farmers and offer guidance pathways for farmers who want to transition.”</i></p> <p><i>“Training and certification of soil consultants, suppliers and farmers on integrated soil management.”</i></p>
<p>Markets (consumers involved in supporting soil health)</p> <p><i>“Paying farmers for ecosystem services other than primary production.”</i></p> <p><i>“We as consumers will have to pay a lot more for our food. We have to give up a bit of prosperity to live in a healthy environment, and thus with healthy agriculture (soil).”</i></p> <p><i>“Fair price for fair product.”</i></p>
<p>Policies (ensuring the suitability of soil health-related policies)</p> <p><i>“Not even more rules, campaigns, subsidies and I don't know what. Because a lot of farmers want (or wanted) to [improve soil health], but are hindered from working in a different way.”</i></p> <p><i>“Soil monitoring law should also really focus on monitoring and only later start thinking about steering at European level on soil health.”</i></p> <p><i>“State aid (you want to support the [soil health] transition; but state aid is often not allowed).”</i></p>

Table NL-Q20A. Four categories of responses from soil stakeholders regarding measures for dealing with perceived hindrances to soil health, including some specific quotes within each category.

Competence development

The last part of the survey addressed competence development, asking respondents: (1) which topics were of most interest to them, (2) whether relevant competence development measures were available to them and (3) what form of development activities they preferred. In the Netherlands, 50% of respondents identified ‘soil management strategies to improve soil health’, followed by ‘soil biology’ (47%), ‘soil biodiversity’ (40%), ‘climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation’ (40%) and ‘how to assess soil health’ (40%). In comparison to all survey respondents, NL respondents were more interested in soil biology and much less interested in ‘the soil health concept in general’ and ‘erosion’.

Despite the interest in competence development, 33% of respondents did not know whether there were relevant competence development measures available. Of those who were able to answer the question, only 7% claimed that such measures were available to a large extent (on a 7 point scale, with 1 being ‘not at all’ and 7 being ‘available to a large extent’, the average NL ‘availability’ response was 3.07). When it came to preferred formats for learning more about soil health, good examples were the highest ranked option (53%), followed by field visits (50%) and interaction with other colleagues/municipalities (40%).

The urban survey

Description of the respondents

Figures NL-Q2 to Q10U present the urban respondents. Note that in Figure Q2, respondents were allowed to choose more than one response. As such, there were two ‘top’ categories of soil-related professions, each identified by 67-77% of respondents: environmental issues and policy. Other professions identified by over 30% of respondents were urban planning, construction and recycling/reuse of soils. Most of the Netherlands respondents had a Masters or Engineer degree (65%), but similar to the agricultural survey, many respondents (35%) did not major in Agriculture, Planning/Architecture, Environmental/Natural Science or Horticulture, instead identifying ‘Other’.

However, they rate their soil knowledge in relation to their needs very highly, strikingly higher than the average across all countries.

Figure NL-Q2U. “In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to...”

Figure NL-Q3U. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent.” Mean value: Netherlands 6.10; Total 5.51.

Figure NL-Q4U. "I am employed by"

Figure NL-Q6U. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure NL-Q9U. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?" Mean value: Netherlands 5.65; Total 4.62.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the background questions, the respondents were presented by the soil health problem formulation from the EU Commission, stating that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. The

responses were predominantly 5 or higher (mean: 5.55), indicating that NL respondents generally agreed with the statement, although strong agreement in NL was strikingly lower than across all countries (Figure NL-Q11U). Next, respondents were asked how they viewed soil – predominantly in terms of soil fertility (i.e. production of crops) or as a source of multiple ecosystem services (i.e. soil health). There were approximately ¼ of respondents who identified each of: 3, 5, 6 and 7 – indicating a tendency toward agreement with the soil health definition, but a strong signal from several respondents that targeted soil use was also a useful definition (Figure NL-Q12U).

As with most respondents across all countries, the NL participants agreed that soil health was a relevant concept for urban soils (Figure NL-Q13aU), but they were slightly less in favour of the concept that the respondents across all countries (NL mean: 5.52, total mean: 5.72). In contrast to the agricultural survey, there was a very clear signal from urban respondents in NL and across all countries that soil health was not yet used within the industry (NL-Q13bU). They were also slightly less confident than their agricultural counterparts with respect to their own skill levels, with a national average of 4.9 when asked about their knowledge of the soil health concept and an average of 4.7 when asked if they considered themselves knowledgeable about how management is affecting soil health (NL-Q14aU and Q14bU). The NL respondents felt that an adoption of the soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil (mean 5,5; Figure NL-Q15aU), and in contrast again to the agricultural respondents, felt that this would change how their own workplace would deal with soil issues (mean 4,9; Figure NL-Q15bU).

Figure NL-Q11U. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to urban soils in your country?” Mean value: Netherlands 5.55; Total 5.60.

Figure NL-Q12U. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Netherlands 4.33; Total 3.82.

Figure NL-Q13aU. “Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils.” Mean value: Netherlands 5.52; Total 5.72.

Figure NL-Q13bU. “The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Netherlands 2.68; Total 2.50.

Figure NL-Q14aU. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?”

Figure NL-Q14bU. “How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?” Mean value: Netherlands 4.90; Total 3.71.

Figure NL-Q15aU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept for urban soils imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Netherlands 5.52; Total 5.24.

Figure NL-Q15bU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept for urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Netherlands 4.90; Total 4.59.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Among the soil challenges listed in Q16A, the main challenge considered to be problems in the urban soils of the Netherlands was soil contamination, followed by water regulation and climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation. Although ranked under 5, recycling and re-use of soils was also ranked considerably higher than any of the other topics. De-sealing and soil erosion were considered the least problematic. The following question, which specifically asked which of those issues was dealt with the most, was consistent with the list from Q16A, highlighting the clear priority toward dealing

with contamination in the urban environment. It also showed, similar to the agricultural survey, that a lot of effort is spent on awareness of soil health and sustainable soil management.

Figure NL-Q16U. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure NL-Q18U. “To what extent does your workplace deal with the following challenges in urban soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Stakeholders’ perceptions of hindrances and measures for soil health were explored through two open-ended questions in the survey. When asked about perceived hindrances, stakeholders identified three general themes: lack of space, limited awareness/knowledge and soil health as a low priority

with respect to other urban interests. Table Q19A shows those three themes, with some key quotes from the survey (note: phrasing may have changed during translation from Dutch and some quotes have been condensed).

<p>Urban area is limited</p> <p><i>“Conflicting interests (housing development, circularity, healthy soil - cannot always be all at the same time).”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of space”; “Use of space”; “Space competition”; “Space scarcity”</i></p> <p><i>“The pressure for available soil.”</i></p> <p><i>“Spatial pressure: we want a lot in a small area. This leads to urban densification and therefore to soil compaction and sealing.”</i></p>
<p>Limited knowledge/awareness of urban soils</p> <p><i>“It plays no role in the education and further training of ‘city makers.’”</i></p> <p><i>“Insufficient knowledge within the organisation.”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of awareness”; “Awareness”</i></p> <p><i>“The idea that soil health is of less importance in urban areas, as urban soil is mostly built-up and covered and no crops are grown.”</i></p> <p><i>“Unfamiliarity of problems”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of a direct ‘action>impact’ relationship: poor soil management does not immediately produce visible and tangible problems.”</i></p> <p><i>“Invisible, so only attention when problems arise.”</i></p>
<p>Urban soil health not prioritized in policies and decisions</p> <p><i>“A client is missing, both administratively and officially. Then it is also not an (integral) part of a project.”</i></p> <p><i>“Who bears/feels responsible for this”</i></p> <p><i>“The potential of the subsurface as a provider of ecosystem services has not been included in the decision-making process early on.”</i></p> <p><i>“No obligation (yet) in policy and regulations.”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of a business case: soil health-threatening issues (energy transition, mobility, housing etc.) have social and political priority and budget.”</i></p> <p><i>“Is seen as a drop in the ocean compared to the gains to be made outside the city. No way an urban development plan will be modified to preserve good soil.”</i></p>

Table NL-Q19U. Three categories of responses from soil stakeholders regarding hindrances to improving soil health, including quotes from respondents within each category.

When asked to suggest measures to deal with perceived hindrances, there were clear overlaps in the answers within each theme. With respect to limited space, the majority of recommendations were focused on more careful planning, and including soil health as one factor in that planning. Under the theme of knowledge/awareness, a focus on improving soil literacy (from schoolchildren to administrators/councillors) was a clear priority of respondents, in addition to research/monitoring of soil to understand and quantify the benefits of urban soil health. Finally, with respect to soil health becoming a priority in policies and decisions, there was a mix of responses, with some respondents suggesting the implementation of rules/regulations and others exploring voluntary mechanisms (payments, support/buy-in at the individual level). Table Q20U shows the three themes from Q19U, with related quotes from the survey (note: phrasing may have changed during translation from Dutch and some quotes have been condensed).

<p>Soil health considered during planning of urban area</p> <p><i>“Create a proper assessment framework to identify conflicting interests so that well-considered choices can be made.”</i></p> <p><i>“Prioritising and careful long-term planning.”</i></p> <p><i>“Determine priorities: where there is still room for improvement (public spaces, gardens) and where is that impossible (e.g. housing)?”</i></p> <p><i>“Cables and pipes can no longer go everywhere...utility companies be forced to cooperate better and create more space for good growing places.”</i></p> <p><i>“Soil becomes an integral part of design and engineering public space.”</i></p> <p><i>“Planning should first carefully consider environmental aspects, including soil (health) and based on the results, the most optimal location should be selected.”</i></p>
<p>Focus on (urban) soil literacy and research</p> <p><i>“Creating awareness” “Raising awareness and money” “Provide political awareness and funding”</i></p> <p><i>“Increase attention, knowledge and awareness in a much wider circle...make officials, councillors and administrators aware that other sustainability/climate adaptation goals can only be achieved with healthy soil.”</i></p> <p><i>“Increasing and sharing knowledge about the subsoil (this starts at primary school, (urban) children become distanced from soil life).”</i></p> <p><i>“Reinforce training for lateral entrants in the field of sustainable urban renewal and responsible management of polluted soil.”</i></p> <p><i>“Research, highlight the importance of healthy soil for residents and administrators, build knowledge.”</i></p> <p><i>“Research for a business case: what does a healthy soil yield compared to an unhealthy soil?”</i></p> <p><i>“Measuring = knowing. So what do we want to improve, what do we need to pay attention to, by monitoring we can tie clear laws and regulations to this.”</i></p>
<p>Mechanisms to increase support for soil health</p> <p><i>“Ensure that the concept/interest of soil health is widely supported throughout the organisation.”</i></p> <p><i>“Set more rules on the use of soil”</i></p> <p><i>“Exploring how and where regulation is possible and then implementing it.”</i></p> <p><i>“It remains difficult as long as no payments can be linked to [soil health] improvements. Then [soil health] almost always loses out, unless rules are introduced. But more rules can also lead to negative sentiments and even more investment needed.”</i></p>

Table NL-Q20U. Three categories of responses from soil stakeholders regarding measures for dealing with perceived hindrances to soil health, including some specific quotes within each category.

Competence development

The last part of the survey addressed competence development, asking respondents: (1) which topics were of most interest to them, (2) whether relevant competence development measures were available to them and (3) what form of development activities they preferred. In the Netherlands, there was strikingly high interest in understanding soil management strategies to improve soil health (74% of NL respondents, in comparison to 49% of total respondents). Other topics of high interest were: how to assess soil health (58%), soil biodiversity (58%) and the soil health concept in general (52%). In comparison to all survey respondents, NL respondents were much less interested in recycling/reuse of soils, soil pollution/remediation and erosion. The reason for this is probably that in Netherlands recycling/reuse of soils and soil pollution/remediation are regulated in legislation and policy and because erosion does not occur in urban areas.

Despite the interest in competence development, 36% of respondents did not know whether there were relevant competence development measures available. Of those who were able to answer, only 3% claimed that such measures were available to a large extent (on a 7 point scale, with 1 being ‘not at all’ and 7 being ‘available to a large extent’, the average NL ‘availability’ response was 3.32). When it came to preferred formats for learning more about soil health, good examples were the highest ranked option (68%), followed by live webinars (61%) and interaction with other colleagues/municipalities (58%).

5.3.4 Discussion

Actions of individuals and organizations are based on their perception of urgency. Therefore, one key question in the survey that highlighted the readiness of the different countries to address soil health issues, was whether influential actors perceived poor soil health as a problem. Respondents were asked how strongly they agreed with the EU Commission’s statement that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy, due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement. The response from the two groups of Netherlands respondents varied, with urban stakeholders agreeing more strongly with the statement (mean of 5.55/7), while agricultural stakeholders were less certain (mean of 4.87/7). Those levels of confidence were consistent with the urban stakeholders across all countries, but lower than the average of all agricultural stakeholders (mean: urban 5.60; agriculture 5.21).

In the results regarding hindrances for improved soil health and measures to deal with these hindrances, there were similarities between the sectors. Table NL-2 below summarizes the recurring themes from the surveys. Lack of knowledge and a need for research was mentioned in both surveys, as was the importance of suitable policies and a focus on improving soil literacy. With respect to competence development, Table NL-3 shows that both groups are interested in understanding the same general topics, and both have a strong preference for good examples and interaction with colleagues/other municipalities, rather than more traditional courses or forms of ‘solo’ learning.

	Agricultural survey	Urban survey
Hindrances for improved soil health	<p>Attitude (lack of land manager motivation to make soil-health-related changes)</p> <p>Knowledge (poor/insufficient information on how to improve soil health)</p> <p>Markets (lack of consumer involvement in supporting soil health)</p> <p>Policies (current legal framework not suited to ensuring soil health)</p>	<p>Urban area is limited</p> <p>Limited knowledge/awareness of urban soils</p> <p>Urban soil health not prioritized in policies and decisions</p>
Measures to deal with identified hindrances	<p>Attitude (motivation to make soil-health-related changes through inclusivity)</p> <p>Knowledge (collect/disseminate information on how to improve soil health)</p> <p>Markets (consumers involved in supporting soil health)</p> <p>Policies (ensuring the suitability of soil health-related policies)</p>	<p>Soil health considered during planning of urban area</p> <p>Focus on (urban) soil literacy and research</p> <p>Increase soil health through voluntary and regulatory mechanisms</p>

Table NL-2. Compilation of the main hindrances for improved soil health and suggested measures to deal with those hindrances from the two Netherlands surveys.

	Agricultural survey	Urban survey
Topics ranked high for competence development	<p>Soil management strategies to improve soil health</p> <p>Soil biology</p> <p>Soil biodiversity</p> <p>Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation</p> <p>How to assess soil health</p>	<p>Soil management strategies to improve soil health</p> <p>How to assess soil health</p> <p>Soil biodiversity</p> <p>Soil health concept in general</p> <p>Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation</p>
Preferred format for competence development	<p>Good examples</p> <p>Field visits</p> <p>Interaction with other colleagues/municipalities</p>	<p>Good examples</p> <p>Live webinars</p> <p>Interaction with other colleagues/municipalities</p>

Table NL-3. Compilation of highly ranked (identified by $\geq 40\%$ of respondents): (1) soil health topics for competence development and (2) preferred format for competence development, from the two Netherlands surveys.

5.3.5 Implication for policy

The two surveys clearly showed that actors in the agricultural and urban sectors of the NL who can influence soil health decisions, generally agree that soil health is an important issue. However, what the surveys did not specifically explore was how those same stakeholders would prioritize soil health in comparison to other factors, in situations where there may be trade-offs. Judging by comments from open-ended questions in the urban survey, in particular, many stakeholders would not prioritize soil health if doing so interfered with other aspects of urban development. Similarly, the agricultural survey stressed very strongly that soil health needs to be a viable part of a farm's business model.

That brief summary suggests two directions for policy. The first direction is to answer the question of priority. Soil health cannot always be the first priority in every situation (especially in the urban context), so the question is: when should it be? Soil literacy, research and awareness efforts need to focus on providing a clear, understandable way for relevant stakeholders to make informed decisions about when/how to prioritize soil health in relation to context, and then provide equally clear, understandable options for soil management strategies to improve soil health, where it is the priority. The second direction is to create a framework to support soil health, which includes (appropriate) regulations, but also a suite of market-related options for soil health, which provide enough flexibility for the required changes in management to be financially viable within the context of different farm/urban business models.

5.3.6 Key messages

Based on the general themes of the two surveys, key messages are:

1. Research and disseminate information to assist decision-making about when/where to prioritize soil health. One dissemination option could be the use of an interactive virtual platform to facilitate co-learning (with links to examples/LL's in Point 2).
2. Provide clear context-specific information about management options, preferably as good (local) examples and/or through the facilitation of networks for interaction (consistent with the mandate of living labs).
3. Support the creation of market-based options (i.e. for the payment of ecosystem services), which include companies and consumers in the responsibility for maintaining soil health.
4. Many respondents indicated the need for regulations to protect soil health (in particular in urban areas). But a key, recurring point was to connect with stakeholders who would be affected by new policies to ensure that soil-related policies are helping rather than hindering changes toward soil health.

5.4. Country report: Poland

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5.4.1. Introduction to the study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study regions

The provinces selected for the analysis within the PREPSOIL Task 6.3 are diverse in Poland area size, historical conditions and natural resources: *Lubelskie Voivodeship*, located in the Eastern part of the country, *Silesia (Śląskie Voivodeship)*, located in southern Poland, and *Wielkopolskie Voivodeship*, located in the western part of the country. Details of the areas are presented below in table Table PL-1.

Region Municipalities	Total land area (ha)	Agricultural area (ha) % of total	Forest area (ha) % of total	Urban area (ha) % of total	Population
Voivodeship Lubelskie	2 513 276	1 735 438 (69.1%)	592 710 (23.6%)	155 414 (6.2%)	2 011 000
<i>Lublin</i>	14 747	41.7%	11.8%	39.0%	329 600
<i>Puławy</i>	5 048	23.5%	43.7%	26.6%	44 504
<i>Końskowola</i>	998	83.6%	0.9%	15.1%	2 020
Voivodeship Wielkopolskie	2 979 726	1 974 005 (66.2%)	793 972 (26.6%)	157 859 (5.3%)	3 487 973
<i>Poznań</i>	26 168	40.9%	18.6%	37.1%	538 439
<i>Szamotuły</i>	1 107	45.7%	2.5%	51.2%	18 398
<i>Baborówk</i>	473	75.1%	17.5%	6.2%	431
Voivodeship Śląskie (Silesia)	1 231 682	611 492 (49.6%)	419 510 (34.1%)	179 091 (14.5%)	4 375 947
<i>Katowice</i>	16 452	12.5%	46.4%	39.7%	432 010
<i>Piekary Śląskie</i>	3 982	52.2%	9.6%	37.6%	54 702
<i>Dąbrówka</i>	3 047	16.8%	80.5%	1.2%	504

Table PL-1. Land use statistics from Polish study regions and municipalities. Compiled from geospatial data using ArcGis software.

Lubelskie Voivodeship is situated in the eastern part of Poland. Its area covers 8% of the country's surface. The climate is moderate continental. The economy of Lublin voivodship is based mainly on agriculture; with good soil and climatic conditions. Lublin is territorially the largest and most populous urban municipality in the Lublin Voivodeship. Puławy is a town located in the north-western part of the Lublin Voivodeship. It is an industrial centre, with chemical, pharmaceutical and construction industries as well as scientific and research institutes [PROGRAM OCHRONY ŚRODOWISKA DLA GMINY MIASTO PUŁAWY NA LATA 2021-2024 Z PERSPEKTYWĄ NA LATA 2025-2028]. Końskowola is a rural municipality located in the central part of Puławy County, in the western part of the Lublin Province. It is an important national centre of horticultural production. Końskowola is the most important rose production centre in Poland [Strategia Marki Gospodarczej Gminy Końskowola na lata 2015-2020, OPRACOWANIE Polska Agencja Rozwoju Regionalnego].

The Wielkopolskie Voivodeship is located in western Poland, at the intersection of important European transport links. The voivodeship occupies the second-largest area in the country. Wielkopolska is an agricultural and industrial region. Agricultural land covers over 58.2% of the voivodeship's area. Soils

are of medium and low quality [https://poznan.wios.gov.pl/monitoring-srodowiska/publikacje/raport2013-2015/02_CharakterystykaWojewdzstwa_13-15.pdf]. Poznań is an important centre for industry, business, culture, higher education and science [<https://www.poznan.pl/>]. Szamotuły - The capital of the region, where the original Wielkopolska folklore has been preserved for the longest time. The Szamotuły commune is located in the direct vicinity of the Poznań district. The town is dominated by the agro-industrial economy [<https://szamotuly.pl/>]. Baborówko is a village located in an area characterised by a fairly high frequency of droughts [<https://www.iung.pl/o-instytucie/struktura/rzd/baborowko/>].

Silesian Voivodship accounts for 3.9% of Poland's area. It is the most industrialised region in Poland based on rich deposits of hard coal and zinc and lead ores. The main industrial centre is the Upper Silesian Industrial District (comprising as many as 14 cities in an area of approximately 1,200 km²), where hard coal mining, iron, zinc and lead smelting, chemical and mineral industries have developed. The food, light and wood and paper industries are slightly less developed [https://www.slaskie.pl/images/wpo/wpo_2.html]. The city of Katowice is the capital of the Silesian Voivodeship. The business tourism sector and the so-called meetings industry are developing dynamically in Katowice [<https://pdm.irmir.pl/miasta/katowice>]. Piekary Śląskie is located in the northern part of the Upper Silesian Industrial District [<https://www.staypoland.com/pl/piekary-slaskie.htm/>]. Dąbrówka is a village in Poland located in Śląskie Voivodeship, Gliwice County, in the Wielowieś Municipality. The location of the regions involved in the analysis is shown in the Figure PL-1.

Figure PL-1. The Polish test areas included in the PREPSOIL survey.

National soil health and environmental discourse

In Poland, the concept of soil health is becoming increasingly known and this aspect is of interest of a considerable number of stakeholders. It should be noted that the soil health concept is most common among the agricultural sector. The agricultural sector in Poland has many support and advisory institutions at national, provincial, district and even local level that reach out directly to the farmer. These institutions offer many training courses especially free of charge, which farmers as well as advisors can use and participate in. The coordinating institution for advisory services in Poland is the

Agricultural Advisory Centre with headquarters in Brwinów and Radom (CDR) (<https://www.cdr.gov.pl/>). In addition, the CDR has branches in each voivodship, of which there are 16. Mention should also be made of district teams. The concept of soil health has also become more and more prevalent in recent years, especially in large cities. This is mainly linked to the introduction of urban climate change adaptation plans and thus increasing urban biodiversity. The issue of forest soil health in Poland, and the promotion of this concept in these areas, is not yet widespread. Of course, there are institutions in Poland that study forest soils, but the results of their research are not sufficiently disseminated. However, activities to raise awareness of the health of forest soils are now increasing.

5.4.2. The respondents

The respondents for this survey were selected to represent most important target groups in terms of soil management across various land use types. Due to the existing administrative system in Poland, the focus was mainly on reaching the public sector, although individuals from the private sector were also contacted. In order to obtain the most reliable results from the survey, the questionnaire was directed to those directly involved in soil management or environmental protection, with a particular focus on soils. Questionnaires were sent to respondents by email after prior phone contacts. It should also be noted that the questionnaire could have been also forwarded by respondents further in their own networks. The groups of respondents to whom the questionnaires were addressed, depending on the type of land use, are shown in the following Table PL-2.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Private actors	Farmers Private advisors Local farmers Consulting companies	Private owners Small private forestry companies	Developers, citizens Private landscape architects Design companies Green areas supervision inspectors People active in the Association of Landscape Architects Private persons who have gardens in the Municipal Allotment Gardens
Public actors	Advisory centres Public agricultural advisors National Agricultural Chemical Stations Chambers of agriculture Agricultural advisory centres, local administrations Agency for the restructuring and modernisation of agriculture Academic centres for agriculture National agricultural support centres Agricultural Experimental Departments Agricultural faculties at universities IUNG-PIB staff Municipalities Powiat district authorities Agricultural land surveying and management offices, Teachers in agricultural schools	State Forests Environmental Protection Directorates Polish State Forests Forest Districts Local administration, forestry department Landscape Park Complex – branches Forest experimental plants Forest nurseries Forestry departments at universities Research institute dealing with forestry issues Dendrological gardens Abortion Forest laboratory soils Office of Forest Management and Forest Surveying Teacher in forest schools Foresters	Spatial planners Environmental protection offices Municipal Boards of Urban Greenery Universities Research institutes Municipal offices of landscape architects Administration of housing estates in cities Botanical gardens Public park managers Spatial planning offices Department of urban greenery and spatial planning at the City Halls Secondary school teachers teaching landscape architecture courses Polish Allotment Gardeners Association
NGOs	Foundation for agricultural development Foundations supporting agriculture and soil conservation Foundation ‘Grunt odnowa’	Naturalists' Club Poland UNEP/GRID-Warsaw Centre Forest Forever Foundation	Łąka Foundation Naturalists' Club Polish Association of Allotment Gardeners local urban activists, Nature lovers' circle Landscapes Foundation, Zielona Foundation Municipal Ecological Circles
Other	Demonstration farms Agronomy branch journals Members of the Polish Agroforestry Association	Persons gathered in hunting associations Persons from the hunting association Members of the Polish Forestry Society	Forum for Culture of Space

Table PL-2. List of selected groups of respondents for the PREPSOIL survey in Poland.

Table PL-3 below shows the number of surveys distributed, the number of surveys started and completed. It also shows the groups of respondents that responded most frequently to the survey, according to the type of land use.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Total number of distributed surveys	46	58	106
Surveys started	88	84	63
Surveys completed	44	42	26
Groups of respondents that responded most frequently to the surveys	Agricultural advisors Persons involved in training and education activities Persons involved in agricultural policy implementation Land classifiers Soil scientists Laboratory persons involved in soil analysis	Forestry supervisors Scientists Natural resource conservation sector Secondary school teachers (education) Research institutes Universities with forestry departments State Forests Forestry Divisions	Scientists Spatial planners Environmental scientists Members of scientific associations Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) Private companies mainly landscape architects

Table PL-3. Number of distributed and completed surveys and most frequent groups of respondents.

5.4.3. Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the Polish survey data. The chapter consists of three sections – one for each survey (agriculture, forest and urban). In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the surveys (see Appendix 1, 2 and 3). The prefix PL indicates that the figures belongs to the Polish chapter and the suffix A, F or U indicates which survey they belong to (Agriculture, Forest or Urban).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

The figures PL-Q2A-PL-Q10A show the responses concerning agricultural soils in the survey conducted. The figure PL-Q2A shows vast majority of respondents to the survey are involved in counselling and training activities in their professional work, this answer was chosen by 64% Polish respondents. 34% respondents are involved in research. The implementation of agricultural policy and regional development is dealt with by 18% respondents, 14% chose conservation of nature. Other professions include: regional and local government, education, promotional activities, environmental management and protection, and others such as: performing land classification, conducting land consolidation, laboratory soil testing. The figure PL-Q3A shows that respondents are employed by a state administration authority in the vast majority of cases (48%), the number of responses obtained in the case of Poland far exceeds the values obtained for other countries taking part in the survey. Other frequently marked jobs were: Educational institution/university/research institute (20%) and regional government authority (16%).

The vast majority of respondents have a master's degree or an engineering degree (80%), which is also the case in other countries participating in the survey. Soil science subjects are dominating in their course of study (75%). This fact is mainly due to the fact that the survey mainly contacted public

institutions dealing with agriculture. Compared to the total number of respondents in Poland, fewer people with a doctoral degree (16%) and secondary education and below took part in the survey (5%).

The main specialisations marked by respondents are agriculture (48%), environmental protection (11%), horticulture (9%) and environmental engineering (9%). The majors, which are marked as the other in the figure, include also natural science (23%) such as: zootechnics, biology, forestry, chemistry, geology, spatial management. However, respondents also declared majors such as management, administration, and sociology this is shown in the figure PL-Q6A. In Poland, 75% of respondents gave a positive answer to the question on studying soil science. In Poland, soil science subjects appear in most natural and environmental science faculties and are obligatory. In the case of soil health training, almost 55% of Polish respondents had received such training, which is lower than the average in other countries. In contrast, 45% of respondents had not received such training.

The respondents who took part in the survey on agricultural soils in Poland have, in the great majority, been involved in soil issues in their work for more than 10 years (52%). It also shows that the persons working have relevant knowledge related to soils and are specialists in their field.

The figure PL-Q9A shows that the 50% of Polish respondents to the survey on agricultural soils overwhelmingly rated their knowledge of soils very good to excellent. Furthermore, nearly 16% of respondents chose excellent. The average obtained for Poland is 4.89.

Figure PL-Q2A. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to"

Figure PL-Q3A. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent" Mean value: Poland 5.41; Total 5.21.

Figure PL-Q4A. "I am employed by"

Figure PL-Q6A. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure PL-Q9A. "In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?" Mean value: Poland 4.89; Total 4.87.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After a series of introductory questions, the respondent answered questions concerning the assessment of the state of soil in the EU. The EU Commission has found that most of the EU's soils are unhealthy due to occurring processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced organic matter content, contamination, loss of biodiversity, salinization and sealing /soil subsidence in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. To the question presented, Polish respondents agreed with this formulation in relation to agricultural soils in their region/country. On a Likert scale, the most common response was 4 (27%) and completely agree (20%). The detailed answers were shown on Figure SE-Q11A, average

4.86. Respondents to the survey are often specialists with an agricultural education and therefore rate their knowledge as high. In the vast majority of respondent positions, soil health issues play a key role, thus they strive to raise awareness and improve soil health in Poland. Regarding the identification of the proximate perspective related to the view on soil, it can be concluded that the Polish respondents agree with both perspectives, as they mostly chose the middle option (more than 34% of the respondents). It should also be noted that more than 20% of respondents from Poland identify with focusing on a broad range of ecosystem services related to soil health. The value obtained for Poland, is slightly lower than the average for the other countries taking part in the survey (average 26%). In contrast, only less than 5% of respondents identify more strongly with crop production as an ecosystem service related to soil fertility, the value obtained for Poland was similar to the average 6%, which is shown in the figure PL-Q12A. The Figure PL-Q13aA shows the view on importance of soil health concept in agriculture. The Polish average for this question was 5.98, while the overall average was 6.07. However, when asked whether respondents believed that "The agricultural sector is already using the concept of soil health", the responses were mainly positive (average value 4.43; Figure PL-Q13bA).

Figure PL-Q11A „To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to agricultural soils in your country?” Mean value: Poland 4.86; Total 5.21.

Figure PL-Q12A. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Poland: 4.59; Total 4.84.

Figure PL-Q13aA. “Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture” Mean value: Poland 5.98; Total 6.07.

Figure PL-Q13bA. “The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Poland 4.43; Total 4.25.

Polish respondents, mainly rated their level of general knowledge about soil health well and very well, the answer 4 was recorded for 27% while 5 for 29%, detailed data is shown in the Figure PL-Q14aA, average 4.14. The answers concerning knowledge on the impact of farming on soil health were also in the range of answers 4-6. Detailed data is shown in the Figure PL-Q14bA, average 4.66.

Figure PL-Q14aA. “How knowledgeable are you regarding soil health concept in general” Mean value: Poland 4.14; Total 4.76.

Figure PL-Q14bA. “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?”– Mean value: Poland 4.66; Total 5.03.

Based on the responses, it can be concluded that broad adopting the concept of soil health in agriculture would mean a substantial change in thinking, the Figure PL-Q15aA shows average 5.32. On the other hand, when asked whether adopting the concept of soil health in agriculture would mean a change in how the way workplaces deal with soil, responses on a 7-degree Likerts scale were almost evenly distributed, the Polish average was 4.23; while total was 4.05 (Figure PL-Q15bA).

Figure PL-Q15aA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Poland 5.32; Total 5.12.

Figure PL-Q15bA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Poland 4.23; Total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

The main challenges emerging in agriculture in the region are shown in detail in the figure PL-Q16A: soil degradation related to urbanisation and mining activities (in the Śląskie Voivodeship), acidification,

use of monoculture cultivation, increasing area of fallow land. Other answers given by respondents were: ‘Soil fatigue, intensive ploughing, high share of cereals in the sowing structure, reduction of natural fertilisers, decrease of humus, acidification limit productivity, lack of soil analyses, under-plant fertilisation’ and ‘The need to improve legislation related to the protection of agricultural land (concerning the national level), in particular the Law on the protection of agricultural and forest land; the need for a new look at the location of photovoltaic farms on agricultural land; Encouraging owners of agricultural land to introduce biodiversity on their land’.

Considering the major challenges defined in this study, the most critical for Poland were those related to SOM, biodiversity, water retention and nutrients. It is worth noting that the results obtained for Poland in the survey of agricultural soils are, for the most part, slightly higher than the values obtained for the rest of the countries. The respondents defined the following issues they deal with in their jobs: promoting awareness on sustainable soil management and the importance of soil, followed by improving soil nutrients and fertility, increasing soil water retention, increasing organic matter. It is important to note that only one of the suggested answers exceeded the average achieved for the other countries, this was the answer related to avoiding soil sealing. The obtained average for Poland is 27%, total 15% .The detailed data are shown in the figure PL-Q18A.

Figure PL-Q16A: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure PL-Q18A. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in agricultural soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

The agricultural survey also included open-ended questions directly related to the perceived obstacles appearing in the way of soil health in Poland and the measures respondents would suggest removing these obstacles. Obstacles limiting the improvement of agricultural soils in Poland based on responses collected from respondents are:

Scattered spatial development, associated with low awareness, leads to excessive restriction of available agricultural space and fragmentation of agricultural land, which hinders its effective management and may have a negative impact on its quality and fertility.

Lack of awareness among farmers, failure to perform basic soil tests, high cost of soil improvement by performing soil tests and applying possible changes in soil fertilization. The growing economic necessity to use intensive methods in crop production can lead to overloading of soils used in agriculture, which in turn can lead to degradation of soil resources, reduced biodiversity and increased pollution. Inappropriate agricultural practices, such as fertilization without testing, are often used to disturb soil conditions.

The lack of amendment of regulations related to the protection of agricultural land prevents the introduction of effective instruments to protect and sustainably use agricultural soils, which may lead to further deterioration of their condition. Lack of stable policies, lack of financial resources. Low prices for agricultural products with high input costs. The following table PL-Q19A shows direct quotes appearing in the survey.

<p>Economic aspects</p> <p><i>"Underfunding of soil liming"</i></p> <p><i>"Low prices for agricultural products. High costs of production inputs"</i></p> <p><i>"Costs of liming, costs of post-harvesting (purchase of seeds, agro-technical treatments), hindrance when performing agro-technical treatments, costs associated with conducting proper agro-technology."</i></p>
<p>Social aspects</p> <p><i>"Lack of awareness of farmers; unawareness of erosion processes; importance of soil biodiversity"</i></p> <p><i>"The need to education of farmers."</i></p> <p><i>"Low knowledge of farmers on these topics. Poor agrochemical processes and too much fertilizer without checking the need."</i></p>
<p>Legal aspects</p> <p>"Lack of amendment of laws related to the protection of agricultural areas."</p> <p>"Uncontrolled urbanization of rural areas (dispersed development)"</p> <p>"Lack of stable policies"</p>

Table PL-Q19A. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

Possible remedial actions perceived by respondents in the context of agricultural soils include mainly economic aspects related to increasing funding directed on agriculture and efforts to raise awareness among farmers. The following table PL-Q20A details the quotes that appeared in the Polish survey.

<p>Aspects to improve the economic situation:</p> <p><i>"Improving economic situation of agriculture in general"</i></p> <p><i>"Dedicated support instruments"</i></p> <p><i>"Economic solutions for GAEC implementation"</i></p> <p><i>"Systemic approaches at national level."</i></p>
<p>Raising awareness and education:</p> <p><i>"Increased awareness of Farmers, through meetings and training with peri-agricultural units in Poland"</i></p> <p><i>"Certified training for farmers"</i></p> <p><i>"Increasing farmers' awareness of the problems and encouraging soil testing."</i></p> <p><i>"Training for farmers. Adequate subsidies for soil improvement in agriculture"</i></p> <p><i>"Introduce sustainable agricultural practices: Agricultural practices that minimize the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers should be encouraged, such as perennial cover crops, organic fertilization, composting, and crop rotation. Sustainable farming methods can increase soil fertility, improve soil structure, and reduce the risk of erosion.</i></p> <p><i>Protecting soil from erosion: It is important to use preventive measures such as maintaining riparian vegetation, building terraces on slopes, planting vegetation strips in fields, and using agricultural practices that minimize soil plowing to reduce the risk of soil erosion.</i></p> <p><i>Adapting to climate change: To cope with the negative effects of climate change on soil health, it is important to adapt agricultural practices to changing weather conditions. Among other things, one can consider using water-saving techniques, growing drought-tolerant crop varieties, and implementing agricultural practices that increase the soil's water retention capacity."</i></p>

Table PL-Q20A. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

The vast majority of respondents when asked what they would like to learn more about, ticked the answer related to the general concept of soil health. This is mainly due to the fact that not all respondents have taken a course on soil health (question 8). Further answers that received a high number of votes (45%) were: soil management strategies to improve soil health (sustainable and regenerative strategies) and the answer how to assess soil health. Other answers selected by a significant number of respondents were: soil biodiversity (39%), soil chemistry (36%), nutrient leaching (34%), soil pollution (30%), carbon sequestration potential (27%), and land degradation (2%). In contrast, other answers were selected by less than 10 respondents from Poland.

To the question on relevant competence development measures on soil health, Polish respondents chose the answer 'I don't' the value obtained for Poland is slightly lower than the value obtained for other countries is almost identical and amounts to 27%. The vast majority of Polish respondents chose the middle values.

Polish respondents in the agricultural survey in the context of what they most often choose when they want to learn more about the condition of soils most often reach for: agricultural magazines (52%), webinars (52%), field visits (45%), through good examples (32%), internet films (recorded material) 36% answers, physical courses (30%). Interviews with other colleagues/local authorities (10). Other responses received less than 10 responses from respondents.

The forest survey

Description of the respondents

Figure PL-Q2F shows the respondents' answers related to soil health issues that directly involve them in their work. A significant group of Polish respondents to the survey related to forest areas were those who deal with education in their daily work, this answer was selected by 12 respondents, representing 29% of the respondents, while education among the other respondents to the survey is dealt with by 14% of the respondents. Other fields selected by Polish respondents were forestry management 26%, nature and natural resources protection 26%, scientific research 21%, and environmental management and protection 10%. Respondents who took part in the survey also ticked: promotional activities, policy work/development of forest policy sales. 17% of respondents indicated that they do not address soil issues in their forestry work. Other responses given by respondents included: service activities, silviculture and forest management. Figure PL-Q3F shows the responses to a question that directly addresses the issue of engagement with soil issues in their work. Respondents participating in the survey most often declared low or very low involvement related to soil health issues (the most frequently selected options from the Likert scale was a range of 2-4). It is worth noting that 14% of respondents to the survey in Poland have very high involvement in forest soil health issues. Figure PL-Q4F shows that the vast majority of Polish respondents are employed in a state administration body or a local government unit, as well as in a scientific institution (the responses for these areas are the same at 24% respectively). Respondents who selected the 'other' option overwhelmingly also write in a state administration body and a scientific institution.

For question 5 about the level of education held, a significant number of respondents from Poland responding to the survey answered that they have a university degree, the value for is higher than for the other countries. Possession of a doctoral degree was indicated by six respondents, while only two respondents from Poland indicated that they had secondary education. In contrast, the number is much higher among respondents from other countries.

The Figure PL-Q6F shows that the respondents from Poland who took part in the survey mostly graduated in forestry/forest engineering, but this value is lower for Poland compared to the other countries taking part in the survey. It should be noted that in Poland, majors in natural sciences such as environmental protection (agriculture, forestry, horticulture, environmental protection) always have soil science subjects, a question that appeared in the survey (question 7), Polish respondents in had 93% soil science subjects. This is also reflected in the survey, also in comparison with respondents from other countries, who had soil science subjects in 79%. In response to question 8 about completing training on soil health issues, as many as 67% of respondents from Poland did not receive such training. Only 33% of respondents declared that they had completed such a course. The answers collected for Poland are similar to the answers from other countries. This effect is reflected in the survey results, mainly due to the fact that such training is not very popular in Poland.

The figure PL-Q9F shows how respondents assess their knowledge of soils in relation to their needs, as many as 33% of respondents assessed their knowledge as good, and 24% as very good. The average for Poland was 4.17, while the total was 4.21.

On the question 10 related to how many years the respondents have been dealing with soil issues in their work in the context of forestry, the vast majority of Polish respondents marked the answer that they do not deal with soil issues in their work (17 people). 10 respondents indicated that they have been working with soil issues for more than 10 years, 5-10 years were also selected by 10 respondents and 5 respondents have been working with soil issues for less than 5 years. In the survey focusing on

forest areas in Poland, 42 respondents took part, while 147 respondents took part in the survey as a whole. Respondents from Poland account for 29% of all respondents who took part in the survey. The largest number of respondents are from urban areas and other areas, as respondents chose the national level. It should be emphasised that the respondents who took part in the forest soil survey represented almost all the regions selected for the task.

Figure PL-Q2F. “In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to”

Figure PL-Q3F. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent.” Mean value: Poland 3.64; Total 4.08.

Figure PL-Q4F. “I am employed by”

Figure PL-Q6F. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Figure PL-Q9F. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Poland 4.17; Total 4.21.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the baseline questions, respondents were presented with a formulation of the soil health problem developed by the EU Commission, which concluded that most soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinity and soil sealing/subsidence on agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. The answers to this question varied. The average for Poland obtained in this question was 3.57; while the total average for all respondents was 4.14 (Figure PL-Q11F). It is worth noting that the condition of forest soils in Poland has not been perceived as a problem so far. The largest group of respondents, as many as 30%, chose the middle one (“4”); only 9% of respondents participating in the study notice a problem related to the health of forest soils. Comparing the answers obtained to the agricultural survey, it is worth noting that in forestry in Poland, issues are less often noticed related to soil health. In the next question, respondents were presented with two main views on soil. It was found to be on one side soil fertility continuum was defined as the ability of the soil to sustain production. In this case, the emphasis is on is mainly for the ecosystem service "providing food, fibre and fuel"/forest raw material. On the other side continuum stated that soil health is defined as the ability of the soil to maintain productivity, diversity and environmental services in terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a wide range of ecosystem services. The question asked respondents to indicate which perspective was consistent with their own view. Respondents from Poland taking part in the study overwhelmingly chose the middle answer - neutral “4”, almost 31% of respondents chose it. Very similar results were obtained in a study on agricultural soils. It should be emphasized that only 19% of respondents believed that the focus should be on a wide range of ecosystem services (soil health); (Figure PL-Q12F). When asked whether

soil health is an important concept in forestry, the vast majority of respondents from Poland (45%) agreed with this formulation. The average obtained for Poland was 5.79, while for the rest of the respondents it was 5.22 (Figure PL-Q13aF). Compared to the responses from the agricultural survey conducted in Poland, the obtained responses are similar. When asked whether the forest sector in Poland uses soil health as a concept, the average obtained was 4.48, while for the rest it was 3.35 (figure PL-Q13bF). The Polish respondents in the forest soil survey significantly agree with the conclusion that soil health is an important concept in forestry, and they also agree that the forestry sector uses soil health as a concept. It should be noted that the Polish averages are significantly higher than those of other respondents. In the question related to the respondents' general knowledge regarding the concept of soil health, the averages obtained are low and amount to 3.48 for Poland and 3.33 for the rest of the countries. This is certainly an area requiring improvement and greater educational activities in this area (Figure PL-Q14aF). In terms of the general level of knowledge about forest management on soil health, the average was higher and amounted to 4.29 for Poland, the total was 4.16 (Figure PL-Q14bF). Most respondents agree that the adoption of the concept of soil health in forestry would change the way of thinking about soil, the average for Poland is 3.67, while the average for total is 4.14 (Figure PL-Q15aF). Additionally, respondents believed that adopting the concept of soil health in forestry would make little or no difference to how workplaces would address these issues, with a mean score of 3.17 (Figure PL-Q15aF).

Figure PL-Q11F. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to forest soils in your country?” Mean value: Poland 3.67; Total 4.14.

Figure PL-Q12F. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Poland 4.17; Total 4.61.

Figure PL-Q13aF. “Soil health is a relevant concept in forestry.” Mean value: Poland 5.79; Total 5.22.

Figure PL-Q13bF. “The forestry sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Poland 4.48; Total 3.35.

Figure PL-Q14aF. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Poland 3.48; Total 3.33.

Figure PL-Q14bF. “How knowledgeable are you about how forest management affects soil health?” Mean value: Poland 4.29; Total 4.16.

Figure PL-Q15aF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Poland 4.21; Total 4.41.

Figure PL-Q15bF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Poland 3.17; Total 3.68.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

The next series of questions in the survey addressed the challenges that respondents face in their professional work. The challenge that received the highest number of votes was improving water retention/infiltration/drainage, which received an average of 5.02, while other challenges declared by respondents included peatland management, which received an average of 4.69, and efforts to reduce erosion, with an average of 4.62. The greatest similarities observed between the challenges of forest and agricultural soils in Poland were the aim to improve water retention and infiltration, the aim to reduce erosion and, in addition, to improve nutrient cycling (Figure PL-Q16F). When asked how the respondents' workplaces deal with the challenges listed above, the most frequent responses were: Improving awareness of sustainable forest management mean 5.19, increasing biodiversity mean 4.76 and aiming to reduce erosion mean 4.45 (Figure PL-Q18F).

Figure PL-Q16F: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in forest soils in your region/country?”

Figure PL-Q18F: “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in forest soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

In the survey, two open questions about perceived hindrances for improved soil health followed by what kind of measures the respondents would suggest to deal with these hindrances were presented. Just as for the agricultural survey, many different hindrances were mentioned. The three main barriers to improving the quality of forest soils in Poland as identified by respondents: 1. Lack of forest water management programs, 2. The need for stand rebuilding with species of adequate species, and 3. Overexploitation of forests, soil pollution, increase in the degree of mechanization of forestry work. The Table PL-Q19F below shows the quotes from respondents.

<p>Legal aspects</p> <p><i>"Legal regulations, poor knowledge of forest soil protection, poor use of forest areas"</i></p> <p><i>"Lack of forest water management programs".</i></p> <p><i>"Convoluting procedures of the Water Law".</i></p>
<p>Cultural aspects</p> <p><i>"Current silvicultural principles directly (cutting methods) or indirectly (species selection) positively influence soil quality."</i></p> <p><i>"Excessive deforestation, associated erosion, forest spraying".</i></p> <p><i>"State of knowledge of foresters, habits, very cursory approach to silviculture".</i></p>
<p>Environmental aspects</p> <p><i>"Low soil moisture due to lack of sufficient rainfall. Inadequate stand composition for soil conditions".</i></p> <p><i>"External influences - climate change, pollution, amount and temporal distribution of precipitation".</i></p> <p><i>"Excessive forestry exploitation, Soil pollution, Climate change".</i></p>

Table PL-Q19F. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

Among the suggested remedies to improve the condition of forest soils in Poland indicated by respondents are: *Implementing sustainable forestry practices, Reducing logging and promoting selective cutting and Training programmes to increase knowledge of forest soils.* Quotes from the survey appear in Table PL-Q20F.

<p>Cultural aspects</p> <p><i>"Reduction of felling, abandonment of spraying in favor of the introduction of multi-species stands more resistant to disease agents"</i></p> <p><i>"Systemic solutions to improve operations".</i></p> <p><i>"Technological advances in forest harvesting operations".</i></p>
<p>Educational aspects:</p> <p><i>"Training, prevention programs, practical measures to counter the effects of degradation."</i></p> <p><i>"Training courses to broaden knowledge on forest soils, change of silvicultural principles and habitat basis of silviculture".</i></p>
<p>Environmental aspects</p> <p><i>"Increasing retention, e.g. by creating dams rather than just reservoirs; fragmenting matter and leaving it in the forest"</i></p> <p><i>"Development of water management programs in forests"</i></p> <p><i>"Reconstruction of stands related to adaptation of stand composition to soil and water conditions".</i></p>

Table PL-Q20F. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

The last part of the study concerned the perceived needs in the field of competence development, whether competence development activities are currently available for a given group of respondents and what forms of activities they prefer. When asked about the topics that Polish respondents would like to learn more about, the dominant topics included aspects related to soil biodiversity (40% of respondents), forest management strategies aimed at improving soil health, aspects related to how to assess soil health (40% of respondents), the general concept of soil health was chosen by over 28% of respondents. Aspects of less interest to respondents were soil pollution, declared by 19% of respondents, desertification by 19% and soil compaction by 16%.

The forms of education most often chosen by respondents if they want to learn more are: field trips (55%), industry magazines (31%), online videos (24%), reports, books (22%), stationary classes or

webinars (19%). Discussions with experts and local authorities and learning from good examples were also very popular among Polish respondents (17%).

The urban survey

Description of respondents

The PL-Q2-10U charts below show respondents participating in the survey from cities in Poland, which were conducted through the online survey. Most of the participants in the urban survey were entities dealing with soil in connection with scientific research (36%), maintenance of parks and gardens (28%), spatial planning (24%) and environmental issues (24%). Other less frequently appearing professions include biomass production (except food) (12%), education (8%), topsoil reuse (4%) (Figure PL-Q2U). The vast majority of respondents are, to a large or very large extent, related to soil issues in their professional work. The average for Poland is 4.62, while for the remaining respondents it is 5.51 (Figure PL-Q3U). The vast majority of respondents participating in the study represented a research unit or university (62%), and a local government unit 15% (Figure PL-Q3U). The vast majority of study participants had higher education and a master's degree (69%), 27% of respondents declared a doctorate degree, while only 4% of respondents declared lower education (Figure PL-Q4U). The vast majority of Polish respondents participating in the survey completed studies in fields related to spatial planning, architecture and urban planning (23%), environmental sciences and engineering (31%), horticulture (19%). Other fields of study were declared by 12% of respondents, including: economics, biology and landscape architecture (Figure PL-Q6U). During their education, over 58% of respondents did not have any soil science courses, while 42% of respondents declared that they had them. However, only 31% of respondents declared that they had completed training on soil health issues. The lack of training on soil health among Polish respondents also appeared during the survey on agricultural and forest soils. In relation to their needs, respondents taking part in the survey on urban soils rated their knowledge as good and very good. The average obtained for this question was 4.15 (Figure PL-Q9U). The answers to the question about the years of work during which respondents dealt with soil issues are almost evenly distributed. They have been dealing with soil-related issues for over 10 years (27%), 23% of respondents declared the range of 5-10 years, 27% of respondents have been dealing with soil issues for <5 years and the survey was attended by 23% of respondents who do not deal with issues related to soil soils. The survey focusing on urban areas in Poland had 26 respondents, while 143 respondents took part in the survey as a whole. The largest number of respondents are from large cities: Katowice, Lublin, Poznań, a significant number of respondents were also from Pulawy. Respondents from Poland who took part in the survey represent 18% of all respondents.

Figure PL-Q2U. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to..."

Figure PL-Q3U. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Poland 4.62; Total 5.5

Figure PL-Q4U. "I am employed by"

Figure PL-Q6U. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure PL-Q9U. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Poland 4.15; Total 4.62.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the first part of the general questions, respondents were presented with the EU Commission's formulation of the soil health problem, arguing that most soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and sealing/subsidence soils on agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. Unlike the agriculture and forestry survey, the majority of urban voices were well into the upper half of the scale regarding the question of whether respondents agreed or disagreed with the problem statement for urban soils. The highest bar was even found in the case of the answer "strongly agree" (46%; mean 5.15; Figure PL-Q11U). The average obtained for this question can be compared with 4.86 for agricultural survey and 3.67 for forestry survey. The poor condition of urban soils is increasingly noticed not only in Poland; half of the respondents agreed with this problem presented by the European Commission.

In the next question, respondents were presented with two main perspectives on soil, and they should indicate which view of soil best corresponds to their own view. At one end of the continuum was the targeted use of soil, which means focusing on one or more specific functions at a time (i.e. as a foundation for buildings/infrastructure, as a medium for water purification, or as a substrate for growing trees and plants). On the other side of the continuum, there is a simultaneous focus on a wide range of soil ecosystem services. In a survey in Poland, 42% of respondents declared a focus on "simultaneously focusing on a wide range of ecosystem services" (Figure PL-Q12U; mean 4.13).

For further questions on the relevance of the concept of soil health to urban soils and whether the urban sector is already using the concept or not, there was variation in respondents' responses, Figure PL-Q13aU shows that over half (54%) of respondents strongly agreed with this statement, the average answer obtained for this question was 5,96. However, based on responses to the next question about whether the urban sector uses soil health as a concept, the question received an average of 2,50 among respondents from all countries (Figure PL-Q13bU). When asked about the general state of knowledge of respondents about the concept of soil health, respondents in Poland answered in a different way – almost 35% of respondents rated their knowledge very good, choosing '5', 27% of respondents rated their knowledge good - '4', and 23% of respondents rated their knowledge as poor (Figure PL-Q14aU). Based on the question about the level of respondents' knowledge about the impact of soil management and its health, one can notice the potential to increase knowledge about the general concept of soil health among managers of Polish cities (average 3.96, figure PL-Q14bU). Based on the question about whether adopting the concept of urban soil health would mean a change in thinking, Polish respondents strongly agreed. The average obtained for this question was 5.42 (Figure

PL-Q15aU). However, when asked whether adopting the concept would change the way workplaces would perceive soils is already diverse, the average obtained was 4.08 (Figure PL-Q15bU).

Figure PL-Q11U. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to urban soils in your country?” Mean value: Poland 5.15; Total 5.60.

Figure PL-Q12U. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Poland 4.13; Total 3.82

Figure PL-Q13aU. “Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils.” Mean value: Poland 5.96; Total 5.72.

Figure PL-Q13bU. “The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Poland 2.92; Total 2.50.

Figure PL-Q14aU. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Poland 3.69; Total 3.71.

Figure PL-Q14bU. “How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?” Mean value: Poland 3.96; Total 4.00.

Figure PL-Q15aU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Poland 5.42; Total 5.24

Figure PL-Q15bU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Poland 4.08; Total 4.59.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Challenges related to soil health in Polish cities that were considered a problem and noticed by respondents were mainly: improving water retention/infiltration/drainage (average 4.88), avoiding soil pollution (5.15), adaptation and regulation to climate change (4.92), increasing biodiversity (5.00), reducing soil erosion (4.77), reducing soil sealing (4.69) (Figure PL-Q16U).

However, when asked to what extent respondents' workplaces cope with the challenges considered, respondents most often chose: Recycling and reuse of soil (4.27), Promoting awareness of sustainable soil management (4.23), Adapting/regulating/mitigating the effects of climate change (average 4.04) and Improvement of water retention/infiltration/drainage (average 4.00). A detailed summary is presented in Figure PL-Q18U.

Figure PL-Q16U. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region/country?”

Figure PL-Q18U. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in urban soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

The survey included two questions related to obstacles that prevent, according to respondents' soil condition and what type of remedial measures respondents would suggest to avoid these obstacles. As in the case of the survey on agriculture and forestry, many similar difficulties were mentioned related to the need for legal changes, increased education, or a change in the view of the environment.

The three key obstacles hindering the improvement of forest soils in Poland as identified by respondents:

1. Investment pressure and lack of awareness of soil management solutions, including the lack of monitoring of building works in aspect of soil - there are no specialized procedures for earthworks in the city. Supervision and penalties for illegal landscaping are not applied. Not taking action by building inspectors in case of non-compliance with requirements for biologically active area, affecting soil sealing and loss of water retention.

2. Deficiencies in legal regulations and urban development planning, Lack of knowledge about the condition of soils and the need to improve them, and low awareness among residents about the health of urban soils
3. Faulty understanding of sustainable transportation - Striving to maximize the built-up or paved area of the plot for parking, in addition to too frequent and too low mowing of lawns in the summer period. In contrast, the excessive use of road salt during the winter period, Lack of resources for alternative forms of counteracting glare than salt.

Table PL-Q19U below shows quotes from respondents.

<p>Legal aspects</p> <p><i>"Lack of legal regulations, deficiencies in the local spatial development plan, omission of environmental issues in spatial planning".</i></p> <p><i>"Lack of awareness of the problem (among city authorities, officials, investors, residents)"</i></p> <p><i>"Investment pressure (prism of investments over protection of nature, soil, air...)"</i></p>
<p>Educational and administrative aspects</p> <p><i>"Urban development, lack of land use plans, low awareness of urban residents about soil health"</i></p> <p><i>"Lack of awareness, lack of funding for research, perception that urban soils are less important than soils used for agriculture"</i></p> <p><i>"Lack of awareness, lack of funding, poor management".</i></p>
<p>Environmental aspects</p> <p><i>"Soil sealing, disturbed water retention, most of the areas that are undeveloped are designated for construction"</i></p> <p><i>"Large areas of land being taken over for development, industry and commerce, high emissions of pollutants and dust"</i></p> <p><i>"Lack of awareness, improper management of soils, pollution".</i></p>

Table PL-Q19U. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

In terms of suggested countermeasures to deal with perceived obstacles, many of the mentioned ideas were related to the need to develop knowledge, changes in spatial planning law and environmental issues were raised. Table SE-Q20U below provides examples of survey citations.

<p>Spatial aspects</p> <p><i>"Limiting the influence of developers on the shaping of space in cities, designing urban greenery, ensuring 100% coverage by Local Development Plans in urban areas".</i></p> <p><i>"Restricting the construction of industrial, commercial and development infrastructure in green areas, limiting car traffic, implementing ecological means of transport, installing filters to capture pollution, replacing harmful substances with safe substitutes".</i></p> <p><i>"Sustainable urban planning that involves the reuse of soils after vacant land, and a campaign to raise public awareness."</i></p>
<p>Legal aspects</p> <p><i>"Revision of legislation and enforcement of current laws"</i></p> <p><i>"Changing legislation, raising awareness among residents".</i></p> <p><i>"Education of local government administrations increased funding to address these issues".</i></p>
<p>Educational aspects</p> <p><i>"Increased awareness of residents on soil health, creation of master plans to protect good quality soils from development."</i></p> <p><i>"Increased public consultation with the local community within settlements and neighborhoods."</i></p> <p><i>"Increased role of education of children, young people and students about the role of soils and its importance."</i></p>

Table PL-Q20U. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

In the context of the question about whether there are adequate resources to develop competences in soil health, respondents rated this question poorly, with an average for Poland of 2.88 and an overall average of 2.66. It is worth emphasizing that many respondents had no opinion.

When asked about preferences as to what form of knowledge respondents most often reach for to learn more about the health of urban soils, the most votes were given to field trips (46%), discussions with experts and local authorities (38%) and gaining knowledge based on good examples. (38%). Other examples that received a significant number of responses (35%) included online videos (recorded material) (35%), books and trade magazines (31%). Less popular among respondents in Poland were: podcasts, digital courses and reports. In terms of topics respondents would like to learn more about, the following aspects received the most votes: How to assess soil health (for specific land use functions) (69%), the general concept of soil health (58%), Soil recycling/reuse (38%), soil management strategies to improve soil health (38%), Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation (23%).

5.4.4. Discussion

Agricultural survey

According to the responses received from the agricultural survey, it should be noted that the involvement of respondents is definitely higher than in the survey conducted in forest and urban areas. The vast majority of respondents came from the Silesian province, it is worth noting that this is not a typically agricultural province. This was followed by respondents from Lubelskie and Wielkopolskie provinces, and there were also respondents from other provinces, but their total number was small. The vast majority of respondents are directly involved in the soil itself in their work, and among the place of employment, the public sector definitely dominates, followed by a scientific unit and a public administration body. It should be noted that the vast majority of respondents involved in agriculture have a university degree related to agricultural sciences or generally related to natural sciences. The vast majority of the Polish respondents have been dealing with soil issues for more than 10 years, which indicates the high knowledge of specialists and reliable analysis of soil problems. The vast majority of the averages of the responses obtained from Polish respondents are close to the total average obtained for all countries participating in the survey. Among the biggest problems, respondents most often cited economic factors, low levels of education, and lack of stable policies. The biggest challenges facing agricultural land managers in Poland are first and foremost efforts to increase soil organic matter, as well as increase biodiversity. Challenges related to agricultural soils in Poland also include improving water retention/infiltration/drainage and soil fertility, as well as peatland management. Given the increasing severity of climate change in Poland, associated with increasing droughts and atmospheric fluctuations, these aspects become even more important. As these changes require an interdisciplinary approach and analysis of the problems, many public sector institutions related to agricultural soils face the challenge of raising awareness related to promoting sustainable soil management and promoting the importance of soil health in Poland.

Forest survey

Based on the results obtained from the survey related to forest soils, it is important to note that respondents largely rate forest soils as well-preserved and healthy. In a way, of course, this is largely a correct statement, but it is worth noting that forest soils are not studied as thoroughly as agricultural soils. The survey mainly involved respondents with professional ties to public administration, local government units (county/ municipality) and a scientific institution university or research institute.

This is mainly due to the fact that a person with professional ties to forestry is easier to contact than a private forest owner. With a decisive majority of respondents having graduated from a university with a degree in forestry, a sound theoretical basis and work experience is an important element related to the reliability of the answers given by respondents. Subjects related to soil science at natural science faculties in Poland are among the compulsory subjects, while it is worth noting that courses related to soil health (regardless of its type of use) are not popular in Poland. Despite having some knowledge of soil science, most foresters and those associated with forestry in their professional work pay little attention to soils themselves. This is a certain reflection of the perception of the forest mostly in terms of production or tourism (without much attention given to forest soils). This is certainly, an element that in the perspective of time in Poland should be subjected to deeper consideration and greater attention to forest soils as well, in terms of raising awareness in this regard. The most noticeable problems in Polish agriculture regardless of the region are first and foremost: reducing desertification and improving water retention/infiltration/drainage, affecting inadequate water relations in forests in the current climate change affect excessive drying of litter, which can lead to forest fires, which have unfortunately been increasing in recent years. Another challenge that emerged from the survey is also the management of peatlands, which are a kind of water store. Respondents to the survey also recognize the challenges of reducing erosion of forest land and the need to improve nutrients in forest soils. As in the survey on agricultural soils, forestry stakeholders in their organizations recognize the need to promote awareness related to soil health and sustainable forest management in Poland.

Urban survey

The questionnaire on urban soils was filled out by the largest number of respondents from Pulawy, this is mainly due to the fact that it is a small city and all institutions are in good contact with each other (IUNG is headquartered in Pulawy), another city that was chosen by a significant number of respondents was Lublin, Other cities that were chosen by respondents were Katowice and Poznan, it is worth noting that these are provincial cities and are their capitals (Poznan of Greater Poland Province, Katowice of Slaskie Voivodeship). Of the remaining smaller county cities (Szamotuły i Piekary Śląskie), the surveys did not appear. The vast majority of respondents are related to soil through research and maintenance of parks and green spaces, as well as urban planning. Respondents from Poland who took part in the survey are less involved in soil-related issues in their work, compared to the rest of the survey respondents. Research institutes and universities dominate among the respondents' workplaces, with local government units with a forestry department also appearing to a significant extent. Polish respondents to the survey overwhelmingly have a university degree. Respondents who took part in the survey are mainly graduates of such majors as environmental engineering, horticulture, urban planning and landscape architecture, it is worth noting that these persons have varied seniority in positions where they deal with soil issues. Despite their varying seniority, they identify with the European Commission's statement in connection with the assessment of urban soils in the EU as unhealthy soils, sharing the opinion of respondents from other countries participating in the survey. On the other hand, in terms of perspectives related to soil, respondents from Poland, are closer to the first perspective, which is focused on the use of soil - Focusing on one or more specific functions.

At the same time, Respondents also identify with the statement that soil health is an important concept for urban soils. Challenges that respondents identified as the most important problems related to urban soils are: reducing soil contamination and remediation of contaminated areas, adaptation and mitigation of climate change, another key aspect that needs to be improved on urban soils is improving its retention/infiltration and drainage. Respondents also included the following as problem areas in Polish cities: improving soil fertility, restoring artificial surfaces, increasing soil

biodiversity, and reducing sealing, among others. Polish Soil Institutions, based on respondents' answers, face the biggest challenge related to: promoting awareness of the importance of soil health, as well as their sustainable management. Other complex aspects include: reducing pollution, including remediating contaminated areas and giving them a new function, improving soil fertility and biodiversity, as well as reducing the sealing of permeable surfaces. Polish Cities face a significant challenge to protect soils in an era of emerging climate change, while developing the infrastructure of Polish cities. To this end, it is essential to introduce nature-based solutions into the urban environment.

Cross-sector

Based on surveys conducted among three groups of stakeholders: users of agricultural land, forests and cities, it is worth noting that to some extent they perceive issues related to soil in a different way. However, some significant conclusions can be drawn. The group most directly related to soil issues is the group linked to agricultural land management. The farmers directly see and experience the effects and consequences of unhealthy or inadequately managed soil on his crops and subsequently his profits. The level of discussion on soil health in agriculture has increased since recent years. In case of urban areas, soil related issues have recently been discussed increasingly. This is related to the need for adaptation of cities to climate change and the possibility of mitigating its effects. Taking into account soil aspects is of great importance here due to the current state of health of urban soils. Urban areas in Poland are dominated by to some extent degraded and significantly sealed land. In order to adapt cities to climate change, it is necessary to improve soil health. Regarding forest areas, soil-related aspects have not been frequently considered (apart from specialized research in the field of forestry and soils), many forestry workers focus little on soil-related aspects in their work. Currently, this focus is changing slightly and the issues of forest soil health, including their protection, are getting more attention. However, it is worth publicizing and promoting these activities and initiatives aimed at improving the health of forest soils on a wider scale. Healthy forest ecosystems constitute a huge potential not only for Poland, so it is worth striving to increase activities aimed at raising awareness, not only among people associated with public forestry, but also among private forest owners. An important conclusion drawn from the analysis is that the respondents, regardless the land use type, unanimously stated that it is necessary to raise the awareness of the authorities and citizens in soil health issues. Citizen awareness is one of the key pillars that influences building a responsible society that cares for the environment, including the soil. Another important aspect that was rated highly in each survey was "improving water retention/infiltration/drainage". This is undoubtedly a very important aspect because disturbances related to inappropriate retention of surface water significantly contribute to the aggravation of climate change, deepening droughts and increased losses in agriculture, may be the cause of forest fires, and in cities they contribute to the creation of a sealed surface, devoid of biodiversity.

The results regarding obstacles to improved soil health and measures to deal with these obstacles were similar between sectors. Table PL-4 below summarises the most common comparisons. Each of the three surveys mentioned a lack of knowledge and awareness of soil health, and a lack of transparent regulation. Certainly, soil health issues, irrespective of site type, are aspects on which awareness needs to be raised on a significant scale. Transparent regulations are necessary for this and must be enforced.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Hindrances for improved soil health	Progressive climate change The occurrence of prolonged droughts during the growing season Limited agricultural funding	Little awareness among foresters and forest managers related to the health of forest soils Perception of the forest mainly in terms of production or tourism (without much interest in forest soils)	Low awareness of the problem (among city authorities, officials, investors, residents) Investment pressure (priority of investments over nature, soil, air protection...)
Measures to deal with identified hindrances	Development of new methods, approaches and concepts for soil management More education and encouragement, e.g. through additional payments for measures to improve soil health	Raising awareness of forest soil health Promotional activities carried out in this field showing the possibilities of improving forest soil health	Introducing climate change adaptation plans in cities, thus introducing nature-based solutions in Polish cities

Table PL-4. Compilation of the main hindrances for improved soil health and suggested measures to deal with those hindrances from the three Polish surveys.

Based on the survey, the need for competence development is noticeable. Respondents to the survey declared very similar needs. The most popular forms of competence development chosen by the respondents are included in the following Table PL-5. The survey participants most preferred field activities and webinars and online courses. The combination of these activities may be an important option to increase awareness and knowledge of soil health issues among key stakeholders.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Soil health topics ranked high for competence development	How to evaluate soil health The general concept of soil health Soil biodiversity Soil management Strategies to improve soil health	Forest management strategies to improve Soil health Soil biodiversity How to assess soil health	How to management urban soils A general concept of urban soil health
Preferred format for competence development	Field visits Professional journals Webinars (live)	Field visits Professional journals Reports	Field visits Talks with local experts Online videos and webinars

Table PL-5. Compilation of the soil health topics ranked high for competence development and preferred format for competence development from the three Polish surveys.

5.4.5. Implication for policy

Concerning implications to policy, the discussions revealed:

- a strong need for developing campaigns to raise awareness on the need to properly manage soils across various land use types. The soil health shall be a key concept and context of these programmes;
- the need was defined to create clear and transparent guidelines for practices to improve soil health for all involved in soil management, including citizens;

- the need for promoting sustainable management of the soil in connection with spatial development along with addressing soil management in the related regulations, since the issue of soil health in urban areas is not sufficient addressed;
- a strong need for awareness raising related to the need for water retention and the creation of so-called 'small retention' in towns, forests, washed fields.
- the need for increasing the importance of peatlands and wetlands, extending protection to these areas.
- the need to involve the importance of soils in the context of urban climate change adaptation policy plans.

5.4.6. Key messages

1. Despite increased discussion on soil health concept there is still a strong need to raise awareness on appropriate soil management across various types of land use.
2. The diverse groups of respondents who took part in the survey are in general aware of challenges related to soil management and where to place emphasis to further improve the situation, thereby increasing soil health.
3. Creating responsible and informed policies seeking to improve soil health is essential to achieving the goals in soil management.
4. Raising awareness should concern all those who manage agricultural, urban and forest areas at every management level, reaching both public stakeholders and private landowners.
5. Special attention shall be given to urban soils since their role for creating living conditions are still underestimated – this shall be addressed by awareness raising and adopting policies.

5.5. Country report: Spain

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5.5.1. Introduction to the study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study regions

Soil health is vital for agricultural sustainability and environmental conservation. Raising awareness about soil issues and implementing solutions is essential in various regions of Spain, each with its own geographical characteristics and specific challenges. This analysis focuses on three regions: Vega-Sierra Elvira, Olivares de Jaén, and Campiña del Henares y Sierra Norte (Figure SP-1), as well as three representative municipalities in each to illustrate their characteristics and challenges in soil health.

Figure SP-1. Map of the three Spanish study regions.

Region 1: VEGA-SIERRA ELVIRA

The Vega-Sierra Elvira region in the province of Granada, Andalusia, combines fertile agricultural areas (the Vega) and mountainous zones (Sierra Elvira). The Vega of Granada is an alluvial plain with nutrient-rich soils, ideal for growing vegetables and fruits, while Sierra Elvira has calcareous soils suitable for pastures and natural vegetation. The selected municipalities in the Vega-Sierra Elvira region and their characteristics are presented in Table SP-1.

	LÁCHAR	HUÉTOR VEGA	GRANADA
Soil characteristics	fertile alluvial soils	fertile, predominantly used for intensive agriculture	nutrient-rich, especially in the Vega
Challenges	soil erosion, water management, and urbanization threatening agricultural lands	urban expansion and soil contamination	urbanization, contamination, and pressure on agricultural lands
Agricultural economy	cultivation of vegetables and fruits	diverse with vegetable crops, vineyards, and olive groves	mainly horticultural, with a growing interest in organic farming
Initiatives	sustainable agriculture programs and soil conservation to mitigate erosion and improve water management	promotion of sustainable agricultural practices and urban planning to protect agricultural lands	sustainable soil management projects and the promotion of urban agriculture

Table SP-1. Selected municipalities in the The Vega-Sierra Elvira region and their characteristics.

Region 2: OLIVARES DE JAÉN

The province of Jaén is known for its vast expanses of olive groves. The calcareous soils in this region are ideal for olive cultivation, but intensive monoculture has led to soil erosion and nutrient depletion issues. The selected municipalities in the Olivares de Jaén region and their characteristics are presented in Table SP-2.

	CAMPORREDONDO	HUELMA	JAÉN
Soil characteristics	calcareous, well-drained	similar to Camporredondo, with erosion problems	calcareous, with good drainage capacity
Challenges	erosion due to monoculture and lack of crop rotation	need for water conservation practices and crop diversification	urbanization and pressure on agricultural lands
Agricultural economy	predominantly based on olive oil production	high-quality olive oil production	olive cultivation, combined with urban areas and oleotourism
Initiatives	implementation of regenerative agriculture techniques and crop diversification	promotion of sustainable agriculture and reforestation programs to improve soil health	agricultural sustainability projects and promotion of soil conservation practices

Table SP-2. Selected municipalities in the Olivares de Jaén region and their characteristics.

Region 3: CAMPIÑA DEL HENARES Y SIERRA NORTE

This region in the Community of Madrid includes agricultural areas in the Campiña del Henares and mountainous zones in the Sierra Norte. The soils range from clayey and fertile in the plain to acidic and less fertile in the mountains. The selected municipalities in the Campiña del Henares y Sierra Norte region and their characteristics are presented in Table SP-3.

	EL CASAR	TAMAJÓN	GUADALAJARA
Soil characteristics	clayey, suitable for cereals and vineyards	acidic and less fertile, focused on forestry and pastures	variety of soils between the plain and the mountains
Challenges	erosion and the need for sustainable agricultural practices	erosion and biodiversity maintenance	urbanization and sustainable soil resource management
Agricultural economy	mainly cereal and wine production	extensive agriculture, livestock, and forestry activities	a mix of agriculture, livestock, and expanding urban areas
Initiatives	crop rotation projects and soil conservation techniques	soil conservation and reforestation to prevent erosion and protect the local ecosystem	sustainability programs and soil conservation in peri-urban areas to promote environmental resilience

Table SP-3. Selected municipalities in the Campiña del Henares y Sierra Norte region and their characteristics

National soil health and environmental discourse

Spain faces a series of environmental and soil health challenges in the agricultural, forestry, and urban sectors. In recent years, the national discourse has focused on addressing these challenges through policy measures, sustainable practices, and innovative solutions, aiming to promote sustainability, improve environmental quality, and increase resilience to climate change.

AGRICULTURAL SOILS

Soil erosion and degradation are major concerns in Spain, particularly in regions with intensive agriculture and monoculture practices, such as olive groves in Andalusia. The loss of topsoil reduces fertility, decreases agricultural productivity, and can lead to desertification. Inappropriate agricultural practices, overgrazing, and deforestation exacerbate these problems. To combat soil erosion, Spain has promoted soil conservation practices such as contour ploughing, terracing, and the use of cover crops. Additionally, agroforestry and reforestation initiatives have been implemented to stabilize the soil, improve biodiversity, and increase carbon sequestration. European Union-funded projects under programs like Horizon 2020 have focused on innovative soil management techniques and sustainable agricultural practices.

Desertification poses a severe threat, especially in the semi-arid regions of southern and eastern Spain. Climate change, overgrazing, deforestation, and unsustainable agricultural practices contribute to land degradation, turning fertile areas into deserts. Spain has developed the National Action Program to Combat Desertification (PAND), focusing on sustainable land management and the restoration of degraded lands. Promoting sustainable land management practices, such as rotational grazing, conservation tillage, and the use of drought-resistant crops, is crucial for maintaining soil health. Improved irrigation techniques, such as drip irrigation and rainwater harvesting, are also being promoted to combat water scarcity.

Water management is a critical issue for Spanish agriculture, especially due to recurrent droughts and the over-extraction of water resources. Agriculture is the largest consumer of water in Spain, and inefficient practices have depleted aquifers and surface water sources. Significant investments have been made in modernizing irrigation systems to increase water use efficiency, adopting drip irrigation systems that deliver water directly to plant roots. Technologies that help save water, such as soil moisture sensors and automated irrigation systems, are being promoted to ensure more efficient water use. The Spanish government has introduced policies to regulate water allocation, ensuring that agricultural water use is balanced with the needs of other sectors and the environment.

Climate change impacts Spain's agricultural sector by altering precipitation patterns, increasing the frequency of extreme weather events, and raising temperatures. These changes pose risks to crop yields, soil health, and water availability, making agriculture more challenging and unpredictable. Developing and adopting climate-resilient agricultural practices is crucial. This includes diversifying crops, improving soil management, and integrating agroecological principles. Ongoing research aims to develop crop varieties more tolerant to heat and drought. Climate change adaptation strategies are being integrated into agricultural policies, including early warning systems for extreme weather, financial support for affected farmers, and initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture.

The loss of biodiversity in agricultural landscapes is a significant concern. Intensive farming practices, monocultures, and habitat destruction have reduced biodiversity, essential for ecosystem health, pest control, and pollination services. To counteract this, organic and ecological farming practices that avoid synthetic pesticides and fertilizers are being promoted to enhance biodiversity. Ecological farming integrates natural processes and biodiversity conservation into agricultural systems. Under the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Spain has implemented agri-environmental schemes providing financial incentives to farmers who adopt practices that protect and enhance biodiversity. Habitat conservation programs are also being implemented to restore natural habitats within agricultural landscapes, creating wildlife corridors, protecting pollinator habitats, and maintaining ecological balance.

The use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture has led to soil and water contamination, affecting human health, aquatic ecosystems, and soil biodiversity. To mitigate these impacts, the use of organic fertilizers and biopesticides is being encouraged to reduce environmental damage and maintain soil health. Stricter regulations have been introduced to control the use of agrochemicals, including setting limits on the quantities used and promoting integrated pest management (IPM) techniques that minimize chemical use. IPM strategies combine biological, cultural, and mechanical control methods to manage pests with minimal chemical inputs, helping to reduce contamination and promote sustainable agriculture.

The need for sustainable agricultural practices encompasses many of the issues mentioned above, including soil health, water management, and biodiversity conservation. Sustainable agriculture aims to balance productivity with environmental stewardship and social equity. The CAP has undergone reforms to better support sustainable farming practices, providing direct payments to farmers who adopt sustainable methods and funding rural development projects. Financial incentives and subsidies are offered to farmers to adopt sustainable practices, including payments for organic farming, conservation tillage, and other environmentally friendly practices. Training and education programs are available to help farmers learn about sustainable agriculture techniques, with extension services providing support and resources to implement these practices effectively.

There is a growing movement towards agroecology and organic farming as ways to achieve sustainable and environmentally friendly agriculture. These approaches focus on working with natural processes and reducing reliance on external inputs. The Spanish government and the EU provide subsidies and support for organic farming, including financial aid for certification, market development, and research. Agroecological practices, which emphasize biodiversity, soil health, and ecological balance, are being promoted through research, education, and policy support. Certification programs ensure the integrity of organic products and help consumers make informed choices, supporting market development for organic and agroecological products.

FORESTRY SOILS

In the forestry sector, deforestation and forest degradation are significant problems in Spain, driven by agricultural expansion, urbanization, and wildfires. These processes lead to biodiversity loss, ecosystem disruption, and increased carbon emissions. Responses include reforestation and afforestation projects to restore degraded lands, increase forest cover, and enhance carbon sequestration. Sustainable forest management (SFM) practices balance the environmental, economic, and social functions of forests, promoting certification schemes like FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) and PEFC (Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification). Measures for wildfire prevention and control, including creating firebreaks, conducting controlled burns, and investing in firefighting resources, are critical, along with public awareness campaigns to reduce fire incidence.

Forests in Spain host a vast diversity of flora and fauna, including many endemic species. Deforestation, habitat fragmentation, and climate change threaten this biodiversity. Spain has established numerous protected areas and is part of the Natura 2000 network, a European network of key sites for rare and threatened species. Habitat restoration projects focus on reintroducing native species, managing invasive species, and improving habitat connectivity. Continuous research and monitoring are essential for understanding and managing forest biodiversity, supported by various research projects and remote sensing technology to monitor forest health and biodiversity.

Forests play a vital role in mitigating climate change by acting as carbon sinks. Deforestation and forest degradation undermine this function, contributing to higher atmospheric CO₂ levels. Programs aimed

at enhancing the carbon sequestration capacity of forests include reforestation, afforestation, and improved forest management practices to increase biomass and carbon storage.

URBAN SOILS

Rapid urbanization has led to significant land-use changes, often encroaching on agricultural and natural lands. This urban expansion reduces green spaces, affects local climates, and increases pollution. Spain has focused on sustainable urban planning, promoting the development of compact and green cities, improving energy efficiency, and managing resources more effectively. Green infrastructure strategies, such as creating urban parks, green roofs, and vertical gardens, have been implemented to increase vegetation in cities, improve air quality, and reduce the urban heat island effect.

Waste management and soil contamination are critical challenges in urban areas. The accumulation of waste and soil contamination from industrial and urban activities affect human health and the environment. To address these issues, Spain has implemented waste management policies that promote the reduction, reuse, and recycling of materials, along with soil remediation efforts. Bioremediation technologies are used to clean contaminated sites by using living organisms, such as bacteria and plants, that degrade contaminants. These practices help restore soil quality and allow the safe use of previously contaminated land.

Climate change also impacts urban areas, increasing the frequency of extreme weather events, such as floods and heatwaves. Urban adaptation strategies include improving drainage infrastructure, creating green areas for stormwater absorption, and designing climate-resilient buildings. Spanish cities are adopting climate action plans that integrate mitigation and adaptation to climate change, promoting urban sustainability and resilience.

Air pollution is a severe problem in urban areas of Spain, primarily due to vehicle and industrial emissions. Air quality policies focus on reducing emissions by promoting public transportation, the use of electric vehicles, and implementing low-emission zones. Improving urban air quality is essential for protecting public health and the environment, and initiatives to increase public awareness and participation in reducing air pollution are fundamental.

Promoting urban agriculture is another strategy to improve urban sustainability and soil quality. Urban gardens and community farming initiatives provide fresh, local produce and improve soil quality while fostering biodiversity in cities. These practices help connect urban communities with nature and promote greater environmental awareness.

In summary, Spain faces a series of environmental and soil health challenges in the agricultural, forestry, and urban sectors. Through policy measures, sustainable practices, and innovative solutions, the country is working to promote sustainability, improve environmental quality, and increase resilience to climate change in all these sectors.

5.5.2. The respondents

In the PREPSOIL T6.3 task, the respondents targeted for the survey were selected from three main groups to assess their awareness and understanding of soil health concepts. These groups include:

Advisors/Consultants within Agriculture and Forestry (Public & Private): this group consists of individuals who provide expert advice and consultation services within the agricultural and forestry sectors. They play a key role in influencing soil health practices among farmers and forest managers.

Actors with the Power of Influencing Urban Soil Management at Local/Regional Level: this group includes professionals involved in urban planning and management, who have the authority to implement soil health practices in urban settings.

Actors with the Potential of Influencing the Soil Health Discourse within Agriculture/Forestry/Urban Soils: this group encompasses individuals and organizations that can shape the conversation and policies around soil health through their positions of influence and expertise.

Each participating country was tasked with selecting three regions that represent different soil types or challenges within their country. Within each region, three municipalities were chosen to cover a variety of landscapes and soil issues: a metropolitan municipality, a rural municipality, and a mixed municipality. The survey was to be conducted within these nine municipalities per country.

The respondents were categorized into private and public actors, NGOs, and other influential networks across agriculture, forestry, and urban spheres. This categorization aimed to ensure a comprehensive understanding of soil health practices and needs across different sectors and governance levels.

The process involved:

- Selecting suitable networks of actors and specific persons to send the survey to.
- Compiling a list of email addresses in collaboration with National Hubs.
- Developing and refining the survey questionnaire to cover background questions, awareness and understanding of soil health, and the impact of soil health on professional practices.

The selection of respondents in the survey has influenced the data in several significant ways, leading to potential gaps in perspective due to the distribution across different employment categories. Firstly, there is an overrepresentation of respondents from academic or educational institutes, universities, or research institutes, which make up 24.30% of the total responses. This may skew the data towards more theoretical or research-focused perspectives rather than practical, on-the-ground experiences of soil health practices.

Conversely, respondents from national authorities or agencies are underrepresented, constituting only 14.95% of the total. This might result in a lack of insight into national policy-making perspectives and large-scale regulatory frameworks that affect soil health management.

There is a more balanced representation of regional authorities/agencies and private companies, each accounting for 14.95% and 16.36% of the responses, respectively. This balance provides a comprehensive view of both local governance and private sector practices related to soil health. However, these perspectives might not fully capture the diversity within each category.

NGOs constitute 8.88% of the total responses, ensuring that civil society and non-governmental perspectives are included, which is valuable for understanding advocacy, grassroots initiatives, and community engagement in soil health.

The self-employed and 'Other' categories are limited, representing 11.21% and 5.61% of the responses, respectively. This limited input may result in a narrower understanding of individualized or unique soil management practices and challenges that do not fit within more conventional organizational structures.

Professional associations make up 12.62% of the responses. Although this is a decent representation, there might still be a gap in capturing a full range of professional views, especially from those deeply embedded in industry-specific practices and business-oriented perspectives.

To address these potential gaps, the survey could increase efforts to target and include more respondents from national authorities to balance the policy and regulatory insights. It could also encourage more participation from the self-employed sector and other unique organizational categories to diversify practical insights into soil health. Ensuring a more even distribution across different professional associations would help capture a broader range of industry-specific practices and needs. By adjusting the selection strategy to ensure more balanced representation across all relevant sectors, the survey can provide a more comprehensive understanding of soil health awareness, practices, and needs.

5.5.3 Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the Spanish survey data. The chapter consists of three sections – one for each survey (agriculture, forest and urban). In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the surveys (see Appendix 1, 2 and 3). The prefix SP indicates that the figures belong to the Spanish chapter and the suffix A, F or U indicates which survey they belong to (Agriculture, Forest or Urban).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

Spanish respondents in the agricultural sector exhibit distinctive characteristics compared to their European counterparts.

In the realm of soil-related professional topics, Spaniards stand out for their emphasis on conservation, consultancy, and communication. Approximately 40% of Spanish respondents are engaged in soil conservation, a figure considerably higher compared to the European average. This focus on conservation and consultancy suggests a strong emphasis on sustainable practices and specialized advice in soil management.

Regarding their relationship with soil in their current employment, Spanish respondents show a high degree of involvement. Nearly 40% of them indicate that they work with soil "to a great extent," reflecting a deep commitment to soil management and study activities, significantly surpassing their European counterparts.

Employment sectors also show notable differences. Spanish professionals have a higher representation in research centres and NGOs, in contrast to the European average. This suggests a tendency towards roles oriented towards research and community action, rather than employment in the private sector or self-employment.

Figure SP-Q4A. “I am employed by”

In terms of educational level, Spanish respondents predominantly hold Master's/Bachelor's degrees in Engineering, with a slightly lower proportion of doctoral degrees compared to the European average. This educational profile indicates a strong academic background, although with a greater concentration at the master's level.

The field of study of Spanish respondents shows a strong presence in agricultural sciences and other engineering fields, with less representation in forestry sciences. This reflects a focus on disciplines directly related to agriculture and applied engineering.

Training in soil sciences is prevalent among Spanish respondents, with over 70% having studies in this field, aligning with European trends. However, there is a slight difference in specific training on soil health, with a somewhat lower percentage of Spaniards having received this training compared to their European peers.

Figure SP-Q6A. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Regarding soil knowledge, Spaniards self-assess with high levels of competence. Most rate their knowledge as good or excellent, indicating robust confidence in their skills and knowledge, which is slightly higher than the average European self-assessment.

Figure SP-Q9A. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 4,00; Total 4,87.

Finally, the work experience of Spanish respondents in soil-related topics is considerable. Most of them have worked in this field for more than 10 years, demonstrating an experienced and committed workforce, similar to the European average.

Figure SP-Q3A. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent.” Mean value: Spain 5.26; Total 5.21.

Figure SP-Q2A. “In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to...”

The respondents and the soil health concept

The EU Commission has stated that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to various processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization, and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban, and forest-natural soils.

When asked to what extent they agree with this problem description in relation to agricultural soils in their region or country, a significant majority of Spanish respondents strongly agreed with this statement (62.86%). Only a small fraction strongly disagreed (5.71%) or disagreed to any degree. The total responses showed a similar trend with 31.78% strongly agreeing and smaller percentages in other categories. The high level of agreement among Spanish respondents (average score of 6.09) compared to the total group (average score of 5.21) indicates a stronger consensus within the Spanish subgroup regarding the issue of unhealthy soils.

Figure SP-Q11A. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your country?” Mean value: Spain 6.09; Total 5.21.

Respondents were also asked about their views on two main perspectives of soil: soil fertility (focused on crop production) and soil health (focused on a broad range of ecosystem services). Among the Spanish respondents, a significant portion (37.14%) favoured the soil health perspective, which emphasizes the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity, and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems. In the total responses, this perspective was also more favoured (26.17%) than the crop production focus (6.07%). This trend suggests a broader recognition of the multifaceted role of soils beyond mere crop production, highlighting the importance of ecosystem services such as biodiversity and environmental sustainability.

When asked if the agricultural sector already uses the soil health concept, the Spanish respondents' views were more divided. Twenty percent strongly disagreed, and another 17% chose a neutral position (rating of 4). The average agreement among Spanish respondents was lower (3.43) compared to the total responses (4.25). This indicates a scepticism or a perception that the concept of soil health has not yet been widely adopted or integrated within the agricultural sector in Spain. The lower average agreement might reflect a gap between current practices and the desired state of soil management.

Figure SP-Q13aA. “Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture.” Mean value: Spain 6.57; Total: 6.07.

Figure SP-Q13bA. “The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Spain 3.43; Total 4.25.

Regarding their knowledge of the soil health concept, Spanish respondents rated themselves fairly high, with an average score of 4.51. A notable 34.29% rated their knowledge at 5 on the scale, indicating a moderate to high level of self-assessed knowledge. The total responses had a slightly higher average (4.76), suggesting that while Spanish respondents are knowledgeable, there might still be room for increasing awareness and understanding about soil health concepts more broadly. This self-assessment points to a relatively well-informed group but also highlights the need for continuous education and information dissemination.

Figure SP-Q14aA. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Spain 4.51; Total 4.76.

Spanish respondents also rated their knowledge about how agricultural management affects soil health fairly high, with an average of 4.97. This suggests a relatively good understanding among Spanish respondents about the impact of agricultural practices on soil health. In comparison, the total responses had a slightly higher average (5.03). This indicates that while Spanish respondents are knowledgeable, there is a slightly higher level of understanding among the broader group surveyed. It underscores the importance of continuing to educate and inform agricultural stakeholders about the critical link between management practices and soil health outcomes.

Figure SP-Q14bA. “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?” Mean value: Spain 4.97; Total 5.03.

When asked to what extent adopting the soil health concept in agriculture would imply a significant shift in how soil is managed, a large majority of Spanish respondents (71.43%) believed it would imply a very large extent of change. This is significantly higher than the total responses, where 25.70% believed it would imply a very large extent of change. The average score among Spanish respondents was 6.46 compared to 5.12 for the total group, indicating a strong belief within the Spanish subgroup that adopting the soil health concept would necessitate a fundamental shift in soil management practices.

Figure SP-Q15aA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 4.28; Total 5.12.

Finally, respondents were asked to what extent adopting the soil health concept in agriculture would change how their workplace deals with soil issues. More than half of the Spanish respondents (51.43%) believed it would change the approach to a very large extent, compared to 14.02% of the total responses. The average score for this question was 5.94 among Spanish respondents, higher than the 4.05 average for the total group. This significant difference suggests that Spanish respondents see a substantial potential for improvement and change in their workplace practices regarding soil issues with the adoption of the soil health concept.

Figure SP-Q15bA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Spain 5.94; Total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the region & soil challenges that the respondents work with

In analysing the survey responses regarding challenges related to agricultural soils, it is observed that Spanish respondents consider these problems more urgently compared to their European counterparts. This trend is particularly evident in the importance attributed to increasing soil organic matter, improving water retention, reducing erosion, and combating desertification. In each of these aspects, a higher proportion of Spanish respondents give the highest ratings, indicating a perception of greater severity and an immediate need for action.

Spanish respondents emphasize the need to increase soil organic matter. Approximately 40% of them consider this challenge to be extremely important, compared to a smaller percentage of European respondents who share this view. Soil organic matter is fundamental to overall soil health as it improves soil structure, increases water retention capacity, and provides essential nutrients for plants.

Water retention, infiltration, and drainage are also areas of great concern for Spanish respondents, with many rating them as critical challenges. This reflects Spain's climatic reality, where water management is vital due to frequent droughts and semi-arid conditions. Efforts to improve these areas are not only essential for agricultural productivity but also for the long-term sustainability of water resources.

In terms of nutrient cycling, Spanish respondents show a heightened awareness of its importance. A notable percentage of them give high ratings to this challenge, highlighting the need for balanced nutrient management to prevent soil degradation and maintain fertility. This concern is shared by European respondents, though with a slightly more balanced distribution of ratings.

Soil erosion is another significant challenge identified by Spanish respondents. Erosion not only reduces the arable layer of soil but also contributes to nutrient loss and degradation of soil structure. The high priority given to this problem underscores the need to implement soil conservation practices and sustainable agricultural techniques to mitigate its effects.

Desertification is a critical concern for Spanish respondents, reflected in the high scores assigned to this challenge. Spain, being one of the countries most affected by desertification in Europe, faces severe risks if appropriate measures are not taken to combat this phenomenon. Sustainable soil management strategies and the implementation of regenerative agricultural techniques are essential to reverse this trend.

Regarding peatland management, this challenge is less relevant for Spanish respondents compared to their European counterparts. This may be due to the smaller extent of peatlands in Spain compared to other European countries, where peatlands play a more significant role in local ecology and economy.

Promoting awareness of the importance of soil is highly valued by Spanish respondents, who recognize the need to increase knowledge and education about soil health among farmers, policymakers, and the general public. This awareness is crucial to fostering the adoption of more sustainable agricultural practices and the implementation of effective soil conservation policies.

Figure SP-Q16A: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

In terms of how workplaces address these challenges, Spanish respondents indicated a high level of activity in areas such as increasing soil organic matter and improving water retention. This reflects a significant commitment to implementing practices that directly address the identified problems. Workplaces in Spain appear to be more involved in the active management of these challenges compared to the European average, suggesting greater urgency and action in response to the specific soil conditions in Spain.

Figure SP-Q18A: “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in forest soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

The main obstacles and limitations to improving soil health in the agricultural sector, as well as suggested measures to address these issues, can be outlined as follows:

A significant number of respondents highlighted the lack of education and knowledge about proper soil management as a primary obstacle. This includes the insufficient training in sustainable agricultural practices, a general lack of awareness about the importance of soil health, and inadequate knowledge regarding water management and maintaining vegetative cover. Additionally, there is a noted disconnection between agricultural research and field practice, coupled with a lack of continuous knowledge transfer over time.

Economic challenges and ineffective agricultural policies were also frequently mentioned as major limitations. This encompasses the vulnerability of small and medium-sized farmers to investment funds and ineffective agricultural policies, including inadequate policies for water decontamination, poorly targeted subsidies and aids, and the pressure from a global economy that prioritizes short-term production over long-term sustainability.

Current unsustainable agricultural practices and the impacts of climate change were identified as critical limitations. This includes the excessive use of herbicides and pesticides, monocultures, overexploitation of water resources, and the adverse effects of climate change. These practices not only degrade soil health but also contribute to problems like erosion and contamination.

To address these obstacles, respondents suggested increasing education and technical advice for farmers. Proposals include improving farmer training in sustainable practices, offering mandatory training courses, providing incentives to learn sustainable soil management techniques, and creating accessible agricultural advisory systems. Additionally, forming knowledge transfer teams to bridge the gap between research and agricultural practice was recommended.

Reforming agricultural policies and subsidies was another key measure suggested. This includes implementing more realistic and context-specific agricultural policies, eliminating subsidies that favour unsustainable practices, and promoting aid based on sustainable results. Furthermore, providing incentives for small and medium-sized farmers, penalizing polluting practices, and adjusting subsidies to better support sustainable farming were emphasized.

Promoting sustainable agricultural practices and effective water management were also important measures proposed. This involves encouraging the use of sustainable farming techniques such as crop rotation, proper management of vegetative cover, and efficient water management. Additionally, learning from traditional practices that were more environmentally friendly and combining those with current innovations was recommended.

Competence development

Spanish respondents show clear and specific interests regarding soil-related topics they would like to learn more about, as well as the ways they prefer to receive this training.

Firstly, the topics of greatest interest to Spanish respondents include "the concept of soil health," "biodiversity potential," and "adaptation strategies." Around 70% of Spanish respondents want to learn more about the concept of soil health, a significantly higher figure than that of European respondents in general. This indicates a strong need for understanding and knowledge in this fundamental area. Additionally, soil biodiversity and adaptation strategies are also areas of great interest, highlighting a focus on sustainability and resilience in soil management.

Regarding knowledge about the existence of relevant training resources in soil health, it is observed that a considerable portion of Spanish respondents (approximately 30%) indicate they are unaware of any, a higher proportion compared to the overall European total. This suggests an urgent need to improve the dissemination and access to educational resources on soil health in Spain. On the other

hand, those who are informed tend to value these training resources, although there is still significant variability in the responses, reflecting a diversity of experiences and accessibility to these resources.

Regarding the preferences of respondents for receiving training on agricultural soil health, the most valued methods by Spaniards are "field visits," followed by "courses" and "seminars." More than 60% of Spanish respondents prefer field visits, emphasizing the importance of practical and experiential learning. Courses and seminars are also highly valued, reflecting a preference for structured and formal methods of acquiring knowledge. Comparatively, European respondents also value these methods, although with a slightly different distribution, showing a more balanced interest across various formats.

Additionally, Spanish respondents show significant interest in "reports" and "journals," indicating a preference for reading academic and technical material to complement their learning. However, there is less interest in "podcasts" and "books," suggesting that audio formats and prolonged reading are less attractive to this group.

The forest survey

Description of the respondents

Spanish respondents in the forestry sector exhibit a series of characteristics that differentiate them from their European counterparts in several key aspects. In terms of professional topics related to soil, Spanish respondents predominantly focus on "consultancy" and "conservation." Approximately 50% of Spaniards indicate that their work is related to soil consultancy, compared to a smaller percentage in the total European sample. Conservation is also a significant area of interest, with around 30% of Spanish respondents involved in this field. This suggests a strong focus on advisory services and soil protection among Spanish professionals compared to their European peers, who show a more balanced distribution across various thematic areas.

Figure SP-Q2F. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to"

Regarding the extent to which their current employment is related to soil, a significant proportion of Spanish respondents indicate a high level of involvement. Nearly 30% of Spanish respondents' state that their work is "to a great extent" related to soil, a figure higher than the European average. This reflects a deeper commitment to soil issues in their professional roles.

Figure SP-Q3F. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Spain 3.84; Total 4.08.

A higher proportion of Spanish respondents work in "private companies" and "government entities/agencies". Approximately 40% of Spaniards are employed in the private sector, compared to a smaller percentage in the total European sample. This pattern indicates greater integration of Spanish professionals in the private sector and in governmental roles within the forestry field.

Figure SP-Q4F. "I am employed by".

The educational level of Spanish respondents also stands out. A significant majority hold a "Master's/Bachelor's degree in Engineering," with over 70% of Spanish respondents reaching this educational level, compared to a smaller proportion in the total European sample. This suggests a strong academic background among forestry professionals in Spain.

In terms of specific training in soil sciences, Spanish respondents show a high prevalence of training in "forestry sciences/forestry engineering," with around 80% indicating this area as their main field of study. This contrasts with a greater diversity of training areas observed in the total European sample, where "agricultural sciences" and "environmental sciences" have a more balanced presence.

Figure SP-Q6F. "What is the major subject in your education?"

The majority of Spanish respondents (over 70%) have training related to soil, which is comparable to the European average. However, only a small proportion have received specific training on soil health, suggesting an opportunity to improve training in this crucial aspect.

Regarding their self-perception of soil knowledge, Spanish respondents evaluate themselves more critically. Around 30% rate their knowledge as "deficient" relative to their needs, a significantly higher figure than observed in the total European sample. This indicates a greater awareness of knowledge gaps and a potential need for more training and educational resources.

Figure SP-Q9F. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 3.00; Total 4.21.

Finally, in terms of work experience, a considerable proportion of Spanish respondents have more than 10 years of experience in soil-related topics. However, there is also a notable percentage (around 30%) who indicate they have never worked on soil-related topics, suggesting a possible lack of continuity or stability in this field.

The respondents and the soil health concept

Spanish respondents show a high alignment with the European Commission's view on unhealthy soils, although with certain variations compared to the European average.

First, regarding the statement on agreement with the description of the problems of forest soils in their region or country, a significant percentage of Spanish respondents (approximately 20%) "strongly agree", slightly exceeding the European average. However, responses are more evenly distributed in the intermediate categories (values 3, 4 and 5), reflecting a diverse but generally affirmative perception of the seriousness of soil problems.

Figure SP-Q11F. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to forest soils in your country?” Mean value: Spain 4.84; Total 4.14.

In terms of the view of soil most aligned with their perspectives, Spanish respondents lean notably towards a view that considers the "wide variety of ecosystem services (soil health)", with nearly 50% selecting this option, in contrast to 30% of the European total. This indicates a more holistic and ecosystemic understanding of soil among Spanish professionals.

The concept of soil health is considered highly relevant in forestry for Spanish respondents, with more than 40% "strongly agreeing" with this statement, significantly exceeding the European average. This

perspective highlights the importance that Spanish forestry professionals attach to soil health as a crucial component in forest management.

Figure SP-Q13aF. "Soil health is a relevant concept in forestry." Mean value: Spain 5.63; Total: 5.22.

On the use of the soil health concept in forestry, Spanish respondents show lower agreement compared to the European average. Most Spaniards are in the intermediate values (3 and 4), suggesting that although the concept is recognized, its implementation is not yet fully integrated into forestry practices in Spain.

Figure SP-Q13bF. "The forest sector already uses soil health as a concept." Mean value: Spain 3.61; Total 3.35.

Regarding general knowledge about the concept of soil health, Spanish respondents have a varied self-perception. Approximately 20% rate their knowledge at an intermediate level (value 4), similar to the European average. However, there is a higher proportion of Spaniards who rate themselves at the lowest levels (values 1 and 2), indicating a perceived need for more training and knowledge in this area.

Figure SP-Q14aF. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Spain 3.26; Total 3.33.

With respect to knowledge of how forest management affects soil health, Spanish respondents show a similar distribution to the European total, with a majority falling in the intermediate values (4 and 5). This suggests a moderate but recognized awareness of the relationship between management practices and soil health.

Figure SP-Q14bF. “How knowledgeable are you about how forest management affects soil health?” Mean value: Spain 3.71; Total 4.16.

Finally, the adoption of the concept of soil health in forestry as a change of mentality is significantly perceived by Spanish respondents. About 25% consider that it implies a change "to a great extent", reflecting a recognition of the need for a transformation in the perception and management of soil within the forestry sector. However, regarding the change in the way the sector would address soil problems, the responses are more distributed, indicating a variability in expectations about the practical implementation of these concepts.

Figure SP-Q15aF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 5.11; Total 4.41.

Figure SP-Q15bF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Spain 4.68; Total 3.68.

Soil challenges in the region & soil challenges that the respondents work with

The analysis of survey responses on soil challenges in the agricultural sector reveals significant differences between Spanish respondents and the European average.

Spanish respondents identify several key issues in forest soils with varying degrees of severity compared to their European counterparts. The primary challenges highlighted by Spanish respondents include increasing soil organic matter, improving water retention and infiltration, and decreasing soil erosion. Specifically, the need to increase soil organic matter and improve water retention are rated as significant challenges, scoring highly (6 to a very large extent) compared to the total European responses.

Spanish respondents also place a strong emphasis on soil biodiversity and soil fertility improvement. These aspects are considered crucial due to their role in sustaining forest health and productivity. Compared to the broader European responses, Spanish participants indicate a higher concern for soil biodiversity, suggesting a more pronounced awareness or impact of biodiversity loss within Spain's forests.

When it comes to soil compaction, salinization, and desertification, Spanish respondents again report these as critical issues, with a notable percentage rating them as significant problems. These issues are less emphasized in the total European responses, indicating potential regional differences in the severity or awareness of these challenges.

Figure SP-Q16F: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in forest soils in your region/country?”

The extent to which workplaces deal with these challenges reflects a proactive approach in Spain towards managing and mitigating soil health issues. Spanish respondents report a higher engagement in increasing soil organic matter and improving water retention and infiltration compared to the European average. This proactive stance is likely influenced by the specific environmental conditions and forestry practices in Spain, which necessitate focused efforts on these areas.

Additionally, Spanish workplaces are significantly involved in promoting awareness of the importance of soil health. This contrasts with the broader European trend, where promoting awareness is less emphasized. This suggests that in Spain, there is a concerted effort to educate and inform stakeholders about the critical role of soil health in forestry.

Efforts to decrease soil erosion, manage peatlands, and reduce desertification are also notable in Spanish workplaces. These initiatives indicate a comprehensive approach to addressing soil health challenges, integrating various strategies to improve overall soil conditions.

Figure SP-Q18F: “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in forest soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Regarding the obstacles and limitations to improving soil health in the forestry sector, respondents have identified several key issues. The lack of knowledge and awareness about the importance of soil is frequently mentioned. Many respondents indicate that soil is largely unknown except when specific activities like reforestation are conducted. Soil erosion and contamination by agrochemicals are critical problems negatively affecting soil health.

Traditional forest management methods, which often do not consider soil health, are cited as significant barriers. The lack of resources, political support, and trained professionals are significant limitations mentioned by respondents. The absence of private investment and the lack of long-term profitability are also factors hindering the implementation of sustainable practices. The private ownership of highly eroded soils and unsustainable soil exploitation are other identified obstacles. Forest fires, desertification, and the effects of climate change are significant challenges complicating the improvement of soil health.

To address these obstacles, it is suggested to increase awareness and education about the importance of soil. This includes training and education for both sector professionals and the general public. Implementing policies that promote sustainable forest management (SFM) and regulating legislation to support sustainable strategies from an environmental, social, and economic perspective is crucial. Improving the perception of sustainable forest management in society and supporting companies and professionals who invest in sustainable practices is another important measure.

Continuous training, awareness-raising, and investment in research and development are essential. Specifically, the need for specific studies and the application of concrete actions to improve soil health is mentioned. Increasing the budget and resources for the forestry sector, including incentives related to ecosystem services, is fundamental to support soil health. Reducing clear-cutting, adopting a more nature-based forestry approach, and improving the management of forest residues and nutrients are recommended measures to maintain soil health.

Investing in the development of more agile and lighter machinery suitable for different soil types is an important measure to minimize negative impacts on soil. Establishing a clear methodology to quantify and value the benefits of healthy soil can help attract private investment for soil conservation and improvement.

In conclusion, respondents have identified several important obstacles to improving soil health in the forestry sector, including lack of knowledge, resources, and unsustainable management methods. The suggested measures to address these challenges include increasing awareness and education, implementing sustainable policies, improving the perception and support for sustainable forest management, increasing resources and investment, and adapting machinery to minimize soil impact. These measures, if properly implemented, could significantly improve soil health in the forestry sector, promoting more sustainable and effective practices.

Competence development

In terms of competency development, respondents have expressed a strong interest in learning more about various topics related to forest soil. A prominent topic is the general concept of soil health, with 63.16% of Spanish respondents showing interest. Additionally, how to assess soil health and forest soil management strategies to improve its health are priority topics, with 55.26% and 71.05% interest, respectively. Other topics of interest include the potential for carbon sequestration (50%) and soil biodiversity (47.37%).

Despite the interest in these topics, there is a significant lack of knowledge about relevant training resources on soil health. Nearly 40% of Spanish respondents indicate they are unaware of any, and 15.79% state they do not know of the existence of such resources. Only a small percentage mention knowing several training resources, suggesting an urgent need to improve the dissemination of information about training opportunities.

Regarding preferred training methods, digital courses and field visits stand out as the most popular, with 68.42% and 63.16% preference among Spanish respondents, respectively. Live online seminars are also popular, with 57.89% interest. This indicates a preference for learning methods that combine flexibility and practical experiences.

In conclusion, respondents show a great interest in increasing their knowledge about soil health, particularly in topics related to its assessment and management. However, there is a clear gap in the availability and awareness of existing training resources. Implementing more accessible educational programs and promoting available training opportunities are essential to meet these educational needs and improve soil health in the forestry sector.

The urban survey

Description of the respondents

The analysis of respondents' answers, comparing Spanish responses with those from the rest of Europe, reveals significant differences and similarities in various aspects.

Regarding professions related to soil, Spanish respondents mainly focus on planning and consultancy, significantly surpassing the European average in these fields. In contrast, European professionals exhibit greater diversity in their roles, spanning areas such as education and research, indicating a broader approach to soil management.

Figure SP-Q2U. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to..."

Concerning the extent to which their current jobs are linked to soil, Spanish respondents report a higher degree of involvement, especially in the higher categories of the scale (5 and 6), suggesting a deeper commitment compared to their European counterparts. This trend is also reflected in the perception of the relevance of the concept of soil health, where Spaniards show a greater agreement with the importance of this concept.

Figure SP-Q3U. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Spain 5.39; Total 5.51.

When considering the workforce sector, a considerable proportion of Spanish respondents work for government entities or agencies, contrasting with the greater diversity observed at the European level, where there is a significant representation of private companies and NGOs. This difference may reflect

different approaches in soil management and environmental policies between Spain and other European countries.

Figure SP-Q4U. "I am employed by"

In terms of educational level, the majority of Spanish respondents hold a master's or bachelor's degree in engineering, exceeding the European average percentage. However, both groups exhibit high academic training, emphasizing the importance of advanced education in soil management.

The main area of education also shows differences, with a predominance of forestry sciences and forest engineering among Spanish respondents, while in Europe, there is a greater diversity of fields, including environmental sciences and other engineering disciplines. This may indicate a greater specialization in forestry in Spain.

Figure SP-Q6U. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Regarding specific training in soil sciences, a similar proportion of respondents in both groups report having received education in this field, although Europeans show a slight advantage. However, a larger portion of Spanish respondents consider their knowledge regarding soil to be deficient, which could suggest a need for further training and professional development in Spain.

Figure SP-Q9U. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 3.00; Total 4.62.

The respondents and the soil health concept

When analysing the responses of Spanish participants compared to the overall European total, we observe certain trends and significant differences in perception and knowledge about soil health.

The majority of Spanish respondents (approximately 25%) "strongly agree" with the description of the issue of urban soils in their region, suggesting a greater awareness or concern about this issue in Spain compared to the overall European total, where agreement is more dispersed across different levels.

Figure SP-Q11U. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to urban soils in your country?” Mean value: Spain 6.28; Total 5.60.

A high percentage of Spanish respondents (around 50%) consider their view of soil to be "focused on a wide range of ecosystem services." This perspective is also prevalent in the overall European total, but with a lower proportion (around 30%).

More than half of Spanish respondents (around 70%) "strongly agree" that soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils, demonstrating a greater acceptance of the concept in Spain compared to the rest of Europe, where this acceptance is less pronounced.

Figure SP-Q13aU. “Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils.” Mean value: Spain 6.61; Total: 5.72.

Regarding whether the urban sector already uses the concept of soil health, there is a diversity of opinions. However, it is notable that a significant percentage of Spanish respondents disagree, indicating that there may still be work to be done in integrating this concept into urban practices in Spain.

Figure SP-Q13bU. “The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Spain 1.94; Total 2.50.

The Spanish respondents show greater variability in their knowledge about the concept of soil health, with a considerable proportion indicating having either "none" or "a lot" of knowledge, which contrasts with the overall European total, where knowledge tends to concentrate at intermediate levels.

Figure SP-Q14aU. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Spain 3.06; Total 3.71.

Similar to the general knowledge, Spanish respondents have a wide distribution in their levels of knowledge about how soil management affects its health. Approximately 20% have "none" knowledge, while a similar percentage has moderate knowledge (levels 4 and 5).

Figure SP-Q14bU. “How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?” Mean value: Spain 3.28; Total 4.00.

The adoption of the soil health concept in urban soils implies a significant mindset shift for most Spanish respondents, with 20% indicating that this change would be "to a large extent." In comparison, the European total shows a more equitable distribution among different degrees of mindset change.

Figure SP-Q15aU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils imply a mindset concerning soil?” Mean value: Spain 6.50; Total 5.24.

Finally, the adoption of the soil health concept would "greatly" change the way the labour sector addresses soil issues for a significant proportion of Spanish respondents (20%), suggesting a potential positive impact on work practices with the adoption of this concept.

Figure SP-Q15bU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Spain 6.50; Total 4.59.

Soil challenges in the region & soil challenges that the respondents work with

The analysis of the responses from Spanish respondents compared to the total European responses shows notable differences in the perception and management of challenges related to urban soils. Spanish respondents consider increasing soil organic matter to be a more urgent problem, with a higher average score than the overall European average. Improving soil fertility is also seen as a critical challenge in Spain, as is reducing soil erosion. Spaniards place greater importance on preventing soil sealing and on the adaptation, regulation, and mitigation of climate change compared to their European counterparts. The reuse and recycling of soils are also considered more relevant in Spain.

Figure SP-Q16U. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region/country?”

Regarding the management of these challenges in their workplaces, Spanish respondents show greater involvement in various areas. Practices related to increasing soil organic matter and improving soil fertility are more active in Spain than in the rest of Europe. Efforts to reduce soil erosion and prevent soil sealing are more notable in Spain, reflecting more decisive action in these aspects. Adaptation, regulation, and mitigation of climate change are also addressed with greater intensity in Spain compared to the European average. Additionally, the promotion of awareness about the importance of soil is significantly higher among Spanish respondents, demonstrating a strong focus on raising awareness and education in this area.

Figure SP-Q18U. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in urban soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Respondents identify several key obstacles hindering the improvement of urban soil health. Among the most frequently mentioned are the lack of political interest and social awareness, as well as the lack of knowledge among technicians and professionals working with soil. This trio of factors points to a widespread need to increase awareness and training regarding the importance of soil health.

Other significant obstacles include the absence of sustainable drainage systems in urbanization projects, the prevalence of systems that waterproof and compact the soil, and poor or non-existent urban planning. Additionally, high population density and the prioritization of economic criteria over environmental ones exacerbate the situation, while inadequate management of waste and technological residues is also considered a significant problem.

Economic interests and conflicts among the various stakeholders involved in land use further complicate efforts to improve soil health. The current legislation, which does not always promote soil health and sometimes relies too heavily on developers, is also perceived as an obstacle.

To address these obstacles, respondents suggest a series of measures including social awareness campaigns and the training of technicians, as well as requiring politicians to comply with environmental policies. The implementation of urban sustainable drainage systems technologies and the promotion of green areas in urban zones are also key proposals. Moreover, fostering proper soil management in agricultural and forest areas near urban zones is seen as crucial for protecting soil health.

Other suggested measures include disseminating information about the importance of soil, promoting soil-protective land uses through subsidies or benefits for landowners, and establishing green infrastructure to avoid unnecessary soil sealing. Awareness programs and stricter legislative measures to ensure soil protection are also proposed.

In summary, respondents highlight the need for greater awareness, training, and legislative changes to address the challenges in urban soil health. These measures, combined with sustainable technologies and better urban planning, could overcome the current obstacles and significantly improve soil health in urban areas.

Competence development

Respondents show a great interest in learning more about various topics related to soil health. Among the most requested topics are the general concept of soil health, soil management strategies to improve its health, and how to assess soil health for specific functions. These interests reflect a need to better understand the basic and applied principles of soil health, as well as management practices that can enhance its condition.

Additionally, there is significant interest in topics such as soil biodiversity, carbon sequestration potential, and climate adaptation, regulation, and mitigation. This suggests that respondents are not only interested in soil health from a local or regional perspective but also in its role in global issues such as climate change.

Regarding the availability of relevant training resources on soil health, a considerable proportion of respondents are unaware of the existence of these resources. This lack of awareness is a significant obstacle to skill development, as it prevents interested parties from accessing the necessary training to improve their knowledge and practices related to soil health.

To address these competency challenges, respondents express a preference for various training modalities. Digital and in-person courses are the most popular options, followed by live online seminars and field visits. Additionally, many respondents also value learning through interaction with peers or municipalities and the implementation of best practices.

The diversity in training preferences indicates the need to offer a variety of educational formats to meet the different needs and learning styles of interested parties. This also underscores the importance of making existing training resources accessible and visible so that more people can benefit from them.

In summary, respondents wish to deepen their knowledge on a wide range of topics related to soil health, highlighting the need for ongoing and accessible education. To overcome the obstacle of unawareness of available training resources, it is crucial to improve the dissemination and accessibility of these resources. Moreover, offering multiple training formats can help meet the diverse needs and preferences of those interested in this field.

5.5.4 Discussion

Agricultural survey

Spanish respondents in the agricultural sector stand out for their emphasis on soil conservation, consultancy, and communication, with a high degree of involvement in their current employment. Approximately 40% of Spaniards work with soil "to a great extent," surpassing the European average. They have a higher representation in research centres and NGOs, suggesting a tendency towards roles in research and community action.

Regarding educational level, they predominantly hold Master's/Bachelor's degrees in Engineering, with a strong presence in agricultural sciences and other engineering fields, and a lesser representation in forestry sciences. Over 70% of respondents have training in soil sciences, although there is a slight difference in specific training on soil health compared to their European peers. Spaniards self-assess with high levels of competence in soil knowledge.

The European Commission states that most soils in the EU are in poor condition. A significant majority of Spanish respondents (62.86%) completely agree with this description, reflecting a stronger

consensus on the issue of poor soil conditions compared to the total group. Additionally, a significant portion (37.14%) of Spanish respondents favour the perspective of soil health over soil fertility.

Spanish respondents are divided on whether the agricultural sector already uses the concept of soil health, showing less agreement compared to the total responses. They rate themselves with high knowledge of the soil health concept, although there is room to increase awareness and understanding. Most of them believe that adopting the soil health concept would imply a significant change in soil management.

In terms of addressing specific soil challenges in the workplace, Spanish and European respondents share similar concerns, although Spaniards place greater priority on increasing soil organic matter, biodiversity, and water retention. Divergences are evident in the focus on salinization and desertification, where Europeans seem to place more importance.

The main obstacles to improving soil health include a lack of education and knowledge, economic challenges, ineffective agricultural policies, unsustainable farming practices, and the impacts of climate change. To address these, respondents suggest increasing education and technical advice, reforming agricultural policies and subsidies, and promoting sustainable practices and efficient water management.

Spanish respondents show interest in learning more about the concept of soil health, biodiversity, and adaptation strategies. They prefer practical training methods such as field visits and courses. They also value reports and journals but show less interest in podcasts and books.

Forestry survey

The survey results reveal several notable differences and similarities between Spanish respondents and their European counterparts in the forestry sector. Spanish respondents in the forestry sector differ from their European counterparts in several key aspects. They predominantly focus on consultancy and conservation, suggesting a strong emphasis on advisory services and soil protection. This finding reflects a possibly higher awareness and priority toward sustainable soil management in Spain.

One of the surprising aspects is the high proportion of Spanish respondents working in private companies and government entities/agencies compared to the European average. Additionally, the educational level of Spanish respondents is notably high, with a significant majority holding a Master's/Bachelor's degree in Engineering. However, there is a considerable proportion that rates their own knowledge as deficient relative to their needs, indicating a critical awareness of their own knowledge gaps.

Similarities between Spanish and European respondents include a high prevalence of soil-related training and moderate awareness of the relationship between management practices and soil health. Both groups also highlight the relevance of the concept of soil health in their respective sectors.

However, the differences are significant in several aspects. Spanish respondents show a greater inclination to consider soil challenges as more significant and urgent. They tend to value more the necessary changes in mindset and soil management practices and perceive a more urgent need to reform work practices to improve soil health.

Regarding specific soil challenges in their workplaces, Spanish respondents deal more significantly with increasing soil organic matter and promoting awareness of the importance of soil. On the other hand,

they show a lower degree of involvement in challenges such as improving the nutrient cycle and peatland management compared to the European average.

Urban survey

The analysis of the survey results on soil perception and management among Spanish and European respondents in the urban sector reveals notable differences and similarities. Spanish respondents primarily focus on planning and consultancy, significantly exceeding the European average in these fields, indicating a more specialized approach to soil management in Spain. In terms of job involvement, Spanish respondents show a higher degree of commitment, especially in the higher categories, suggesting a deeper focus compared to their European counterparts.

A considerable proportion of Spanish respondents work for government entities, in contrast to the greater diversity observed at the European level, where there is significant representation from private companies and NGOs. Regarding educational level, most Spanish respondents hold a Master's or Bachelor's degree in engineering, surpassing the European average, which underscores the importance of advanced education in soil management.

Regarding specific training in soil sciences, both Spanish and European respondents have a similar proportion of training, although Europeans show a slight advantage. However, a larger portion of Spanish respondents consider their soil-related knowledge to be inadequate, suggesting a need for more training and professional development in Spain.

In terms of perception and knowledge about soil health, Spanish respondents show a high alignment with the European Commission's vision on unhealthy soils. The majority are "totally in agreement" with the description of the urban soil problem in their region, indicating greater awareness in Spain. Spanish respondents also place more value on a vision of soil centered on a wide variety of ecosystem services and consider soil health a relevant concept for urban soils.

However, there is a perception that the urban sector in Spain has not yet fully embraced the concept of soil health, indicating an area for improvement. Spanish respondents show greater variability in their knowledge about soil health, indicating a need for additional training.

The barriers identified to improving soil health include a lack of political interest, social awareness, and technical knowledge, as well as the absence of sustainable drainage systems and poor urban planning. Suggested measures include awareness campaigns, technical training, compliance with environmental policies, implementation of sustainable drainage technologies, and promotion of green areas.

In summary, Spanish respondents in the urban sector show greater awareness and urgency regarding sustainable soil management, prioritizing planning and consultancy. Although they share many concerns with their European counterparts, the Spanish prioritize certain aspects of soil management with greater emphasis, reflecting both the specific soil conditions in Spain and a proactive mindset towards improving soil health in the urban sector.

Cross-sector discussion

The analysis of perceptions, challenges, and soil management practices in Spain and Europe, covering the agricultural, forestry, and urban sectors, reveals both commonalities and significant differences. Spanish respondents in these sectors show a high awareness of the importance of soil health, often exceeding the European average. This awareness is reflected in the widespread acceptance of the issues described by the European Commission regarding unhealthy soils.

High educational levels are consistent among Spanish respondents, with a majority holding Master's, Bachelor's, or Engineering degrees. However, there is a cross-sectoral need for more specific training in soil health. The lack of education and knowledge about sustainable soil management practices is a recurring obstacle mentioned across all sectors, highlighting the need for more technical training and continuous education. Unsustainable agricultural and forestry practices, as well as the impacts of climate change, are widely recognized challenges. The implementation of sustainable practices and improved water management are commonly suggested measures to mitigate these challenges. There is significant interest in sustainable practices such as agroecology, soil conservation, and biodiversity management, reflecting a long-term focus on sustainability across all sectors.

In terms of differences, Spanish respondents in the agricultural and urban sectors show a higher degree of involvement in soil-related activities compared to the forestry sector. This commitment is reflected in a higher proportion of respondents who work intensively with soil in their professional roles. In the agricultural sector, there is a strong emphasis on soil conservation and consultancy, while in the forestry sector, consultancy and conservation are also prominent, with an additional focus on sustainable forest management. In the urban sector, planning and consultancy are dominant areas, reflecting a more specialized focus on urban soil management.

In all sectors, Spanish respondents have a high alignment with the European Commission's vision regarding unhealthy soils. However, in the urban sector, it is perceived that the concept of soil health is not as integrated as in the agricultural and forestry sectors, indicating potential areas for improvement in the implementation of this concept in urban practices. In the agricultural sector, respondents prioritize improving soil organic matter, biodiversity, and water retention. In the forestry sector, promoting awareness about the importance of soil is a highlighted challenge. In the urban sector, a lack of political interest and poor urban planning are significant obstacles.

To address these challenges, it is suggested to improve technical and continuous training in sustainable soil management practices, create accessible educational programs, and promote existing training resources. Reforming agricultural and forestry policies to support sustainable practices and offering incentives to farmers and soil professionals is fundamental. In the urban sphere, it is crucial to implement policies that promote the use of sustainable drainage technologies and the creation of green areas. Developing awareness campaigns and promoting research in soil health are key measures, including the active participation of civil society, support for research projects, and the implementation of innovative technologies for soil management.

Comparing the survey results among different types of land use highlights a greater awareness and urgency among Spanish respondents regarding sustainable soil management. Despite sharing common challenges, each sector shows specific differences in the perception and management of these issues. The suggested measures emphasize the need for continuous education, effective policies, and sustainable practices to ensure healthier and more efficient soil management in Spain.

5.5.5. Implication for policy

Agriculture

It is essential to enhance education and training in sustainable soil management practices. Farmers need access to educational and technical programs that teach them about soil conservation, agroecology, and biodiversity management. Establish regular field-based workshops and virtual training modules through a Web Portal to facilitate practical learning and knowledge sharing among farmers. Awareness campaigns should be developed to highlight the importance of soil health and

promote sustainable agricultural practices. Additionally, agricultural policies need to be reformed to support sustainability, offering economic incentives and subsidies to those who implement soil conservation practices and improvements in water management. Efficient irrigation techniques and crop rotation should also be encouraged to prevent erosion and improve soil fertility. Incorporate pilot projects in Living Labs to test these practices, ensuring that successful methods can be scaled up with appropriate policy support.

Forest

In the forestry sector, it is crucial to implement and promote sustainable forest management practices. Authorities should provide continuous and specialized training in forest soil management, emphasizing the importance of biodiversity conservation and increasing soil organic matter. Develop joint training programs that combine scientific research with practical field experience, possibly leveraging demonstration sites as Living Labs. Additionally, policies should be developed to incentivize reforestation and the sustainable management of forest waste. Promoting awareness about the importance of soil should be a central objective, with campaigns that educate the public and professionals about sustainable practices. Furthermore, infrastructures for the prevention and control of forest fires should be improved, and research in innovative technologies for forest soil management should be encouraged. Encourage the use of digital platforms to monitor and disseminate best practices in forest soil management, integrating real-time data and research findings.

Urban

In the urban sphere, it is essential for authorities to promote urban planning that incorporates sustainability and soil health. They should encourage the development of sustainable drainage infrastructures, such as green roofs and vertical gardens, which help reduce soil impermeability and improve air quality. Promote urban Living Labs where pilot projects on green infrastructure and sustainable drainage systems can be tested and showcased. It is necessary to implement policies that promote the creation of green spaces and urban agriculture, which will not only enhance soil health but also improve citizens' quality of life. Authorities must launch awareness campaigns to increase public consciousness about the importance of urban soil health and the need for sustainable practices. Moreover, it is crucial to establish stricter regulations for waste management and soil pollution, and to promote the remediation of contaminated soils through innovative techniques such as bioremediation. Integrate incentives for public-private partnerships aimed at restoring contaminated urban soils and converting them into community green spaces.

5.5.6. Key messages

1. **Education and Training:** Increase education and continuous training in sustainable soil management practices across agricultural, forestry, and urban sectors. Provide farmers, forest managers, and urban planners with access to educational programs that focus on soil conservation, biodiversity, and efficient water management. Ensure that training programs are delivered through both in-person field visits and digital platforms to maximize accessibility and impact.
2. **Policy Reform and Incentives:** Reform agricultural, forestry, and urban planning policies to support sustainable practices. Offer financial incentives and subsidies to those implementing soil conservation measures, such as crop rotation, agroforestry, and urban green infrastructure projects. Adjust subsidies to discourage unsustainable practices and promote long-term soil health. Develop clear metrics and monitoring tools—potentially integrated into a central digital dashboard—to assess the effectiveness of policy reforms.

- 3. Awareness and Public Engagement:** Launch widespread awareness campaigns to highlight the importance of soil health and sustainable practices. Engage the public, professionals, and policymakers in understanding the critical role of healthy soils in environmental resilience, food security, and climate change mitigation. Utilize social media and community outreach programs to foster broader engagement and support for soil health initiatives.
- 4. Innovative Technologies and Practices:** Promote the adoption of innovative soil management technologies, such as precision agriculture, sustainable forest management techniques, and urban sustainable drainage systems. Support research and development in soil health, focusing on practical applications that can be readily implemented by stakeholders. Facilitate collaboration between research institutions and industry through pilot projects in Living Labs to accelerate the transfer of innovative technologies to practice.
- 5. Integrated Management and Collaboration:** Foster collaboration between different sectors and stakeholders, including public and private entities, NGOs, and local communities. Encourage integrated soil management approaches that consider the interconnectedness of agricultural, forestry, and urban ecosystems, ensuring a holistic and sustainable management strategy for soil health across Spain. Establish multi-stakeholder platforms—both physical and virtual—to coordinate efforts and share best practices across sectors.

5.6. Country report: Sweden

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5.6.1. Introduction to the study regions and the national soil health discourse

The study regions

The three regions that represented Sweden in this study was *Region Västerbotten* in the northern part of Sweden, *Region Närke* in the middle part of Sweden and *Region Skåne* in the southernmost part of Sweden. As seen in the table and map below (Table SE-1; Figure SE-1), the proportion of agricultural land of the total land area differs a lot in Sweden, both between and within regions. Northern Sweden (represented by Region Västerbotten) is forest dominated, mostly with spruce and pine. Agricultural land is found along coasts, rivers and lakes and agriculture is often rather extensive to its character (low input and lay dominated). In the middle part of Sweden (represented by Region Närke), there is still a lot of forests, but the proportion of agricultural land has increased. The agriculture is varied with both areas with rather extensive production as well as areas with more intensive agriculture – especially on the plains. The further south in Sweden, the more crops are able to be grown. Growing cover crops are however rather uncommon in Region 2, as the window for establishment are often considered too short. Region Skåne has the largest proportion of agricultural land in Sweden and here you find some of the best agricultural conditions in Sweden. Growing cover crops are more common in Region 3 than in Region 2. Even though Region 3 is considered as being an agricultural dominated area in Sweden, there are still rather large proportion of forest land – especially in the northern part of Skåne. As there are both more and larger cities in the southern half of Sweden, the pressure on land and the competition between land uses increases further south. Table SE-1 shows the differences in land use among the study regions and the three municipalities within each region.

Figure SE-1. The three Swedish study regions. Map from Jordbruksverket with land use data from 2020. [Jordbruksmarkens användning 2020. Slutlig statistik - Jordbruksverket.se](https://jordbruksmarkens.anvandning.2020.Slutligstatistik-Jordbruksverket.se)

Region <i>Municipalities</i>	Total land area (ha)	Total agricultural land area (ha) (% of total)	Total forest land area (ha) (% of total)	Built up and developed land (ha) (% of total)	Population
Region Västerbotten	5 500 000	69 600 (1.3%)	3 946 000 (72%)	78 500 (1.4%)	279 000
<i>Umeå</i>		5.3%	78.1%	4.7%	132 200
<i>Skellefteå</i>		3.8%	82.8%	2.7%	74 700
<i>Lycksele</i>		0.3%	83.4%	1.3%	12 200
Region Närke	854 000	111 700 (13%)	644 000 (75%)	43 700 (5%)	378 000
<i>Örebro</i>		29.5%	55.2%	8.1%	158 00
<i>Kumla</i>		48.1%	32.3%	12.1%	22 479
<i>Askersund</i>		10.8%	78.2%	4.0%	11 500
Region Skåne	1 100 000	493 000 (44%)	435 000 (39.5%)	110 600 (10%)	1 400 000
<i>Malmö</i>		30.7%	1.9%	45.4%	357 400
<i>Kristianstad</i>		42.3%	44.4%	8.8%	86 700
<i>Örkelljunga</i>		8.3%	74.9%	8.1%	10 500

Table SE-1. Land use statistics from the Swedish study regions and municipalities. Built on land use data from 2020 (SCB; [Markanvändningen i Sverige, hektar efter region, markanvändningsklass och vart 5:e år. PxWeb \(scb.se\)](#) and [Kommuner i siffror \(scb.se\)](#)).

National soil health and environmental discourse

In Sweden, the concept of *soil health* has hitherto not been part of the public soil discourse to any larger extent. In agriculture, however, the concept has received more and more attention the last few years and soil health events tend to attract many participants. Among farmers, the concept is mostly used by those who are managing their farms according to the strategies that are commonly called Conservation Agriculture and Regenerative Agriculture. These farmers experience a weak support from the established AKIS, both in soil health related issues as well as issues related to new management practices that differ from the conventional or organic norm (Höckert and Lundström, 2024).

At policy level, the Swedish environmental discourse is framed by the sixteen environmental quality objectives that the Swedish Parliament has decided on. These objectives describe the state of the Swedish environment that environmental actions should be geared towards ([Swedish environmental objectives \(naturvardsverket.se\)](#)). These quality objectives includes both agricultural, forestry and urban land uses.

Within agriculture, the Swedish environmental discourse has mostly been influenced by the large public funded advisory programme called *Focus on Nutrients* that started in 2001 ([In English - Greppa](#)). The background of Focus on Nutrients was twofold: the adoption of the new environmental quality objectives in Sweden and the start of a new period in the EU Common Agricultural Policy (Greppa Näringen, 2011). The environmental quality objectives meant that for the first time farming had its own requirements for the reduction of nitrogen and phosphorous emissions. In Sweden, there was a desire to work with competence development of farmers and with voluntary involvement in relation to these issues, instead of introducing fertiliser accounts according to a Danish model (ibid). Co-

financing through the EU budget enabled a new approach to advisory services with a degree of systematisation that had not existed before (ibid). Being a public funded undertaking, Focus on Nutrients offers advisory services that are free of charge to the farmer. The main purpose has been to reduce nutrient leaching and emissions of greenhouse gases, but during the years the scope of the programme has widened and the number of advisory modules have increased. Since 2023, the word *soil health* is mentioned in some of their modules (e.g. [Ny rådgivning med hållbarhetsfokus - Greppa](#)).

When it comes to forest and urban soils, *soil health* is not a concept that is being used to any larger extent. However, aspects of soil health is of course discussed but with another terminology – just as in agriculture. In Swedish, there is a special word for forest soil fertility – *bonitet* – that is a measure of how much a forest grows per year on average during an orbital period under ideal circumstances ([Bonitet - Skogshögskolans system - Skogskunskap](#)). The last years, the public forest environmental debate has focussed on forest as a carbon sink (Skogsstyrelsen, 2022) as well as peatland management and greenhouse gas emissions (Skogsstyrelsen, 2021). In both agriculture and forestry, soil compaction is an issue that is discussed (e.g. [Markpackning - Greppa](#); [Körskador - Skogsstyrelsen](#)). The importance of biodiversity is also a common topic in the Swedish environmental discourse, regardless of land use – albeit with a focus on above-ground biodiversity (e.g. Tunón and Sandell, 2021).

5.6.2. The respondents

The selection of potential Swedish survey respondents was based on the case study regions and municipalities selected for the survey. As different actors have different geographical areas where they conduct their work, the search for potential respondents somewhat differed between the three surveys. For actors within agriculture and forestry, the regional level is the most common geographical working area, while the local level is the most common in an urban soil perspective. As we wanted to reach out to those actors who have the mandate to influence the soil management in the different land uses, we also sent the survey to some actors working on national level. The groups of actors that the surveys were sent to are summarised in Table SE-2 below.

Email addresses were collected through webpages and by taking contact with identified relevant actors. As the goal was to reach out to key actors with different functions in relation to soil management in each land use type, all relevant persons found was included in the send list. Hence, gender was not a selection criterion. Table n presents data for the share between male/female in the distributed surveys. As gender was not a question in the survey, we do not have statistics regarding gender distribution among the finalised answers that was used for result presentation and analysis.

The surveys were distributed by emails in the beginning of February 2024. Besides the link to the survey, the mail included a cover letter where the purpose of the study was briefly presented. The cover letter also contained a personal greeting and a description of why we regarded them as a key person for the survey.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Local/ Municipality level			Municipality offices: urban planning/community development park management municipal ecologists environmental office Landscape Architect Offices
Regional level	County Administration Board: Rural unit Federation of Swedish Farmers Advisors in Focus on Nutrients Farmers private advisors in crop production	The Swedish Forest Agency: regional forest consultants County Administration Board: Nature conservation/Forest Regional forest member organisations: consultants/inspectors Skogssällskapet (public service foundation)	County Administration Board: planning + environmental protection Landscape Architect Offices (including geotechnicians, environmental investigators, environmental consultants)
National level	Board of Agriculture Environmental Protection Agency The Swedish Society for Nature Conservation KRAV (label for organic food) Organic Farmers Svenska Foder Researchers at SLU Agricultural magazines	Environmental Protection Agency Federation of Swedish Farmers The Swedish Society for Nature Conservation WWF Greenpeace Researchers at SkogForsk (Forestry Research Institute of Sweden) Researchers at SLU Forest magazines	Environmental Protection Agency Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions Researchers at SLU
Total number of distributed surveys	91	138	113
<i>Female No (%)</i>	54 (59%)	43 (31%)	65 (58%)
<i>Male No (%)</i>	33 (36%)	95 (69%)	40 (35%)
<i>Anonymous email address No (%)</i>	4 (4 %)	0	8 (7%)
Started surveys	60	87	77
Completed surveys	32	52	38

Table SE-2. Identified key actors including numbers of number of distributed surveys, started surveys and completed surveys.

The three surveys was distributed in the three chosen study regions. As the regions differ regarding the proportion between agriculture and forestry as well as density regarding population, an equal numbers of surveys were not sent to each region and/or municipality. Table SE-3 presents the number of distributed vs number of completed surveys at regional/municipality and national level. In the agricultural survey, Region Västerbotten and Närke are underrepresented compared to Region Skåne. This is not surprising, as the number of agricultural actors are fewer in these regions. For the forest and urban surveys, however, the completed surveys are rather evenly distributed between the regions. From now on, only country-level results will be discussed.

	Agricultural survey No of completed vs distributed surveys	Forest survey No of completed vs distributed surveys	Urban survey No of completed vs distributed surveys
Region Västerbotten	2 (12)	8 (8)	1 (3)
<i>Umeå</i>		3 (9)	5 (20)
<i>Skellefteå</i>		3 (9)	3 (5)
<i>Lycksele</i>		2 (6)	(4)
Region Närke	2 (17)	7 (25)	2 (20)
<i>Örebro</i>		2	5 (1)
<i>Kumla</i>		1	4 (4)
<i>Askersund</i>			5 (9)
Region Skåne	12 (26)	13 (42)	4 (9)
<i>Malmö</i>		1	3 (15)
<i>Kristianstad</i>		3	2 (5)
<i>Örkelljunga</i>		2	2 (3)
National level	16 (36)	20 (39)	3 (15)
Other	2	5	1
Total	32 (91)	52 (138)	38 (113)

Table SE-3. Number of completed¹ and distributed surveys in different regions/municipalities.

5.6.3. Results and analysis

This chapter presents and comments on the Swedish survey data. The chapter consists of three sections – one for each survey (agriculture, forest and urban). In the following text, the numbering of the figures follows the numbering of the questions in the surveys (see Appendix 1, 2 and 3). The prefix SE indicates that the figures belongs to the Swedish chapter and the suffix A, F or U indicates which survey they belong to (Agriculture, Forest or Urban).

The agricultural survey

Description of the respondents

Figures SE-Q2-Q10A below present the agricultural respondents in different graphs related to the background questions in the survey. The agricultural survey was mostly answered by actors working with soil in relation to counselling/advisory work, followed by environmental issues and education (Figure SE-Q2A). That corresponds well with the survey intention. As most agricultural advisors in Sweden who are engaged in production as well as environmental issues work in private advisory companies, that respondent group was the largest (Figure SE-Q4A). Most of the Swedish respondents holds a master's degree (50%) in agricultural sciences (75%; Figure SE-Q6A) and 84% have studied soil sciences during their education. Moreover, 87% of the respondents claimed that they have received training in soil health related issues. The largest proportion of the respondents perceived themselves to be working with soil issues to a very large extent (28%), although the Swedish mean value was slightly lower than for the total group of respondents (Figure SE-Q3A, Swedish mean value 5.02; Total mean value 5,21). Half of the respondents have worked with soil related issues for more than 10 years.

¹ As an employee can work in several municipalities/at different levels, the total sum of completed surveys reported in the table exceeds the total number of completed surveys. However, the numbers give an indication of the distribution of answers between regions.

In relation to their needs, 75% of the respondents rated their knowledge concerning soil as either a 5 or a 6 on a 7-graded scale, thus being higher than for the total group of respondents (SE-Q9A; Swedish mean value 5.38; Total mean value 4.87).

Figure SE-Q2A. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to..."

Figure SE-Q3A. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Sweden 5.03; Total 5.21.

Figure SE-Q4A. "I am employed by"

Figure SE-Q6A. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Figure SE-Q9A. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 5.38; Total 4.87.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the background questions, the respondents were presented by the soil health problem formulation from the EU Commission, claiming that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. The question to what extent the respondents agreed with that problem formulation in relation to agricultural soils in their region/country gave rise to a large and relatively even distribution along the 7-point Likert scale (Figure SE-Q11A). Equal numbers of respondents (19%) answered 2 respectively 7. Obviously, there were very different perceptions of whether poor soil health is a problem or not, despite a relatively homogeneous educational and experiential background among the respondents. The Swedish mean value was lower than for the total (4.22 compared to 5.21).

In the following question, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil. The first perspective was *soil fertility*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain plant growth. In Sweden that would correspond to the traditional view on soil in agriculture. The soil fertility concept focus mainly on the ecosystem service “provision of food, fibre and fuel”. The second perspective was *soil health*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services in terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services. In the question, the respondents should indicate what perspective on soil that aligned with their own view. The Swedish respondents answered similar to a Bell-shaped curve, with a peak on the neutral value 4 (mean 4.19). This could be compared with the curve for the total group having two peaks – one at 4 and one at 7 (soil health) (Figure SE-Q12A). Although both the total group of respondents and the Swedish respondents “strongly agree” that soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture, the Swedish respondents were not as convinced as the total

group (Swedish mean 5.34 vs Total mean 6.07; Figure SE-Q13aA). When it came to the question whether the sector is already using the concept or not, the Swedish mean was higher than for the total (5.00 vs 4.25; Figure SE-Q13bA). Although soil health was considered to be a relevant concept, it has obviously not reached any larger spread in the sector yet. There are hence potentials for improving the respondents' knowledge about the soil health concept in general as well as how management is affecting soil health (Swedish mean 5.09 vs 5.28). The Swedish respondents did not seem to think that an adoption of soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil (mean 4.28; Figure SE-Q15aA), neither would it change how their own workplace would deal with soil issues (mean 2.81; Figure SE-Q15bA).

Figure SE-Q11A. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to agricultural soils in your country?” Mean value: Sweden 4.22; Total 5.21.

Figure SE-Q12A. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Sweden: 4.18; Total 4.84.

Figure SE-Q13aA. “Soil health is a relevant concept in agriculture.” Mean value: Sweden 5.34; Total: 6.07.

Figure SE-Q13bA. “The agricultural sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Sweden 5.00; Total 4.25.

Figure SE-Q14aA. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Sweden 5.09; Total 4.76.

Figure SE-Q14bA. “How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?” Mean value: Sweden 5.28; Total 5.03.

Figure SE-Q15aA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 4.28; Total 5.12.

Figure SE-Q15bA. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in agriculture change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Sweden 2.81; Total 4.05.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Among the soil challenges listed in Q16a, the main challenges in Sweden were perceived to be “To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage” (mean 5.22) and “To decrease soil compaction” (mean 5.16), followed by “To improve soil fertility” (mean 4.63), and “To avoid soil sealing” (mean 4.41). The challenges that got the lowest rating from a Swedish perspective was (as expected) “To decrease desertification” (mean 1.13) and “To decrease salinization” (1.84).

The following question, regarding the extent to which the respondent’s workplace dealt with the challenges considered as a problem, was put in order to see whether there was a mismatch between the two. The only challenge where there seems to be a gap, is regarding soil sealing. Obviously, the respondents perceived the problem with soil sealing of agricultural land not being an issue that lies in their hands to influence. The challenges that the respondents worked the most with was more general to its character, “To promote the awareness of sustainable soil management” and “To promote the awareness of the importance of soil health”. This prioritising was shared with the total group of respondents.

Figure SE-Q16A. “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in agricultural soils in your region (or country if you work at national level)?”

Figure SE-Q18A. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in agricultural soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

There were two open questions in the survey. One about perceived hindrances for improved soil health, followed by what kind of measures that the respondents would suggest to deal with these hindrances. In total, many different hindrances were mentioned, but the three mentioned most times were poor economy/profitability, lack of knowledge and lack of political governance/today’s regulations. Other aspects also mentioned by several respondents were for example short-term leasing of land, that animal and crop production often are separated, access to relevant technology, poor crop rotation and culture. Table SE-Q19A below presents examples of quotes from the surveys.

<p>Poor economy/profitability</p> <p><i>“Generally poor profitability”</i></p> <p><i>“In many cases, the economy prevents investments in basic/long-term improvement measure”</i></p> <p><i>“Profitability – cannot sell lay”</i></p> <p><i>“Economy drives large-scale operations”</i></p>
<p>Lack of knowledge</p> <p><i>“Knowledge of methods that improves soil health”</i></p> <p><i>“Knowledge of alternative practices that are profitable”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of knowledge about the importance of microlife”</i></p> <p><i>“Poor knowledge about soils among advisors and other actors in agriculture”</i></p>
<p>Political governance/today’s regulations</p> <p><i>“Lack of political governance that rewards sustainability and increased self-sufficiency”</i></p> <p><i>“The existing regulatory framework for both direct support and environmental compensation often hinders work with soil health”</i></p> <p><i>“Misdirected support”</i></p>

Table SE-Q19A. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

When it came to suggesting measures to deal with the perceived hindrances, they were more diversely formulated. However, two main themes appeared; knowledge/competence development and subsidies to support soil health. Other measures mentioned were for example the need to value food that are produced in a sustainable manner higher and the need to make it easier for young farmers to develop their business. Table SE-Q20A below presents examples of quotes from the surveys.

<p>Knowledge/competence development</p> <p><i>“Training of advisors and giving statues to these issues”</i></p> <p><i>“Competence development measures – but these need to lead to tangible improvements on farm level”</i></p> <p><i>“Increased means for spreading knowledge about methods”</i></p> <p><i>“Experience exchange groups for farmers to share knowledge and experiences”</i></p> <p><i>“Free advisory services on soil health issues”</i></p> <p><i>“Start dialogues about the importance of good soil health”</i></p> <p><i>“Cultural changes needs good examples/role models who can also demonstrate financial benefits”</i></p> <p><i>“Instead of trying to set up a control system where soil health can be measured based on different threshold values, it would be better to identify the possible problems that exist in a given location and then, based on context and situation, try to solve them with appropriate management methods. That is, a system that is based on knowledge and competence and not on an artificial control system.”</i></p>
<p>Subsidies that support soil health issues</p> <p><i>“Support for carbon sequestration in crop cultivation”</i></p> <p><i>“Simplify the support for intermediate crops/catch crops”</i></p> <p><i>“Direct support that take biodiversity more into account”</i></p> <p><i>“That we favor farmers who actively work with soil improvement measures”</i></p> <p><i>“Support for farmers ecosystem services”</i></p> <p><i>“Use the resources in CAP to guide in the right direction”</i></p>

Table SE-Q20A. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

The last part of the survey concerned perceived needs for competence development, if there were competence development activities available for the respondent group and what kind of competence development they preferred. The soil related topic that the respondents ranked highest to learn more about was “to assess soil health” (53%). This topic was followed by “potentials for carbon sequestration” (41%), “soil biology” (38%) and “the soil health concept in general” and “soil

biodiversity” (34 % each). Over 30% of the Swedish respondents did not know whether there are relevant competence development measures available for them and a further 22% of the respondents gave a neutral response. Hence, if there already are available competence development measures for the respondent group, they are obviously not well known. When it came to suitable formats for learning, digital courses (59%) followed by field visits, experience exchange with colleagues (53% each) and live webinars (41%) got the highest ranking.

The forest survey

Description of respondents

Figures SE-Q2-Q10F below present the forest respondents in different graphs related to the background questions in the survey. The forest survey was mostly answered by actors working with soil in relation to exercise of authority, followed by nature conservation, environmental issues and counselling/advisory work (Figure SE-Q2F). Since the forest survey was sent to many respondents working at authorities and organisations providing advice to forest owners, this corresponds well to the sending list. The forest survey was distributed to a larger number of researchers than the agricultural survey, which explains the rather high bar for respondents engaged in research. It is notable that 15% of the Swedish respondents did not perceive themselves working with soil related issues. Most of the respondents were employed by a national authority, an academic institute or a private company (SE-Q4F). A majority held a master's degree (40%) in forest sciences (69%; Figure SE-Q6F) and 79% had studied soil sciences during their education. However, only 17% of the respondents had received training on soil health issues (compared with 87% of the agricultural respondents). Among the forest respondents, there was a great variation to what extent they perceived themselves to work with soil issues. 40% ranked it 1-3 on the Likert scale and 47% ranked it as 5-7, resulting in a mean of 4.35 (Figure SE-Q3F). Half of the respondents have worked with soil related issues for more than 10 years. In relation to their needs, 65% of the respondents rated their knowledge concerning soil as a 5-7 on the Likert scale, thus higher than the total group of respondents (SE-Q9F; Swedish mean value 4.90; Total mean value 4.21). However, when comparing the mean for Q9 between the agricultural (5.38) and the forest (4.90) respondent groups, the forest respondents rate their soil knowledge lower despite that both respondent groups had studied soil science to a similar extent (approximately 80% for both groups).

Figure SE-Q2F. "In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to"

Figure SE-Q3F. “In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent.” Mean value: Sweden 4.35; Total 4.08.

Figure SE-Q4F. “I am employed by”

Figure SE-Q6F. “What is the major subject in your education?”

Figure SE-Q9F. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 4.90; Total 4.21.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the background questions, the respondents were presented by the soil health problem formulation from the EU Commission, which claim that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. Just as for the agricultural survey, the question to what extent the respondents agreed with that formulation in relation to forest soils in their region/country gave rise to a wide spread among the responses, however, with a majority of votes in the lower half of the scale (Figure SE-Q11F). The mean among the forest respondents (3.69) was lower than both the total group of forest respondents (mean 4.14) and for the Swedish agricultural respondents (mean 4.22). Obviously, poor soil health is not perceived as a problem in Swedish forest soils, although there is a group of respondents who “strongly agree” with the statement (7.7%).

In the following question, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil. The first perspective was *soil fertility*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain production. Focus is mainly on the ecosystem service “provision of food, fibre and fuel”/production of forest raw material. The second perspective was *soil health*, defined as the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services in terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services. In the question, the respondents should indicate what perspective on soil that aligned with their own view. Just as for the agricultural respondents, the Swedish forestry respondents had a peak on the neutral value 4 (mean 3.96). The biggest difference compared to the total group was that among the Swedish respondents only 15% voted for the soil health option compared with 27% for the total (Figure SE-Q12F).

There was more doubt whether it is relevant to talk about soil health within forestry than there was in agriculture (mean 4.48 (Figure SE-Q13aF) compared with 5.34 for the agricultural survey). Among the respondents, 17% “strongly agree” that it is. There was no doubt, however, that the forestry sector did not use the concept yet as 40% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that the sector already use the concept (Figure SE-Q13bF; mean 2.08). Obviously, the respondents saw a potential of introducing soil health to the forest sector discourse. Based on relatively low means in Q14, it can be concluded that there is a potential to increase knowledge about both the soil health concept in general (mean 3.08; Figure SE-Q15aF) as well as for how forest management is affecting soil health (mean 4.10; Figure SE-Q15bF) among the forest respondents. The Swedish respondents did not seem to think that an adoption of the soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil (mean 4.06; Figure SE-Q15aF), neither would it change how their own workplace would deal with soil issues (mean 3.37; Figure SE-Q15bF).

Figure SE-Q11F. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to forest soils in your country?” Mean value: Sweden 3.69; Total 4.14.

Figure SE-Q12F. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Sweden: 3.96; Total 4.61.

Figure SE-Q13aF. “Soil health is a relevant concept in forestry.” Mean value: Sweden 4.48; Total: 5.22.

Figure SE-Q13bF. “The forest sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Sweden 2.08; Total 3.35.

Figure SE-Q14aF. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Sweden 3.08; Total 3.33.

Figure SE-Q14bF. “How knowledgeable are you about how forest management affects soil health?” Mean value: Sweden 4.10; Total 4.16.

Figure SE-Q15aF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 4.06; Total 4.41.

Figure SE-Q15bF. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Sweden 3.37; Total 3.68.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Among the soil challenges listed in Q16, none of them were perceived as a problem within forestry. This applies both in Sweden as for the total. From a Swedish perspective, only three challenges received a higher mean than 4 – that is, “To increase soil biodiversity” (mean 4.56), “To manage peatlands” (mean 4.14) and “To decrease soil compaction” (mean 4.13). Just as for the agricultural survey, the challenges that got the lowest rating from a Swedish perspective was “To decrease desertification” (mean 1.40) and “To decrease salinization” (2.06). The biggest differences between the agricultural and forestry challenges was that in forestry “To increase soil organic matter” and “To avoid soil sealing” was not perceived as big challenges – which was not particularly surprising.

The following question, regarding the extent to which the respondent’s workplace dealt with the challenges considered as a problem, was put in order to see whether there was a mismatch between the two. When comparing the two graphs, no gaps were identified. The two challenges that the respondents work the most with was “To promote the awareness of sustainable forest management” (mean 5.40) and “To increase soil biodiversity”. This prioritising was shared with the total group of respondents as well.

Figure SE-Q16F: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in forest soils in your region/country?”

Figure SE-Q18F. “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in forest soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

In the survey, two open questions about perceived hindrances for improved soil health followed by what kind of measures the respondents would suggest to deal with these hindrances were presented. Just as for the agricultural survey, many different hindrances were mentioned. Also this time, the two largest themes were related to economy and lack of knowledge. Another theme that occurred repeatedly was a one connected to culture. Table SE-Q19F below presents examples of quotes related to these themes. Some of the quotes revolved around the fact that soil health was not yet a topic used in forestry. One respondent stated: *"There is no talk about soil health in particular and that is probably due to the fact that there is no stated mission regarding it as the Forestry Agency is very much governed by government mandates"*.

<p>Economy</p> <p><i>"Economy - most of it is about economy"</i></p> <p><i>"Economy (gentle forestry machines are expensive)"</i></p> <p><i>"That you have to use the land in an efficient way to make the economy work."</i></p> <p><i>"The more efficient forestry gives little room for added value, so the forest economy, product demand and willingness to pay. As well as the long turnaround times in the forest, which make it difficult to see direct results from measures."</i></p>
<p>Lack of knowledge/awareness</p> <p><i>"Lack of knowledge, lack of knowledge and lack of knowledge - affects politics, decisions, everything"</i></p> <p><i>"Knowledge - more and better knowledge in these subjects for machine operators and others active in the forest"</i></p> <p><i>"You have to be aware of the problem to know if it exists and, if so, to be able to fix it"</i></p>
<p>Culture</p> <p><i>"Business as usual"</i></p> <p><i>"Tradition - many do what they have done in the past"</i></p> <p><i>"Casual forest management"</i></p>

Table SE-Q19F. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

When it came to suggest measures to deal with perceived hindrances, many of the ideas mentioned were related to the need for knowledge/competence development and increased governance. Table SE-Q20F below presents examples of quotes from the surveys.

<p>Knowledge/competence development</p> <p><i>"Knowledge requirements. More knowledge in schools, more requirements to be able to carry out the work. Tougher grip on certifications. Several certifications do not work in reality at the ground level."</i></p> <p><i>"Better dissemination of knowledge among the forest consultants who meet the landowners. Training for professionals, but also media mobilization which can trigger a change."</i></p> <p><i>"Long-term studies are the only way to know if something is changing at a specific location, so continuous sampling at many locations to be able to detect changes."</i></p> <p><i>"Policy briefs & knowledge compilations for decision-makers and practitioners, model projects, show economic and societal costs & benefits, collaboration between research, practitioners and advocacy organizations"</i></p>
<p>Clearer governance</p> <p><i>"Political clarity from government to ministries and on to managers"</i></p> <p><i>"Political movement/commitment for new legislation that provides better conditions for maintaining ecosystem services (including soil health)"</i></p> <p><i>"Must be highlighted by the government that this is important in forest policy. Then the Forestry Agency must be given the resources to implement the new forest policy."</i></p> <p><i>"Reintroducing the Ministry of the Environment would be a good start. It is difficult to get an overall perspective on environmental issues otherwise"</i></p>

Table SE-Q20F. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

The last part of the survey concerned perceived needs for competence development, if there were competence development activities available for the respondent group today and what forms or activities they preferred. Of the suggested topics, over 50% of the respondents would like to learn more about three of them. These were; “the soil health concept in general” (58%) “potentials for carbon sequestration” (53%) and “soil biodiversity” (50%). Also, “How to assess soil health” and “Forest management strategies to improve soil health” were ranked high (42% each). These topics were also the ones who got the highest ranking from the total group of respondents.

More than 40% of the Swedish respondents did not know whether there were relevant competence development measures on soil health related issues available for them. When it came to preferred formats for learning, digital courses were by far the alternative that got the highest ranking (62%). Other preferred activities were live webinars and experience exchange with other colleagues (46% each) followed by recorded web movies (44%) and field visits (42%).

The urban survey

Description of respondents

Figures SE-Q2-10U below present the urban respondents in different graphs related to the background questions in the survey. The urban survey was mostly answered by actors working with soil in relation to urban planning (66%) and environmental issues (58%) (Figure SE-Q2U). Moreover, approximately 20% of the respondents worked with maintenance of parks, construction, exercise of authority and recycling/reuse of soils respectively. As the aim was to reach out to actors active in urban planning, park management and environmental issues, this corresponds well to the sending list, although the park managers became somewhat underrepresented. This is, however, not a consequence of them not answering the survey, rather that there are a lot more people working with planning and environmental issues at a more general level. A regional authority (74%) employed most of the urban respondents, followed by a private company (13%; Figure SE-Q4U). As the survey was above all sent to municipality offices and landscape architect offices, this is in line with what one could expect. Most of the respondents perceived themselves to work with soil related issues “to a very large extent” (42%; mean 5.68; Figure SE-Q3U).

Since the urban survey was sent to a wide range of actors, the education among the respondents varied more than for the other two surveys. Most of the Swedish respondents held a master (71%) in a subject not mentioned among the answer alternatives (39% answered “other” on the question concerning their major subject (Figure SE-Q6U) – ranging from economy and journalism to geology and political science, while 24% answered natural science/engineering or planning/architecture respectively. During their education, half of the respondent group had studied soil science and half had not. Moreover, only 21% had received training in soil health issues (which is thus approximately the same as for the forest respondents). In relation to their needs, most respondents rated their soil knowledge as a 5 on a 7-graded Likert scale (mean 4.47; Figure SE-Q9U). The urban respondent group had the largest variation in their experience of working with soil related issues, as 32% had worked with soil issues for less than 5 years and 39% for more than 10 years.

Figure SE-Q2U. “In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to...”

Figure SE-Q3U. "In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent." Mean value: Sweden 5.68; Total 5.51.

Figure SE-Q4U. "I am employed by"

Figure SE-Q6U. "What is the major subject in your education?"

Figure SE-Q9U. “In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 4.47; Total 4.62.

The respondents and the soil health concept

After the background questions, the respondents were presented to the soil health problem formulation from the EU Commission, claiming that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils. In contrast to the agricultural and forest survey, a majority of urban votes was on the upper half of the scale regarding the question whether the respondents agreed with the problem formulation for urban soils or not. The highest bar was even found on the answer option “strongly agree” (29%; mean 5.34; Figure SE-Q11U). This mean could be compared with 4.22 for the agricultural survey and 3,69 for the forest survey. Obviously, poor soil health was perceived as a problem for urban soils. For the total group of urban respondents, the mean was even higher (5.60) and 41% of the respondents strongly agreed with the problem formulation from the EU Commission.

In the following question, the respondents were presented to two main perspectives on soil, where they should indicate what perspective on soil that aligned best with their own view. The first perspective was called *targeted soil use*, defined as *focus on one or a few specific functions at a time* (i.e. as foundation for buildings/infrastructure, as medium for water purification or as growing medium for trees and plants). The second perspective was called *focus on a wide range of soil ecosystem services simultaneously*. Although 21% of the respondents put their vote on “focus on a wide range of ecosystem services simultaneously”, the majority of the votes were found at the targeted soil use side of the continuum (Figure SE-Q12U; mean 3.47).

When it came to the questions regarding the relevance of the soil health concept for urban soils and whether the urban sector already used the concept or not, one can conclude that there is a discrepancy between the two answers. Figure SE-Q13aU showed that a majority of the respondents found the soil health concept relevant for urban soils (mean 5.18). However, a vast majority of the respondents (76%) voted either 1 (strongly disagree) or 2 on the 7-graded scale, resulting in a mean on 2.03. Based on the answers on Q14, one can conclude that there is a potential to increase knowledge about the soil health concept in general (mean 3.47; Figure SE-Q14aU) as well as how management affect soil health (mean 3.50; Figure SE-Q14bU) among the urban respondents. However, the Swedish respondents did not seem to think that an adoption of soil health concept would imply a mindshift concerning soil to any larger extent (mean 4.71; Figure SE-Q15aU), neither would it change how their own workplace would deal with soil issues (mean 3.37; Figure SE-Q15bU).

Figure SE-Q11U. “To what extent do you agree with the problem description by EU Commission, in relation to urban soils in your country?” Mean value: Sweden 5.34; Total 5.60.

Figure SE-Q12U. “The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view.” Mean value: Sweden: 3.47; Total 3.82.

Figure SE-Q13aU. “Soil health is a relevant concept for urban soils.” Mean value: Sweden 5.18; Total: 5.72.

Figure SE-Q13bU. “The urban sector already uses soil health as a concept.” Mean value: Sweden 2.03; Total 2.50.

Figure SE-Q14aU. “How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?” Mean value: Sweden 3.47; Total 3.71.

Figure SE-Q14bU. “How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?” Mean value: Sweden 3.50; Total 4.00.

Figure SE-Q15aU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils imply a mindshift concerning soil?” Mean value: Sweden 4.71; Total 5.24.

Figure SE-Q15bU. “To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?” Mean value: Sweden 4.32; Total 4.59.

Soil challenges in the regions and soil challenges that the respondents are working with

Among the soil challenges listed in Q16, four got a higher mean than 5; “To avoid or remediate contamination of soils/soil pollution” (mean 5.47), “To avoid soil sealing” (mean 5.39), “Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation” (mean 5.29), “To increase soil biodiversity” (mean 5.13) (Figure SE-Q16U). The challenges that got the lowest rating from a Swedish perspective was “To decrease soil erosion” (mean 3.84) and “To increase organic matter” (mean 4.03).

The question regarding to what extent the respondent’s workplace dealt with the listed soil challenges, was put in order to see whether there was a mismatch between considered challenges and what they worked with. However, no gaps were identified (Figure SE-Q16U). It was notable, however, that a very little focus is put on “To promote the awareness of sustainable soil management” (mean 2.68). As soil health was not yet introduced to the urban soil discourse, the low rating for “To promote the awareness of the importance of soil health” (mean 2.53) was no surprise.

Figure SE-Q16U: “To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region/country?”

Figure SE-Q18U: “To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in urban soils?”

Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

There were two open questions about perceived hindrances for improved soil health and what kind of measures that the respondents would suggest to deal with these hindrances. In total, many different hindrances was mentioned, but the three mentioned repeatedly were related to high pressure on land, lack of political governance and lack knowledge. Table SE-Q19U present examples of quotes from the surveys.

<p>High pressure on land</p> <p><i>“The expansion of cities on agricultural and forest land where detailed plans sometimes allow very high levels of exploitation so that not much of the natural soil and habitat for animals and plants remains.”</i></p> <p><i>“Densification and motoring”</i></p> <p><i>“That society requires new housing”</i></p> <p><i>“Buildings, roads and high land prices. The function of urban areas is to be a gathering place for people and their cars. The higher land prices, the greater the driving force that most of the land surface is used for buildings and transport instead of green spaces that solve well-being, climate and drainage. It is not the builders who bear the cost of ill health and floods.”</i></p> <p><i>“Conflicts of interest: we need to build more, both to improve the municipality's economy and to increase the number of housing units. It almost always comes first.”</i></p>
<p>The political governance</p> <p><i>“That we have a political goal to densify the city, that there is less space for green infrastructure”</i></p> <p><i>“There is no governing document that regulates how ecosystem services within the municipality are to be safeguarded, protected and restored.”</i></p> <p><i>“What we are expected to focus on based on our mission. If we could use more time to train our own staff and to develop new routines for how we work with green areas as well as urban plantings, we could change strategy more easily. Today, such a focus falls outside our own goal fulfilment. We are working a little with these issues, but even at the next management level there is not enough knowledge for us to get through the necessary changes on the scale that really gives the issue the focus it requires”.</i></p>
<p>Lack of knowledge/awareness</p> <p><i>“Poor knowledge of the soil’s function and contribution to ecosystem services”</i></p> <p><i>“More people need to know about the concept. I have not heard it before and such a discussion is not held in the administration or within the municipal organization.”</i></p> <p><i>“That the issue is hardly on the agenda”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of knowledge about how to improve soil health”</i></p>

Table SE-Q19U. Quotes regarding hindrances for improved soil health.

When it came to suggest measures to deal with the perceived hindrances, they were significantly fewer than the list of hindrances. However, several of the ideas mentioned were related to the need for knowledge/competence development and increased governance. Table SE-Q20U present examples of quotes from the surveys.

<p>Knowledge/Competence development</p> <p><i>“Education on the issue, what is meant by soil health and why it is important to consider the soil as a resource for several different ecosystem services.”</i></p> <p><i>“Increased awareness”</i></p> <p><i>“A lecture for politicians as well as the head of administration regarding the situation. What affects ecology and biological diversity, what happens in our soils and the importance of living soils for us to have good urban living environments. So, more clear communication and training that motivates changed norms.”</i></p> <p><i>“Improve knowledge of what soil health is and what it contributes to: Why invest in soil health? I think mainly of the construction industry and decision makers. I think the interest in investing in soil health will increase if the “community builders” understand why it is good and important. In urban areas, it may not be seen as important when there are still houses and roads everywhere. A clearer motivation may then be needed.”</i></p>
<p>Clearer governance</p> <p><i>“Legislation and guidance from national authorities is a prerequisite.”</i></p> <p><i>“Produce steering documents, which can also increase knowledge among employees.”</i></p> <p><i>“Changed policy and legislation. The only thing we really work with is soil pollution (which is regulated by legislation) and to some extent infiltration (because floods have major economic consequences).”</i></p>

Table SE-Q20U. Quotes regarding measures for dealing the perceived hindrances.

Competence development

The last part of the survey concerned perceived needs for competence development, if there were competence development activities available for the respondent group today and what forms of activities they preferred. Of the suggested topics, “the soil health concept in general” was the far highest ranked (68%). In addition, also the alternatives “recycling/reusing of soils” (50%), “climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation” (47%) and “how to assess soil health” (45%) were ranked high.

Over 47% of the Swedish respondents did not know if there were relevant competence development measures available for them, while 16% claimed that there were to a very large extent. When it came to preferred formats for learning more about soil health, digital courses were by far the highest ranked alternative (74%). Other preferred formats were live webinars (50%) followed by recorded web movies (45%) and good examples (42%).

5.6.4. Discussion

Agricultural survey

Based on the background questions in the survey, a majority of the respondents identified as influential actors when it comes to soil health issues in agriculture have studied soil science. A majority of the respondents also claimed that their soil knowledge is good in relation to their needs. However, within advisory services, the issue of soil health is not particularly present yet (see for instance Chapter 5.6). It was not until recently that the large Swedish environmental advisory programme *Focus on Nutrients* began to mention soil health in their modules. Moreover, from interviews with farmers engaged in production strategies focussing on soil health (such as Conservation Agriculture and Regenerative Agriculture), we know that these farmers perceive a lack of soil health knowledge among the Swedish agricultural advisors (Chapter 5.6; Höckert and Lundström, 2024). Many of the respondents agreed on that soil health was a relevant concept in agriculture; however, there were also many respondents who disagreed that poor soil health was a problem in Swedish agricultural soils. This is in line with the conclusions drawn in a SLU report from 2021 (Eriksson, 2021) about the current status of Swedish arable soils and cereal crops. Eriksson (2021) states *“the condition of the soil in terms of content of organic matter, pH and plant nutrition is generally good [in Swedish soils]”*. However, in the report *“Costs of the Green Transition of Agriculture”* (LRF, 2023) the Federation of Swedish Farmers

refer to an own survey of Swedish farmers who claim that the biggest threats to soil health on their farms are insufficient drainage followed by low pH and low content of organic matter (LRF, 2023).

As long as soil health is not regarded as a problem, the incentives for working on the issue is of course weak – regardless of whether you consider yourself to have sufficient competence in the matter or not. In the survey, the respondents perceived themselves to have a rather good knowledge about the soil health concept in general as well as how agricultural management affects soil health. However, the survey pinpointed the need for competence development regarding, above all, how to assess soil health. Issues related to soil biology and soil biodiversity was also ranked high. As the focus in Sweden has been on physical and chemical properties of soil (e.g. Eriksson, 2021) these answers were not particularly surprising. If key actors would be more confident in how to assess soil health, they would most likely be keener to engage in soil health discussions together with farmers.

Forest survey

Also among the forest respondents, a large proportion had studied soil science. However, in their current jobs they did not perceive to work with soil issues to any larger extent. Despite this, they did not rank their soil knowledge particularly high in relation to their needs. Consequently, it seems as the soil science taught during their university studies was not completely relevant for the issues they now work with in their professions. The soil health concept was not used within the Swedish forestry sector, and there were doubts whether it is relevant to talk about soil health in forest soils or not. Furthermore, among the respondents a majority did not believe that the EU Commission's problem description regarding poor soil health applied to Swedish forest soils. This could relate to the fact that most respondents rated their knowledge about the soil health concept in general as rather weak. Accordingly, the highest ranked topic for competence development was the soil health concept in general. From this survey, it was not possible to tell whether the low interest in soil health issues in forest soils was because it was not perceived as relevant, or if it was the limited knowledge of the soil health concept that made it irrelevant for the forest respondents.

Urban survey

The urban respondents differed from the other Swedish respondent groups, since only half of them had studied soil science. In their profession, though, over 40% stated that they worked with soil issues “to a very large extent”. This was higher than for both the agricultural (28%) and the forest (19%) respondents. According to the survey, their soil knowledge seemed to fit their needs fairly well. However, a vast majority of the respondents ranked themselves on the lower half of the scale regarding their knowledge concerning soil health. Similar to the forest respondents, this topic was the highest ranked regarding the need for competence development. Interestingly enough, the urban respondents agreed to the EU Commission’s problem description regarding poor soil health, and they perceived the concept as relevant for urban soils. Just as for the forest sector, however, the concept was not used within the sector yet. Obviously, there is a potential for introducing the soil health concept in this context.

Cross-section

In the surveys, there were one question of key importance for soil health related action in a country – namely whether influential actors perceived poor soil health as a problem or not. Based on the survey result, we can state that respondents doubted whether poor soil health is a problem in Sweden or not. Among the three sectors, the urban respondents agreed the most with the statement from the EU Commission concerning soil health (mean: urban 5.34; agriculture 4.22; forest 3.69). If you do not perceive a topic as important or a problem, you will probably not pay much attention to it. This of

course raises the question: *Is poor soil health a problem in Swedish soils or not?* Within the agricultural sector, where the topic is considered the most, the opinions differ. On the one hand, there are farmers engaged in Conservation Agriculture and Regenerative Agriculture who claim that there are not enough focus on soil health issues in Sweden (see for instance Chapter 5.6), on the other hand, there are advisors who claim that there farmers have a “religious” attitude to their strategies (see also Chapter 5.6).

The results regarding hindrances for improved soil health and measures to deal with these hindrances, there were similarities between the sectors. Table SE-4 below summarizes the recurring themes from the surveys. Lack of knowledge and soil health awareness were mentioned in all three surveys, as was the importance of clear governance. As long as there are no clear missions or signs to prioritise a certain issue from the government, other topics will be on the agenda for both national agencies as well as for actors working closer to soils managers.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Hindrances for improved soil health	Poor economy/ profitability Lack of knowledge Political governance/ today's regulations	Economy Lack of knowledge/ awareness Culture	High pressure on land The political governance Lack of knowledge/awareness
Measures to deal with identified hindrances	Knowledge/Competence development Compensations	Knowledge/Competence development Clearer governance	Knowledge/Competence development Clearer governance

Table SE-4. Compilation of the main hindrances for improved soil health and suggested measures to deal with those hindrances from the three Swedish surveys.

Regarding the need for competence development as well as preferred formats for such measures there were great similarities between the groups (Table SE-5). Digital courses about the soil health concept in general combined with tailored trainings and collegial learning could be options to increase awareness and knowledge in soil health issues among key stakeholders.

	Agricultural survey	Forest survey	Urban survey
Soil health topics ranked high for competence development	How to assess soil health Potentials for carbon sequestration Soil biology The soil health concept in general Soil biodiversity	Soil health concept in general Potentials for carbon sequestration Soil biodiversity How to assess soil health Forest management strategies to improve soil health	Soil health concept in general Recycling/Reusing of soils Climate adaptation/ regulation/mitigation How to assess soil health
Preferred format for competence development	Digital courses Field visits Intervision with colleagues Webinars	Digital courses Webinars Intervision with other colleagues Web movies	Digital courses Webinars Web movies Good examples

Table SE-5. Compilation of the soil health topics ranked high for competence development and preferred format for competence development from the three Swedish surveys.

5.6.5. Implication for policy

Based on the three surveys and the discussion above, there are two obvious implications for policy: *i)* a clearer governance in soil health issues is needed, if key actors are to prioritise working with these issues, and *ii)* development of adequate competence development measures to increase soil health awareness among key stakeholders is needed.

The EU Commission statement is clear – unhealthy soils are a big problem in Europe. Influential key actors in the Swedish soil discourse can probably agree with that. However, according to them it was not obvious that the mentioned soil health issues exist in Sweden. Having followed the Swedish soil health discourse in agriculture for approximately six years, it is evident that there are no consensus. Accordingly, key actors do not prioritise to work with and invest in competence development activities on soils from a soil health perspective. However, with a clearer governance indicating that soil health promoting activities are not only relevant but also important to work with in a Swedish context, the situation could change. The EU Commission have increased soil health literacy as one of their goals in the Soil Health and Food Mission. Increased knowledge about as well as awareness of soil health related issues are key factors to be able to make informed and sustainable decisions concerning present and future challenges in agriculture, forest as well as the urban sector. Accordingly, vivid soil health discussions in society will not be possible, until people have basic soil health knowledge.

5.6.6. Key messages

Based on the three surveys, key messages are:

1. Among the Swedish respondents, there is uncertainty about whether the EU Commission's problem formulation regarding poor soil health also applies in Sweden. Among the respondent groups, the urban respondents agree the most with problem formulation in general (see Question 11).
2. Soil health is considered a relevant concept when talking about soil in all three land uses (agricultural soils, forest soils and urban soils).
3. Hitherto, in Sweden the soil health concept is only used within the agricultural sector – although it is still not integrated in advisory services to any larger extent. As key stakeholders find the concept relevant, there is a (non-used) potential for more nuanced conversations about soil issues if the concept got a wider spread.
4. In order for key stakeholders to prioritise working with soil health issues, a clearer governance is needed (for all land uses). As long as the Swedish government and/or key agencies for the different land uses do not advocate for the importance of promoting soil health, and/or include it in steering documents, other issues will be higher on the agendas.
5. Lack of soil health knowledge and awareness is identified as a hindrance for working with improving soil health. In order to involve more key actors in the work with improved soil health (provided that it is also considered important from a Swedish perspective), soil health literacy needs to be improved through adequate trainings adapted to the actor's needs.

Chapter 6. Potentials of improved co-learning on soil health in agriculture

This chapter reports the findings from the qualitative study described in chapters 1.2 and 2.2. The data will be presented as country wise reports; 6.1. Denmark, 6.2. Germany, 6.3. The Netherlands, 6.4. Poland, 6.5. Spain and 6.6. Sweden.

The country reports follow the same structure. In the first part, the participants are described. In the second part, the farmers and advisors view on the soil health concept is presented. The third part consists of SWOT analyses related to soil health learning. Depending on how the data collection was conducted, the perspective of the SWOT analyses somewhat vary between countries. However, all SWOT analysis is about soil health learning - its strengths and weaknesses as well as how it could be developed and what restricts soil health learning. The fourth part presents the potentials for improved co-learning about soil health, while the fifth part describes what the participants believe hinders learning about soil health and what measures could be taken to improve the learning. The last two parts consists of recommendations to policy and key messages.

6.1. Country report: Denmark

Authors: Jorge Federico Miranda Vélez and Lene Hegelund (Aarhus University)

6.1.1. The participants

Two groups of stakeholders were recruited for participation in focus group interviews in the spring of 2024. The first focus group involved five farmer's consultants from four different firms in different regions of Denmark. Both groups were brought together for the purpose of the focus group interview and the participants had no prior knowledge of each other.

The advisor group

The selection of participants for the advisor focus group was based on gender, age and geography. And prioritizing advisors who worked at least partially with non-conventional practices and advisors who had a stated interest in soil quality/health in their online professional profiles, for instance at the advisory firm's website, LinkedIn, etc.

The group consisted of five advisors from four different companies in different regions of Denmark. The participants' gender was split 3 to 2, men to women, and age ranged from mid-30's to mid 50's. A majority were educated as agronomists in the 1990's or 2000's and their experience as advisors ranges from 6 to 31 years. Their advisory focus included primarily organic agriculture (3 participants) and conservation tillage (2 participants). These two practices are the two most prevalent non-conventional currents in Denmark, representing approximately 12% and 26% of the total area of cropland in Denmark, respectively [34, 35].

The farmer group

The farmer focus group consisted initially of five farmers with non-conventional practices and an active interest in soil management and soil health, as determined by the online profiles or via references in farmers' network and during preliminary telephone conversations. Due to scheduling conflicts, the group interview was held with only three participants, while a fourth was interviewed individually afterwards and relayed the main statements and topics from the earlier group interview. One participant was unable to attend at all. The selection of farmers was based on agricultural practice, interest in soil quality/health, gender and age.

The gender among the farmer participants was split equally between men and women in the final interview participants. Their background was varied, including one biologist (MSc. Level), one farmer who attended conventional farmer's education in the 1980's, one farmer who attended an organic farmer's education in the 2000's and a former photographer. Their agricultural practices, as characterized by the participants themselves, included conservation tillage, permaculture, organic agriculture (in the horticultural Market Garden modality) and regenerative agriculture.

6.1.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

Farmers and agricultural advisors that took part in the focus group interviews expressed rather different systems of learning, different priorities for knowledge communication regarding soil health and, importantly, different concepts for soil health.

The participating farmers all expressed similar, quite pragmatic descriptions of a healthy soil. Generally, they described healthy soils as those that allowed for healthy plants and resilient crop performance,

although not explicitly mentioning yields or productivity. During free exchange regarding soil health, the participants focused primarily on a highly functional organic and microbial component in the soil, characterized by a high organic matter content, high microbial biodiversity and a good balance between bacteria and fungi:

"[In my soil, I prioritize] having a greater diversity of microorganisms and especially measuring the ratio between fungi and bacteria and the organic content in the soil." (Market garden farmer, organic.)

For this, they agreed that photosynthesis, in the shape of green plant cover as often as possible, was the most effective driver for organic matter accumulation in the soil.

"I'm very much of the belief that where we create long-term carbon storage, it's through photosynthesis and not so much through [added] organic matter. It [added organic material] is a little bit faster metabolisable. [...] It's a bit like peeing your pants [for warmth], to add organic material, because it also disappears quickly."

Additionally, all participating farmers mentioned the importance of good soil structure, expressed as resilience against compaction and drought, "airiness" and manual workability. Overall, the farmers expressed that they obtain information regarding the state of their soils, including the microbial component, mainly by inference from the growth of their crops, direct observations made in the field and their accumulated experience:

"The goal is for there to be mycelium, i.e. mycorrhiza fungi that can connect the trees to each other. But how we can see that, we can't see that. We have just noticed that when the trees have tapped into the existing [mycelial] network in the soil, there is suddenly a quantum leap in growth, and we see the same thing with the perennial vegetables that grow there." (Permaculture farmer)

Indeed, the importance of "looking at one's soil", meaning fully sensorially observing the changing state of the soil, including by smell, was expressed several times during the interview:

"It's like [permaculture farmer] mentioned before with soil health. We have to look at the soil and that's what it's all about. We have to look at what kind of soil we need; what kind of soil do we want and how do we get it." (Conservation tillage farmer)

"I sometimes take a spade to kind of open up and see if there are any worms going through, how does the ground smell". (Market garden farmer, conventional)

However, at least one of the participating farmers also had a microscope at home for closer study of soil and plant specimens.

The agricultural advisors expressed a similarly pragmatic concept for soil health as the farmers, characterized by properties and processes that allowed for stable and resilient plant production. However, the advisors had a stronger focus on a reduced need for nutrient inputs and the efficient cycling of nutrients in the soil.

"In my world, [a key element of soil health] is the soil's ability to receive and release nutrients." (Conservation Agriculture advisor 1)

"It's also a bit like a soil that can support healthy plant growth without too many inputs... Yes, it can support the plants without us having to provide too many inputs. I think of it as a healthy soil." (Organic advisor 1)

"I think [soil health] has a lot to do with yield stability." (Organic advisor 2)

Biodiversity, in terms of soil microbes and macroscopic fauna as well as a diverse choice of crops, was also mentioned as a component of a healthy soil, related to an increased capacity for self-regulation and for supporting crop health. In other words, a healthy soil was defined largely as a soil that can sustain healthy crops and yield stable crop production with low nutrient imports and minimal agrochemical and mechanical interventions. Finally, increased organic carbon content and better water retention capacity were also mentioned, but not expanded upon.

6.1.3. SWOT analyses on soil health learning

The advisory learning system

The participating advisors described having access to a broad range of resources for acquiring knowledge regarding soil health. Among other things, they highlighted experience-sharing groups with advisors across farms, contact with research institutions, both national and international and, notably, the learning from farmers they advise. Furthermore, the advisors placed their professional role at least partially as an intersection between practical knowledge constantly generated by farmers and farmer CoPs, and formal/theoretical knowledge generated in research institutions.

“For me, it’s like two legs. There’s the one where I learn a lot from the farmers, right? And they learn from each other. And then there’s the whole [research] institutions with the universities and [private research institutes], who also produce a lot [of knowledge], and one is very practical and the other very theoretical. And then it’s like an interaction between the 2. I think that [the interaction] is where I get my knowledge from.” (Organic advisor 1)

In this capacity, the agricultural advisors also expressed that they typically have access to funding for establishing field trials in order to provide farmers with better empirical evidence for ideas obtained through their CoPs.

“We have an experimental program so that we can test some of these things, because sometimes things come up that we have never even thought of, and it’s not enough to just talk about [them], you have to say ‘we’re going to make it an experiment’, and that means there will be some inspiration from the farmers in terms of practical experiments at least.” (Conservation agriculture advisor 2)

Regarding the knowledge sources they observed among farmers, the participating advisors identified social media sources outside Denmark as significant sources for inspiration and new ideas. In turn, they expressed that the new inspiration and knowledge sources used by the farmers also provided them with valuable inputs, which they often applied professionally to some extent.

Figure DK-2 shows a SWOT analysis of the advisory learning system from the advisors’ perspective.

SWOT analysis: The advisory learning system			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisors interested in soil health have access to large amounts of information, both research-based and community-based, and stand in a unique position to provide well-rounded assessments to farmers. • Advisors can serve as facilitators/moderators of knowledge sharing between farmers (e.g., in experience-sharing groups) and add their experience and knowledge to the conversation. • Advisors can serve as filters against politically or economically motivated pressures passing off as advice from different sources (e.g., from seed and agrochemical vendors) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced or shallow communication with farmers when advisory firm has many clients. • Time and effort conflict between helping with regulation and bureaucracy and advising on soil health matters. • Requires considerable economic investment by farmers. • Advice drowned out by information overload online • Advisors aren't effective at changing attitudes of farmers, so the reach of advice is limited to those already interested in soil health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting contact and knowledge sharing between advisors and farmers e.g., by arranging more frequent visits to the farmers and involving other farmers with similar interests/problems. • Increase use of online media, e.g., videos and podcasts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Greenwashing" and co-opting of farmer's intentions towards soil health by economic and political interests. • Policy and regulation that contradicts advisors' judgements regarding soil health, pollution and emissions. • Ongoing centralisation of advisory services into few overly large firms.

Figure DK-2. SWOT analysis: The advisory learning system (from the advisors' perspective).

The farmers' learning system

The participating farmers relied mainly on local CoPs for knowledge, as well as online resources ranging from short-form online posts (e.g., on Instagram) to podcasts created by fellow farmers.

"I listen to a lot of podcasts and I'm also on YouTube and [listen to] audiobooks. But at any rate Instagram, it's really something where we try to share what we ourselves do, but where we also follow a lot of other farms, in USA and in other places in Europe and wherever." (Market garden farmer 1)

"YouTube does a lot, but definitely also books and [our own] experience. Visiting other farmers; I think it's really exciting to visit people who farm on a larger scale." (Permaculture farmer)

Books were mentioned as a source of inspiration and a general ideological foundation for their approach to soil and farming. Mentors were mentioned by two participants as having had important roles as teachers, providers of foundational practical knowledge as well as inspiration and ideology. Finally, all participants seemed to rely or have relied in the past on advice from a single farmer's advisor, whom they judged to be updated and open-minded towards innovative farming practices.

Generally, the participating farmers relied most in other farmers, in both local and international communities, when seeking knowledge for caring for their soil. The principal reason for this was the perception that farmers have a nearer experience of the complexity inherent to agroecosystems, novel farming systems, as well as the needs and interests of other farmers. Advisory services and research institutions were not perceived as innovative or fast enough to provide knowledge on less conventional systems. They, along with the government setting regulations, were seen as too inflexible slow and/or antiquated and out-of-touch with the present-day knowledge and needs among farmers:

"Consultants, that's where you have to sort out who you're talking to. Because consultants [sometimes] also think very traditionally." (Conservation tillage farmer)

“I think we need to work a little more in terms of training our advisors, where they need to get out and away from the theoretical approach, out and see how things work in reality on many different sites.” (Permaculture farmer)

“It’s a little slower to get the experiments into the [academic] institutions, because there is more bureaucracy and things sometimes have to be investigated first before they can be taught and then sometimes it’s already outdated because so many years have passed, so the institution is actually extremely heavy” (Market garden farmer 2)

“Bridges really need to be built, where universities and agricultural associations need to work more on making it so that it isn’t taboo to talk about a different way of cultivating the land.” (Permaculture farmer)

Figure DK-3 shows a SWOT analysis of the farmers’ learning system from the farmers’ perspective.

SWOT analysis: The farmers’ learning system			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical relatable advice, directly relevant for the farmer’s needs. • Practical knowledge, relevant for current and evolving challenges. • Covers the knowledge needs of new and alternative practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of scientific background among CoPs to provide a more solid foundation for the exchange of knowledge. • Lack of insight in differences between farms that could explain effects/lack of effect. • Missed long-term considerations/systematic learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding the knowledge sharing among farmers from practical field-related questions to market, food-chain and value-chain questions to help farmers benefit from new practices beyond the health of their crops and soils. • Creating and expanding spaces, physical and editorial, for meeting and sharing knowledge across CoPs (e.g., special issues in publications, sessions in conferences, events at farms). • Projects for scaling up knowledge and practices from small-scale to large-scale farms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over-reliance on the internet for communication and access to information, with all the communication challenges attached to online interactions. • Lack of follow-through with trials or innovations that require years to verify and possibly won’t work. • Knowledge sharing within and among CoPs is not set up to help with navigating the tight and complex regulatory landscape in Denmark. • Conservatism among practitioners can counteract the innovative learning environment in a CoP.

Figure DK-3. SWOT analysis: The farmers’ learning system (from the farmers’ perspective).

6.1.4. Potentials for joint learning

Both farmers and advisors expressed interest and enthusiasm in bringing the knowledge and learning spheres of farmers, advisors and research institutions closer to each other via the creation of co-learning spaces. Based on the opinions expressed in the interviews, two concrete joint learning opportunities can be highlighted. Firstly, dedicated co-learning sessions at conferences and academic spaces, where a broad range of actors, including farmers, directly discuss innovative soil health-minded practices currently being implemented by farmers. Secondly, themed experience cohorts where farmers and advisors visit members of a CoP regularly over a period of time as they apply innovative practices, allowing both farmers and advisors to apply their expertise and learn from shared experiences.

6.1.5. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

One of the main concerns expressed by participating farmers as hindrances for improved soil health in the future, is the slow speed at which beneficial practices improve soil health, compared to the great

speed at which challenges and crises arise. This is compounded by the farmer's intrinsic reliance on self-trials, which can mean years are wasted with little improvement or even deterioration of the health of their soils. Similarly, they expressed frustration at the slowness and inflexibility of regulators and the institutions that advise them, who they perceive as not moving fast enough to innovate and tackle the fast-evolving soil health challenges they face. This, they generally agreed, makes it particularly difficult for "atypical" or pioneer farms to comply with and/or take advantage of current policies and plans. Finally, they expressed that regulatory frameworks in Denmark are focused primarily on avoiding nutrient pollution and harmful emissions, and do not currently consider soil health. Thus, current regulations often act as hindrances to the application of practices beneficial to soil health.

6.1.6. Implications for policy

The principal implication of the opinions summarized here for policy in Denmark is that a shift in regulation away from pollution mitigation and towards improved soil health is needed. The consensus among the participating farmers was that achieving good soil health and implementing beneficial practices would render pollution-related regulations unnecessary. By optimizing soil use, farmers would require fewer nutrients and agrochemical inputs. Advisors emphasized shifting away from regulations and toward incentives to encourage farmers to adopt new practices that benefit soil health and the broader environment, rather than merely complying to avoid sanctions.

6.1.7. Key messages

1. There is a need and broad willingness for active knowledge-sharing and co-learning between farmers, advisors, the research community and regulators, which can be greatly supported with the establishment of Living Labs.
2. Co-learning among farmers already takes place locally and internationally, with substantial reliance on online resources, including social media. It is therefore necessary not only to create online knowledge-sharing platforms accessible to a broad range of stakeholders, such as the PREPSOIL Knowledge Hub, but to successfully link these with existing online CoP's.
3. Incentives towards beneficial management practices are more likely to promote better soil health in agriculture than punitive regulations focused on limiting emissions/pollution. This would also provide a regulatory scheme where innovative management practices are better included and therefore can be 'rewarded' for their effort.
4. More focus is needed in researching emerging and alternative agricultural practices that can potentially benefit soil health but are not widely known or supported by scientific evidence. This research can be uniquely benefit from Living Lab schemes.

6.2. Country report: Germany

Authors: Keerthi Bandru, Katharina Helming, Lukas Bayer (ZALF)

6.2.1. The participants

The Regional Soil Health workshop within PREPSOIL WP2 took place on the 26.5.2023 in Müncheberg, Brandenburg. Intentionally invited were a broad selection of stakeholders from Brandenburg but also from Germany, who became aware about the workshop through related Soil Mission projects (Nati00ns). The aim was to identify driving forces (future framing conditions), including the advisory service needs for soil protection for the year 2030. Additionally, to the future frame conditions, we asked what soil management activities they would like to take to the future (which practices work well for you today?). This elicited an understanding of what management practices; advisory services currently work well in the farming and agricultural services systems in Brandenburg and might also be practiced in 2030. The discussions focused on the identification of the benefits and shortcomings of the existing management practices, advisory services. Since these discussions align with the topics of the proposed activity, the soil needs assessment workshop content was converted into the structure of the report. The reporting format may vary in comparison to other countries given that the structure of the workshops was different. The workshop format will not allow to write two separate SWOT analysis for the farmer and advisory groups. Therefore, the results will be presented in the combined manner.

The workshop participants

Heterogeneous male dominated farmer group. The group attended the workshop because they did not want a “scientific – only” conversation on the topic and were vehemently sharing their attitudes towards politics and soil. Soil was regarded mainly as a location factor for productivity. They shared their experiences because we asked them for it. They discussed mainly the use of ploughing, glyphosate and productivity gains that they will lose when glyphosate is banned. Table DE-3 and

Figure DE-2 gives the detailed information about the participants of the workshops.

The participants from the workshop represented several stakeholder groups related to advisory services. Farmer consultancy and private companies represented the private actors directly engaged in the advisory services. Whereas, the farmers and farmer associations, water and soil associations represented the users of soil knowledge. The policy and decision makers were from regional and state level that indicated the implementation side of the advisory practices.

Stakeholder	Expertise
Arable farmers (9)	Including intensive, extensive, nature inclusive, and organic arable farming
State policy makers (ministries) (1)	Implementation of national policies at provincial level. Regional development plan, agro-environmental measures, second pillar CAP and projects to meet national policy goals. Topics: climate change, sustainability, water protection, soil protection, rural development, arable agriculture, agroforestry
Private company (2)	Companies working in the agriculture input sector
State administration	Administration of environment protection (soil, water resources) and agriculture
Water and soil associations	Regulate and verify water and soil quality
Nature protection organizations	Improve, recover or maintain nature areas and create corridors that connect nature areas.
Farmer associations (Landesbauernverband Brandenburg) (1)	Represent the interest of their members (farmers)
Farmer consultancy (2)	Private consultancy for farmers on agricultural practices
Citizen/consumers	Consumers of space and food and other ecosystem services including recreation.
Regional development agencies (Leader program) (1)	Seeking sustainable investment in the region
Nature protection parks (1)	Management of nature inclusive agriculture, limited agricultural activity possible in the region
Scientific organizations (5)	Align agricultural production with the provision of ecosystem services

Table DE-3: Stakeholder groups in soil health workshop in Germany.

Figure DE-2: The stakeholder participation in the soil needs assessment workshop, Brandenburg, Germany

5.2.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

Farming in the Brandenburg area is hampered by the area's poor soil quality, which is of young Pleistocene origin and primarily made up of sand and loam. The agricultural area has a large proportion of low-quality soils; about two-thirds are sandy or sandy-loamy soils. This situation, combined with less than average rainfall (less than 579, average 1991-2020), makes agricultural output difficult. One-third is used for crop cultivation, one-third for fodder crops, and one-third for mixed crop and livestock production. Brandenburg encompasses Berlin and is greatly impacted by its position. For example, agricultural property is under constant pressure in Berlin's suburbs due to requests for rededication as

residential land. Furthermore, Berlin residents are increasingly interested in regional food production in the neighbouring state.

Soil health was perceived mainly through the productivity eco-system service among the participants. The German system for soil fertility rates soil from 0-100. Most soils in Brandenburg range between 30-40 points, making the soils relatively poor, in comparison to the rest of Germany. The threat of climate change leads to farmers' eagerness to change their production system to make it resilient for future conditions. Digitalization is seen as a key measure to manage the risks and to introduce such changes by the agronomist community in the region, both in terms of management practices for soils and of consumer-producer communication. Expected impacts may be higher impact due to less dependency on value chain actors, higher soil organic carbon and less erosion by implementing agroforestry, diversified cropping system and crop rotations impact positively soil health such as soil structure, nutrition balance and inhibit soil borne diseases and increase biodiversity.

Ecosystem services are also impacted negatively and have through the large-scale farming activity seen a decrease, especially in soil organic matter and soil fertility. The workshop participants were asked to rank the services provided by soils according to participant's importance. Each participant had 6 votes. The results show that the concern lies with an efficient production and resilient farming practices. While soil played less of a role for regional development.

1. Efficient production (30 votes)
2. Resilience of farms (29)
3. Habitat for biological diversity (24)
4. Climate protection (23)
5. Water retention and quality (21)
6. Regional development (13)

This is one of the reasons why Brandenburg farmers either produce in the organic niche, benefiting from the high prices offered in Berlin for regional, organic food, or use advanced technology, like heavy-duty machinery and intense fertilizer and pesticide use. Moreover, the large farm sizes (250 ha), tenured farmers/corporations dominate agricultural practices in Brandenburg towards the economic profitability. Additionally, 8% of Brandenburg is set aside as a conservation area, which has a significant impact on bird biodiversity.

6.2.3. SWOT analysis on soil health learning

Important for the context in Brandenburg is that agriculture advisor services were privatized in the 1990s. Agricultural extension policy had a significant change as it began to be privatized and commercialized. Politically, the deregulation of the old Soviet economies required more accountability from individuals and businesses. Almost all the stakeholders agreed that the emphasis should be on farm economics when it comes to content of the advisory systems because farmers were thought to be sufficiently knowledgeable about agricultural technologies and the environment was not a concern. Knuth & Knierim (2014) identified the limited applied research activities carried out by Brandenburg's public organizations in combination with a poor dissemination to farmers and advisors as one reason of little exchange of information regarding the knowledge needs of farmers and advisors.

The soil related advisory systems are discussed in the context of overall agriculture with socio economic, environmental and political influence on the soil health. The participants represent the predominantly research, policy and advisory systems. The workshop outcomes were converted into SWOT categories by the researchers. The views might not directly appear in the SWOT format but

having read the responses from the survey and organised the workshop, the expertise was quite helpful. Therefore, the views presented in the SWOT analysis (Table DE-4) shows the various aspects that go beyond the technical dimension of learning systems.

In Brandenburg, the advisory systems are a combination of top-down and bottom up which was dominated by the private actors. The soil health improving measures are influenced by the economic policy and administrative measures. The advisory systems on the other hand, lacks the clear thematic concepts tailored to farmers. The family-owned farmers are consistently interested and willing to pay to receive tailored advisory services to improve the soil health that supports the practices like agro-forestry and organic farming. There is consensus among the stakeholders on the negative impacts of climate change on agriculture productivity and soil health, biodiversity loss. However, the advisory systems do not include these complex topics that also go beyond the farm towards the policy level. One the one hand, farming is becoming less economically viable, and aging population with less interest in changes in the farming practices is affecting. On the other side, demand for the sustainable and healthy products is increasing.

SWOT analysis: Soil health and learning systems in Brandenburg			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge exchange science/practical application • Regional production, supply chain changes • Better equipment of farmers is available to learn • Knowledge among the practitioners on Resilient plant breeds • Agreements on the impacts of climate change, Biodiversity loss • Understanding complex interconnections of soil functions • Family-owned farms is increasingly interested in soil health concepts • Community feeling is very strong among the farmers and farming organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmer's respect is loosing, Appreciation of farmers • Reliability of machine technology is decreasing • Know-how needed to better manage technologies- thematic knowledge • CAP – funding is decreasing – less money for more performance • Financial support for soil improving measures is lacking • Compensation for farmers is poor • maintain diversity in organizational structures of farming enterprises • Better information for political decision-makers is needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willingness to pay for the advisory systems • Changes to trade (fairer), import export • Desire for regional production/ sustainability • Innovation potential in products • Maintain technological standard • Importance of climate change in agricultural debates • Business model changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural and aging population • Land sealing-Farmers resistance • Tenure farming -large size farms • Limited access to advisory systems • Volatility of the input and output markets • Climate change impacts-late freezing • Invasive species (insects, mushrooms, weeds) • Longer vegetation periods • Water retention in decline • Higher quality for a lower price • Less demand for eggs and animal products

Table DE-3: SWOT analysis of soil health and learning systems in Brandenburg, Germany

6.2.4. Potentials for joint learning

The stakeholders have developed a common understanding of the gaps and demands in the advisory systems. The thematic learnings on the following would assist in improving the joint learning among the stakeholders.

- Need more field visits and in-person trainings for sharing best practices
- Soil conservation management practices
- Precision farming
- Small partial farming, fertilizer, pesticides, seeds
- Context adapted agriculture

- Flexible, site adapted soil management
- Soil as crop location factor
- Self - determination of farmers, Develop: Agri-Photovoltaics, Agroforestry
- Areas for the retention of water

Innovation activities should focus on the one hand on the knowledge transfer system in Brandenburg, as it has been described as severally impacted after reunification. The farming system in Brandenburg and its focus on efficient production in large field sizes will increasingly rely on digitalisation and robotics. This is made possible by large agricultural enterprises who have the financial capital for investment. Nonetheless, this future is one of many depending on the political framing conditions of the future, smaller scale farming may become more prominent again. Now the system is still affected by its past decisions and strong path dependency due to field and farm structure. The circumstances limit self-determination and effect management decisions of today, especially in terms of spatial organisation.

6.2.5. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Despite their efforts in policy advocacy on soil health, there is room for enhancement in effectively influencing subsidy-related discussions and ensuring that the voices of farmers and sustainability experts are adequately represented. Additionally, while existing educational programs have been valuable, there is a need for more practical, low-threshold training programs tailored to the specific needs of farmers practicing organic farming and agro-forestry. Similarly, while advisory systems have expanded educational programs and facilitated knowledge transfer, there is a need for more practical, low-threshold training programs and regional best-practice demonstrations tailored to the local agricultural and soil context. Furthermore, while advisors play a crucial role in raising awareness and engaging with policymakers, there is a lack of focus on training advisors in advocacy and communication skills and building alliances with relevant stakeholders.

Participants expected training on the regionalised agriculture management practices. These soil management practices should be included in the advisory trainings so that the water retention capacity of soils may be increased or stabilized, by implementing no-till and increasing better soil structures. Specific micro-climates on and landscape level should be considered to adapt to different climate conditions. Additionally, a diversified product portfolio may offer an adaptation strategy, which can also meet changing societal consumption preferences and diets. Furthermore, it could protect against price shocks, when a price of a crop comes drops unexpectedly due to external influences. This may occur when adapted value chain forms, primary products which are processed into food may provide one source of income. Reconnecting the urban-rural linkages is of special relevance in this regard for Brandenburg as Berlin is in its centre (Zasada, 2012; Fries, 2020; Vincente-Vincente et al., 2023)

As a response to the lack or limitations of the knowledge transfer and diffusion in the privatized agricultural extension service (Münchhausen; Häring, 2012), the Climate change Adaptation Brandenburg Berlin Network was created and ran until 2015. The aim was to ensure the sustainability of the land and water use in Brandenburg. However, this response failed with the end of the project, highlights the need for continuing activity. Joint learning processes were in the forefront and knowledge on climate change is distributed and show the need for such as continued practices with long term learning capacities. Closely related to knowledge sharing platforms are activities such as the Digital Agricultural Knowledge and Information System (DAKIS), assigning new roles to advisors, such as facilitator and intermediaries and the role of digitalization in agriculture (Mouratiadou et al., 2023).

The historical impact of misguided advice and implementation challenges in German agriculture necessitates a critical reappraisal of past recommendations by advisory systems. Transparency and accountability are crucial in acknowledging past mistakes and communicating the rationale behind new recommendations effectively. Economic pressures and high lease prices in Brandenburg pose significant challenges to soil health, requiring advisory systems to provide tailored support and promote long-term leasing arrangements conducive to sustainable management practices. Monocultures and intensive cultivation practices prevalent in agriculture demand proactive promotion of diverse crop rotations and specific erosion prevention strategies by advisory services. To bridge the gap between research and practice, advisory systems must provide hands-on support for implementing soil health measures and customize advice to the unique conditions of each farm.

6.2.6. Implications for policy

In Germany, agricultural advisory systems have made significant strides in advocating for sustainable soil management practices and providing support to farmers. These systems have been instrumental in redesigning subsidy frameworks to prioritize soil health and offering financial planning services to facilitate the transition to sustainable practices. Moreover, they have played a crucial role in expanding educational programs, bridging the gap between research and practice, and raising public awareness about the importance of soil health.

To enhance the agricultural advisory systems and soil health concepts, several key recommendations are proposed. Firstly, there is a need for greater emphasis on interdisciplinary collaboration within advisory systems to provide tailored advice on soil health. Strengthening partnerships with research institutions will ensure the rapid translation of scientific developments into practice. Additionally, fostering farmer networks to facilitate peer-to-peer learning and continuous competence development for advisors are essential for staying updated with techniques in soil health management.

6.2.7. Key messages

1. There is strong consensus among the stakeholders about the poor quality of agricultural soils in Germany and their reasons.
2. While the knowledge about the soil health concepts is high, the action and the access to advisory services is a bit less accessible in Germany.
3. Science-policy-society interactions need to be established or strengthened to improve the efficient transfer the knowledge.
4. The challenges related to national and European policies, mainly economical, administrative needs to be integrated in the governance of soil advisory systems.

6.3. Country report: The Netherlands

Author: Amanda Matson and Hanneke Heesmans (WUR)

6.3.1. The participants

In the Netherlands, both farmers and advisors were asked for their views on soil health and joint learning. Information was gathered from a group of farmers had known one another for approximately 20 years. The main trigger for them to begin exchanging with one another was how to manage soil fertility, and topics around soil fertility continue to be their main focus of discussion. The farmer discussions were focused on the soil health concept and SWOT analysis for learning systems (6.3.2 and 6.3.3), but did not include a further exploration of hindrances to soil health and potential measures to address them.

Information was gathered from individual advisors, as it was difficult to organize a group meeting. The advisors who shared their views were closely linked to the research community, so we do recognize that there may be a bias with respect to the knowledge background of these interviewees, who likely do not represent the views across the entire advisory community in the Netherlands. Nevertheless, they were able to provide some advisor perspectives, and were able to go into more detail than the farmer group. In addition to providing input on the soil health concept and SWOT analysis for learning systems (6.3.2 and 6.3.3), advisors provided additional perspectives on joint learning, hindrances to soil health and potential measures to address perceive hindrances (6.3.4 and 6.3.5).

6.3.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

In agriculture, there are two main perspectives on soil: soil fertility and soil health. Soil fertility is defined as the ability of soil to sustain plant growth, whereas soil health is the ability of soil to sustain productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems. When asked about these two perspectives, farmers and advisors agreed with both definitions. However, on a scale of 1 to 7, with 1 being exclusively soil fertility and 7 being exclusively soil health, farmers identified their perspectives on soil as falling between 1 and 3, whereas advisors were between 5-6. In explaining their perspective, farmers felt that they did not actually have the freedom to have their 'own view'. Instead, they felt they had to adopt the view that allowed them to generate an income, and saw soil fertility as being more relevant to the business side of the farm. Some farmers did like the soil health emphasis on the full range of ecosystem services, but again noted that such a view had to fit within a business model. Although advisors identified more strongly than farmers with the soil health perspective, they made similar comments about the need for a pragmatic soil perspective in which farm income was still prioritized.

Both groups were asked about sources of information/inspiration for learning about soil health, including support systems, milestones and critical events that affected their learning journey. Farmers noted that other farmers, agricultural networking and field visits from advisors were all important sources of information, and emphasized how important it was for them to have practical information on practices that were relevant for their farm. They noted that seeing how things worked in the field was one of the strongest motivators for change. A specific anecdote related how some farmers had commented on no-till fields, describing them as looking 'not clean' and requiring ploughing. However, the negative views changed to interest when, after heavy rain, those fields were not waterlogged, and the farmer could enter the fields to start sowing weeks before their neighbors. Advisors also emphasized the importance of experiential learning, naming field visits, soil/crop inspections,

discussions with farmers and maps/models as preferred sources for inspiration, specifically mentioning how important it was to have practical rather than just theoretical information.

6.3.3. SWOT analyses on soil health learning

Advisory services

In discussions with farmers and advisors, two types of learning systems were the focus: peer-to-peer learning, in which farmers learn together in an information-sharing, experience-rich, local learning system, and structured/formalized learning through advisory services, anchored in research. Advisors were asked to assess advisory services from a farmer's perspective. Farmers were asked for their perspectives on both types of learning systems. Table NL-4 summarizes how farmers and advisors view advisory services with respect to learning about soil health issues.

While farmers generally recognize advisory services as having access to detailed, up-to-date soil knowledge, their main interest when discussing advisory services was the perception that advisors are often biased due to commercial interests. Discussion was predominantly about how to recognize 'commercial' advice and how to access 'objective' advice. Advisors provided much more detail about the type of information that advisory services can provide to farmers, with an emphasis on advice for dealing with emerging issues, such as climate change. However, they also recognized the potential for biased advice, as well as the need for advisory services to share knowledge with each other and be better equipped to provide context-specific information.

SWOT analysis of advisory services – from farmers' and advisors' perspectives			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers: • Understanding of soil processes and source of current, research-based knowledge on soil management practices to improve soil health. • ----- • Advisors: • For non-soil farmers (i.e. dairy), they have little basic soil knowledge, so you can show them a lot about their soil on a field visit and give them perspective about what they can do to improve. • Can provide knowledge on how to deal with new climate change challenges, increasing salinity, re-wetting of peatlands, shifting from traditional to biological/extensive farming systems, etc. • How to monitor things and using the data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers: • Lack of trust. Advisors may be giving biased or one-sided information, as advisory is often linked with company sales and targets. • ----- • Advisors: • Fragmented services. In the past, there was one umbrella, they had different knowledge under one roof. • Lack of compulsory education. There is not a lot of time investment for keeping advisors up to date with the latest knowledge, due to the commercial focus. • Always talk in a general sense and the farmer wants to know about their field. • National pressure and how to deal (negative framing). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers: • There is no governmental extension in NL; every advisor visiting the farm is paid by the farmer. How can advisors be 'objective' and how, as a farmer, can you recognize 'commercial' advice? • ----- • Advisors: • Let different commercial companies make agreements on how to exchange knowledge. Agree on a number of hours to exchange, ask questions, etc. • Framing (so farmers don't feel like they are targets). • Advisors serves need to prove their advice is independent (perhaps a label). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers: • Biased information (advisory linked with fertilizer/pesticide company sales and targets). • ----- • Advisors: • Have to make money. There is so much to learn and not enough dedicated time to do it. • Farmers have a lot to deal with, too often an academic exercise. • Too much, too soon, too complicated – don't put researchers at the front. • Miscommunication - use of words, good words are important, use farmer's words.

Table NL-4. SWOT analysis of advisory services for soil health from the perspective of farmers and agricultural advisors in the Netherlands. (What strengths do advisory service have?; What are the weaknesses of advisory services?; How could advisory service change to better support soil health?; What are the main threats to learning about soil health issues?)

Farmer co-learning

Farmers were generally positive about the benefits of peer-to-peer learning, emphasising context-specific topics, flexibility (both with time and topics) and having live interaction. However, they were still missing some practical aspects (i.e. in-field learning) and follow-up. One key barrier to knowledge was identified as the lack of guidance when dealing with the overwhelming amount of information available. This is consistent with advisors' observations that a threat to learning about soil health is inundating farmers with too much and too detailed information.

SWOT analysis: Farmers' learning system			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The (evening) meetings are flexible (in time and presence required) and the topics diverse. • Focus is on soil (fertility) as a general topic, but with a group of farmers together, often during coffee breaks, many more (technical and practical) issues can be discussed. • The live interaction with fellow farmers is the most important part of these meetings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no learn-and-apply option: topics are discussed, but it stays only at the discussion level; there is no field-learning aspect (meetings of that type can take place with other organisations, but are not necessarily done with this group). • The group dynamic may not always have the learning attitude you seek, due to different interests and personalities. This influences how much information you take up. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is little focus on 'next steps for learning' for each individual farmer; the focus is more on hearing about the latest fellow developments in soil fertility, and how fellow farmers practice their farm management. Practices that sounds interesting and relevant can be taken back home to apply/test or think about. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group discussions often get sidetracked to common threats (very often regulations and restrictions) that a farmer alone cannot influence by him/herself (governmental level). • Dutch farmers are considered some of the most educated farmers in the world, but they do not often feel like that. They feel like they have to search through available knowledge and make interpretations themselves for what can be useful on their farm.

Table NL-5. SWOT analysis of co-learning systems for soil health from the perspective of farmers in the Netherlands. (*What are the strength of your learning group?; Are there any weaknesses to this kind of peer-to-peer learning?; How could your learning system be improved?; Does anything inhibit your learning potential?*)

6.3.4. Potentials for joint learning

Co-learning between advisors and peer-to-peer farmer groups was seen as a positive opportunity from the advisor perspective. Peer farmer groups often have an advisor that they are in contact with, which was seen as a win-win for both sides. The role of advisors in this case would be to provide farmers with specific information that they requested (addressing, as identified above, the 'overwhelming amount of knowledge' barrier). At the same time, the advisors could use such a group as a 'thermometer' to understand the atmosphere within the farmer community and to hear first-hand, current questions/issues from the field. Other advisors, who don't have this direct contact with 'pioneer' farmers, interacted with such individuals at organized meetings or workshops. Though a step removed from the specific context, these interactions were still seen as valuable for advisors to hear farmers' experiences and to exchange information.

One concrete suggestion from an advisor to capitalize on the potentials of co-learning, was to organize meetings including farmers, nature organizations, provinces and municipalities all together, to discuss all types of questions and issues. The idea would be for the group to come together to address a specific problem (i.e. working together on a practical case), bringing theoretical knowledge together with local knowledge, so each participant had something to contribute, bringing energy to the discussions, and a high potential for creative solutions.

Specific suggestions from advisors for how to support peer-to-peer farmer learning groups were focused on the knowledge barrier. Advisors generally thought that addressing lack of knowledge (possibly linked with too much information) was to provide a central hub which provided a way for farmers to easily access high-quality, trusted, up-to-date information (on the specific issue of importance to them). This could be a digital hub and/or a connected network of specialists, organized and available to address issues within their area of specialization. This need for trusted, high-quality information is consistent with the views shared in an EU-wide workshop of agricultural advisors carried out as part of the EJP SOIL program (<https://ejpsoil.eu>). In that workshop, two key messages from advisors across Europe were the need for context-specific information (i.e. not just general, theoretical knowledge) and the need for support in ‘sorting through’ all of the available information, to ensure decisions were made based on trusted, high-quality research.

6.3.5. Hindrances for improved soil health

When asked about general hindrances and measures to improved soil health, advisors identified a number of issues, consistent with the results of the survey (Chapter 5.3). In the agricultural survey, four themes were identified: attitude, knowledge, markets and policies. In discussions with advisors, only attitude from that list was not specifically mentioned.

The knowledge system was most strongly criticized. While there is extensive soil and agricultural research carried out in the Netherlands, advisors perceive knowledge generation as poorly organized, with scattered results, lacking an overview, and ultimately resulting in a loss of both energy and information. Further to that, advisors specifically note that they do not know where to find data, and see lack of access to good data (defined as context-specific, practical and user-friendly) as a key barrier to improving soil health.

Issues with markets and policies were also mentioned. It was noted that efforts to improve soil health directly impact profits, as shifts from ‘intensive management’ to ‘sustainable management’ were not rewarded by current markets. Instead, there is conflicting and unclear legislation, with subsidies that last only a couple of years, which is not enough to build a business. It was also noted that there is a lack of financing for pilots, although pioneer farmers in particular may be interested in opportunities – a view that was also reflected in the survey responses from Chapter 5.3, where several respondents expressed interest in experimentation but experienced a lack of support for innovative field trials.

6.3.6. Implications for policy

Although measures to address issues with the knowledge system were seen as a positive step toward improving soil health, advisors generally felt that other measures that needed to happen were at the market/policy level. Key changes that were identified as necessary were: a long-term vision for agricultural subsidies, addressing legislative conflicts and providing stability within the legislative framework, and working within the value chain, imposing rules on companies that farmers supply to, while exploring the potential for ecosystem service payments. These are all consistent with survey results from the agricultural and urban sectors. Both groups identified a need for appropriate policies and for markets that prioritize soil health.

6.3.7. Key messages

The outcomes of the farmer and advisor discussions were consistent with the survey outcomes from Chapter 5.3. Therefore, key messages from Chapter 5.3 are shown here, with additional information based on the interview results.

1. Synthesize existing knowledge in an organized way and use this to both disseminate information and identify knowledge gaps for future research. Make knowledge available in a clear way to assist decision-making about when/where to prioritize soil health, possible through a well-organized, interactive, online platform.
2. Provide access to high-quality, context-specific data/information about soil management options, preferably as good (local) examples and/or through the facilitation of networks for interaction (consistent with the mandate of living labs).
3. Support the creation of market-based options (i.e. for the payment of ecosystem services), which include companies and consumers in the responsibility for maintaining soil health.
4. Simplify the complexity of the agricultural policy framework and ensure soil-related policies are helping rather than hindering changes toward soil health.

6.4. Country report: Poland

Authors: Karolina Świątek and Grzegorz Siebielec (IUNG)

6.4.1 The participants

The farmer group

Due to problems with directly reaching a group of farmers that would create a mutual learning system in Poland, we had to choose another strategy. Instead of making interviews, we made an online survey using Google Forms.

A significant number of farmers were contacted through Agricultural Advisory Centers, and 58 farmers from various regions in Poland participated in the survey. The survey was conducted on the basis of 19 questions asked, and the answers were collected collectively in the form of charts. The surveyed group of farmers was characterized by considerable diversity, resulting from the type of production they carry out, the region in which they operate, the equipment and technology they use, as well as the degree of knowledge they possess. The diverse research group made it possible to gather very reliable information on farmers' perceptions of soil health. An overwhelming majority of farmers who participated in the survey perceived and understood the difference between soil fertility and soil health. Yet for the rest of the respondents, additional clarification of these differences would be necessary. In terms of which soil perspective that is closer to farmers own perspective on soil, the vast majority declared that it is the focus on cultivation and the productive function of soils. A smaller proportion of farmers agreed with the prospect of focusing on a broad range of soil ecosystem services.

Almost all of the farmers in Poland who took part in survey rated advisory services as well or very well, and used advisory services in soil health matters or planned to use them. Almost all of those who took part in the survey confirmed that it is possible to exchange experiences together on the advisor-farmer and farmer-farmer lines. Farmers also declared that they were willing to share their farming experiences with others. The most common measures to support soil health improvements on farm level were: using crop rotation, applying compost and manure and performing regular soil analysis. The biggest obstacles to improving the health of agricultural soils mentioned by the farmers were lack of awareness about soil health, limited access to advanced technologies and insufficient financial support from the public sector. Farmers suggested the following as countermeasures to reduce emerging obstacles: organizing training for farmers, creating funds to support agriculture and promoting good agricultural practices.

The advisor group

A physical workshop with advisors was held on 18-19 April 2024 on soil health related issues. The organisation of the workshop was linked to other projects carried out under Horizon Europe: NBSOIL, PREPSOIL and NUTRI-CHECK NET. The survey involved 26 advisors from all over Poland. They represented Agricultural Advisory Centres from each province. As part of the PREPSOIL part, the participants filled a paper survey questionnaire containing 12 questions.

The group of advisors who took part in the workshop had different length of work in the profession. Among the participants, there were advisors with more than 10 years of work experience, as well as those who had less than one year of experience as an advisor. As the workshop was attended by persons working in Agricultural Advisory Centres, the vast majority worked at a public sector institution. A significant proportion of the advisors participating in the survey had a university degree (23 of 26 advisors, while 3 had a secondary education. It is worth noting that in Poland, having a

university degree is sometimes necessary to apply in public sector institutions, including advice centres. Persons with secondary education very rarely work in the public sector in Poland. Because agricultural advisory centres in Poland are public organisations, the services they offer are also included in the public sector.

In the questionnaire, the advisors stated that the soil health aspects that they are the most interested to learn more about are management strategies to improve soil health and methods to assess soil health. Soil biodiversity and nutrient leaching were also important aspects. Based on the data collected, it was concluded that agricultural advisors in Poland are less interested to learn more about soil pollution, erosion, desertification and soil compaction.

In terms of sources for information and inspiration related to soil health issues, the advisors preferred courses and training followed by experience exchange from other agricultural professionals. They also readily turned to agricultural professional publications and valued going on field trips and reading research reports.

6.4.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

Regarding the view of soil as perceived by the participating farmers and advisors, it should be noted that both groups perceived a difference between the concepts of soil fertility and soil health – although additional clarification of both aspects was sometimes needed. It is worth mentioning this difference when organising trainings, workshops, educational materials, to raise awareness on the issue. Since agriculture in Poland is one of the key branches of the country's economy, advisors, as well as farmers, identify more with the production perspective of soil as the main ecosystem service. This is mainly due to the desire to maximise yields and profits obtained from agriculture. A small group of respondents identified with the perspective of focusing on a broad range of soil ecosystem services (soil health) as compliant with their own view on soil.

6.4.3. SWOT analyses on soil health learning

Making a SWOT analysis on advisory service was one of the activities during the workshop organized with advisors. The result of that activity is shown in Table PL-5. A SWOT analysis was also compiled based on four questions in the online survey directed to farmers. That SWOT concerned the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to their own learning system from the perspective of a farmer (Table PL-6).

As can be seen, the two SWOT analyses are very similar. This is mainly due to the fact that the two groups/learning communities know common problems that arise in local, regional and national areas (they are almost identical). For collaborative learning mechanisms to function smoothly, it is necessary to minimize emerging threats and eliminate weaknesses. It is also necessary to introduce appropriate mechanisms, especially in the financial aspect, so that these systems can develop efficiently.

SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil issues from the advisors' perspective

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High accessibility and geographical distribution of advisors to farmers • Complex advisory service • Central funding of advisory institutions • Interaction of advisors and farmers with research institutions • Constant development of advisory services • High knowledge of individual farms with their specificities • Available training to reduce nutrient losses, build fertility, secure humus • Good knowledge of local conditions by advisors in the region • Possibility of obtaining additional direct support measures for agronomic measures that take soil conservation into account • Efforts to increase yields • Willingness to reduce use of fertilisers and plant protection products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Little interest of some farmers in more sustainable practice • Underestimation of advisors' knowledge • Poor up-to-date knowledge of how the soil works and insufficient knowledge of the plant-soil link • Uncertainties related to what to test and how to do it? • Lack of advisors dedicated to soil issues • Farmers closed to change • Still limited availability of tools and access to soils information • Extensive agricultural advisory administration • Soil testing available does not address important soil processes • High fragmentation of agricultural parcels in Poland • Constantly evolving legislation • Age of advisors • High number of advisors' tasks • Relying on outdated data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in soil projects • Development of private companies providing professional soil advice • Availability of soil and agricultural maps to support professional advice • Awareness raising of farmers • Field trips with farmers to assess soil health/use, training of farmers by advisors on improving soil health • Specialisation of advisors in soil health • Opportunities to help financially vulnerable farms • Provision of tools (programmes) for advisors on soil counselling • The messages on soil management are comprehensive • More experiences and examples showing tangible effects, financial results, demonstrations (Lighthouses) of good practice directly on farm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in incentives to farmers • Increasing requirements reduces interest in soil health • Adding bureaucracy for farmers • Lack of specific specialisation of advisors • Farmers' reluctance to take up programmes - No immediate financial effect for the farmers • Time-wasting procedures discouraging farmers • Theory not supported by practice • No funding for soil advisors • Declining staff in advisory and increase in new tasks • Lack of time during the year for education for advisors and farmers • Too many new practices required at the same time • Too many soils in corporate leases and little influence of advisors on the practice used • Uncertain situation in agriculture, Weak profitability of production • Strong pressures from companies selling products

Table PL-5. SWOT analysis on advisory services about soil issues from the advisors' perspective. Developed during an advisor workshop.

SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil issues from the farmers' perspective

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisors' level of education and knowledge and practice, assistance in decision-making which makes opportunity for knowledge transfer from the advisory network • Increased level of general awareness among farmers • Demonstration of advantages in the use of ecoscheme • Existing exchange of experience • Consultation with science available to some extent • Good practice examples available across farmers • Cooperation between farmer and advisor exists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scarce availability and lack of structured dissemination services • Insufficient practical experience among farmers • Difficulties to follow regulatory changes • Lack of time to dedicate to field visits • Lack of up-to-date data on climate change • Lack of experts in the respective fields regarding production or soil management • Poor funding for advisory services and lack of funding for self-learning • Narrow specialization in a particular field 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing demand for advisory services • Expanding knowledge, exchange of information useful for agricultural farm management • Funding of practical forms of learning services from the Ministry of Agriculture • Information provided in a "nutshell" • Improving the efficiency of the farm, thanks to analyses - demonstrating their advantages • More online opportunities • Organization of training courses and field demonstrations • More training for specialists and more contact with specialists • Personal meetings at the centers. Cooperation with an advisor, acquisition of information, participation in workshops • Continuous access to current news and the opportunity to consult and solve the problem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive commercialization of consulting. Competitive companies - focused on profit • Bad economic situation in agriculture • Fear of using services • Too much bureaucracy • Lack of subsidies and therefore lack of opportunity to apply and help with applications. • Very few persons want to educate themselves in the direction of agriculture • Increasingly older advisory staff

Table PL-6. SWOT analysis on advisory service from the farmers' perspective. Compiled from answers in an online questionnaire.

6.4.4. Potential for joint learning

Based on the data collected through the SWOT analyses, the following conclusions can be presented. The potential for mutual learning between both groups of advisors and farmers exists, but for it to be effective, it is necessary to strive to minimize the existing weaknesses and limit the emerging threats presented by both research groups. It is also important to remember that despite the identified difficulties, there is also enormous potential and willingness for cooperation. It is worth mentioning the significant knowledge of advisors and their constant improvement of their competences and qualifications. As an element of capacity building, it should also be emphasized that there are advisors in every commune. In this respect, it is crucial to expand the advisory staff so that farmers feel supported by the advisor's presence. In order to fully exploit the joint learning potential of both groups, efforts should be made to increase the financing of this sector for capacity-building activities, and it is also worth striving to increase the importance of the counselling profession so that this profession is attractive on the labour market in Poland. An undoubted advantage and opportunities in the field of consulting is participation in various types of training and workshops conducted by many organizations, including those increasingly organized online and addressed to a large group of recipients. The key to building the joint learning capacity of a group of advisors and farmers is to focus activities on increasing awareness of soil health.

6.4.5. Hindrances and measures for improves soil health

Based on the information collected, it should be concluded that the greatest threat to the common potential is an overly developed administrative system that slows down the work of advisors, as well as advisors leaving their jobs and showing little interest in working in such a position. Despite the declaration of availability of advisors, it should be borne in mind that it might be inappropriately distributed throughout the country, which means that not all farmers may have quick and easy access to such services. The limitation that may have a significant impact on the potential of joint learning of both groups is largely financial constraints, the current bad economic situation in agriculture, constantly introduced changes in the law and the lack of specific specializations in consulting, including specializations typically in soil matters. Other identified weaknesses and possible threats include the fact that agricultural advisors in Poland do not have specific specializations, including soil specializations. Undoubtedly, if the human resources of Agricultural Advisory Centers in Poland included specialists dealing only with soil-related issues, it would certainly have a significant impact on increasing the potential for joint learning, thus striving to jointly improve soil health. The threats that appear from advisors include the lack of interest on the part of the farmer, resulting from the fact that he sometimes does not directly notice the financial effects of the implemented activities. Both groups defined the advisory offered by the profit companies as linked with sale of means of production to some extent as a threat.

6.4.6. Implications for policy

Based on workshops conducted with advisors and individual interviews with farmers in order to determine the potential for joint learning, the actions that need to be taken include:

- Increasing administration awareness aimed at improving soil health (not only agricultural soils).
- Social campaigns to build overall soil health capacity, easily accessible to citizens.
- Launching appropriate financial mechanisms aimed at training agricultural advisors on soil health and co-creation and demonstrate of best practice to local conditions. Especially management options financially effective shall be better demonstrated.
- Organization and implementation of campaigns to improve soil health as an element of support for farmers.

6.4.7. Key messages

1. There is a strong need to increase financial mechanisms aimed at improving soil health at the national, regional, local and individual levels – farmers.
2. There is high potential for knowledge transfer from advisory to farmers and co-learning, however the existing advisory systems shall be optimised to increase their focus and efficiency, and the eco-learning and demonstration activities shall be structured and supported.
3. Creating educational programs and demonstration networks is highly demanded to share examples of benefits from soil health, including financial issues.

6.5. Country report: Spain

Authors: Pablo Gómez (INIA-CSIC), Jose Luis Pita-Romero (INIA-CSIC), Iván Sánchez (EEZ-CSIC) and Ana Segura (EEZ-CSIC)

6.5.1. The participants

The farmer group

The farmers' session included seven participants, mostly male, with six men, and one woman. The age distribution among these participants showed a concentration in the more experienced age group, with five individuals aged between 46-60 and two in the 30-45 age range. This demographic profile suggests a mature group with a wealth of experience in farming.

The participants are involved in specific agricultural sectors, focusing on the eco-production of fruit trees by one farmer and the cultivation of olive trees by the remaining six. The olive tree cultivation is further distinguished by the methods used, including integrated production or traditional production. This indicates a specialization in tree cultivation, with a significant emphasis on sustainable and environmentally conscious farming practices, especially for the individual focused on eco-production.

Regarding education, there's a mix of backgrounds among the participants. Some hold university degrees, indicating a formal educational background in potentially relevant fields, while others do not have specific formal education in agriculture. This mix suggests a combination of theoretical knowledge and practical, hands-on experience within the group.

The years in professional capacity among the farmers are quite varied, ranging from 5 to 22 years. This diversity in experience levels (from relatively new newcomers to highly experienced veterans) could contribute to a rich exchange of knowledge and perspectives, especially in discussions around evolving practices in eco-production and integrated or traditional olive cultivation.

The primary motive behind organizing the farmers' session was the recognized need to exchange information among participants. The farmers began to share their experiences mainly due to the need to exchange information, a fundamental requirement in the agricultural sector where practices and challenges are as varied as the crops cultivated.

The farmers discussed a range of soil-related issues that are crucial for the sustainability and productivity of their operations. These include erosion, strategies and practices to minimize soil loss and degradation; vegetal covers, the implementation of cover crops to protect and enhance soil health; pruning waste application, utilizing waste from pruning as a resource for soil improvement; compost production and application, creating and using compost to enrich soil fertility and structure; herbicides application, the impact of herbicide use on soil health and strategies for its management; organic matter, the importance of organic matter in maintaining soil quality and supporting crop growth; and PAC requirements, adhering to policy and regulatory requirements, likely referring to the Common Agricultural Policy (PAC) in the European context, which may include stipulations for soil management and conservation practices.

The farmers communicate through in-person interactions with family, friends, and neighbours, attend informal and organized meetings, and use WhatsApp groups to exchange information and share experiences.

The advisors

The advisors' session involved a group of seven participants, characterized by a gender distribution of three males and four females. The participants were divided into two age groups: four individuals aged between 30-45 and three individuals aged between 46-60. All advisors come from professional backgrounds in research and advisory services related to cooperatives, and they all hold university degrees.

This session was marked by the diversity of its participants, not only in terms of their demographic characteristics but also in their professional focus areas. The advisors can be broadly categorized into two groups based on their primary activities: those who are engaged in research and those who work directly with farmers. Among these advisors, there is a further specialization in terms of their focus on agricultural practices. Some advisors are dedicated to implementing sustainable protocols, indicating a commitment to environmentally friendly and sustainable agricultural methods. In contrast, others concentrate on the application of pesticides, pointing towards a focus on crop protection and yield optimization. Additionally, a notable aspect of this group is the involvement of some advisors with demonstrative farms. These advisors are responsible for managing these farms, which serve as practical, real-world examples of best practices in agriculture.

The advisors were brought together by a shared goal of improving agricultural practices and addressing challenges at the farm level through multidisciplinary expertise. They started to share their experiences to pool knowledge and offer comprehensive solutions to complex agricultural challenges, taking advantage of their diverse competencies.

The soil issues discussed by the advisors include soil health, fertility management, sustainable soil management practices, soil degradation, and conservation techniques. They communicate through meetings, workshops, field visits, email, online forums, and specialized agricultural advisory apps, combining face-to-face and digital communication methods.

6.5.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

Farmers' perception of soil health reveals a complex intersection between the concepts of fertility and health, which are often confused. Most consider a healthy soil and a soil with sustained fertility to be the same, highlighting a lack of clear distinction between these two critical aspects of soil management. This confusion underscores a prevalent reality in the agricultural realm: when the soil degrades, not only is its health affected, but its fertility as well. This emphasizes the interdependence between soil health and its ability to be productive and fertile over the long term. However, despite the recognition of the importance of soil health, soil fertility and productivity are prioritized by farmers. This focus reflects the nature of farming as a business rather than a hobby, emphasizing the need to keep the land not only healthy but also productive.

The concept of soil health has not yet had a significant impact on their practices for the moment. Farmers are beginning to become aware of this concept, mainly through the Common Agricultural Policy (PAC).

The perspective of advisors on soil and soil health is nuanced and multifaceted, reflecting an understanding that encompasses both the ecological aspects of soil health and the pragmatic needs of agricultural practice. They recognize the fundamental difference between fertile soil and healthy soil, where fertile soil is directly associated with the capability to support crop growth, and healthy soil encompasses a broader set of characteristics that include, but are not limited to, fertility. Advisors acknowledge that the definition of healthy soil varies depending on its intended use. In the context of

agriculture, a soil must not only be alive and maintain ecological functions but also be productive and fertile to be considered healthy. This recognition underlines the importance of productivity in the agricultural context, where the primary goal is to sustainably achieve high yields to support human activities.

This understanding has significantly influenced their practice. Advisors now approach soil management with a holistic perspective that seeks to balance productivity with sustainability. They are keenly aware of the necessity for soil to be productive enough to meet farmers' needs, which often requires integrating practices that enhance soil fertility while maintaining or improving soil health. This balance is crucial in ensuring that soil can support farming activities over the long term without degrading its health or fertility.

The concept of healthy soil is acknowledged to be variable, influenced by different land uses, edaphoclimatic conditions, and local particularities. This variability has led advisors to adopt a more tailored approach to soil management, considering the specific needs and conditions of each site rather than applying a one-size-fits-all solution. Economic considerations also play a critical role in defining what constitutes a healthy soil, as the feasibility of adopting certain practices often depends on their cost-effectiveness and impact on profitability. Although high biodiversity is commonly associated with healthy soil, advisors recognize that, in the context of agriculture, high biodiversity is not always necessary for a soil to be considered healthy. Instead, there is a need to find a compromise between maintaining a soil's health and ensuring it remains productive. This compromise is pivotal in agricultural practices, where the goal is to sustain both the soil's fertility and its ecological functions over time.

One of the key attributes of a healthy soil in agriculture, as understood by advisors, is its resiliency. A resilient soil can withstand and recover from the impacts of its management, including the use of fertilizers, pesticides, and mechanical tillage. This resilience is indicative of a soil where fertility does not decrease over time while employing sustainable practices, ensuring long-term sustainability and productivity of agricultural lands.

6.5.3. SWOT analyses on soil health learning

The SWOT analysis on advisory services about soil health, based on conversations with farmers, reveals several insights (Table SP-4). Strengths include the fact that most advisory services are provided by cooperatives or associations, indicating an established support network for farmers. However, weaknesses include instances where commercial advisors mislead farmers with the aim of selling products, the inability of some small groups of farmers to afford advisory services, and negative past experiences with advisors which limit the overall effectiveness of advisory efforts.

Opportunities lie in the "mandatory" training activities, which are perceived as a beneficial way to educate farmers, particularly those initially uninterested in sustainability. Such training can significantly improve the adoption of sustainable practices. Threats include the lack of sufficient public advisors in cooperatives to support farmers and the limited availability of time for farmers to engage in advisory activities that could enhance soil health and sustainable practices.

SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil health from the farmers' perspective			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support network: existing cooperatives and associations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial objectives: priority on sales over advice. • Economic access: limited for small groups. • Distrust: previous negative experiences reduce openness to new advice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education: mandatory training activities to promote sustainability. 	

Table SP-4. SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil health from the farmers' perspective

Regarding their own learning systems, farmers recognize several strengths, including a strong interest in the sustainability of their farms and the effectiveness of collective learning, which has been a natural strategy for decades (Table SP-5). Despite these strengths, weaknesses persist, such as the current learning system not fully meeting all farmers' needs.

Opportunities for enhancing this learning system include promoting and funding local associations to strengthen farmer-to-farmer learning and integrating external advisory services to bring new perspectives and knowledge. Threats include the historical unfamiliarity with associativism in some agricultural sectors, which could hinder the adoption of more effective collective learning systems.

SWOT analysis: The farmers' learning system			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers are committed to sustainability. • Collective learning among farmers demonstrates effective community collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current learning systems fail to fully meet farmers' needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting local associations can strengthen farmer-to-farmer learning and enhance agricultural sustainability. • Introducing external advisory services can diversify knowledge within the learning system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of familiarity with associativism in some agricultural sectors may impede the adoption of effective collective learning systems.

Table SP-5. SWOT analysis on farmers' learning system from their own perspective.

Advisors also provided a SWOT analysis based on their experiences (Table SP-6). Strengths identified include a variety of information sources for farmers, such as periodic meetings, workshops, peer-to-peer information exchange, and individual advisory sessions, offering multiple avenues for knowledge and support. However, weaknesses are evident, including the reluctance of some farmers to participate in these activities and the insufficiency of advisors in large cooperatives or farmers' associations, leading to inadequate assistance.

Opportunities exist in developing new strategies to engage reluctant or sceptical farmers, thus increasing participation and the effectiveness of advisory services. Providing public independent advisory services to every farmer who needs them could greatly enhance the accessibility and impact of soil health guidance. However, a significant threat is the challenge of ensuring that advisors and farmers speak the same "language" to avoid miscommunication and improve the effectiveness of advisory sessions.

SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil health from the advisors' perspective			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various information sources available to farmers, including meetings, workshops, peer exchanges, and individual sessions, offering diverse support options. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some farmers are hesitant to participate, requiring motivation or compensation for increased engagement. • Limited advisors in large cooperatives lead to inadequate assistance for farmers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing new strategies to engage reluctant farmers could improve participation and effectiveness of advisory services. • Providing public independent advisory services to all farmers could enhance accessibility and impact of soil health guidance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring effective communication between advisors and farmers to avoid misunderstandings poses a challenge.

Table SP-6. SWOT analysis on advisory service about soil health from the advisor's perspective

6.5.4. Potentials for joint learning

Demonstrative farms are highlighted as crucial for enabling farmers to take responsibility for transferring practices or knowledge to others. Farmers trust the experiences and knowledge of their peers more than external agents who may lack a deep understanding of real soil matters. This trust forms a solid foundation for collaborative learning. Workshops organized by farmers for other farmers on soil health issues are seen as an effective method to "educate" peers. This peer-led approach leverages the trust and respect farmers have for one another's expertise and experiences related to soil health.

The possibility of providing incentives to farmers who actively inform and teach others is mentioned. Advisory services could support these farmers by offering solid training, ensuring that the knowledge shared is both accurate and practical. The creation of effective channels for information exchange between farmers, and between farmers and advisors, is suggested as a key component for facilitating learning and collaboration. Such channels would enable the sharing of knowledge and experiences more efficiently.

Farmers generally recognize the value of knowledge advisors can provide and respect the insights each brings from their own perspective on soil-related issues. This mutual respect is essential for effective collaboration. Farmers' knowledge is also seen as a potential source of inspiration for future research lines, suggesting a reciprocal relationship where practical experiences can inform scientific inquiry. During workshops or training sessions, an exchange of knowledge occurs that is highly beneficial for both farmers and advisors, indicating the value of direct interaction for joint learning. Advisors are encouraged to engage more closely with real farm problems related to soil to better understand the challenges farmers face and to offer more relevant solutions.

Independent advisory services are positively regarded by farmers, contrasting with their view of auditors, which is negative. This distinction underscores the preference for advice that is perceived as supportive rather than evaluative or critical. A clear need for independent public advisory services with no commercial interests is expressed, pointing to a desire for the revival of "Servicios de Extensión Agraria" in Spain, which disappeared some time ago. Such services are seen as essential for providing unbiased support and information to farmers.

6.5.5. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

Based on the responses from the interview, several obstacles and bottlenecks were identified in the suggested measures for improving soil health. These include the requirements of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which are sometimes seen as unrealistic and not useful. Farmers suggest that CAP regulations should consider their feedback each year to be more effective and relevant. Additionally, eradicating certain misconceptions is challenging, and local cultural aspects must be considered in CAP regulations.

Demonstrative actions by public advisory services could help consolidate certain practices, yet there is a widespread lack of information, especially analyses focused on soil properties over time, not just on plant characteristics. Some farmers do not value the importance of the soil they manage, maintaining a short-term vision, and advised practices are changing over time, which can create confusion. The lack of water in some areas makes it difficult to comply with certain regulations, such as those related to the CAP, as authorities do not consider these local problems, generating discomfort among farmers facing public pressure.

National and European regulations on soil health often do not consider local conditions, creating discomfort and confusion among farmers. The revival of former public advisory services, like agricultural extension, could be a real solution to the lack of information. Administrative support is sought by some farmers who cannot adequately interpret CAP regulations, and economic constraints hinder the development of sustainable practices or following CAP requirements.

Farmers see the role of authorities more as monitoring and sanctioning rather than training and informing, and they demand fewer sanctions and more informational support. More collaboration between authorities and farmers is required, with monitoring services visiting farms to understand the real problems and limitations farmers face. The provision of public resources to farmers or cooperatives is essential, and financial support will be necessary if sustainable practices are mandatory; otherwise, many farmers will need to leave their farms. A key is to raise awareness among landowners and farmers about the importance of soil health in the long term.

Advisors have identified several key hindrances and bottlenecks to the measures they suggest for improving soil health. Formation and diffusion activities tend to be biased, as the participants in these sessions are often the same, mainly those practicing ecological or regenerative agriculture. A notable segment of other farmers never attends these activities. There is a notable lack of confident, reliable sources of information on soil health, underscoring the need for credible and accessible knowledge dissemination. Soil health is a relatively new concept slowly permeating among all actors involved in soil management, and it will take time for this concept to be fully integrated into various processes.

A concern is raised about the lack of long-term commitment and responsibility from soil users who are not owners but merely exploiters of the land, indicating a need to foster a sense of stewardship among those who work the land. It is believed that new generations of farmers will be more conscious of soil health issues, playing a pivotal role in the transition towards more sustainable practices. Commercial advisory services often provide biased information on soil health, leading to negative outcomes, and there is a call for regulation to mitigate this issue.

The unique characteristics of each plot of land must be taken into account when assessing soil needs, emphasizing the individuality of each soil and its specific requirements. A challenge exists in achieving mutual understanding between farmers and advisors, and enhancing communication to "speak the same language" is deemed essential for developing effective solutions for soil health. Living labs and field demonstrations are suggested as effective means for transferring knowledge between academia

and the agricultural sector, helping to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Offering incentives or privileges to farmers who participate in certain educational activities could encourage practices beneficial to soil health in the long term.

6.5.6. Implications for policy

Based on the feedback provided by both focus groups regarding the improvement of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) concerning soil health issues, the following recommendations are suggested for national authorities:

- Avoid overly strict regulations. Farmers advise against implementing drastic changes or excessively tightening regulations that could lead to a mass abandonment of crops. Regulations should be realistic and consider the practical challenges faced by farmers, ensuring they are feasible and supportive rather than punitive.
- Enhance public advisory services. Farmers stress the need for strengthening public advisory services with well-trained personnel. They advocate for investing in the education and training of advisors specializing in soil health. This would ensure that farmers receive accurate, practical, and up-to-date information that can be directly applied to improve soil health.
- Incorporate farmers' feedback into policy-making. It is crucial that CAP regulations and other relevant policies consider farmers' feedback each year to remain relevant and effective. Policies should be flexible and adaptable, reflecting the real-world conditions and challenges faced by farmers.
- Promote demonstrative actions and practical examples. Demonstrative farms and field demonstrations should be widely supported and used as practical, real-world examples of best practices in soil health management. These initiatives can help consolidate effective practices and build trust among farmers.
- Facilitate effective communication channels. Creating effective channels for information exchange between farmers, and between farmers and advisors, is essential for facilitating learning and collaboration. These channels should combine face-to-face interactions with digital communication methods, ensuring efficient and comprehensive knowledge dissemination.
- Support independent advisory services. There is a clear need for independent public advisory services with no commercial interests. Reviving initiatives like the "Servicios de extensión agraria" could provide unbiased support and information to farmers, bridging the gap between research and practical application in the field.
- Provide financial support and resources. National authorities should ensure that financial support is available for farmers to adopt sustainable practices. This includes providing public resources to farmers or cooperatives and offering incentives or privileges to those participating in educational activities and adopting beneficial soil health practices.
- Encourage a long-term perspective on soil health. Raising awareness among landowners and farmers about the importance of soil health in the long term is key. Policies should promote a sense of stewardship and long-term commitment to maintaining soil health, ensuring the sustainability and productivity of agricultural lands for future generations.

6.5.7. Key messages

Based on the perspectives shared by farmers and advisors three key messages for policymakers regarding soil health are highlighted:

1. **Awareness of soil health:** Increase awareness among landowners and farmers about the long-term importance of soil health for agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability. Highlight the critical role soil plays in the long-term viability of agricultural lands and in environmental protection.
2. **Support and resources for sustainable practices:** Provide assistance, incentives, and resources to farmers to facilitate the transition to sustainable agricultural practices. This support should include funding, technical advice, and policies that ensure the economic viability of farming operations during the transition, as well as promoting communication and the exchange of best practices among farmers.
3. **Improved knowledge transfer and advisory services:** Develop robust mechanisms to ensure that scientific research findings effectively reach farmers in an accessible and practical manner. Implement living labs and collaborative environments to facilitate practical experimentation and learning, and establish independent public advisory services, free from commercial interests, to provide unbiased and reliable support in soil management.

6.6. Country report Sweden

Authors: Christina Lundström and Jenny Höckert (SLU)

6.6.1. The participants

The farmer group

Five farmers (all male) united by an interest in regenerative systems and methods, primarily by how they want to develop and manage their crop production, made the farmer focus group interview. They are geographically dispersed, from Skåne in the south, to Västra Götaland in the west and Västmanland in central Sweden. Accordingly, their cultivation conditions differ, but since there are few like-minded farmers in Sweden, as far as they know, they appreciate the contact and exchange of knowledge and experiences. They cultivate between 200 – 500 hectares of arable land. Two of them have no animals, and the others have cattle, sheep, bees, pigs or laying hens. Three of the farmers has studied agriculture at the university and have a solid education. They are concerned and convinced that agriculture must change in order to decrease input dependency and that improvement and development of soil biology is key to succeed. All of them has had contact with a specific advisor situated in Norway and they have met and understood that they shared an interest in those issues. Some of them have had contact for four to five years, and all of them take part in a project group since two years.

Minimum tillage and cover crops are important tools to improve soil health. But since the farmer group have organic production, there are challenges to make it work in practice. Nevertheless, they are very interested in management concerning reduced tillage, cover crops and different ways to strengthen the crop and benefit soil life. It could be different strategies for making composts or ferments and magaging weeds. They appreciate to discuss, exchange experiences and reflect on those issue with each other since other colleagues often have other perspectives and thoughts. It would be much easier to cooperate with neighbours, but those are either not at all interested or hesitant to the kind of system that those farmers are developing. They mostly communicate per telephone and different events, but they also participate in a project and meet digitally.

The advisor group

The advisor group of four advisors was selected due to an interest in soil topics and experiences concerning soil modules in the Swedish advisory program *Focus on Nutrients* ([Greppa - Greppa](#)) (for further presentation see pp 182-183) which offers free advisory services on environmental issues for farmers. Focus on Nutrients focus mainly on reduction of diffuse nitrogen and phosphorus pollution to water sources and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture, and is a joint venture between The Swedish Board of Agriculture, The County Administration Boards, The Federation of Swedish Farmers and a number of farm companies. The Focus on Nutrients' webpage would be a convenient platform to provide information about the soil health concept and how it should be interpreted and used within the Swedish agricultural sector. Today, the web platform provide almost no information concerning soil health issues.

The advisors represented different regions in Sweden; Skåne in the south, Kalmar in the southeast and Västra Götaland in the western part of Sweden. Unfortunately, two more advisors should have taken part, but made a withdrawal shortly before the meeting. Three of the participating advisors were male and one female.

6.6.2. Perspectives on the soil health concept

Both farmers and advisors claimed that the focus in both conventional and organic farming contexts in Sweden are on chemically and partly on physical soil aspects. There is little discussion concerning soil biology.

Characterising for this farmer group is that they take their starting point in the soil health perspective in order to reach soil fertility. Their focus is on the crop yield, but to get a good yield they claim that a broad perspective on the soil is required. They have an ambition to feed and focus on the soil in order for the soil to feed the crop. Their focus is on the crop, high crop yields and to earn money. However, since the way to reach high yields in conventional agricultural systems are not considered sustainable, they claim we need new strategies. Accordingly, these farmers focus on soil biology and the possibility to use soil organisms to increase soil health and extract already existing nutrients in the soil. Their aim is to maintain a good production with as low inputs as possible.

The advisors stated they were more used to the concept of soil fertility (than soil health) and thus production as the main goal. They even thought that soil fertility was a wider concept, since soil health focused on biology. This shows that the agricultural sector does not even agree on what the concept of soil health means, let alone how it can be used in practice. It confirms the need for basic information, and then, possibly, via the state-funded advisory service Focus on Nutrients. One of the advisors said that soil biology is something you can work with when the economy is all right. However, he used a tool to investigate the soil in field with farmers. He had one demanding customer who forced him to rethink and learn. Another related soil health to a soil without soil borne diseases as club rot, or different difficult weeds. They mentioned that soil health could be considered an environmental issue, not that important for production. Without facts regarding economy aspects on soil health, advisors have difficulties to work with it. This is the opposite of how the farmers presented it. However, none of the advisors reflected on the need for systemic change and thus a demand for lower input in agriculture. Soil fertility is the concept they use in contact with farmers. They are dependent on their customers and thus do what they think the customers want. However, one reflected on the fact that her starting point was that farmers are not interested in the broader perspective, but sometimes they actually are. Two of the advisors add that their thinking concerning soil biology and biodiversity has changed. 15 years ago, there was a total focus on production and yield. Nowadays, the interest for biodiversity, at least above ground, is much more in focus. One of the advisors confirmed that the soil fertility focus is totally dominating in the most important agricultural region in Sweden, even though some advisors have a specific soil interest.

6.6.3. SWOT analyses on soil health learning

The advisors highlighted that soil and soil health is central in agriculture and should be easy to discuss with farmers. However, soils can on the one hand be evaluated in practice, it is not as diffuse as leaching, but on the other hand, there are few facts about the benefit of soil health, it is a complex concept and the definition is blurred, according to the advisors. One advisor mentioned the risk for private advisors to only what you think the customers want. Another one said that the culture in the advisory organisation was negative to the soil health concept. Limited demand from customers, a perception that facts are missing and an all in all negative attitude from advisory organisations, there is little interest and big difficulties to build competence. A critic to the most interested and well-known conservation agriculture farmers in Sweden was that they are "religious". *"The conventional advisory service has not gone into that religion somehow... we maybe have a little more open eyes"*. Later this advisor mentioned the importance of talking to people with different competence. How farmers could

be interested in complex non-profit biodiversity issues when they meet biologists with an agricultural understanding.

Our interpretation of the advisors reflections on soil health issues was that they are framed by a rather conventional mindset, which is also the most common mindset in Swedish agriculture. As long as soil health is referred to as “religion” and as long as advisors engage in questions that they think that their customers are interested in, the advisors that meet farmers on regularly basis will most likely not be an important change agent in soil health issues at farm level. The regenerative farmers emphasised the time needed to change their own mindsets, relearn, and understand new things, since, the conventional soil mindset and the Swedish agricultural context do not highlight biological aspects on soils.

SWOT analysis on soil health learning from the advisors' perspective			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sweden has a wellknown and established advisory model, Focus on Nutrients which could involve soil health issues more. • The soil is not diffuse – easy to investigate in practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisors adapt to their customers, they do not introduce new concepts as soil health, without knowing that the farmers are interested. • Advisors do focus on the plant, not the soil • Many advisors do not feel comfortable to dig in fields together with farmers. • Soil health issues are not considered an important issue among advisory service companies. Not from the management and not in the company culture. • Good facts are difficult to find. • Soil health is complex and thus difficult to handle. • Soil health is difficult to evaluate from an economic perspective. • Soil health must be considered an important issue discussed among advisors. Today it's up to the individual to handle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advisors' attitude to biodiversity, at least above-ground is changing. The interest is increasing among both advisors and farmers. • There are differences between different advisory service companies in the interest for soil health issues. • Soil health issues would fit under the umbrella of Focus on Nutrients. • Advisors like to solve problems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative culture in advisory organisations to farmers with new ideas – it is a kind of “religion”. • The attitude among advisors that farmers consider soil health as an environmental issue and thus not important for production. • Advisors work under economic pressure and must sell services. To develop new competences a clear demand from farmers is needed. • Soil health should not be a question only for farmers with reduced tillage. That could be considered a hinder to start considering it.

Table SE-4. SWOT analysis on soil health learning from the advisors' perspective.

The farmers stated that there is little competence in Sweden on soil biology and the concept of soil health. Accordingly, they must find information outside the Swedish AKIS. One said: *“Previously, when I was employed, I worked in the system, with the information channels that were established. Now you have to somehow completely scrap it... and somehow search via the Internet and different contacts”*. Another one stated: *“Focus on Nutrients ([In English - Greppa](#)) has been great... but what they really show is that the system we have used for the last 70 years is not sustainable. Knowing that road is not a viable road ...that is good!”* The same farmer continued: *“Then there is no more in the traditional extension to seek, and I have to find information somewhere else”*. One threat is that the development

is to slow and maybe in the wrong direction, or based on the same, conventional mindset as always. However, the farmers found this kind of learning group very valuable. It is ok to be curious and test things. However, evaluation of practices is difficult. They do not have the knowledge and time to do proper evaluation and accordingly, there is a risk to interpret the results in a wrong way. To learn more, evaluation support is necessary. It is important for farmers to gain deeper knowledge about the basics in cultivation and the soil. Regarding the opportunities, one farmer said: *“We can all sign that we have done something different that is far too interesting not to look at it more. We can't let this go”*. *“Everything points to the fact that it has to go this way”*. However, they need support to evaluate their systems.

The learning group was very appreciated. To keep it, they could need someone who facilitate group meetings, organise information collection, on farm research and evaluation of such trials. They have a feeling that they make improvements, but do they? *“There are always questions whether you're doing the right thing.”* That is the most important weakness, one farmer said, to handle his own concern, whether he did things right.

The advisors were positive to learn together with farmers. The advisors mentioned that they appreciate to be challenged with new problems. Maybe soil health problems can be a bit difficult since they could be diffuse and measures to improve soil health need long-term interventions without clear results in soil health, economy or yield. One advisor on the one hand claimed that advisors as well as farmers learn mostly by experience, but on the other hand that advisors need facts. *“There is nothing as conservative as an advisory organization”*. They cannot say anything without proof. To learn together could be challenging and must be based on mutual engagement and interest in a specific issues.

Table SE-4 presents the SWOT analysis discussion with the advisors on soil health learning, while Table SE-5 present the SWOT analysis discussion on soil health learning from the farmers' perspective.

SWOT analysis on soil health learning from the farmers' perspective			
Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To learn together with people who has the same mindset. • To have contact with advisors from other countries and attend meetings and courses abroad. • To use the internet and different sources of information there. • The group thinks they have entered an interesting pathway concerning improvements of soil health as an enabler to increased yield as well as sustainability in their production systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-farm research is difficult. Accordingly, it is difficult to evaluate the results of new strategies. • There is a need for more facts concerning good soil health strategiers • Soil health is difficult to evaluate. • Advisors react on problems - they are not pro-active. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitation of group meetings and activities by an interested advisor, who does not need to be experienced. • More people are getting interested in those issues, from subsidies to advisors. Things are changing. • Information from other domains meeting the same kind of challenges is interesting and inspirering, as medicin. • Priorites subsidies to keep the soil green with as much diversity as possible • Pay for result and let farmers chose the way to reach the goal, within limitations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conventional perspective on soil issues in the conventional farming context • Focus on the plant not the soil • It takes time both to change mindset and to change a system and improve soil health. • The soil health perspective is not obvious in agriculture education • The soil health perspective is not obvious for advisors • Without facts advisors have difficulties to work with the topic.

Table SE-5. SWOT analysis on soil health learning from the farmers' perspective.

6.6.4. Potentials for joint learning

Based on those focus group interviews there seems to be openings from both sides. The advisors would try to solve their customers' questions and the farmers want support to facilitate a learning process and handle on farm research. But, who will start? Those very interested farmers are not keen on teaching advisors and the advisors they want to engage with, are very busy and often conduct their business abroad. Probably, some kind of state-funded advisory concept is required to develop the soil health knowledge and mindset in Sweden. If so, the culture and attitudes in advisory organisations must change. They need to be more curious of new ways of thinking and have possibilities to engage in the kind of soil mindset that those farmers are interested in. However, one advisors stated that, soil health questions should be part of everyday work for crop advisors in order to make big impact in practice. Advisory services are often reactive, not proactive. It is much harder to get paid for things you do proactively. To build soil health takes time. The farmers wished for a person who could tell them exactly how to do and how long it would take to get the desired results. The conventional agricultural system in Sweden talks about drainage, manure, liming and ley in relation to improvement of soil health. The farmers wanted to learn more about soil biology, the importance of plant diversity and how to use ferment, cover crops, composts, reduced tillage etc.

6.6.5. Hindrances and measures for improved soil health

A negative and doubtful attitude as well as culture among high ranked advisors, both state funded and others, would counteract development in agriculture. If established actors do not involve in soil health issues in a way interesting for the farmers with this new mindset and perspective on soil, their possibilities to develop new solutions would be harder and slower. The results of new strategies will not be evaluated properly and other farmers will not get in contact with those ideas, resulting in slower adoption and change. We should encourage curiosity and openness to new ideas and possibilities. Effective measures would be to introduce 1) a new module or changes to the existing ones, with a soil health focus in the state-funded project Focus on Nutrients and 2) cooperation projects or Living labs where people with different views can discuss, test and evaluate different measures on different farms, with a case study approach. But, if the attitudes in different kinds of advisory organisations is hesitant and not open to new ideas or perspectives, there will never be a systemic change. Many people talk about it but few people really work for it.

6.6.6. Implications for policy

The results show that there is a need for more:

- Basic information about the soil health concept and what it means in a Swedish agricultural context.
 - How to define and grade soil health from chemical, physical and biological perspectives on a specific farm.
 - How to analyse, interpret and manage issues on soil biology at a specific field. Development of soil health Living Labs for different production systems would be an important measure.
- Measures to support dialogue and openness between different stakeholders in the Swedish AKIS concerning soil health issues.
- Subsidies concerning cover crops, reduced tillage and other soil health promoting measures, that still allow adaptations to local conditions.
- State funded advisory interventions concerning soil health, such as a new module within the Focus on Nutrient program which put emphasis also on biological aspects of soil.

6.6.7. Key messages

1. Stay curious and allow new ideas and mindsets to flourish in dialog with different stakeholders in the Swedish AKIS. Seek inspiration for systemic change from neighbouring countries as Norway, Finland and Denmark with similar cultivation conditions.
2. State funded projects and living labs involving different stakeholders in AKIS is required, where new ideas are considered and on-farm research is used as a tool.
3. There is a need for improved i) strategies concerning how to define soil health in agricultural soils in Sweden, ii) knowledge on soil biology in agricultural soils in Sweden and finally iii) how different production systems impact soil health.

Chapter 7. Discussion

As the country-specific results have been discussed as parts of the country-wise reports in Chapters 5 and 6, this chapter will discuss the findings at a more general level. The first sub-chapter discusses the findings from the quantitative surveys on soil health awareness, while the second sub-chapter discusses the qualitative studies on potentials for improved co-learning on soil health in agriculture.

7.1. Soil health awareness among key stakeholders in agricultural, forest and urban land uses

The surveys revealed several interesting results presented in Chapters 4 and 5. In the following sections, we will highlight and discuss a few of them per land use.

7.1.1. The agricultural survey

A key question that influences other questions related to the willingness to take measures to improve soil health, is the question regarding the extent to which people agree with the problem formulation of poor soil health put by the EU Commission or not. As long as key actors in agriculture do not share the view that soil health is a problem in the region and/or country, other issues will have higher priority. In Spain, France and Germany more than 80 % of the respondents agreed with the general problem description, which can be compared with less than 40% in Sweden (Figure CC-Q11A). This is also seen in Table CC-Q16A, which presents which aspects of soil health that is perceived as a problem or not in each country. The soil challenge that was scored as the largest problem for all countries was “To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage”. By looking at the different country means and standard deviations, we can conclude that it is important to let each country (or even each region) to decide which soil aspects to work on.

Although there were differences regarding whether soil health is a general problem in the own country or not, many of the respondents agreed that soil health is a relevant concept when talking about soil issues in agriculture (Figure CC-Q13aA). Even if the Swedish respondents were the least convinced of its relevance, still 70% of the respondents found the concept relevant. Despite the perceived relevance among the respondents, soil health had not yet reached any widespread use within the agricultural sector (Figure CC-Q13bA). The largest discrepancy between perceived relevance and concept-in-use was found in Spain. While 95% of the Spanish respondents found soil health to be a relevant concept, only 25% believed that it was used within the agricultural sector. Obviously, the soil health concept holds a potential that has yet to be realized.

There are several possible explanations for this gap. Table CC-Q19A summarizes the perceived hindrances for improved soil health mentioned by the respondents in the surveys. Three themes were mentioned as hindrances in all countries: *lack of knowledge/awareness*, *economic aspects* and *lack of political governance*. The perceived lack of knowledge/awareness applies to all actors in AKIS – from farmers to policy makers. Among the respondents, over 50% voted that they would like to learn more about “how to assess soil health” and “soil management strategies to improve soil health” – two highly relevant topics in order for the soil health concept to be integrated in advisory practice. Although most respondents rated their soil knowledge in relation to their needs as rather good, only the Denmark and The Netherlands had more than 20% of respondents that rated their soil knowledge as “excellent”. It is worth noting, that the topics that the respondents found relevant for competence development differed from country to country. So did the preferred format for competence development, although

field visits got the highest total mean (Table CC-Q23A). It is hence of crucial importance that each country learn about the needs mentioned among their mediators for change, in order to support desired change processes at farm level.

The economic-related hindrances were both related to the low profitability in agriculture and counterproductive subsidies. The first-mentioned aspect is of course difficult to influence with the help of policies, but the second aspect will of course be important if the EU Commission and the respective country's authorities are to be able to support the work to improve soil health in Europe. The theme of lack of profitability is thus integrated into the third theme - lack of governance. It is of course a serious and a major shortcoming if current subsidies and governance do not support the development that the EU Commission has decided on. Respondents claim that the current legal framework is not suited to support an improvement of soil health. As the Common Agricultural Policy in EU is constantly changing, it is of crucial importance to find regulations and subsidies that support the fulfilment of Mission Soil Health. However, as the perceived soil health related issues differ from country to country, and as different management practices works different well depending on natural geographical conditions, the regulatory framework must be flexible enough to meet context-specific needs.

Clear governance is most likely a key issue for actors to prioritize working actively with soil health issues. As long as national policies and authorities do not speak clearly about the importance of working to improve soil health - and that this is not mirrored in steering documents or is a part of the national discourse as well as subsidy system - focus will be on other issues. This applies both to prioritizations regarding competence development efforts and to issues that are discussed in advisory services together with farmers.

7.1.2. The forest survey

Unfortunately, only three participating countries managed to reach the set goal regarding number of answered surveys – even though both Germany and France are countries with large areas with forest cover. Hence, the gathered data in this survey is not as rich as for the other two surveys.

Unsurprisingly, the soil health concept was not as widespread in forestry as in agriculture. In the agricultural survey, 45 % of the respondents agreed with the statement that the agricultural sector already uses the concept (Figure CC-Q13bA). In the forest survey, this number was 23% (Figure CC-Q13bF). There are, however large differences between the three countries. In Poland, 45% of the respondents claimed that the soil health concept was already in use, which can be compared with 2% in Sweden. The Polish and the Spanish respondents were also more positive to soil health being a relevant concept when talking about forest soils (approximately 80% of their respondents found it relevant, compared with 40% in Sweden; Figure CC-Q13aF). As with the agricultural survey, there was a gap between the perceived relevance and the usedness of the soil health concept within the forestry sector (Figure-CC13aF and Figure CC13bF). Despite the high numbers for the Polish respondents in the above-mentioned questions, only 30% of their respondents shared the EU Commission's problem formulation regarding poor soil health in relation to forest soils in Poland (Figure CC-Q11F). In order to make forest actors feel part of and take responsibility for the fulfilment of the EU Mission Soil, a more vivid conversation about what soil health could mean and how it could be supported and improved within forestry is probably needed. This is seen in Figure CC-Q21F, showing that two of the topics that got the highest score regarding need for further competence development was "The soil health concept in general" and "Forest management strategies to improve soil health".

The survey gave some indications on what the respondents perceived as hindrances for improved soil health in their respective countries. Two themes were mentioned in all three countries: *lack of knowledge/awareness* and *the prevailing culture* (Table CC-Q19F). For both these themes, advisors/consultants could play an important role to achieve change. However, for that to happen, a clearer governance is probably needed. As long as the forestry sector does not have an outspoken mission to increase forest soil health, other issues will be prioritized.

The role of advisors/consultants and policymakers to support a change of forestry practices with increased emphasis on soil issues, brings the attention to the soil science knowledge among these stakeholders. Although a large share of all respondents had studied soil science (Figure CC-Q7F), the Spanish respondents did not think that their knowledge matched their needs (Figure CC-Q9F). This mismatch is of course alarming and worth studying further. For already educated professionals, competence development measures are probably needed – but in the longer run, maybe there are reasons to update the curricula for students in forest science.

7.1.3. The urban survey

The urban respondent group was, by natural reasons, more heterogenic than the other two respondents groups, as we wanted to target professionals working with different aspects of urban soil issues (such as planning, park management and environmental issues). Consequently, the respondents came from diverse educational backgrounds, and only 45% had studied soil sciences (Figure CC-Q7U). Although more than 70% of the respondents claimed they worked with soil issues (Figure CC-Q3U) (which can be compared with slightly less than 70 % for the agricultural survey (Figure CC-Q3A) and less than 40% for the forest ones (Figure CC-Q3F)), only 20% of the urban respondents felt that they had too little soil knowledge in relation to their needs (Figure CC-Q9U). This can be compared with 15% of the agricultural respondents and 27% of the forest respondents (Figures CC-Q9 A and F), although 80% of them had studied soil sciences during their education (Figures CC-Q7A and F). In all three surveys, the Spanish respondents constituted the largest share of respondents who judged their soil knowledge as deficient in relation to their needs. Of course, that can depend on several reasons. Either the Spanish curricula differs from those in other countries – but more likely, the last years with severe droughts in Spain have highlighted new soil related challenges to deal with which has also emphasized the need for new soil knowledge. If so, due to climate change, professionals in other European countries will most likely eventually share their opinion.

Maybe a bit surprisingly, the urban respondents were the ones who shared the EU Commission's problem formulation of poor soil health to the largest extent (Figure CC-Q11U). In line with the above reasoning, the Spanish respondents strongly agreed with the problem formulation to the largest extent in all three surveys (Figures CC-Q11A and F). A vast majority (80%) of the all respondents found soil health to be a relevant concept when talking about urban soils (Figure CC-13aU), however, the urban sector is not yet using it (Figure CC-13bU). As with the other surveys, there is a non-used potential for more nuanced and more holistic conversations about soil also within the urban sector.

As in the other surveys, the respondents were invited to share thoughts on what they perceived hinders improvement of urban soil health. As the other surveys, *lack of knowledge/awareness* was identified as one reason as well as *lack of governance* (Table CC-Q19U). Of course, these two hindrances might very well be connected – that it is due to the lack of soil knowledge and soil health awareness that soil health is not considered as an issue to take into consideration in urban policies and steering documents. As the soil health concept is more or less not at all used in the urban sector, and as the professionals working with urban soil issues both come from diverse educational backgrounds

and are working in a broad range of workplaces, increasing soil health literacy might become a bit of a challenge.

7.2. Potentials of improved co-learning on soil health in agriculture

The initial ambition with this study was that each participating country would conduct two focus group interviews with *a)* a group of farmers engaged in soil health promoting practices who are sharing knowledge and experiences among themselves as a small learning community and discuss their experiences on soil health learning and advisory services in soil related issues with them, and *b)* a group of advisors active in soil related advisory service and discuss similar questions with them. For several reasons, this study has not been conducted in a similar way in all countries, which makes the SWOT analyses on different soil health learning systems somewhat difficult to compare.

When analyzing the narratives told in relation to the potentials of co-learning between pioneer farmers and advisors, however, it becomes clear that both sides are open to finding suitable co-learning spaces for learning about soil health (Table 7). These spaces could also include research institutions (as mentioned in Denmark) and other actors like nature organizations and regions/municipalities (as mentioned in The Netherlands). In Spain, the importance of demonstration farms was highlighted as a valuable resource when it comes to support learning – especially when it comes to farmer peer-to-peer learning. And in Denmark jointly regularly visits under a period of time to farms within a certain community of practice for both farmers and advisors was mentioned as a suggestion. We can thus see that the creation of structures for e.g. “lighthouse” activities for demonstrations and as spaces for co-learning could be a promising effort to build awareness and share good examples among different AKIS actors. In Germany, the importance of discussing “context adapted agriculture” and “site adapted soil management” was mentioned. This advocates for the importance of creating a network of different “lighthouses” with various kinds of productions and/or natural geographical conditions, to support learning in an effective way. Both the need for practice based in-field learning sites as well as the importance of regional showcases is supported by the results in the quantitative study.

Building a structure of “lighthouses” and creating spaces for joint learning, raises the question of financing. In Poland, it was emphasized that there is a need for increased financing to support capacity-building activities. And in Sweden it was suggested that the some kind of state-funded advisory concept is probably needed to develop soil health knowledge and mindset. Another aspect that is of importance in relation to fostering learning about soil health is the need for trustworthy information/knowledge on soil health related issues, as mentioned in The Netherlands. They suggested a central digital knowledge hub as a potential solution. These ideas are in line with discussions held in e.g. EJP Soil and PREPSOIL. To support learning, however, it is of outmost importance that the knowledge resources are found in native languages, related to context specific challenges, easy to find and considered as a trustworthy source of knowledge.

	Potentials of improved co-learning
Denmark	<p>Farmers and advisors interested and enthusiastic in bringing knowledge and learning spheres of farmers, advisors and research institutions closer via creation of co-learning spaces. This could be achieved by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-learning sessions at conferences • Themed experience cohorts where farmers and advisors visits members of a CoP regularly over a period of time.
Germany	<p>Thematic learnings on identified topics would assist in improving joint learning among stakeholders, i.e regarding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need more field visits and in-person trainings for sharing best practices • Soil conservation management practices • Context adapted agriculture • Flexible, site adapted soil management • Soil as crop location factor
The Netherlands	<p>Co-learning between advisors and peer-to-peer farmer groups was seen as a positive opportunity from the advisor perspective.</p> <p>One concrete suggestion from an advisor to capitalize on the potentials of co-learning, was to organize meetings including farmers, nature organizations, provinces and municipalities all together, to discuss all types of questions and issues.</p> <p>Advisors generally thought that addressing lack of knowledge (possibly linked with too much information) was to provide a central hub which provided a way for farmers to easily access high-quality, trusted, up-to-date information (on the specific issue of importance to them).</p>
Poland	<p>There is an enormous potential and willingness for cooperation between farmers and advisors.</p> <p>In order to fully exploit the joint learning potential of both groups, efforts should be made to increase the financing of this sector for capacity-building activities, and it is also worth striving to increase the importance of the counselling profession so that this profession is attractive on the labour market in Poland.</p>
Spain	<p>Demonstrative farms are highlighted as crucial for enabling farmers to take responsibility for transferring practices or knowledge to others.</p> <p>Workshops organized by farmers for other farmers on soil health issues are seen as an effective method to "educate" peers.</p> <p>The creation of effective channels for information exchange between farmers, and between farmers and advisors, is suggested as a key component for facilitating learning and collaboration.</p> <p>During workshops or training sessions, an exchange of knowledge occurs that is highly beneficial for both farmers and advisors, indicating the value of direct interaction for joint learning.</p>
Sweden	<p>Based on the focus group interviews there seems to be openings from both sides. The advisors would try to solve their customers' questions and the farmers want support to facilitate a learning process and handle on farm research. But, who will start?</p> <p>Probably, some kind of state-funded advisory concept is required to develop the soil health knowledge and mindset in Sweden.</p>

Table 7. Compilation of potentials of improved co-learning among pioneer farmer and advisors (in Germany also other AKIS actors) mentioned in interviews, workshops and surveys (presented in Chapter 6).

Chapter 8. Recommendations

In Chapters 5 and 6, all country reports end by stating a number of key messages. Although it is of course important to understand the national context to fully understand these messages, there are some themes that are mentioned repeatedly in several countries. Table 8 summarises the key messages from the quantitative survey and Table 9 the key messages from the qualitative study.

	Key messages based on quantitative internet-based survey on soil health awareness (agricultural, forest and urban key stakeholders)
Denmark	<p>Danish agricultural practitioners should engage with authorities and researchers on soil health using the Living Labs concept.</p> <p>Shifting agricultural policy from pollution avoidance to sustainable soil health practices can benefit both farmers and global concerns.</p> <p>Greater awareness of soil health is needed among Danish urban soil users, managers, and regulators.</p> <p>Low forest stakeholder engagement highlights the need for outreach and advocacy on forest soil health.</p>
Germany	<p>Coordinated efforts are needed for funding, education, awareness, and implementation of sustainable soil health practices.</p> <p>Scientific knowledge on soil health is not effectively applied, leading to soil degradation.</p> <p>Varied interest levels among participants highlight the need for targeted education on key soil health topics.</p> <p>Demand is growing for accessible advisory services and competence development in sustainable soil management.</p> <p>Institutional changes are needed to improve the advisory system.</p>
The Netherlands	<p>Research and disseminate information to guide soil health priorities, possibly via an interactive platform.</p> <p>Provide localized guidance on management options using examples and network facilitation.</p> <p>Develop market-based solutions like ecosystem service payments to involve companies and consumers.</p> <p>Regulations are needed, but stakeholder involvement is crucial to ensure effective soil policies.</p>
Poland	<p>Awareness of proper soil management is still needed across all land uses.</p> <p>Respondents recognize soil challenges and know where to focus improvements.</p> <p>Informed policies are key to achieving better soil health management.</p> <p>Awareness efforts should target all land managers, public and private.</p> <p>Urban soils need more attention through awareness and policy adoption.</p>
Spain	<p>Increase education and training on sustainable soil practices across sectors, with both in-person and digital access.</p> <p>Reform policies to support sustainable practices, offer incentives, and develop monitoring tools.</p> <p>Launch campaigns to raise awareness of soil health's importance for resilience, food security, and climate change.</p> <p>Promote adoption of technologies like precision agriculture, sustainable forest management techniques and urban sustainable drainage systems, and support research for practical applications.</p> <p>Foster collaboration across sectors, encouraging integrated soil management and establishing platforms for knowledge-sharing.</p>
Sweden	<p>Uncertainty in Sweden about whether the EU's soil health concerns apply locally; urban respondents agree more.</p> <p>Soil health is considered relevant concept for agricultural, forest, and urban soils.</p> <p>Soil health is mostly used in agriculture, but more nuanced soil discussions could occur if more widely spread.</p> <p>Clear governance is needed for prioritizing soil health across land uses, with stronger government advocacy.</p> <p>Lack of knowledge is a barrier; improving soil health literacy through tailored training is essential.</p>

Table 8. Key messages in condensed form from national reports on quantitative internet surveys (Chapter 5).

	Key messages from qualitative study on potentials of improved co-learning on soil health in agriculture
Denmark	<p>Active knowledge-sharing and co-learning between farmers, advisors, researchers, and regulators can be enhanced through Living Labs.</p> <p>Online resources and social media play a key role in co-learning for farmers. New knowledge-sharing platforms should be linked with existing Community of Practice networks.</p> <p>Incentives for sustainable farming practices are probably more effective than punitive regulations.</p> <p>More research is needed on alternative agricultural practices that could improve soil health. Living Labs can play a key role.</p>
Germany	<p>Consensus exists on the poor quality of agricultural soils in Germany and its causes.</p> <p>High awareness of soil health concepts, but access to advisory services remains limited.</p> <p>Stronger science-policy-society interactions are needed for effective knowledge transfer.</p> <p>Governance of soil advisory systems should integrate economic and administrative challenges at national and EU levels.</p>
The Netherlands	<p>Organize and synthesize existing knowledge to identify research gaps and support decision-making on soil health, ideally through an interactive online platform.</p> <p>Provide access to high-quality, context-specific soil management options, using local examples and network facilitation, aligning with the Living Labs approach.</p> <p>Develop market-based solutions, such as payments for ecosystem services, to involve companies and consumers in maintaining soil health.</p> <p>Simplify agricultural policies to ensure they support, rather than hinder, improvements in soil health.</p>
Poland	<p>Increase financial mechanisms at national, regional, local, and individual levels to improve soil health.</p> <p>Optimize advisory systems to enhance knowledge transfer and co-learning, with better focus and efficiency, and support eco-learning and demonstration activities.</p> <p>Create educational programs and demonstration networks to share benefits of soil health, including financial aspects.</p>
Spain	<p>Increase awareness among landowners and farmers about the importance of soil health for agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>Provide support and resources to farmers for transitioning to sustainable practices, including funding, technical advice, and policies that ensure economic viability, while promoting communication and best practice exchange.</p> <p>Improve knowledge transfer and advisory services by ensuring scientific research reaches farmers in a practical way, utilizing living labs for experimentation and establishing independent, unbiased public advisory services for soil management.</p>
Sweden	<p>Encourage curiosity and foster new ideas and mindsets in dialogue with various stakeholders in the Swedish AKIS, seeking inspiration from neighbouring countries like Norway, Finland, and Denmark.</p> <p>State-funded projects and living labs involving diverse stakeholders in AKIS are necessary to explore new ideas, using on-farm research as a tool.</p> <p>Improve strategies for defining soil health, expanding knowledge on soil biology, and understanding how different production systems impact soil health in Sweden.</p>

Table 9. Key messages in condensed form from national reports on qualitative study with farmers and advisors (Chapter 6).

Based on the tables above and the themes highlighted in the discussion (Chapter 7), two main key recommendations arises in order to support Mission Soil and improve soil health:

1. There is a general need for increased soil health literacy among key stakeholders (and beyond, including e.g. practitioners, citizens and civil society) regardless of land use type – both in theory and practice – anchored in trustworthy, reliable, unbiased knowledge.
2. There is a need to develop a clear governance to promote soil health and sustainable soil management – not only on EU level (as through Mission Soil), but also on national level and adapted to different sectors (e.g. agriculture, forest, urban).

These recommendations are strongly linked to the hindrances for improved soil health mentioned by the respondents in the three surveys. As stated earlier, a majority of the respondents (except for the Swedish respondents in the forest survey) agree that soil health is a relevant concept when talking about soil issues – regardless of land use type. However, our study also shows that the potential that the concept holds is yet to be realised, as it is not used widely across land use types yet. In order to unlock this potential, increased soil health knowledge is one key.

In all three surveys, “the soil health concept”, “how to assess soil health” and “soil management strategies to improve soil health” was emphasized as topics that the respondents would like to learn more about. It is stressed that the competence development needed concerns many stakeholders – from field level practitioners to policy makers. The Living Lab approach, where stakeholders meet across competencies, share experiences and learn together, is often mentioned as a promising way of developing knowledge on soil health related issues. In agriculture, the importance of national networks of demonstration farms where farmers, advisors and researchers could meet and co-create knowledge and learn together were also highlighted. This is important, as there is a strong need for robust, trustworthy and unbiased knowledge that is anchored in regional conditions and challenges. The importance of on-farm demonstrations to support learning has been emphasized in research earlier (e.g. Sutherland and Marchand, 2021). However, back-office activities in advisory services (such as for instance local experimentation and scientific monitoring) have been reduced as a consequence of the privatisation of advisory services (e.g. Labarthe and Laurent, 2013). Hence, there is a need for establishing structures that can ensure long-term experiments that includes soil health promoting measures, preferably at sites identified as regional “lighthouses”.

The importance of regional “lighthouses” and/or demonstration sites, as well as the demand for reliable and unbiased knowledge by a trustworthy actor, leads to the other key of the unlocking – the need for a clear governance related to soil health issues. Based on the data from surveys and interviews, the need for a clearer governance is multidimensional. This is in line with FAO who writes:

Soil governance involves policies, strategies, and the processes of decision-making by nation states and local governments on how the soil is utilized. Governing the soil requires international, national and local collaboration between governments, local authorities, industries and citizens. This is to ensure the implementation of coherent policies that encourage practices and methodologies that regulate the usage of the soil resource to avoid degradation and conflict between users. (FAO, 2021)

In our studies, some of the mentioned aspects related to the need for a clear governance concerns:

- *Lack of a knowledge platform* where it would be possible to find adequate and trustworthy information and knowledge about soil health related issues for different land use types and different kinds of stakeholders.
- *Lack of structures and mechanisms* to support the creation and maintenance of a network of regional “demonstration sites” where pioneer practices can be monitored by research on a long-term basis and which could function as a co-learning spaces among stakeholders with various backgrounds.
- *Lack of clear guidance from national and regional authorities and governing documents* that soil health issues is a priority subject to work with. As seen in the survey, however, it is important that which aspects of soil health that is relevant to work with, should be decided on regional level to use resources most efficiently. But, as long as soil health is not mentioned in governing documents and regulations for different land uses, soil health related issues will not be prioritized in relation to competence development efforts, be a vivid part of the soil discourse within the different land uses or integrated in different working praxis.

Chapter 9. References

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9.7. Chapter 8: Recommendations

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This study is aimed at actors who work in different ways with agricultural soils. The purpose of the survey is to gain increased knowledge about how key stakeholders consider soil health related issues. The study is conducted in seven EU countries: Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Poland, France, The Netherlands and Spain. Your region has been selected to represent your country and you are one of the key stakeholders.

We kindly ask you to answer our questions.

Thank you!

[Name of the country's contact person and organisation]

1. General background questions**Language**

- English
- Swedish (svenska)
- Danish (dansk)
- Dutch (Nederlands)
- German informal (Deutsch)
- Polish (polski)
- French (français)
- Spanish (español)

Which of the following alternatives do best correspond to the geographic area in which you work?

- In [Name of your Region 1]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- At national level
- Other: _____

2. General background questions**In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to:**

- Policy work/Policy development
- Exercise of authority
- Counselling/Advisory work
- Education
- Research
- Communication
- Financial mechanisms, for example CAP
- Nature conservation
- Environmental issues
- Lobbying
- Sales
- I do not work with soil related issues
- Other _____

3. General background questions

In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent: Not at all To a very large extent

4. General background questions**I am employed by:**

- National authority / agency (e.g. Agricultural Agency, Environmental Agency)
- Regional authority / agency (e.g. County Administration Board or Municipality)
- Private company
- NGO (non-governmental organization)
- Professional associations
(Interest / Business / Cooperative)
- Academic or educational institute / University / Research institute
- My own company / self employed
- Other _____

5. General background questions**What is your level of studies (diploma)?**

- Bachelor's degree (or less)
- Master's degree/Engineer degree
- PhD/Doctorate

6. General background questions**What is the major subject in your education?**

- Agricultural science / Agricultural engineering
- Forest science / Forest engineering
- Environmental science / Environmental engineering
- Horticulture
- Natural science / Engineering
- Other _____

7. General background questions**Have you studied soil science?**

- Yes
- No

8. General background questions**Have you recieved training on soil health related issues?**

- Yes
- No

9. General background questions

	Deficient		Excellent		Not applicable
In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil?	<input type="checkbox"/>				

10. General background questions

How many years have you worked with soil related issues?

- I have not worked with soil issues
- <5 years
- 5-10 years
- >10 years

11. Questions related to soil health

The EU Commission has stated that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy. This is due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils.

	Strongly disagree		Strongly agree
To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to agricultural soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

12. Questions related to soil health

There are two main perspectives on soil:

- 1) Soil fertility is defined as *the ability of soil to sustain plant growth*. The focus is mainly on the soil ecosystem service: provision of food, fibre and fuel.
- 2) Soil health is defined as *the ability of the soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems*, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services.

	Focus on crop production as the ecosystem service (soil fertility)		Focus on a broad range of ecosystem services (soil health)
The following perspective of soil alignes with my own view:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Questions related to soil health

To what extent do you agree on following?

	Strongly disagree		Strongly agree
<i>Soil health</i> is a relevant concept in agriculture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The agricultural sector already uses <i>soil health</i> as a concept	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. Questions related to soil health

	Not at all		To a significant extent
How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How knowledgeable are you about how agricultural management affects soil health?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. Questions related to soil health

19. Hindrances for improved agricultural soil health

What would you say are the three main hindrances/bottlenecks for improved soil health in agriculture?

20. Measures for improved agricultural soil health

What measures would you suggest to address these hindrances/bottlenecks?

21. Questions related to competence development

Which soil related topics would you like to learn more about?

- the soil health concept in general
- land degradation
- potentials of carbon sequestration
- soil biodiversity
- soil compaction
- erosion
- salinization
- desertification
- soil pollution
- soil chemistry
- soil physics
- soil biology
- nutrient leaching
- climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation
- how to assess soil health
- soil management strategies to improve soil health (i.e. sustainable or regenerative strategies)
- none of these topics
- other: _____

22. Questions related to competence development

	Not at all						To a very large extent	I don't know
Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

23. Questions related to competence development

I would like to learn more about agricultural soil health through:

- physical courses
- digital courses
- web movies (recorded material)
- webinars (live)
- podcasts
- reports
- books
- field visits
- agricultural magazines
- intervision with other colleagues/municipalities
- via good examples
- I am not interested to learn more about soil health
- other _____

24. Other comments or ideas

Do you have any other comments or ideas related to agricultural soil health that you would like to share?

Thank you for your time!

Would you like to know more about PREPSOIL? Please visit our website: <https://prepsoil.eu/>

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This study is aimed at actors who work in different ways with forest soils. The purpose of the survey is to gain increased knowledge about how key stakeholders consider soil health related issues. The study is conducted in seven EU countries: Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Poland, France, The Netherlands and Spain. Your region has been selected to represent your country and you are one of the key stakeholders.

We kindly ask you to answer our questions.

Thank you!

[Name of the country's contact person and organisation]

1. General background questions

Which of the following alternatives do best correspond to the geographic area in which you work?

- In [Name of your Region 1]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- At national level
- Other: _____

Language

- English
- Swedish (svenska)
- Danish (dansk)
- German informal (Deutsch)
- Polish (polski)
- Dutch (Nederlands)
- French (français)
- Spanish (español)

2. General background questions

In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to:

- Policy work/Policy development
- Exercise of authority
- Counselling/Advisory work
- Education
- Research
- Communication
- Financial mechanisms
- Nature conservation
- Environmental issues
- Lobbying
- Sales
- I do not work with soil related issues
- Other _____

10. General background questions

How many years have you worked with soil related issues?

- I have not worked with soil issues
- <5 years
- 5-10 years
- >10 years

11. Questions related to soil health

The EU Commission has stated that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy. This is due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils.

	Strongly disagree							Strongly agree
To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to forest soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?	<input type="checkbox"/>							

12. Questions related to soil health

There are two main perspectives on soil:

- 1) Soil fertility is defined as *the ability of soil to sustain production*. The focus is mainly on the soil ecosystem service: provision of food, fibre and fuel.
- 2) Soil health is defined as *the ability of the soil to sustain the productivity diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems*: i.e. a broad range of ecosystem services.

	Focus on forest raw materials as the ecosystem service (<i>soil fertility</i>)							Focus on a broad range of ecosystem services (<i>soil health</i>)
The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Questions related to soil health

To what extent do you agree on following?

	Strongly disagree							Strongly agree
<i>Soil health</i> is a relevant concept in forestry	<input type="checkbox"/>							
The forest sector already uses <i>soil health</i> as a concept	<input type="checkbox"/>							

14. Questions related to soil health

	Not at all							To a significant extent
How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?	<input type="checkbox"/>							
How knowledgeable are you about how forest management affects soil health?	<input type="checkbox"/>							

15. Questions related to soil health

To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept in forestry...

	Not at all							To a very large extent
... imply a mindshift concerning soil?	<input type="checkbox"/>							
... change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?	<input type="checkbox"/>							

16. Assessment of 11 challenges concerning forest soils

To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in forest soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?

	Not at all						To a very large extent
To increase soil organic matter	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To increase soil biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve water retention / infiltration / drainage	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve soil fertility	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve nutrient cycling	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease soil compaction	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease soil erosion	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease salinization	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease desertification	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To avoid soil sealing	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To manage peatlands	<input type="checkbox"/>						

17. Other forest soil challenges

Do you face other challenges related to forest soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?

18. Soil challenges that your workplace deals with

To what extent do your workplace deals with the following challenges in forest soils?

	Not at all						To a very large extent
To increase soil organic matter	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To increase soil biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve water retention / infiltration / drainage	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve soil fertility	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve nutrient cycling	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease soil compaction	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease soil erosion	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease salinization	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease desertification	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To avoid soil sealing	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To manage peatlands	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To promote the awareness of sustainable forest management	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To promote the awareness of the importance of soil health	<input type="checkbox"/>						

19. Hindrances for improved forest soil health

What would you say are the three main hindrances/bottlenecks for improved soil health in forestry?

20. Measures for improved forest soil health

What measures would you suggest to address these hindrances/bottlenecks?

21. Questions related to competence development

Which forest soil related topics would you like to learn more about?

- the soil health concept in general
- land degradation
- potentials of carbon sequestration
- soil biodiversity
- soil compaction
- erosion
- salinization
- desertification
- soil pollution
- soil chemistry
- soil physics
- soil biology
- nutrient leaching
- climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation
- how to assess soil health
- forest management strategies to improve soil health
- none of these topics
- other: _____

22. Questions related to competence development

	Not at all						To a very large extent	I don't know
Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

23. Questions related to competence development

I would like to learn more about forest soil health through:

- physical courses
- digital courses
- web movies (recorded material)
- webinars (live)
- podcasts
- reports
- books
- field visits
- forestry magazines
- intervision with other colleagues/municipalities
- via good examples
- I am not interested to learn more about soil health
- other _____

24. Other comments or ideas

Do you have any other comments or ideas related to forest soil health that you would like to share?

Thank you for your time!

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We kindly ask you to answer our questions.

Thank you!

[Name of the country's contact person and organisation]

1. General background questions

Which of the following alternatives do best correspond to the geographic area in which you work?

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- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 1]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
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- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 2]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your rural municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your mixed municipality]
- In [Name of your Region 3]: [Name of your metropolitan municipality]
- At national level
- Other: _____

Language

- English
- Swedish (svenska)
- Danish (dansk)
- German informal (Deutsch)
- Polish (polski)
- Dutch (Nederlands)
- French (français)
- Spanish (español)

2. General background questions

In my profession, I work with soil issues in relation to:

- Maintenance of parks, gardens and/or green areas
- Urban planning
- Construction
- Exercise of authority
- Policy work/Policy development
- Environmental issues (such as Agenda 2030, remediation of contaminated sites, biodiversity, climate adaptation)
- Recycling/ Reuse of soils
- Biomass production (except food)
- Food production
- Education
- Research
- Communication
- Lobbying
- Sales
- I don't work with soil related issues
- Other _____

3. General background questions

In my current job, I work with soil issues to following extent: Not at all To a very large extent

4. General background questions**I am employed by:**

- National authority / agency (e.g. Environmental Agency)
- Regional authority / agency (e.g. County Administration Board or Municipality)
- Private company
- NGO (non-governmental organization)
- Professional associations (Interest/Business/Cooperative)
- Academic or educational institute / University / Research institute
- My own company / self employed
- Other _____

5. General background questions**What is your level of studies (diploma)?**

- Bachelor's degree (or less)
- Master degree / Engineer degree
- PhD / Doctorate

6. General background questions

What is the major subject in your education?

- Horticulture
- Agriculture science / Agricultural engineering
- Environmental science / Environmental engineering
- Natural science / Engineering
- Planning / Architecture
- Other _____

7. General background questions

Have you studied soil science?

- Yes
- No

8. General background questions

Have you received training on soil health issues?

- Yes
- No

9. General background questions

In relation to your needs, how do you rate your knowledge concerning soil? Deficient Excellent Not applicable

10. General background questions

How many years have you worked with soil related issues?

- I have not worked with soil issues
- <5 years
- 5-10 years
- >10 years

11. Questions related to soil health

The EU Commission has stated that a majority of the soils in the EU are unhealthy. This is due to processes such as erosion, compaction, reduced content of organic matter, pollution, loss of biodiversity, salinization and soil sealing/settlement in agricultural, urban and forest-natural soils.

To what extent do you agree with the problem description above, in relation to urban soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)? Strongly disagree Strongly agree

12. Questions related to soil health

There are two main perspectives on soil:

1) Targeted soil use - Focus on one or a few specific functions at a time: (i.e. as foundation for buildings/infrastructure, as medium for water purification or as growing medium for trees and plants)

2) Focus on a wide range of soil ecosystem services simultaneously. Soil health is the ability of soil to sustain the productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems.

	Targeted soil use	Focus on a broad range of ecosystem services
The following perspective on soil aligns with my own view:	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Questions related to soil health

To what extent do you agree on the following?

	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
<i>Soil health</i> is a relevant concept for urban soils	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The urban sector already uses <i>soil health</i> as a concept	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. Questions related to soil health

	Not at all	To a significant extent
How knowledgeable are you regarding the soil health concept in general?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How knowledgeable are you about how soil management affects soil health?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. Questions related to soil health

To what extent would an adoption of the soil health concept concerning urban soils...

	Not at all	To a very large extent
... imply a mindshift concerning soil?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
... change how your workplace would deal with soil issues?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

16. Assessment of 11 challenges concerning urban soils

To what extent are the following challenges considered as a problem in urban soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?

	Not at all	To a very large extent
To increase organic matter	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To improve soil fertility	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To increase soil biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To decrease soil erosion	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To decrease soil compaction	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To avoid soil sealing	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Desealing artificial surfaces	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To avoid or remediate contamination of soils / soil pollution	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recycling/Reuse of soils	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

17. Other urban soil challenges

Do you face other challenges related to urban soils in your region (or country, if you work at national level)?

18. Soil challenges that your workplace deals with

To what extent do your workplace deal with the following challenges in urban soils?

	Not at all						To a very large extent
To increase organic matter	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve water retention/infiltration/drainage	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To improve soil fertility	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To increase soil biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To decrease soil erosion	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Decrease soil compaction	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To avoid soil sealing	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Desealing artificial surfaces	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To avoid or remediate contamination of soils/soil pollution	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Recycling/Reuse of soils	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To promote the awareness of sustainable soil management	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To promote the awareness of the importance of soil health	<input type="checkbox"/>						

19. Hindrances for improved urban soil health

What would you say are the three main hindrances/bottlenecks for improved urban soil health?

20. Measures for improved urban soil health

What measures would you suggest to address these hindrances/bottlenecks?

21. Questions related to competence development

Which soil related topics would you like to learn more about?

- the soil health concept in general
- potentials of carbon sequestration
- climate adaptation/regulation/mitigation
- recycling/reuse of soils
- soil pollution/remediation of soils
- erosion
- soil biodiversity
- soil chemistry
- soil physics
- soil biology
- how to assess soil health (for specific land use functions)
- soil management strategies to improve soil health
- none of this topics
- other _____

22. Questions related to competence development

	Not at all						To a very large extent	I don't know
Are there relevant competence development measures on soil health for you?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

23. Questions related to competence development

I would like to learn more about urban soil health through:

- physical courses
- digital courses
- web movies (recorded material)
- webinars (live)
- podcasts
- reports
- books
- field visits
- industry magazines
- intervision with other colleagues/municipalities
- via good examples
- I am not interested to learn more about soil health
- other _____

24. Other comments or ideas

Do you have any other comments or ideas related to urban soil health that you would like to share?

Thank you for your time!

Would you like to know more about PREPSOIL? Please visit our website: <https://prepsoil.eu/>

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Task 6.3
Survey protocol:
Focus group interview
with farmers

Setting the scene: EU & The Soil Health Mission

The European Union has a set of overarching goals known as the "Missions of Horizon Europe." These missions are ambitious, targeted initiatives designed to address some of the most pressing challenges facing society. These are:

1. Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities
2. Mission on Cancer
- 3. Mission on Soil Health and Food**
4. Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change Including Societal Transformation
5. Mission on Healthy Oceans, Seas, Coastal and Inland Waters

Setting the Scene: Mission on Soil Health and Food & The project Prepsoil

✔ The goal of the Soil Health Mission is:

To promote sustainable agricultural practices, improve soil health, and ensure a resilient and environmentally friendly food system within the European Union.

✔ **Prepsoil** is one of the projects within the Soil Health Mission.

Prepsoil involves 12 participating EU countries

This study is conducted in Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and France

Objectives of this study

- ✔ The objective of this sub-task is two-fold:
 - i) to explore and analyse the strengths and weaknesses among two different kinds of learning systems (Communities of Practices) within soil health in agriculture – one **grass-root, self-organised farmer initiative** and one **public/private extension programme/advisory service**, and
 - ii) to identify possible improvements through co-learning between these two learning systems.

Soil fertility vs Soil health

In agriculture there are two main perspectives on soil.
(There are several definitions to chose from...)

- ✔ **Soil fertility:** *the ability of soil to sustain plant growth.*
The focus is mostly on the ecosystem function "provision of food, fibre and fuel".
- ✔ **Soil health:** *the ability of soil to sustain productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem functions.*

✔ Do you distinguish between soil fertility and soil health? (Y/N)

Which perspective on soil aligns with your own view?

Focus on crop production as the ecosystem service	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Focus on a broad range of ecosystem services
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	--

Make a round and make a quick motivation of your chosen number and if your view has changed over the years.

What brings you together?

- ✔ How long have you known each other?
- ✔ Why did you start to share knowledge and experiences about soil issues with each other?
- ✔ What soil issues do you mostly discuss?
- ✔ Do you try/explore things that you somehow evaluate together? (Please explain)
- ✔ Do you have support from someone who is not a farmer?

Describing the farmer practice within the group

Could you give examples of soil health promoting measures that you do on your farms?

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.

Other things?

Learning about soil health

- ✔ What are important sources for information/inspiration?
- ✔ Is there something that you lack/have lacked, that could have made your soil health-learning journey easier? Some kind of support?
- ✔ Have you experienced any milestones or critical events that has been crucial for you in your soil health learning/interest? (Something that could be important for others?)

Experiences of advisory service related to soil (health) issues

- 🌱 What experiences of advisory services related to soil (health) issues do you have?
- 🌱 What did you think about it?

SWOT analysis: Your learning system (farmers learning together)

What are the STRENGTHS of your "learning group"?	Are there any WEAKNESSES of this kind of peer-to-peer learning?
OPPORTUNITIES: What would be the next step in your learning journey? How could your learning (system) be improved?	THREATS: Do you face any challenges in your peer-to-peer learning? Is there anything that inhibits your learning potentials?

SWOT analysis: Advisory services on soil health

What STRENGTHS would you say advisory services in soil health have?	What WEAKNESSES would you say they have?
OPPORTUNITIES: How would you like advisory service to change? What kind of support did you miss <i>or</i> would you have valued when you went from thought to action in the beginning of your soil health-learning journey?	THREATS: What would you say are the main threats to learning about soil health related issues?

Potentials for joint learning

Two different kinds of "learning system" with different strengths and weaknesses.
What are the potentials for joint learning?

FARMERS LEARNING TOGETHER

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

Informal, experience-rich, local based learning system

ADVISORY SERVICES

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

Formalised (structured) way of working, anchored in research

What would you say are the three main hindrances/bottlenecks for improved soil health in agriculture in general?

What measures would you suggest to address these hindrances/bottlenecks?

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Task 6.3
Survey protocol:
Focus group interview
with advisors

Appendix 5: Survey protocol - Focus group interview with advisors

Funded by
the European Union

Setting the scene: EU & The Soil Health Mission

The European Union has a set of overarching goals known as the "Missions of Horizon Europe." These missions are ambitious, targeted initiatives designed to address some of the most pressing challenges facing society. These are:

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 - ii) to identify possible improvements through co-learning between these two learning systems.

Exploring the advisory group – who are you?

- 🍃 What educational background do you have?
- 🍃 For how long have you been working as advisors in agriculture?
- 🍃 Where do you work?
- 🍃 What kind of advisory services do you offer? (Public/private, what kind of expertise?)

Soil fertility vs soil health

In agriculture there are two main perspectives on soil. (*There are several definitions to chose from...*)

- ✔ **Soil fertility:** *the ability of soil to sustain plant growth.* The focus is mostly on the ecosystem function "provision of food, fibre and fuel".
- ✔ **Soil health:** *the ability of soil to sustain productivity, diversity and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems, i.e. a broad range of ecosystem functions.*

Do you distinguish
between soil fertility
and soil health?
(Yes/No)

Which perspective on soil aligns with your own view?

Focus on crop production as the ecosystem service	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Focus on a broad range of ecosystem services
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	--

Make a round and make a quick motivation of your chosen number and if your view has changed over the years.

How confident do you feel in engaging in discussions with farmers about soil health?

Not confident at all	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Very confident
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Make a round and make a quick motivation of your chosen number.

Learning about soil health

- ✔ What are important sources for information/inspiration?
- ✔ Is there anything related to soil health that you would like to learn more about?

SWOT analysis: Advisory services on soil health

<p>If you take a farmers perspective, what STRENGTHS would you say advisory services on soil health issues have?</p>	<p>What are the WEAKNESSES in today's advisory services on soil health?</p>
<p>OPPORTUNITIES: How do you think that advisory services would need to change, in order to better support a positive development of soil health in agriculture in your country?</p>	<p>THREATS: What would you say are the main threats to learning about soil health related issues?</p>

Experiences from soil health pioneer farmers

- ✔ In most countries there are groups of very soil health interested farmers, who have learnt most of what they know themselves and who share experiences among each other. Can you use their experiences in your work? Do you use it? How?
- ✔ Do you think there is any kind of service that you could offer to these farmers to make their soil health-learning journey easier/"better"?

Potentials for joint learning?

Two different kinds of "learning system" with different strengths and weaknesses.
What are the potentials for joint learning?

FARMERS LEARNING TOGETHER

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

Informal, experience-rich, local based learning system

ADVISORY SERVICES

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

Formalised (structured) way of working, anchored in research

What would you say are the three main hindrances/bottlenecks for improved soil health in agriculture in general?

What measures would you suggest to address these hindrances/bottlenecks?

